

THE INTERNATIONAL RICE RESEARCH INSTITUTE

**Annual
Report
1965**

Rice, a member of the great family of grasses, produces a fruit that for hundreds of millions of people epitomises the difference between plenty and scarcity, hunger and non-hunger, life and starvation. It is the staple diet for 60 percent of humanity.

But in Asia, where 90 percent of all rice is grown and eaten, the weight of grain produced per unit area of farmland is, by world standards, disastrously low. The causes are by no means all technical; there are social and political aspects which are not proper subjects for study by the physical scientist. But it is true that crops are ravaged by diseases and pests; that some soils lack the nutrients essential for prolific growth; and that the cultural practices and the varieties grown are not necessarily the most suitable. Such impediments to greater abundance are susceptible to agricultural research.

It was the conviction that the food scarcity now menacing human life could be attacked successfully with the weapons of science that prompted the establishment of The International Rice Research Institute.

The Institute is a joint venture by The Rockefeller Foundation and The Ford Foundation in cooperation with the Government of the Philippines. It was incorporated in 1960 and dedicated in 1962 when the research program began.

This document, the fourth annual report published by the Institute, describes in some detail the work performed during 1965, and, where possible, discusses the salient findings in relation to the practical problems confronting the Asian rice farmer.

NUTRIENT SOLUTIONS are used in physiological studies of the rice plant—see Plant Physiology (page 19-63).

**The International Rice Research Institute
Los Baños, Laguna, Philippines
1966**

Annual Report 1965

**MAIL ADDRESS AND CITY OFFICE: IRRI, MANILA HOTEL, MANILA
CABLE ADDRESS: RICEFOUND**

Contents

Board of Trustees	6
Personnel	7
Institute Climate and Soils	11
Director's Introduction	15
Plant Physiology	19
Biochemistry	65
Cereal Chemistry	69
Varietal Improvement	79
Plant Pathology	107
Soil Chemistry	125
Soil Microbiology	167
Agronomy	184
Entomology	233
Agricultural Engineering	267
Agricultural Economics	289
Statistics	303
Experimental Farm	323
Office of Communication	327
Library and Documentation Center	337
International Activities	339
Publications and Seminars	353

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Plant Physiology

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NORMITA M. MANAHAN, B.S.A., Research
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*Left during year

**On study leave until July 10, 1965

Plant Pathology

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MANUEL K. PALOMAR, B.S.A., Research Assistant
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SONIA P. EBRON, B.S.M. Tech., Laboratory Aide

Soil Chemistry

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RUBY U. CASTRO, B.S. Chem., Research Assistant
TERESITA A. LOY, B.S. Chem., Research Assistant
ESTRELLA G. MARTINEZ, B.S. Chem., Research Assistant
ELSA P. REYES, B.S. Chem., Research Assistant
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Soil Microbiology

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TERESITA F. CASTRO, B.S. Chem., Research Assistant

Agronomy

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Entomology

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GERARDO B. AQUINO, B.S.A., Research Assistant
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EDWIN S. RAROS, B.S.A., Research Assistant
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†Arrived during year.

Agricultural Engineering

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Agricultural Economics

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EDITO S. RUFON, Multilith Operator
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*Left during year

†Arrived during year

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REBECCA C. PASCUAL, M.S., Manager*
NENITA C. ESGUERRA, B.S.H.E., Acting
Manager
ESTER P. NOVERO, B.S. Home Tech.,
Acting Assistant Manager
EMILIA A. AQUINO, E.T.C., Matron
CHITA A. GUERRERO, B.S.N., Junior
Matron
AURORA T. VERGARA, B.S. Home Tech.,
Junior Matron
MARCIANA V. CUYNO, B.S. Home Tech.,
Food Supervisor
ROSE MARIE A. DANS, B.S. Home Tech.,
Food Supervisor
ESTELA G. DIVINAGRACIA, B.S. Nutrition,
Food Supervisor

ROSARIO B. CUMAGUN, A.B.H.E., Food
Supervisor
VIOLETA C. MERCADO, B.S.F.N., Assistant
Food Supervisor
PRIMO D. RUZON, Chef

Buildings and Grounds

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VICTOR T. ARAÑEZ, Assistant to the
Superintendent
RIZALINO T. DILAG, JR., B.S.A., Ground
Superintendent
EDUARDO B. VILLASANTA, B.S.C.E.,
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*Left during year

Institute Climate and Soil

The International Rice Research Institute is adjacent to the College of Agriculture, University of the Philippines, at Los Baños, Laguna, on the island of Luzon. It is 65 kilometers (40 miles) southeast of Manila, at 14° 10' N, 121° 15' E, and 127 feet above sea level. The experimental fields embrace 146 ha of poorly drained and almost flat land at the base of Mount Makiling, a tree-clad volcanic cone.

As in many tropical rice-growing regions, the year is divided into regularly alternating and fairly distinct wet and dry seasons. Climatic data, collected by the College of Agriculture and presented in Table 1, show that the wet season at the Institute normally lasts from May to November, and although some rain may be expected from December to April, neither the amount nor the reliability are sufficient for rain-fed crops; this period of five months is therefore regarded as the dry season.

Mean daily temperatures range from about 25 C in January to nearly 29 C at the commencement of the wet season in

May. Average monthly values for relative humidity also rise during the wet season, reaching a maximum of 86% in August.

Typhoons, bringing heavy rain and strong winds, may be expected from as early as April until December. Those experienced during the later part of the season cause widespread lodging of rice crops. The average frequency of typhoons at Los Baños between 1959 and 1964 is shown in Fig. 1.

Solar radiation, now recognized as an agriculturally important climatic factor in the tropics, has been measured by the College of Agriculture since 1959. The short-term means give quantitative expression to the pronounced cloudiness during the wet season, particularly toward its end when crops are nearing harvest.

In Figs. 2 and 3 average rainfall and solar radiation are compared with the amounts received in 1964 and 1965. Whereas 1964 recorded above-average rainfall, particularly in June and November when typhoons brought heavy

TABLE 1. Climatic averages, Los Baños, Laguna, Philippines.

	Rainfall (in)	Number of rainy days	Mean daily temperature (°C)	Relative humidity (%)	Solar radiation (g-cal/cm ²) (1959-65)
January	2.3	12	25.1	84	9,140
February	1.1	6	25.7	78	10,060
March	1.2	7	27.0	78	11,790
April	1.6	5	28.5	76	14,850
May	6.2	12	28.7	78	13,680
June	8.3	17	28.0	84	11,890
July	11.1	20	27.5	85	10,710
August	10.9	19	27.3	86	11,180
September	10.2	19	27.2	84	10,000
October	9.9	17	26.7	85	11,040
November	11.0	17	26.2	84	9,580
December	5.8	17	25.4	85	8,140

Fig. 1. Average frequency of occurrence of typhoon-days within 150 miles of Los Baños, Laguna (1959-64).

falls, 1965 was comparatively dry and free of typhoons. In both years solar radiation toward the end of the wet season was below the 1959-65 average.

The soils of the experimental fields were mapped and classified in 1962 by the Bureau of Soils, Philippine Department of Agriculture and Natural Resources. The following account is based on the Bureau's report and subsequent laboratory examination by scientists at the Institute.

The soil cover is believed to have formed mainly from the underlying

tuffs derived from Mount Makiling during a previous period of active eruption. A portion of the material, however, may be alluvium weathered from similar tuffs on the adjacent slopes.

Two soil types of the same series, the Maahas clay (also known as Calumpang clay) and the Maahas clay loam, are recognized. Both types are further subdivided into three phases based on the effective depths of soil that may be expected to be available to plant roots. Thus, apart from the normal phase, each type is classified into moderately

Fig. 2. Monthly distribution of rainfall, Los Baños, Laguna, Philippines.

shallow and shallow phases having 50 to 90 cm and 25 to 50 cm of effective soil respectively.

The normal Maahas clay is a dark-colored soil with hydromorphic fea-

Fig. 3. Monthly distribution of solar radiation, Los Baños, Laguna, Philippines.

tures. The surface (pH 6-7) is a grayish-brown to black clay which, al-

though sticky and plastic when wet, becomes cracked into hard compact clods upon drying. X-ray diffraction studies at the College of Agriculture have shown that the dominant mineral is montmorillonite. The subsoil, occurring at from 25 to 40 cm, is lighter colored and, toward the bottom, mottled with light brown and gray. Manganese and tuffaceous concretions are also present in the lower portions of the horizon. The substratum, encountered at from 60 to 140 cm, is grayish brown to brown clay which merges with the underlying tuff. Analytical data on the surface horizon are presented in Table 2.

Apart from surface texture, the Maahas clay loam is similar to the Maahas clay, although it is usually found on slightly higher ground where external drainage is less restricted.

Grading operations have caused some areas of soil which were naturally shallow to become critically so. The consolidated tuff has been exposed and mixed with the surrounding soil in some places, causing some variability in composition and probably fertility also.

TABLE 2. Chemical properties of the surface horizon of the Maahas clay, IRRI.

pH ^a	Organic matter (%)	Total N (%)	P ^b (ppm)	Cation exchange capacity (m.e./100 g)	Exchangeable cations ^c (m.e./100 g)			
					Ca	Mg	Na	K
6.0	2.0	0.14	20	45	17.4	13.3	4.2	0.8

^a 1:1, soil:water; ^b Extracted with 0.02 N H₂SO₄; ^c Extracted with neutral ammonium acetate and analyzed by flame spectrophotometer.

Director's Introduction

One of the important achievements of the year was the identification of certain selections from the Institute's breeding program which were sufficiently outstanding to warrant testing throughout the tropical and sub-tropical rice-growing regions. Most of the selections sent to other areas have been in the F6 or F7 generation. Although by the end of 1965 more than 570 crosses had been made, it was only the progeny of crosses made in 1962 that had become sufficiently stable to permit appropriate evaluation and widespread testing.

The three selections that seemed particularly outstanding under Philippine conditions and, at this stage, especially on the Experimental Farm, are IR8-288-3, IR9-60, and IR5-47-2. It happens that each of these three lines have the variety Peta as one of the parents. Peta is a tall, tropical *indica* variety with high vigor, seed dormancy, and resistance to certain important diseases. It was developed in Indonesia but is now one of the Seed Board varieties in the Philippines.

One of the best selections resulting from the crossing of Peta with Degeo-woo-gen (a short *indica* variety from Taiwan) was IR8-288-3. This line has high yielding ability, some resistance to the tungro virus disease, is short and nitrogen responsive, and has desirable cooking and eating qualities.

The crossing of Peta with I-geo-tze, another short *indica* from Taiwan, also produced a promising selection, IR9-60. It has fairly high seed dormancy, is short (95 cm high), non-lodging, and nitrogen responsive. In many trials it has yielded between 6,000 and 7,000 kg/ha under good management.

The IR5-47-2 selection is a cross between Peta and Tankai Rotan, a relatively tall *indica* variety from Malay-

sia, selected as a parent because it was not as tall as most *indicas* and, in early trials, appeared to be vigorous and non-photoperiod-sensitive. The IR-5-47-2 is a line of medium height (138 cm) and maturity (132 days), and appears to be rather resistant to the tungro virus disease and to bacterial leaf blight. In recent preliminary yield trials, it has produced over 6.5 metric tons per hectare in the monsoon season. It is now being widely tested in Southeast Asia.

It is perhaps no coincidence that these three outstanding selections are pure *indicas*; there are no *japonica* varieties in their ancestry. They have high seedling vigor (specifically high tillering ability) and superior qualities of disease resistance, characteristics which perhaps are more easily obtained from crossing *indicas* with *indicas*. In any case, it seems clear that the breeding program of the Institute could not have made such rapid strides in the early stages if the short *indicas* from Taiwan with the single recessive gene for shortness had not existed.

The varietal improvement program has developed a series of lines with a desirable plant type, rather good grain qualities, and high yielding ability. The big task ahead is to introduce disease resistance into the already established selections, particularly resistance to bacterial leaf blight, the tungro virus disease, and the rice blast disease, the latter resistance to be as broad as possible because of the various physiological races.

During 1965, much of the basic work was completed on the gamma isomer of benzene hexachloride (lindane) as a systemic insecticide for rice stem borer control. It has been generally established that, under Philippine conditions, when this insecticide is applied to the irrigation water every 30 days at the

rate of 2 to 3 kg/ha, the pest is successfully controlled. Naturally, the method must be tested widely in other countries where the species of the stem borer and the degree of water control may be different from those in the Philippines.

Work on the application of other chemicals, such as diazinon, to the irrigation water is proving so successful that in the near future the lowland rice farmer may be able to discard his sprayer and apply all of his insecticides in a granular form with no more equipment than is needed to broadcast fertilizer.

During 1965, Institute agronomists obtained the highest average yields ever achieved at Los Baños. In the dry season, when yields are always the highest, many experimental plots produced at the rate of 6,500 to 7,500 kg/ha, and seven varieties each yielded more than 8,000 kg/ha. Even during the cloudy monsoon season, yields ranged from 4,500 to 7,000 kg/ha, with many being between 5,000 and 6,000 kg/ha. Under continuous cropping, three crops of rice totalled 17,800 kg/ha in 384 days, an average grain production of 46 kg/ha per day.

These high yields can be attributed partly to the absence of typhoons and to a lower than average rainfall, but, also, partly to better control of insects and to the more general use of short, stiff-strawed varieties that respond to nitrogen without lodging.

Another innovation was the design and use of an electric fence for controlling rats on the experimental fields. Rats have been a serious problem ever since the Institute started its program. In January, the superintendent of our Experimental Farm proposed that a low fence made of chicken wire be electrified at night by storage batteries, but with the current amplified to either 110 or 220 volts a.c. This procedure proved to be successful and during the 12-month period beginning in mid-January, more than 22,000 rats were killed on the 80-hectare field.

The agricultural engineers designed and built a set of special lug wheels

that can be mounted on the inner and outer sides of the rear rubber tires of 40-60 Rph tractors. With these wheel attachments, and a 300-cm rotary tiller made in our shop and mounted on the rear of a tractor — driven, of course, from the power take off — an excellent job of wetland preparation can be done. The designing of this equipment marks a forward step in solving the problem of mechanizing paddy land preparation.

The plant pathologists have screened many thousands of varieties and genetic selections for the three most common rice diseases: rice blast, bacterial leaf blight, and the tungro virus. Varieties resistant to each disease have been found, thus identifying materials that can be used in the breeding program to introduce disease resistance into otherwise improved varieties.

The Office of Communication, in addition to editing and preparing for publication the writings of the scientific staff, carried on an effective training program for extension workers. Those who received this instruction, which ranged from 6 to 12 months duration, could be classed as rice production specialists. They not only gained practical experience in every operation connected with growing a rice crop, but also obtained a good understanding of the scientific basis for modern rice production practices.

Furthermore, they learned how to lay out, on farmers' fields, applied research plots to determine the extent to which certain modern rice-growing methods and the newer varieties could increase rice yields in specific environments. When successful, these plots are followed by demonstration and instructional activities to teach and motivate farmers.

In addition to conducting this training program, the Office of Communication worked closely with the Commission on Agricultural Productivity (the extension arm of the Philippine government) and the Bureau of Plant Industry in establishing applied research plots in many parts of the Philippines. These field experiments were conducted primarily to test the effectiveness of lindane and of several improved rice

varieties under the various environmental conditions that exist in the Philippines.

The training of rice production specialists and the establishment, in co-

operation with government agencies, of applied research plots throughout the Philippines constitute a pilot effort to assess whether such methods can have a measurable impact on national yields.

STAFF CHANGES

One replacement, three additions, and one resignation were the only changes during the year in the scientific staff.

Dr. Yasuo Natori, biochemist, replaced Dr. Takashi Akazawa, who resigned in late 1964.

Dr. K. C. Ling, virologist, was added to the staff in Plant Protection, while

Mr. William G. Golden, Jr., rice production specialist, and Mr. E. A. Jackson, editor, joined the Office of Communication staff.

In mid-year, Dr. Vernon W. Ruttan, agricultural economist, resigned his position to accept the post of head of the Department of Agricultural Economics, University of Minnesota.

TRUSTEES

There was no change in the composition of the Board of Trustees. The Board, however, passed a resolution changing the possible number of trustees from 10 to 14, which would allow

members to be chosen from any of eight major rice-producing countries. The other six members would continue to be determined by the positions they hold.

FINANCES

The financial support of the Institute continued to come largely from two private foundations in the United States — The Rockefeller Foundation and the Ford Foundation.

Actually, the general operating costs of the Institute were divided equally between the two Foundations. In late 1964, the Institute received from the Ford Foundation a grant of \$4,900,000, designed to cover one-half of the operating costs of the Institute during the 7-year period beginning January 1, 1965. A portion of these funds is to be released to the Institute each year. The amount received during 1965 was \$633,000.

The Rockefeller Foundation made a grant of \$635,000 as its contribution toward the operating costs of the Institute in 1965, \$390,000 of which was in the form of cash and the remainder covered by the salaries, perquisites and travel expenses of the eight Rockefeller Foundation staff members assigned to the Institute.

Other grants received by the Institute in 1965 are as follows:

From the National Science Development Board of the Philippines, \$6,230.75 toward the study of the nature and control of virus disease of rice and \$15,363.73 toward a study of insecticide residue problems of rice production with emphasis on the gamma isomer of benzene hexachloride. Both amounts represent the sums released during 1965 from 3-year grants made for each of the two projects.

From the National Science Foundation of the United States, \$14,950 as a part of its 4-year grant for the research project on the description and preservation of the world's rice germ plasm.

From the Esso Research and Engineering Company, \$3,100 as part of its 2-year grant in support of the Institute's fertilizer research program.

From the International Potash Institute and the Foundation for International Potash Research, \$750 toward the support of a study of the potassium

and phosphorus fertilization of calcareous soils in Bohol.

From the Ford Foundation, \$301,300.90 was used or committed by November 30, 1965, for the international training and cooperative research program under the 3-year grant of \$800,000 made by the Foundation in late 1964.

From the Agency for International

Development of the Government of the United States, \$360,000 for a research project on farm and equipment power requirements for the production of rice and associated food crops in the Far East and in South Asia. None of the money from this grant, which is for a 3-year period, was spent in 1965 because of the delayed arrival of personnel.

Plant Physiology

In broad terms, factors controlling the growth and productivity of rice in the tropics include light, water and soil conditions. Light may have its effect through photosynthesis and through photoperiod reactions, while soil conditions of importance are not only those related to plant nutrient level and balance, but may involve organic toxicants as well. In varying degrees, the work in Plant Physiology is directed toward the study of these growth-controlling factors.

PHOTOSYNTHESIS, RESPIRATION, AND GROWTH

Growth efficiency

Photosynthesis supplies organic substances which are used as raw material in the plant body and as energy sources in respiration. As photosynthesis and respiration are closely related, and both intimately linked with growth, it is important to understand these processes.

Growth efficiency is defined here as W/S , where W is the plant weight increase and S the weight of substances used for growth. S can be further subdivided into two categories: the substances used for respiration (R) during the growth period, and those which became constituents of newly grown organs (W). Thus the growth efficiency can be expressed as

$$\frac{W}{W + R}$$

Growth efficiency was studied in an experiment with Peta seeds germinated in darkness at 21, 26, and 32 C for 10 days. The dry weight of seedlings was regarded as W and the decrease of seed weight during the germination period as $W + R$. By using these data, growth efficiency was calculated.

TABLE 1. Effect of temperature on growth efficiency of Peta seedlings grown without light.

Temperature °C	Weight of seedlings (mg/100)	Growth efficiency (%)
21	4.5	56
26	8.3	58
32	10.6	57

High temperature hastened the growth, but growth efficiency was kept almost constant at about 60% (Table 1). This implies that when 1 unit weight is used for growth, 0.4 unit will be used for respiration and 0.6 unit will result in new organs.

The growth efficiency of grown panicles was also estimated. Panicles of Peta plants grown under ordinary field conditions were sampled at successive growth stages starting from panicle ini-

tiation. Their respiratory rate was measured by the Warburg manometric method and their weight recorded. At early stages of panicle primordium development, the growth efficiency was about 60%. The efficiency during maturing was higher, amounting to about 75%.

These results demonstrate that growing organs, such as seedlings or young panicle primordia, have a growth efficiency of about 60%.

Data are insufficient for many generalizations. However, respiration may be regarded as being either geared or not geared with growth. In active, growing organs, the growth efficiency appears to be nearly constant, about 60%. If, as under some conditions, the growth efficiency is less than 60%, some proportion of respiration is not geared with growth.

Growth as the result of photosynthesis and respiration

To understand the growth of the rice plant on the basis of photosynthesis and respiration, Peta was grown in a field at 30 x 30 cm spacing with 100 kg/ha N in the rainy season.

Fig. 1. Growth of Peta plants at 100 kg/ha N, 1965 wet season.

The growth rate was low at the beginning, increased to a high point during the tillering stage, started to decrease at about the panicle initiation stage, and became low after the milk stage. The lower leaves started to die after the maximum tiller number stage, and the weight of dead leaves increased progressively with growth. After flowering, the straw weight decreased and the panicle weight increased (Fig. 1).

Photosynthetic rate of the population at full sunlight, 100 Klux, (P_{100}), and respiratory rate (R) both increased with growth, reached a maximum, and then decreased (Figs. 2 and 3). The maximum photosynthetic rate was reached at the panicle initiation stage and maximum respiratory rate followed. The decrease of photosynthetic rate after reaching the maximum was much more abrupt than that of the respiratory rate.

The $P_{100}-R$ ratio was maintained at a high value until the panicle initiation stage was reached and then decreased. From this trend it is apparent that the balance between photosynthesis and respiration was favorable at early growth stages but poor at later stages, especially if low intensity on cloudy days is considered.

Fig. 2. Leaf area index, photosynthetic rate and light transmission ratio at different growth stages of Peta at 100 kg/ha N, 1965 wet season.

From dry weight (W), and respiratory rate (R), the growth efficiency at various growth stages was computed as described above. Growth efficiency was kept at about 60% during early growth stages when the photosynthetic rate was much higher than the respiratory rate (Fig. 3). During this growth period, respiration is the factor limiting growth rate; a higher respiratory rate caused, for example, by a high temperature, promotes growth.

After the panicle initiation stage, however, the efficiency decreased due to a low photosynthetic rate compared with the respiratory rate, indicating that after this stage photosynthesis, rather than respiration, was the growth-limiting factor. High respiration is not necessarily linked with more growth.

After the panicle initiation stage, the lower leaves started to die, due in part to deficiency of energy source in these leaves. Consumption of energy sources by respiration in these mutually shaded leaves, and the elongated internodes at the base of the culm, were the causes of low growth efficiency.

Fig. 3. Respiratory rate and growth efficiency at different growth stages of Peta at 100 kg/ha N, 1965 wet season.

The leaf area index (LAI) increased with growth, reached a maximum at booting stage, and then started to decrease due to the death of lower leaves (Fig. 2). The light transmission ratio (LTR) decreased with the increase of LAI. Thus, photosynthetic rate per unit leaf area of the population decreased

with growth. The decrease was not, of course, due solely to the mutual shading, but partly to the decrease of potential photosynthetic rate per unit leaf area resulting from a shortage of energy source in lower leaves under mutually shaded conditions.

The apparent assimilation rate-light intensity curves of the population explained clearly the nature of mutual shading (Fig. 4). At the early growth stages, from 20 to 40 days after transplanting, the assimilation rate and the saturation point increased with the increase of LAI. At booting stage, there was no saturation point. The assimilation rate at this growth stage was lower than at panicle initiation stage, except at high light intensity. At flowering, the apparent assimilation rate decreased. This was partly due to decreased LAI, but mostly to decreased potential photosynthetic rate of leaves.

On the whole, it is apparent that at early growth stages, because photosynthetic rate was much higher than re-

Fig. 4. Response to light intensity of apparent assimilation rate at different stages of growth of Peta population.

spiratory rate, light intensity and mutual shading did not influence growth directly. However, at later growth stages, photosynthesis was more intimately related to growth.

Fig. 5. Light transmission ratio (LTR), weight of various organs, and respiratory rate at different heights of Peta population at flowering, 1965 wet season.

Respiratory rate per unit weight was high at early growth stages but decreased with growth. However, as plant weight increased, the respiratory rate of the population was large (Fig. 3).

At flowering, the respiration in the portions receiving only a low light intensity was considerable (Fig. 5). Active leaves were distributed 120 to 180 cm from the ground, where light intensity was high. Below this level, some active leaves were distributed, but due to low light intensity as well as weakness of the leaves, apparent assimilation may have been negative. Nevertheless, below 120 cm, there was a large amount of leaf sheath and culm.

The respiration of organs located above 120 cm was about 40% of total respiration. This respiration may be well geared with growth. The respiration of organs below 120 cm, where there was no positive apparent assimilation, was more than half the total respiration of the population. Respiration here consumes both recent and accumulated products of photosynthesis drawn from the upper organs, and has no relation to the growth of new organs.

Respiratory rate during photosynthesis

While measuring apparent assimilation of rice populations, a peculiar respiration behavior was frequently observed.

For example, on August 29, the morning was cloudless and at noon the light intensity was above 100 Klux. At 2 p.m. it became cloudy and from 3 to 5 p.m. a

light intensity of about 2 Klux was maintained and the apparent assimilation was negative. Just after it became cloudy a large negative value was recorded followed by an increase. During sunset, of course, apparent assimilation decreased to a constant night value (Fig. 6, left).

Another example was observed on fine days such as October 2. Immediately after sunset, the respiratory rate was

To test this speculation, potted flowering Peta plants kept in the sun with various light intensities were transferred to darkness and the change in respiratory rate was traced for several hours.

Control plants kept constantly in the dark respired at a constant rate. However, the plants subjected to light respired more actively just after being placed in darkness and the rate grad-

Fig. 6. Apparent assimilation of Peta population under selected light conditions. The curve on the left demonstrates results under unusually low light intensity during the mid-afternoon hours while that on the right shows fairly typical late afternoon conditions.

high for one hour or so, before decreasing to a constant value which was maintained till the next morning (Fig. 6, right).

A similar phenomenon was also often observed in the morning. Just after sunrise, the respiratory rate increased followed by positive apparent assimilation when the light intensity increased.

These observations suggest that when plants are photosynthesizing, respiration is more active, and when an actively photosynthesizing plant is transferred to darkness, active respiration continues for some time.

usually decreased. The stronger the light intensity during the pre-treatment, the higher the respiratory rate immediately after the dark treatment (Fig. 7).

In another experiment, a Peta plant was fed with C¹⁴O₂ for 2 hours and then kept in natural conditions for 3 days. The C¹⁴O₂ release was then measured in the sun and, immediately after, in darkness. The values were 125 x 10³ and 390 x 10³ dpm, respectively. The C¹⁴O₂ release was increased by transferring the plant from light to dark.

It appears that a plant actively photosynthesizing respire more actively

than one that is not. In the dark, accumulated substances are used for respiration, whereas in the light, newly photosynthesized substances are the major substrates of respiration.

Fig. 7. Change in respiratory rate of Peta plants moved into darkness after being kept under various light intensities.

Factors affecting grain yield during ripening

From data obtained in many experiments conducted by this department, a statistical examination was made of the factors controlling grain yield during ripening.

Grain yield was not necessarily correlated with plant weight at flowering (Fig. 8, top). When plant weight was small (less than 0.6 kg/m^2), grain yield was small and tended to increase with increased plant weight. However, when plant weight was larger, there was no simple relation between plant weight and grain yield. With an increase of plant weight, the variation in grain yield became greater. With large plant weights, ranging from 0.8 to 1.4 kg/m^2 , grain yield was high in some cases and extremely low in others. With an extremely large plant weight, above 1.5 kg/m^2 , there was no instance of high grain yield.

Grain yield was positively related to the increase of plant weight after flowering (Fig. 8, bottom). When there was a decrease of plant weight after flowering, grain yield was consistently low.

High grain yields can be expected only if nitrogen has been applied; there-

Fig. 8. Relation of grain yield to plant weight at flowering and to plant weight increase after flowering.

fore, only results with nitrogen application will be further discussed. Plant weight at flowering with nitrogen application was larger than 0.6 kg/m^2 , except in one or two cases. The increase of plant weight after flowering tended to be smaller when plant weight at flowering was larger. This indicates that if plant weight at flowering is already large, there is no chance of a big increase later because mutual shading is serious, and the respiration not geared with growth is a large proportion of the total respiration.

Plant weight increase after flowering was not simply related to total solar radiation during the 30-day period after flowering. However, the multiple regression of increase after flowering (Y , kg/m^2) with weight flowering (X_1 , kg/m^2) and total solar radiation during the 30-day period after flowering (X_2 , Kcal/cm^2) was highly significant.

$$Y = 0.137 - 0.55^{xx}X_1 + 0.072^{xx}X_2$$

This correlation strongly suggests that a high grain yield with nitrogen

Fig. 9. Effect of support on grain yield of Peta at different levels of nitrogen.

application was possible only if a large amount of dry matter was produced after flowering. The dry matter pro-

duced after flowering was large if plant weight at flowering was not excessive and the total solar radiation after flowering was large.

With no nitrogen applied, LAI at flowering was barely 3 regardless of plant weight, but where nitrogen was applied, it was usually above 4 and sometimes as high as 9. When LAI is greater than 4, an increase does not significantly increase the photosynthetic rate but makes mutual shading more serious. The greater the solar radiation, the greater is the photosynthetic rate. On the other hand, the negative correlation between plant weight at flowering and plant weight increase after flowering indicated that the larger the plant weight, the larger will be the proportion of respiration which is not geared with growth.

With a large plant, LAI is large, and if solar radiation is high, photosynthetic rate greatly exceeds respiration and produces a high grain yield. However, if solar radiation is small, respiration dominates photosynthesis and grain yield is low. The grain yield is there-

TABLE 2. Effect of leaf pruning at different growth stages and at different heights on grain yield of Peta grown with 100 kg/ha N, 1963 wet season.

Time of pruning		Level of pruning (cm from highest collar)	Grain yield (kg/ha)
Days after transplanting	Growth stage		
40	Maximum tiller number stage	+ 10	3100
		0	3376
		- 10	2862
55	15 days before panicle initiation	+ 10	3286
		0	3412
		- 10	2708
70	Panicle initiation	+ 10	2734
		0	2812
		- 10	2886
Control			2596
LSD			531

fore strongly influenced by the amount of solar energy if plant weight at flowering is large. Thus the optimum plant size at flowering depends on the amount of solar energy received during ripening.

Mutual shading and lodging

With leafy rice varieties, mutual shading and lodging at high nitrogen levels cause decreased grain yield. To separate the adverse effects of mutual shading and lodging, an experiment was conducted with Peta planted at 30 x 30 cm spacing in the rainy season, 1965. There were four nitrogen levels: 0, 50, 100, and 150 kg/ha. Each level was subdivided into three further treatments: control, supported from lodging till flowering, and supported till harvest.

In the control plot, all plants lodged at harvest at all nitrogen levels but at high levels lodging started before flowering. The grain yield of the plot supported till harvest increased where nitrogen was applied at 50 kg/ha but decreased with more nitrogen (Fig. 9). The population at high nitrogen levels was extremely leafy and the decreased grain yield was caused by mutual shading.

Lodging caused a decrease in grain yield which was greater at higher than at lower nitrogen levels. This was partly due to earlier lodging at higher nitrogen levels. It is also considered that when plants lodged the leaf arrangement is disturbed, causing the photosynthetic rate to decrease. Under such conditions, high nitrogen levels cause more serious adverse effects due to the higher respiratory rate than low nitrogen levels.

The adverse effect of lodging after flowering was also significant though not as serious as that before flowering. The plots supported till flowering lodged more or less simultaneously at four nitrogen levels, but the loss of grain yield due to lodging was greater at high nitrogen levels. This demonstrates that the higher respiratory rate at higher nitrogen levels causes the

greater loss of grain yield.

From these data it can be concluded that mutual shading *per se* at a high nitrogen level results in decreased grain yield. However, the effect of mutual shading is less than that of lodging. Higher respiratory rate at a higher nitrogen level aggravates the adverse effect of lodging. It should also be mentioned that by promoting lower internode elongation, mutual shading at early growth stages can be one of the indirect causes of lodging.

Effect of leaf pruning

Since an excessive LAI reduces grain yield, the yield should be improved by pruning leaves from an extremely leafy population at an adequate height and a suitable growth stage.

The effect of pruning was studied in the 1963 wet season with Peta plants planted at 30 x 30 cm spacing with 100 kg/ha N. Leaves were pruned at three growth stages and at each growth stage, three degrees of pruning were imposed: a similar experiment in the 1964 wet season gave similar results.

The control plot was leafy with an LAI, at its maximum, of 8.7. The LAI was, of course, decreased by pruning but it increased again later at about the same rate as in the unpruned population. For plants pruned at the highest collar position between the stage of maximum tiller number and 15 days before panicle initiation, grain yield increased significantly (Table 2). By pruning earlier, LAI at flowering was too large, whereas by pruning at panicle initiation, the development of panicle primordium was adversely affected and the LAI at flowering was too low. One of the beneficial effects of pruning before panicle initiation was the retardation of basal internode elongation and thus, delayed lodging.

The extent to which grain yield can be improved by leaf pruning was disappointingly small. Non-leafy varieties are more productive than pruned leafy varieties.

PLANT TYPE, YIELDING ABILITY AND NITROGEN RESPONSE

Growth duration

The relationship of growth duration to yielding ability and nitrogen response of different varieties has been studied for several years. A further experiment was conducted to collect more information on the balance between photosynthesis and respiration in varieties with different growth durations.

Fig. 10. Photosynthetic and respiratory rate at flowering of rice populations with various growth durations.

They were planted at 30 x 30 cm spacing with 0 and 100 kg/ha N.

At the high nitrogen level, the photosynthetic rate at flowering increased as the growth duration (from sowing to flowering) increased up to 90 days. This resulted from an increase of LAI without mutual shading becoming serious. However, if growth duration exceeded 90 days, the photosynthetic rate declined markedly due to increased and prolonged mutual shading (Fig. 10, top). At the low nitrogen level the photosynthetic rate was generally lower than at the high nitrogen level, and varieties with a growth duration of 110

days had higher rates of photosynthesis than those with either shorter or longer growth durations.

At the high nitrogen levels, respiratory rate at flowering increased with an increase of growth duration, reached a maximum, and then decreased abruptly. At the low nitrogen level, however, respiratory rate was more or less constant regardless of growth duration (Fig. 10, bottom).

At the high nitrogen level, the apparent assimilation rate at flowering was highest with varieties of about 90-day duration but declined as the duration exceeded 90 days because of low photosynthetic and high respiratory rates. The data also indicated that the grain-straw ratio declined markedly with increased growth duration. At high nitrogen levels, as concluded in previous years, the assimilation after flowering is an important factor in grain production. The relationship between photosynthetic and respiratory rates at flowering, described above, thus explains the relationship between

Fig. 11. Grain yield and nitrogen response of varieties with various growth durations.

TABLE 3. Angles of tillers and leaves, light extinction coefficient (K) and grain yield of upright- and open-tiller lines with two nitrogen levels at two spacings, 1964-65 dry season.

Line	Spacing (cm)	N level (kg/ha)	Tiller angle ^a	Leaf angle ^a	K	Grain yield (ton/ha)
B5617 A36-69-2-2 (upright-tiller)	15 x 15	0	82	80	0.38	2.68
		100	79	72	0.48	5.97
	30 x 30	0	76	69	0.48	2.57
		100	75	69	0.61	3.80
B5617 A40-24-2-2 (open-tiller)	15 x 15	0	67	63	0.60	2.95
		100	69	61	0.56	5.11
	30 x 30	0	63	60	0.54	3.01
		100	58	59	0.73	3.56

^a Angle between the outermost one and horizontal line.

Fig. 12. Tillering habit of B5617 A36-69-2-2 (left) and of B5617 A40-24-2-2 (right).

TABLE 4. Height, grain-straw ratio, grain yield at 100 kg/ha N, and nitrogen response of four varieties with different plant heights, 1965 rainy season.

Variety	Growth duration (days)	Height at harvest (cm)	Grain-straw ratio	Grain yield (ton/ha)	Nitrogen ^a response (ton/ha)
Hung	109	222	0.74	3.79	0.51
Century Patna 231	109	174	0.92	4.33	1.47
Chianung 242	115	149	1.22	5.28	1.68
Taichung (Native) 1	115	122	1.31	5.91	1.63

^a Grain yield at 100 kg/ha N — grain yield at 0 kg/ha N.

grain yield and growth duration. Varieties with a growth duration of about 90 days yield highest (Fig. 11, top).

At the low nitrogen level, differences in assimilation rate at flowering among varieties with different growth durations were smaller than those at the high nitrogen level. Varieties with longer periods of growth accumulate more carbohydrate in the straw at flowering, and, for this reason, the longer growth duration, the higher the grain yield at the low nitrogen level (Fig. 11, top).

Because the response in grain yield to growth duration differs according to nitrogen level, the response to nitrogen

was greater in short duration varieties than in long duration ones (Fig. 11, bottom).

There is an optimum growth duration for obtaining the highest grain yield under a given set of conditions. The optimum varies with the environmental conditions in which the plant grows. The optimum growth duration is shorter under high than under low nitrogen levels. Varieties with total growth duration (sowing to harvest) of about 120 days are more likely to give highest grain yield under high nitrogen levels, and those of 150-160 days are more likely to do this under low nitrogen levels. Nitrogen response tends to be larg-

Fig. 13. Taichung (Native) 1, Chianung 242, Century Patna 231, and Hung (from left to right) at flowering.

TABLE 5. Translocation percentage and growth efficiency of varieties with different plant heights, 1965 rainy season.

Variety	Straw weight at flowering (kg/m ²)	Translocation percentage ^a	Photosynthetic rate at flowering (g CO ₂ /hr/m ²)	Relative Growth rate (mg/g/day) ^b	Respiratory rate (mg/g/day) ^c	Growth efficiency (%)
Hung	1.09	74	4.5	6.6	13.8	32
Century Patna 231	0.83	58	5.2	16.8	19.0	47
Chianung 242	0.88	27	4.0	17.3	18.7	48
Taichung (Native) 1	0.93	51	5.0	21.4	19.2	53

^a Decrease of straw weight from flowering to harvest
Increase of panicle weight from flowering to harvest x 100.

^b During period from flowering to milk stage.

^c Average value of respiratory rate at flowering and at milk stage expressed as equivalent glucose weight.

er with shorter than with longer duration varieties.

Tiller angle

Two lines, i.e., B5617 A40-24-2-2 (open-tiller) and B5617 A36-69-2-2 (upright-tiller) (Fig. 12), with identical parentage but different tiller angles, were planted in November, 1964. These varieties flowered and were harvested on the same date.

The tiller angle (the angle between outermost tiller and horizontal line) was larger in the upright-tiller line than in the open-tiller line, and at 15 x 15 cm than at 30 x 30 cm spacing. At 100 kg/ha N, the angle was slightly smaller than at 0 N (Table 3). The leaf angle (the angle between the outermost leaf and horizontal line) was affected in a similar manner.

The extinction coefficient of the up-

right-tiller line was much smaller than that of the open-tiller line. It was larger at 30 x 30 cm than at 15 x 15 cm spacing, and also at 0 than at 100 kg/ha N.

The upright-tiller line yielded more at 100 kg/ha N, especially at 15 x 15 cm, than the open-tiller line. The open-tiller line yielded better at 0 N, especially at 30 x 30 cm, than the upright line.

From these data, it can be concluded that at a low nitrogen level and a wide spacing, the open-tiller type yields better. However, with a heavy nitrogen application and at a close spacing, the upright-tiller type produces a higher grain yield.

Plant height and grain-straw ratio

Among varieties with about the same growth duration, there are differences in plant height. To collect data on var-

TABLE 6. Length of internode and leaf blade of varieties with different plant heights, 1965 rainy season.

Variety	Internode length (cm)						Leaf length (cm)	
	1 ^a	2	3	4	5	6	1st ^b	2nd
Hung	47	38	37	32	18	7	47	65
Century Patna 231	48	28	26	17	8	3	42	66
Chianung 242	46	26	21	10	5		44	62
Taichung (Native) 1	34	23	15	8	3		36	47

^a Counted from top.

^b Flag leaf.

ious plant characters associated with plant height, four varieties with more or less the same growth duration (Fig. 13), 110 days, were planted at 30 x 30 cm spacing with 0 and 100 kg/ha N in the main season, 1965.

At 100 kg/ha N, plant height ranged from 122 to 222 cm and the grain yield as well as grain-straw ratio decreased with increase of plant height. Nitrogen response was also greater with the shorter varieties (Table 4).

The straw weight at flowering was largest in Hung, but there was no clear

Fig. 14. Changes of percentage of fertilizer nitrogen over total absorbed nitrogen and amount of fertilizer nitrogen absorbed at successive growth stages of Tainan 3 and Peta at 40 and 80 kg/ha N, 1964 wet season.

trend among the other three varieties (Table 5). Translocation percentage (defined as the ratio, expressed as a percentage, of straw weight decrease from flowering to harvest to panicle weight increase over the same period)

Fig. 15. Amount of soil nitrogen absorbed by Tainan 3 and Peta at various levels of applied nitrogen, 1964 wet season.

was larger with taller than with shorter varieties, although Taichung (Native) 1 had a high value. There was no consistent trend among varieties in the photosynthetic and respiratory rates at flowering. The plant weight increase after flowering was less in taller than in shorter varieties.

The growth efficiency was small in tall varieties and large in short ones, indicating that respiration during ripening of short varieties was well geared with growth, but that of tall varieties was not.

Tall varieties had more and longer elongated internodes (Table 6). Respiration of the extra elongated internodes, especially at the base, could be the reason for the low growth efficiency of tall varieties.

There was an association of tall stature with long leaves (Table 6). Taller varieties had larger extinction coefficients.

These data suggest that the short variety had no organ that respired inef-

ficiently at flowering, and for this reason, respiration detracted less from grain production. Tall varieties tended to mature with reserve substances in the straw that had been accumulated before flowering; a large portion of the photosynthetic production after flower-

Fig. 16. Seasonal variability of grain yield of Taichung (Native) 1 and Peta at various nitrogen levels.

ing was wasted by respiration in extra elongated internodes which also made the plant more susceptible to lodging.

With Taichung (Native) 1, not only was the growth efficiency high, but also the translocation percentage. These two beneficial characters resulted in a high grain-straw ratio.

Varietal difference in soil nitrogen absorbing ability

Previous studies have shown that actively vegetative, leafy varieties absorb nitrogen more actively than less vegetative, non-leafy varieties but there had been no attempt to differentiate between fertilizer and soil nitrogen.

To compare the effect on leafy and non-leafy varieties of applying nitrogen fertilizer, and how this affects the uptake of nitrogen from the soil, Peta

Fig. 17. Seasonal variability of plant height and panicle-straw ratio of Taichung (Native) 1 and Peta at various nitrogen levels.

(leafy) and Tainan 3 (less leafy) were transplanted at 30 x 30 cm spacing in the 1964 wet season. Ammonium sulfate labelled with ^{15}N was applied basally at three levels: 0, 40, and 80 kg/ha N. Plant samples were taken from time to time and analyzed for total N and ^{15}N .

With increased nitrogen application, uptake of fertilizer N, and percentage of fertilizer N to total N absorbed by the plant, increased. The percentage of fertilizer N was higher in Tainan 3 than in Peta (Fig. 14). The uptake of soil N increased with increased nitrogen application, being apparent in Peta, but very slight in Tainan 3 (Fig. 15). When a large amount of nitrogen was applied, fertilizer N was absorbed rapidly and soil N gradually. In Peta the loss of fertilizer N from plants at later growth stages was more significant than that of soil N. The loss was not observed in Tainan 3.

In a parallel experiment, the effect of

Fig. 18. Variability of leaf area index and leaf thickness of Taichung (Native) 1 and Peta at various nitrogen levels.

nitrogen applied during growth was also tested. The results indicated that the application of such nitrogen promoted, naturally, the uptake of both fertilizer and soil N.

These findings indicate that nitrogen application to leafy varieties promotes the uptake not only of fertilizer N but also of soil N. Thus, if there is abundant nitrogen in the soil, the effect of fertilizer nitrogen is magnified in leafy varieties more than in non-leafy ones. Non-leafy varieties are more dependent on fertilizer nitrogen than on soil nitrogen compared with leafy varieties.

Wide adaptability

The ideal variety would be one giving a consistently high grain yield in any season of the year and with a more or less constant cultural method. Sea-

sonal varieties behave differently according to the time of year in which they are grown; consequently the ideal variety must be sought among non-seasonal varieties. However, while some of these give high yields, reasonably consistently, irrespective of planting season, others yield well only at certain times of the year.

If the breeding objective is to get varieties giving high grain yield with intensive management at a relatively high nitrogen level — for example the ability to produce high grain yield consistently at a high nitrogen level at any time of the year should be the criterion of wide adaptability.

In the dry and wet seasons, 1965, nine varieties, including Taichung (Native) 1 which produces consistently high yields, and Peta which gives rela-

tively high yields in the dry season but low yields in the rainy season, were planted at 20 x 20 cm spacing with 0, 30, 60, 90, and 120 kg/ha N.

At optimum nitrogen level (120 kg/ha N) Taichung (Native) 1 gave high yields fairly consistently. On the other hand, Peta (at 90 kg/ha N) showed a bigger difference in grain yield which might have been larger if the rainy season of 1965 had not been unusually favorable (Fig. 16). Based on the yield data, Taichung (Native) 1 was considered to be typical of varieties with wide adaptability, and Peta typical of those with narrow adaptability. On this basis, various plant characters were analyzed for possible association with the adaptability.

Peta was much taller than Taichung (Native) 1. Both varieties were taller in the wet than in the dry season. Differences in height between seasons and nitrogen levels were much larger in Peta than in Taichung (Native) 1 (Fig. 17, left).

The panicle-straw ratio of Taichung (Native) 1 was much larger than that of Peta and showed smaller variation in both seasons (Fig. 17, right).

In both varieties LAI increased with nitrogen level and, at flowering, was larger in Peta than in Taichung (Native) 1. At high nitrogen levels, LAI for Peta was larger in the wet season than in the dry but the relationship was reversed for Taichung (Native) 1 (Fig. 18, left).

Leaf thickness at flowering decreased with an increase in nitrogen level and was also less in the wet than in the dry season. It did not vary between seasons with Peta as much as with Taichung (Native) 1 (Fig. 18, right).

Among the various characters observed, height and panicle-straw ratio in plants at rather high nitrogen levels, and flanked in different seasons, are those that can be measured easily and are closely associated with degree of adaptability.

TABLE 7. Summarized data of grain yield from maximum yield trials in several countries.

Country			Grain yield (ton/ha)	Total dry matter production (ton/ha)
Japan			8.08	14.1
Taiwan	1st crop		7.15	13.4
	2nd crop		5.80	11.3
Philippines	Rainy season	Local variety	3.36	14.0
		Improved variety	5.01	13.4
	Dry season	Local variety	5.86	15.1
		Improved variety	7.61	14.5
Malaysia	Main season		2.46	10.1
	Off season		4.32	11.0
Australia			9.72	14.5

POTENTIAL RICE YIELD IN TROPICAL ASIA

A project on the growth process of the rice plant as related to variation in environmental factors was started in 1963. The emphasis is on tropical Asia but Japanese and Australian data are included for comparative purposes.

In 1964-65, this project was continued at 12 sites in five countries in which cooperative experiment stations and farmers tried to obtain maximum

rice yields. Each station or farm was free to use all available techniques and one of the best available varieties. In the Philippines, there were two sets of experiments, one using the best local varieties, and another using varieties that proved to be promising at IRRI (Tainan 3 or Taichung (Native) 1).

Summarized yield data are shown in Table 7. Though the number of trials

has not been large enough to make any conclusive statement, it is apparent that the highest yield was obtained in Australia and the next highest in Japan. There was a marked seasonal difference in the tropics: the first crop in Taiwan, the dry season in the Philippines, and the off-season in Malaysia gave much higher yields than the second wet season, and main season crop, respectively. The yield in the better season was more than 1.5 ton/ha higher than in the other season.

The yield with improved varieties in the Philippines in the dry season was

low yield in Malaysia may be due, partly, to the varieties used.

Total dry matter production ranged from 10.1 to 15.1 ton/ha. The relatively low values in Malaysia may be related to extremely low content of potassium, manganese, and silica in the plants. However, in other places the total dry matter produced was more than 13 ton/ha. Total dry matter production was not related to grain yield but dry matter increase after flowering was positively related to grain yield (Fig. 19, left).

The duration of the flowering to har-

Fig. 19. Grain yield correlated with plant-weight increase after flowering and days from flowering to harvest.

as high as 8 ton/ha. Such a high yield was possible only with improved varieties; the difference in grain yield between one of the best Philippine varieties and improved varieties was at least 1.5 ton/ha in both seasons. The

vest period seemed to be related to grain yield; if longer than 40 days, yields were frequently high but if less than 40 days there was a wide variation in grain yield (Fig. 19, right). The duration of this period was related to the

average temperature during the period. The lower the temperature, the longer the maturing period (Fig. 20, top). But there was no apparent relationship be-

Fig. 20. Correlation of mean temperature during ripening with duration from flowering to harvest and with grain yield.

tween temperature during ripening and grain yield (Fig. 20, bottom). When temperature was low, the period from flowering to harvest was long and total sunshine, in many cases, large. Even if the temperature was high and the duration from flowering to harvest therefore short, if there was plenty of sunshine during this period, as during the dry season in the Philippines, the yield was high.

These data indicate that in the wet season in the tropics a yield of about 6 tons is possible if improved varieties are grown under intensive management. A high yield (exceeding 8 tons) probably is more frequent in temperate regions where temperature during ripening is rather low. However, a high temperature during ripening does not necessarily result in a low grain yield. If a high temperature is accompanied by abundant sunshine, grain yield can exceed 8 tons.

In some experiments, such as at Bukit Merah, Malaysia, plant mineral contents were apparently subnormal, i.e., low in potassium, manganese and silica. In such cases high yields cannot be expected unless appropriate measures are taken to correct soil deficiencies or otherwise ameliorate soil conditions.

RESPONSE TO PHOTOPERIOD

Varietal response to photoperiod

Surveys of the flowering response of varieties to different photoperiods are being continued. Table 8 shows additional data on varieties tested during 1964-65.

Growth duration and leaf number response to different photoperiods

The response of BPI-76, a highly photosensitive variety from the Philippines, to different photoperiods was examined. The plants were subjected from germination to flowering to photoperiod: 8, 10, 12, 13, 14, and 20 hours.

Figure 21 shows the number of days from sowing to flowering of plants grown under different photoperiods. Photoperiods longer than 13 hours greatly delayed flowering. The leaf

Fig. 21. Effect of different photoperiods on days to flower and number of leaves.

TABLE 8. Photoperiod response of different varieties.

Variety	Origin	Photoperiod (hr)											BVP ^a	PSP ^b
		8	10	12	13	14	16	24						
Milfor-6(2)	Philippines	—	108	108	106	111	—	104	69	5				
IR9-60	IRRI	—	80	86	80	92	89	87	45	12				
Kaohsiung 68	Taiwan	—	104	107	98	113	118	120	63	22				
BPI-76 (Maligaya)	Philippines	77	70	85	99	114	110	—	35	44				
BM 5	Malaysia	72	64	80	112	119	121	—	29	57				
Bengawan	Philippines	—	79	119	115	133	139	142	44	63				
Norin 18	Japan	—	61	73	74	120	138	—	38	65				
Tjere Mas	Philippines	—	73	105	105	134	133	145	38	72				
Radin Kling	Malaysia	67	67	77	94	139	137	139	32	72				
Radin Siak 34	Malaysia	106	88	116	146	153	171	168	53	83				
Unbanjoo	Korea	—	53	56	77	82	140	—	18	87				
Sk. 36 Str. 482	Philippines	80	73	125	c	c	c	c	38	127+				
Raminad Str. 3	Philippines	71	69	121	c	c	c	c	34	131+				
Radin China 4	Malaysia	66	65	116	c	c	c	c	30	135+				
Siam 29	Philippines	62	61	112	c	c	c	—	26	139+				
Engkatek	Malaysia	61	60	107	c	c	c	c	25	140+				
Siam 48	Malaysia	51	51	80	c	c	c	—	16	149+				
Serendah Kuning 60	Malaysia	58	51	109	c	c	c	—	16	149+				

^a BVP = Basic vegetative phase.^b PSP = Photoperiod sensitive phase.^c No panicle emerged after 200 days of growth.

number was almost parallel to the number of days to flower, possibly indicating that under increasing photoperiods the vegetative phase was prolonged more than the reproductive phase.

BPI-76 produced a minimum of nine leaves at flowering when grown under 10 hours of light. This would mean that at the time of panicle initiation, the plant had about four fully developed leaves, one leaf emerging, and four immature leaves. At a 4-leaf stage or earlier, the plant was apparently responsive to variations in photoperiod.

TABLE 9. Photoinductive cycles needed at different photoperiods.

Photoperiod (hours)	No. of cycles	Days to initiation
10	5	a
10	6	a
10	8	18
10	10	15
10	12	14
10	Continuous	13
11	6	a
11	8	28
11	10	17
11	12	14
11	Continuous	13
12	18	a
12	20	a
12	22	a
12	24	36
12	30	35
12	Continuous	35

^a No initiation after 100 days of growth, starting from treatment.

At 12 hours of photoperiod, it produced 14 leaves. This suggests that either the plant was not receptive until the 9-leaf stage when grown at 12 hours of light or it was receptive after the 4-leaf stage but the photoperiodic effect was not intense enough under the 12-hour photoperiod.

Photoinductive cycles needed at different photoperiods

This experiment was to determine if the minimum number of photoinductive cycles necessary for photoinduction is different at different photoperiods.

BPI-76 was grown under a 24-hour photoperiod for 35 days and then sub-

jected to different numbers of photoinductive cycles at different photoperiods, after which the plants were transferred back to the 24-hour photoperiod. Four plants were dissected until the stage when the panicle primordium was visible to the naked eye (around 1 mm). The date of this stage was then taken as the date of the inflorescence initiation.

The minimum photoinductive cycles required for initiation varied with the photoperiod used (Table 9). At 10- and 11-hour photoperiods, 8 cycles were

TABLE 10. Effect of plant age on photoperiod sensitivity.

Plant age (Days from soaking to beginning of photoinductive treatment)	Panicle initiation		Flowering stage (days after sowing)
	Days after treatment	Days from sowing	
11	—	—	b
13	a	a	b
15	26	41	b
17	21	38	b
19	19	38	73
21	18	39	73
23	16	39	74
Control	37	37	58

^a No panicle initiation after 200 days.

^b No panicle emergence after 200 days.

needed, and at 12-hour photoperiods, 24 cycles were needed for initiation. More cycles were needed with a longer photoperiod. Two cycles differing between treatments frequently made a big difference in days to initiation of flowering.

At the minimum number of photoinductive cycles needed for different photoperiods, the short photoperiods resulted in initiation of panicle primordia earlier than did the long photoperiods. In the three photoperiods used, the more photoinductive cycles, the earlier the initiation.

These observations support the impression that the "flowering" intensity at a 12-hour photoperiod is not as great as that at a 10-hour photoperiod so that more cycles are needed at the 12-hour photoperiod. They also largely explain why plants at a 10-hour photoperiod flower earlier than those at a 12-hour

TABLE 11. Flowering of tillers formed before, during and after short-day treatment and grain yield with various photoinductive cycles.

No. photo-inductive cycles	Treatment to flowering (days)	No. tillers	No. panicles	Tillers formed						Grain weight (g/plant)
				Before treatment		During treatment		After treatment		
				Flower-ing	Not flowering	Flower-ing	Not flowering	Flower-ing	Not flowering	
10	46	42.0	11.5	10.0	0.0	1.0	8.5	0.0	22.5	33.8
14	40	32.5	16.5	8.5	0.0	8.0	5.0	0.0	11.0	55.7
18	38	31.5	16.0	7.5	0.0	8.5	6.5	0.0	9.0	60.3
22	37	31.5	26.0	10.0	0.0	16.0	3.5	0.0	2.0	78.7
28	35	26.0	22.0	8.5	0.0	13.5	4.0	0.0	0.0	73.5

photoperiod even though either may be short enough eventually to induce flowering.

The basic vegetative phase

The basic vegetative phase (bvp) is the early growth period of the rice plant in which the photoinductive cycles have no effect on the initiation of the panicle primordium. In the previous experiment, the flowering of BPI-76 occurred in 52 days at a 10-hour photoperiod. As it takes about 35 days from the start of the photoinduction to flowering, the bvp is about 17 days for BPI-76. The experiment was designed to check this assumption.

Plants were grown at a 24-hour photoperiod and given 14 10-hour photoinductive cycles after a specified number of days of growth ranging from 11 to 23 days. The control plants were grown under a continuous 10-hour photoperiod.

Table 10 shows that panicle initiation occurred in 15-day-old plants given 14 photoinductive cycles but that it was earlier in the 17-day-old plants. The 3-day delay in panicle initiation of the 15-day-old plants may indicate that the bvp of BPI-76 is longer than 15 days. The 15-day-old plants had to reach the 17-day threshold before initiating the panicle primordium. A bvp of around 17 days as found in this experiment agrees with the calculated value.

Although the 17- to 23-day-old plants initiated panicle primordia more or less on the same calendar date, the panicle primordia of the older plants were visible after fewer photoinductive cycles.

In the 15- and 17-day-old plants, although the panicle was initiated, flowering or panicle exertion did not occur even after 200 days from treatment. Possibly, 17 days is below the actual bvp so that the 14 photoinductive cycles given, which induced flowering in the older plants, was not sufficient to in-

TABLE 12. Length of leaf blade, leaf sheath and first internode of tillers formed before and during the photoinductive treatments (cm).

No. cycles	Tillers formed	Leaf blade	Leaf sheath	First internode
10	Before treatment	61.9	41.9	37.9
	During treatment	80.3	41.8	18.5
14	Before treatment	44.6	41.4	43.9
	During treatment	53.8	41.4	41.3
18	Before treatment	39.9	39.4	41.1
	During treatment	48.5	39.2	35.6

duce flowering in the younger ones. The fact that panicle initiation can occur but not exertion indicates that the latter does not completely depend on the initiation. A difference of one photoinductive cycle may determine whether the panicle will be exerted.

Effect of number of photoinductive cycles on plant characters

When BPI-76 is planted at Los Baños during the off-season (February, March and April) flowering is delayed and extremely irregular. There are also more ineffective tillers, and flag leaves are longer.

In rice each plant may have many tillers. In the field some of these are formed before the photoinductive day-lengths occur and some are formed during or after this. The behavior of the tillers may differ according to when they were formed and such differences may explain why plant characters are different from one season to another.

To examine this assumption, BPI-76 was grown under a 14-hour photoperiod for 25 days and then shifted to a 10-hour photoperiod. After receiving specified numbers of 10-hour photoperiods (10, 14, 18, 22, and 28) the plants were returned to a 14-hour photoperiod.

The more photoinductive cycles received, the earlier was the first flower-

ing (Table 11). The number of leaves on the main culm was more or less the same, 14 for all treatments. Plants that received more photoinductive cycles had fewer tillers but more panicles than plants that received fewer photoinductive cycles.

All tillers formed before the photoinductive treatments flowered; those formed after the discontinuation of treatments did not flower. Some tillers formed during the short dry treatment flowered, whereas others did not; the fewer photoinductive cycles given, the fewer panicle-bearing tillers produced (Table 11).

The length of the panicle and the leaf blade of the flag leaf decreased as the number of photoinductive cycles was increased. The tillers formed before the photoinductive treatments had shorter flag leaves than the tillers formed during the treatment. There was little variation in the leaf sheath length. The length of the internodes of tillers formed during the treatment were shorter than those formed before the treatment (Table 12).

The grain yield per plant increased with the number of photoinductive cycles (Table 11). This increase was mainly the result of more panicles. With more photoinductive cycles, the number of spikelets per panicle increased, but

TABLE 13. Effect of photoperiods on emergence and size of panicles.

Number 10-hr-cycles	Additional photo- period treatment (hr)	Days after 10-hr-cycles to flowering	Panicle length (cm)	First internode length (cm)
10	10	39	23	30
	12	53	31	35
	13	60	43	26
	14	62	44	27
	16	65	46	20
	24	Not flowered	—	—
	15	10	38	23
12		44	28	37
13		46	29	37
14		47	29	38
16		46	29	40
24		46	26	38

the percentage of sterility also tended to increase so that the difference in the number of grains per panicle was not large.

Plants grown during the off-season have daylengths that lengthen with growth so that late tillers are exposed to long daylengths. Off-season plants also receive fewer photoinductive cycles, and fewer tillers receive sufficient photoinductive cycles. These off-season plants are comparable to the plants in this experiment that received only 10 photoinductive cycles.

The long panicle and flag leaf observed during the off-season appear to be due to the fewer photoinductive cycles received. In this season many tillers are formed during and after the photoinductive daylengths, resulting in a high proportion of non-bearing tillers and a low grain yield.

Evidence strongly suggests that some of the quantitative and morphological differences noted between the regular and the off-season result mainly from the number of photoinductive cycles received by the plant and from the time at which the photoinductive cycles occur.

Effect of photoperiod on panicle emergence and size

Previous experiments have shown that photoperiod treatment affects the degree of panicle exertion. Preliminary results indicated that panicle exertion was delayed in plants receiving fewer photoinductive cycles. Sometimes the

panicle was not fully exerted until maturity.

BPI-76 plants, after being grown under a 24-hour photoperiod for 30 days, were divided into two sets: one set was subjected to 10 cycles of 10-hour photoperiod, which is about the minimum number needed to initiate the panicle primordium, and a second set was exposed to 10-hour photoperiods for 15 cycles or until the panicle primordium was visible (1-2 mm). Each set was then sub-divided into six groups treated at 10-, 12-, 13-, 14-, 16-, and 24-hour photoperiods.

As shown in Table 13, all plants given 10 photoinductive cycles flowered. Panicle exertion was delayed if the plants were transferred to longer photoperiods after the 10-hour cycles. If the panicle primordium had been initiated or the plants were given 15 photoinductive cycles, the subsequent length of photoperiod had almost no effect on panicle exertion except in the 10-hour treatment which caused exertion to be about 8 days earlier than the other treatments. Apparently, the extra five cycles beyond the minimum requirement were enough for normal elongation of internodes and eventual exertion of the panicle.

The length of the panicle and first internode were not affected by photoperiod if the plants were given 15 photoinductive cycles. In plants that received only 10 cycles panicles became longer and internodes shorter as the subsequent photoperiod was lengthened.

WATER AND GROWTH

Transpiration ratio

Solar radiation, which influences dry matter production through its role in photosynthesis, also controls transpiration. While different wave lengths are involved in the two processes, they both have a common source, and it may be expected that dry matter production (W) and transpiration (T) will be parallel and that the transpiration ratio (W/T) will be constant.

To test this thesis, Milfor-6(2) was grown in culture solution, one plant per

pot in populations of 5 x 5 pots with 30 x 30 cm spacing between plants. The standard culture solution used was renewed weekly or more frequently to insure abundant water and nutrients throughout the life cycle. Plants at the periphery and center of the population were referred to as 'outer' and 'inner' plants respectively. Samples were collected at maximum tiller number stage, flowering, maturity, and the transpiration ratio was computed from data on plant weight and water transpired.

At harvest, the weights of outer and inner plants were 240 and 100 g, respectively, indicating the magnitude of difference in mutual shading between inner and outer plants. The transpiration ratios were fairly constant (Table 14) and tended to increase with plant age, possibly because of an increased

TABLE 14. Transpiration ratio of plants situated at different positions within a population at different growth stages.

Growth period	Position of plants	
	Outer	Inner
Transplanting-maximum tillering	287	282
Transplanting-flowering	307	282
Transplanting-maturity	348	388

ratio of respiration to photosynthesis. There was no consistent difference between plant positions.

The consistency of transpiration ratio, at least at early growth stages, demonstrates the parallel nature of transpiration and dry matter production. On the bases of the observed transpiration ratio of 280, and using the value of solar energy needed for evapotranspiration as estimated by the Agricultural Engineering Department (932 cal/g), the efficiency of solar radiation for dry matter production was about 1.4% assuming 1 g of dry matter is equivalent to 3,600 cal.

Transpiration, moisture content, leaf temperature, and apparent assimilation

To examine the relationship between light intensity and transpiration, measurements were made at 30-minute intervals from morning to evening of the transpiration of sand-cultured plants at booting stage with concomitant measurements of light intensity. The pots were divided into two groups: one group was kept flooded, and in the other group, to simulate upland conditions the culture solution was drained away in the evening previous to the day of measurement.

In the flooded group, transpiration

increased with increase of light intensity. Under the upland conditions, transpiration was less than under flooded conditions at the same light intensity. This indicates that although transpiration is a function of solar radiation, under upland conditions water movement from the roots cannot keep pace with

Fig. 22. Change in moisture content of various organs of rice plants after being subjected to reduced water supply.

evaporation from the leaves and transpiration therefore declines.

After draining the pots, the moisture content in all organs decreased with time; the decrease was most abrupt in the old leaves. The leaf sheath and culm maintained a fairly constant value for a long period and then started to lose moisture. The fourth leaf, which was the active center leaf at that growth stage, maintained a constant moisture content for the longest period (Fig. 22).

In another experiment with detached leaves it was demonstrated that the younger leaves hold water longer than older ones, indicating that when plants are subject to water stress the old leaves lose moisture rapidly and die. On the other hand, the active center leaf maintains a fairly constant moisture content for a longer period by its strong water-retaining capacity and also, pos-

sibly, at the expense of moisture in the leaf sheath and culm.

Under lowland conditions, the water supply from roots to leaves is ample and transpiration is parallel to the energy input of solar radiation. Under upland conditions, however, soil water supply is limiting, the rate of water supply to the leaves cannot match the rate of evaporation from the leaves, and the transpiration is less than under lowland conditions.

When transpiration is parallel to the energy input, heat energy will be removed by evaporation, but if transpiration cannot match the energy input, the leaf temperature may rise.

To test this supposition, rice plants were grown in soil placed in long cement pipes in a greenhouse; some pipes were kept under lowland conditions and the others under upland conditions in which the water table was maintained at 50 cm below the soil surface. Leaf temperature was measured by a thermistor with its sensitive side against the upper surface of the leaf.

The temperature of leaves of upland rice was higher than that of leaves of

plants grown under lowland conditions. The difference was negligible at night but larger during daytime when light intensity was high (Fig. 23). Thus, it can be concluded that if transpiration does not match the energy input of solar radiation, leaf temperature increases.

To test the change in apparent assimilation rate of plants under water stress conditions, the culture solution was drained at mid-day from pots in which rice plants were sand-cultured; the change in apparent assimilation rate was followed with time, starting just before draining. The moisture content of the leaf blade was also measured periodically.

The apparent assimilation rate decreased with the decrease of moisture content of leaf blades and eventually became a negative value (Fig. 24). From these data it can be concluded that when soil water supply is limited, the moisture content of leaves decreases, the transpiration becomes slower, the leaf temperature under a high light intensity increases, and the apparent assimilation rate decreases.

Fig. 23. Diurnal change in difference of leaf temperature between upland and lowland grown rice plants and light intensity.

Fig. 24. Relation between apparent assimilation and moisture content of leaves subjected to water stress condition.

Interaction between water regime and light intensity

The degree of moisture stress is a function of the balance between energy input and rate of water supply from roots to leaves. If this is so, under upland conditions where the rate of water supply to leaves is lower, a reduction in the energy input may lessen moisture stress.

On this assumption, in the 1965 dry season, PI 215936 was grown with 120 kg/ha N in split applications at three growth stages. There were three water regimes: lowland, irrigated upland (sprinkled every week), and rainfed upland. Two light regimes were superimposed on these water regimes: natural light and 70% natural light.

On a fine day at booting stage, diurnal changes in leaf blade content were followed. The moisture content of the lowland plants was higher than that of the upland plants and decreased during daytime. Under reduced light, the moisture content was higher and the decrease during daytime was smaller (Fig. 25). With natural light, the lowland rice yield exceeded that of the

Fig. 25. Diurnal change of moisture content of leaf blade under different water regimes and under natural and reduced light intensity in the field on a cloudless day.

other water treatments. With reduced light intensity, grain yield decreased for lowland rice but increased in upland rice, especially in the rainfed upland treatment (Table 15).

These data demonstrate that under lowland conditions, light is the factor limiting yield. However, under upland conditions, moisture content of the leaves is the critical factor; reduced light lessens water stress, and grain yield is increased.

TABLE 15. Grain yield of PI 215936 under various water regimes with natural and reduced light condition, 1965 dry season.

Light treatment	Lowland	Irrigated upland	Rainfed upland
	(ton/ha)		
Natural	7.15	6.01	0.74
Shaded	6.10	6.20	1.37

OBSERVATIONS ON MINERAL NUTRITIONAL DISTURBANCES IN ASIA

General survey of nutritional disturbances

Physiological diseases of the rice plant, as caused by submerged soil conditions, have been reported in a number of countries. Such diseases have local names but their causes have usually not been identified, and there have been few or no comparative studies made of diseases from different countries. There are also certain growth disturbances that are, or appear to be, caused by soil problems not necessarily associated with soil inundation.

Over the past 3 years, extensive surveys have been made of the physiological disease problem over parts of Ceylon, Java (Indonesia), Japan, Malaysia, the Philippines, and Taiwan. During traverses through the countryside, plant and soil samples were collected from fields in which plants were abnormal but not obviously suffering from pathogenic disease, pest attack, or drought. Apparent nitrogen deficiency was common, but samples were not collected from such situations.

Selected data from plant analyses are given in Table 16. As the plants sampled were at different growth stages, it is impossible to discuss the data in detail, but some general suggestions on the cause of the disturbances can be made in many cases.

"Bronzing" in Ceylon, consisted of a bronze discoloration of the leaves, starting as small dots on the lower leaves; in severe cases whole leaves became bronze in color. Plant samples have low contents of potassium, magnesium, phosphorus and silica, and high amounts of iron. The Bombuwela sample was low in manganese. The sample collected from a lateritic soil in Malacca had identical symptoms and was characterized by high iron, low silica, and low manganese.

The samples collected at Nagrek, West Java, were characterized by stunted growth, weak tillering, browning and death of lower leaves, and reddish, narrow upper leaves. The condition is reputedly a type of "mentek." The plant sample was high in iron and aluminum,

and low in phosphorus. At Lohbener, a condition known locally as "omo merah" had narrow leaves with brown spots, and many dark brown dead lower leaves. The mineral content of samples was similar to that at Nagrek. The sample from Djublen of a condition known locally as "ama merah" was characterized by green narrow upper leaves and brown dead lower leaves. The mineral content of the plant was similar to that of the samples from Nagrek and Lohbener but the sodium content was also high.

The abnormal plants at Sumber Bandung were suffering from what is known locally as "prekeke." The plants had weak tillering, dark green upright upper leaves, and orange-yellow lower leaves — all typical symptoms of phosphorus deficiency. This type of disorder was widely distributed on latosols around Djakarta. The plant samples were low in phosphorus and high in iron and aluminum.

The plant sample at Banten was collected from a swampy coastal area where soils are high in undecomposed organic substances. Rice plants were growing well but the leaves had many brown spots. The mineral content was normal apart from a rather high calcium content.

At Kitakami, Japan, the soils were derived from volcanic ash (Ando soil). Plants in some fields exhibited typical phosphorus deficiency symptoms and were low in phosphorus and magnesium but high in manganese. In other fields that were newly converted into paddy fields from upland fields, and especially those newly developed from forest, plants were suffering from "Akagare type III," characterized by irregular brown spots which develop from the tips of lower leaves. Plants were low in magnesium and silica.

Typical symptoms of "Akagare types I, II and III" were observed in pot cultures at the National Institute of Agricultural Sciences, Konosu, Japan. "Akagare type I" plants had low potassium and silica, rather high calcium and iron, and high sodium contents.

TABLE 16. Analysis of plants suffering from various nutritional disturbances in Asia.

	P (%)	K (%)	Ca (%)	Mg (%)	Fe (ppm)	Mn (ppm)	Al (ppm)	SiO ₂ (%)	Na (%)	Note
<i>Ceylon</i>										
Pussellawa	0.16	0.50	0.18	0.12	760	262	177	7.75	0.84	Bronzing
Batalagoda	0.11	2.10	0.27	0.25	530	654	296	12.35	1.34	("Akiochi"?)
Bombuwela	0.18	0.80	0.47	0.13	950	66	289	4.38	0.91	Bronzing
Karapincha	0.21	0.75	0.11	0.06	600	249	156	6.68	1.20	Bronzing
<i>West Java, Indonesia</i>										
Nagrek	0.09	2.47	0.46	0.29	1533	43	720	10.0	0.24	A type of "mentek" (?)
Lohbener	0.10	2.67	0.45	0.38	1516	313	694	9.8	0.65	"Omo merah"
Djublén	0.15	1.79	0.47	0.49	1355	375	728	9.3	2.88	"Prekeke" (P deficiency?)
Sumber Bandung	0.09	2.36	0.36	0.27	1183	575	459	9.3	0.65	"Ama merah"
Banten	0.20	2.50	0.59	0.38	336	125	292	9.9	1.07	Dark-green leaves with brown spots
<i>Japan</i>										
Kitakami	0.08	2.84	0.34	0.14	196	1400	289	8.43	1.88	P deficiency
Kitakami	0.15	3.08	0.30	0.14	193	600	185	3.56	1.68	"Akagare type III"
Chiba	0.32	1.49	0.70	0.27	443	88	129	4.02	2.80	"Akagare type I"
Chiba	0.38	3.19	0.73	0.38	502	150	222	5.02	2.01	"Akagare type II"
Mikatagahara	0.08	2.28	0.45	0.08	228	556	295	3.41	1.64	"Akagare type III"
Himeji	0.25	3.55	0.42	0.20	184	656	181	7.76	1.04	"Akiochi"

<i>Malaya</i>										
Malacca acid soil	0.23	2.36	0.29	0.20	648	40	408	6.8	2.34	Brown spots, Interveinal chlorosis (Bronzing)
Malacca laterite	0.19	1.99	0.31	0.20	608	68	204	5.5	0.62	
<i>Philippines</i>										
Bilar, Bohol	0.20	0.49	1.30	0.27	165	78	245	5.86	1.36	K deficiency <i>Helminthosporium</i> spots Same as above
Carcar, Cebu	0.06	1.08	0.95	0.39	168	31	90	8.16	3.17	
Makilala, Cotabato	0.18	2.50	0.35	0.37	947	469	170	10.82	1.24	Stunted, old leaves dying. Deep anthocyanin pigment (BPI-76) Same as above
Ginoo, Davao	0.22	3.09	0.28	0.95	1400	156	279	9.66	1.64	
Bueno Suerte	0.05	1.95	0.46	0.28	588	750	200	11.1	1.15	P deficiency. <i>Helminthosporium</i> -like spots
<i>Taiwan</i>										
Ilan	0.19	2.34	0.36	0.43	178	1825	299	7.7	0.93	Suffocation disease
Pingtung	0.12	2.44	0.37	0.36	144	338	184	10.1	0.91	Same as above

TABLE 17. Some chemical characters of soils on which nutritional disorder of rice plants were observed.

Soils	pH	C (%)	C E C (me/100 g)	Exchangeable cations (me/100 g)			Phosphorus absorbing power (mg/100 g)	KCl extractable Al	Active Fe (%)	Reducible Mn (ppm)
				K	Na	Ca				
<i>Acid-sulfate soils</i>										
Malacca	3.52	19.0	41.3	0.23	2.83	0.80	2.80	282	1.036	0.5
Vietnam	3.70	7.7	24.0	0.36	2.44	1.70	5.80	274	0.330	10.0
<i>Coralline calcareous soils</i>										
Bilar	7.40	14.8	40.9	0.18	0.30	47.0	4.30	1.3	0.088	7.0
<i>Soils producing bronzing</i>										
Pussellawa	5.18	4.0	9.5	0.17	0.26	2.0	1.2	7.2	0.508	8.0
Bombuwela	5.15	2.3	3.6	0.15	0.17	2.0	1.2	7.0	0.159	0.8
Karapincha	5.15	2.9	5.2	0.15	0.17	1.5	1.2	8.7	0.280	23.0
Malacca laterite	4.80	5.3	8.1	0.31	0.30	2.0	1.2	34.0	0.574	4.0

"Akagare type II" plants had rather high calcium and iron contents. "Akagare type III" plants were low in phosphorus, magnesium and silica.

The plant sample from Himeji was a case of typical "akiochi," characterized by *Helminthosporium* spots and death of lower leaves. The analysis did not show any special abnormality except rather low contents of silica and magnesium. The symptoms of the sample from Batalagoda, Ceylon, were more or less identical with "akiochi."

The plants on Malacca acid-sulfate soils had brown spots on the leaves; newly planted young plants showed interveinal chlorosis. Aluminum content was also quite high. The plants were high in iron and low in manganese.

The plant samples from Bilar, Bohol, and Carcar, Cebu, the Philippines, were collected from the paddy fields on soils derived from coralline limestones. Plants had many *Helminthosporium*-like spots and appeared to be deficient in potassium. The samples were low in potassium and in some cases, phosphorus, and high in calcium. Manganese and silica contents were low. The sample from Carcar was high in sodium.

The plants (BPI-76) at Makilala, Cotabato, were stunted, lower leaves were dead and upper leaves were highly anthocyanin pigmented. They appeared deficient in phosphorus. The analyzed samples were rather low in phosphorus and high in iron.

The plants at Ginoo, Davao, had symptoms similar to those at Makilala. The soil was peat-mixed with volcanic ash. The plant sample was high in iron.

At Bueno Suerte, Bohol, the plants showed phosphorus deficiency symptoms. They were low in phosphorus but rather high in iron and aluminum.

The plants at Ilan, Taiwan, were suffering from what is known locally as "suffocation disease." They had brown leaf spots and dead lower leaves, symptoms similar to those of potassium deficiency. The sample collected was not low in potassium, however; it was high in manganese. The one at Pingtung was also suffering from "suffocation disease." The analysis did not show any abnormality.

The impression gained during the survey was that in most parts of south-east Asia, little attempt has been made to amend the mineral nutritional status of the soils; the correlations between soil analysis and plant analysis are therefore much more apparent in these areas than where large amounts of fertilizers have been applied. Thus, this survey-type of approach is promising as a method of establishing a good understanding of soil-plant relationships and in helping to identify the problems.

In some cases, the sample collected showed no abnormality in analysis and later proved to be affected by virus disease. Visual diagnosis of nutritional disturbances should be employed with some reserve because it is difficult to differentiate some types of nutritional disorders from virus diseases.

Helminthosporium-like spots were frequently observed in plants suffering from nutritional disorder. The relationship between nutritional status of plants and incidence of *Helminthosporium* will be an important subject of future study.

Disorder on acid-sulfate soil

Acid-sulfate soils from Malacca and Vietnam were studied. Such soils have low pH, a high cation exchange capacity due to a high content of organic substances, and are low in exchangeable cations and base saturation. They have much active aluminum but not necessarily active iron, are low in reducible manganese, and high in phosphorus-absorbing power (Table 17).

Successive leachates with water adjusted to pH 3.6 with H_2SO_4 were collected and analyzed for aluminum. Aluminum level in the leachates decreased successively (Table 18). After adding adequate ammonium sulfate to the leachates, rice seedlings were grown in them. The seedlings in the first to the fourth leachates were dead or abnormal but those in the fifth to the eighth leachates grew normally. This indicates that if rice plants were grown under upland conditions in these soils aluminum toxicity would be the cause of disturbance. The toxic level of aluminum in the

TABLE 18. Aluminum content of successive leachates from Malacca acid-sulfate soil and growth of rice seedling in them.

Leachate	Leachate		Al in plants grown in soil solution (ppm)	Condition of plant
	pH	Al (ppm)		
1st	3.7	71	352	Almost dead
2nd	3.7	55	252	Yellowing, brown streaks
3rd	3.7	42	234	Yellowing, brown streaks
4th	3.8	25	216	Few brown streaks
5th	3.8	21	162	Normal
6th	3.8	16	159	Normal
7th	3.8	11	113	Normal
8th	3.8	9	120	Normal

soils can be lowered, at least partly, by leaching.

When the soils were kept submerged, the aluminum level in the soil solution decreased and the iron level increased (Table 19). Rice seedlings grown in the submerged soils suffered from iron toxicity, the major cause of trouble with lowland rice on acid-sulfate soils. Manganese level in the soil solution tended to decrease after prolonged submergence; plants did not absorb manganese actively at low pH, and manganese toxicity is therefore improbable.

After CaCO_3 application, soil pH increased, the level of iron in the soil solution decreased, and plants grew well (Table 20). The soils were low in available phosphorus and plants suffered from a deficiency if no phosphorus was applied. The application of phosphorus

in small amounts appeared to accelerate soil reduction, increase iron level in the soil solution and cause more serious iron toxicity; however, plant growth was better than with no phosphorus application. A large phosphorus application decreased iron level in the soil solution and allowed plants to grow satisfactorily.

These data demonstrate that under upland conditions aluminum toxicity can cause trouble in acid-sulfate soils. However, under flooded conditions, iron toxicity is the major problem. The soils are high in phosphorus-fixing power and low in available phosphorus. Phosphorus application is therefore essential. Added calcium carbonate or phosphate lowers the iron level in the soil solution of submerged soils and improves the plant growth.

TABLE 19. Iron, aluminum and manganese content of soil solutions of acid-sulfate soils and those of seedlings grown in them.

	Vietnam acid soil		Malacca acid soil	
	Pre-incubation period (days)			
	0	30	0	30
	pH of soil			
	3.5	3.8	3.4	3.9
	Element content of soil solution (ppm)			
Fe	4.0	1232.0	22.0	1690.0
Al	35.0	0.8	35.0	0.8
Mn	9.6	13.0	5.3	2.0
	Element content of seedlings (ppm)			
Fe	1900	1750	3829	6057
Al	1041	368	1235	548
Mn	186	106	28	32
Condition of plant	Al tox. then Fe tox.	Fe tox.	Fe tox. then dead	Fe tox. then dead

TABLE 20. Effect of calcium carbonate and phosphate application on Vietnam acid-sulfate soil.

CaCO ₃ (g/pot)	Ca(H ₂ PO ₄) ₂ H ₂ O	Soil pH	Fe in soil solution (ppm)	Plant weight (g/plant)	Element content of plant		Symptom
					Fe (ppm)	P (%)	
0	0	4.35	322	0.35	320	0.07	P def.
	1.25	4.30	854	3.25	441	0.17	P def. + Fe tox.
	2.5	4.15	1246	4.37	630	0.23	Fe tox.
	5	4.20	1162	5.66	1031	0.31	Fe tox.
	10	4.25	238	7.56	153	0.37	Normal
25	0	5.20	126	1.10	253	0.09	P def.
	1.25	5.25	36	4.43	171	0.17	Normal
	2.5	5.30	53	5.86	144	0.23	Normal
	5	5.35	31	5.76	135	0.24	Normal
	10	5.40	35	10.56	135	0.28	Normal

Disorder on calcareous soils derived from coralline limestone

Rice plants growing on soils derived from coralline limestones on Bohol Island were extremely abnormal, characterized by weak tillering, yellowing and death of lower leaves, extremely weak straw and development of *Helminthosporium*-like spots; they have low potassium but high calcium contents.

The soils have a high pH, much calcium (mostly calcium carbonate) and organic material, but are low in exchangeable potassium. They are oversaturated with bases. Phosphorus-absorbing power is high due to high pH and the high calcium content (Table 17). Available potassium and phosphorus are low, and seedlings respond remarkably to application of these elements (Table 21).

When the soils were submerged, the calcium level in the soil solution increased markedly due to increased partial pressure of CO₂ and increased con-

centration of organic acids (Table 22). The specific conductance of the soil solution increased to 3,321 micromhos/cm 10 days after submergence. When the soil solution was exposed to the air, calcium carbonate was precipitated and the specific conductance dropped to 1,982 micromhos/cm.

A high level of calcium with a rather low level of potassium is the major cause of the disorder in lowland rice plants on this type of soil. To simulate such a condition, a culture solution experiment was conducted in which CaCO₃ was suspended in an ordinary culture solution and CO₂ was bubbled through. Potassium treatments were superimposed on the CaCO₃ + CO₂ treatment. At no or low potassium in the CaCO₃ + CO₂ treatment, symptoms similar to those observed on plants grown in the Bilar soil were observed: browning of midribs, irregular brown spots on the leaf blade starting from lower leaves, and yellowing and drying

TABLE 21. Effect of potassium and phosphorus on the growth of rice seedlings on coralline calcareous soil, Bilar, Bohol.

	Treatment		
	Complete	— P	— K
Dry weight (g/plant)	0.260	0.133	0.075
Element content			
P (%)	0.43	0.15	0.45
K (%)	0.05	4.87	1.58
Ca (%)	0.98	0.88	1.41

TABLE 22. Calcium, potassium and organic acids in successive leachates obtained from incubated calcareous soil from Bilar, Bohol.

Days after incubation	pH of soil	Ca (ppm in leachate)	K (ppm in leachate)	Organic acids (millinormal)
0	7.8	100	0.6	0.12
2	7.0	360	3.2	6.90
4	6.6	680	3.7	14.30
8	6.6	610	3.4	7.90
11	6.6	550	3.2	7.90
15	6.6	670	3.2	4.70

of the leaves from the tip. At high potassium levels, plants were normal even in the $\text{CaCO}_3 + \text{CO}_2$ treatment. Calcium content of the plant was much higher in the $\text{CaCO}_3 + \text{CO}_2$ treatment than in the control and it decreased with the increase in potassium level (Table 23).

In another culture solution experiment the symptoms developed with a combination of high calcium chloride and low potassium.

From these observations, it can be concluded that when calcareous soils are submerged, the CO_2 tension and the organic acid concentration in the soil increase. Calcium carbonate is converted to calcium bicarbonate or organic acid salts, which are high in solubility, and the calcium in the soil solution increases to a high level. This, together with a low level of potassium, results in the typical symptoms. Application of potassium not only increases the potassium content of the plants but also retards calcium uptake; plant growth is thereby improved. Solubility of phosphorus is low at high pH and with an abundance of calcium. Application of phosphorus may therefore be necessary also.

With this information from laboratory and greenhouse experiments, a trial was conducted in a farmer's field at Bilar in the 1965 wet season with Tai-chung (Native) 1 and Lubang; phosphorus and potassium were tested at several levels.

Application of phosphorus and potassium improved grain yield significantly (Table 24). There were also indications that split applications of potassium may be desirable. However, the results did not conclusively determine the optimum applications of phosphorus and potassium nor lead to a full understanding of the interaction between phosphorus and potassium levels. Further studies will be continued in the farmer's field.

"Bronzing"

In Ceylon, a physiological disease called "bronzing" occurs on sandy soils derived from acidic rocks such as those at Pusselawa, Bombuwela, and Karapincha. The soils contain a large amount of quartz sand and have rather low pH, low cation exchange capacity, low exchangeable cations, and low phosphorus-absorbing power. They do not contain excessive amounts of active iron, aluminum, or reducible manganese (Table 17).

Plants with bronzing symptoms were low in phosphorus, potassium, magnesium, silica, and frequently, calcium and manganese, but high in iron. Aluminum content was moderate.

Rice seedlings were grown for 30 days in Bombuwela soil placed in bottles to which culture solutions lacking various nutrient elements were added. The plants grown with the no-potassium culture solution exhibited serious "bronzing" symptoms in addition to po-

TABLE 23. The dry weight and content of potassium and calcium in the straw and the yield of rice plants grown in various levels of potassium interacted with a $\text{CaCO}_3 + \text{CO}_2$ treatment (40 days after planting).

	K (ppm)				
	0	3	10	40	200
	Control (40 ppm Ca)				
Dry weight (g/plant)	13.50	15.90	16.70	23.50	22.10
K (%)	0.40	0.68	1.18	2.80	3.40
Ca (%)	0.54	0.46	0.42	0.44	0.30
Panicle weight (g/plant)	0.90	17.50	53.60	68.70	93.60
	$\text{CaCO}_3 + \text{CO}_2$ (500 ppm Ca)				
Dry weight (g/plant)	4.70	8.90	14.40	17.1	17.50
K (%)	0.78	0.98	1.38	3.40	4.80
Ca (%)	1.70	1.56	1.44	1.36	1.16
Panicle weight (g/plant)	0.40	8.80	28.00	55.70	88.20

tassium deficiency symptom, and had low potassium and high iron contents (Table 25). The plants grown with the no-manganese solution also showed

Fig. 26. Relationships among phosphorus level in soil solution, phosphorus content of seedling, and weight of seedling.

Fig. 27. Effect of phosphorus application on seedling growth.

TABLE 24. Effect of phosphorus and potassium application of grain yield and element content of straw at flowering, Bilar, Bohol, 1965 rainy season.

P ₂ O ₅	K ₂ O	Grain yield (kg/ha)	Element content in straw at flowering		
			P (%)	K (%)	Ca (%)
0	300	2715	0.21	2.73	1.17
50	300	3114	0.25	2.68	1.05
100	300	2368	0.24	2.54	0.93
300	300	2347	0.27	2.18	0.91
300	300 (split)	2705	0.27	2.14	1.08
300	100	2087	0.27	1.51	1.18
300	100 (split)	2270	0.27	1.45	1.13
300	50	2246	0.27	1.32	1.22
300	0	1414	0.29	0.92	1.22
No fertilizer		1577	0.19	1.17	1.14
LSD		591			

Taichung (Native) 1 and Lubang were tested and data of the average of these two varieties are presented.

Potassium was applied in three equal split applications: basal, 40 days and 80 days after transplanting.

some "bronzing" symptoms and weak magnesium deficiency symptoms. They were moderately high in iron content. With the non-manganese solution,

Fig. 28. Effect of phosphorus application on phosphorus level in soil solution (3 days after application).

plants exhibited manganese deficiency symptoms and had low manganese and high iron contents but did not show "bronzing" symptoms. Phosphorus deficiency symptoms developed in plants in the no-phosphorus solution.

These results indicate that "bronzing" symptoms develop when plants are high in iron and simultaneously low in potassium and/or magnesium. Manganese was very low in the soil but a rela-

Fig. 29. Relation between exchangeable potassium in soil and potassium content of plants.

tion between low manganese and "bronzing" was not apparent. Phosphorus was also low in the soil, but "bronzing" did not appear to be directly related to low phosphorus.

The sample collected from Malacca lateritic soil had bronzing-like symptoms, and analyses of plant and soil gave results similar to those associated with true bronzing, indicating that the plants were in fact suffering from bronzing.

Low cation exchange capacity, low phosphorus-absorbing power, and low content of various nutrient elements of the soils on which bronzing occurs, indicate that management of this type of soil will be extremely difficult.

Varietal difference in bronzing re-

TABLE 25. Effect of nutrient deficiencies on the development of bronzing symptom and nutrient content of Peta grown in Bombuwela soil.

Treatment	Plant weight (g/plant)	Symptom	Nutrient content					
			P (%)	K (%)	Ca (%)	Mg (%)	Fe (ppm)	Mn (ppm)
Control	1.68	Healthy	0.26				410	93
— P	0.74	P def.	0.12	2.83	0.36	0.31	673	67
— K	0.47	Severe K def. & bronzing	0.27	0.47	0.27	0.51	2301	57
— Ca	1.11	Healthy	0.20	2.13	0.27	0.28	765	40
— Mg	1.20	Slight Mg def. & bronzing	0.23	2.37	0.36	0.23	763	62
— Mn	0.67	Mn def.	0.26	3.63	0.54	0.46	1140	17

sistance has been observed: Murungakayan 303 is more susceptible than H4. However, analyses of plants collected from the field and also from a greenhouse solution culture experiment, indicated that H4 was affected as badly as Murungakayan 303, but that the symptoms were very different. With H4, yellowing of leaf-tips occurs rather than bronzing. Identification of varietal differences in susceptibility to factors causing bronzing is therefore difficult and cannot be made on the basis of the degree of bronzing.

Phosphorus deficiency

Cases of obvious but different degrees of phosphorus deficiency were encountered during the survey, and analyses confirmed the observations. This implies that though the phosphorus problem is presently not considered serious, it may become one of the major problems of tropical rice cultivation when farmers adopt better management practices and good varieties.

Using soils on which phosphorus deficiency was observed, a bottle experi-

Fig. 30. Relation between exchangeable magnesium in soil and magnesium content of plants.

ment was conducted. Two hundred grams of each soil treated with adequate amounts of ammonium sulfate, potassium sulfate, and graded levels of calcium phosphate ($\text{Ca}(\text{H}_2\text{PO}_4)_2 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$) were placed in inverted small amber bottles from which the bottoms had been removed, and submerged for 3 days; a small sample of the soil solu-

tion was analyzed for phosphorus. Seedlings were grown in the soils for 3 weeks; a small sample of the soil solution was analyzed for phosphorus. Seedlings were grown in the soils for 3 weeks, harvested, and analyzed for phosphorus.

Where no phosphate was applied, there was a relationship between the phosphorus level in the soil solution and the phosphorus content of the seedlings (Fig. 26, top), and between phosphorus content of the seedlings and their weight (Fig. 26, bottom). These data indicate that phosphorus level in the soil solution is a good indicator of soil phosphorus supply.

Of the various types of phosphorus response curves, five prominent ones are presented in Fig. 27. With Kitakami soil, the response, although small due to residual phosphorus from past applications, was nevertheless evident up to the highest level of phosphorus applied. In

Fig. 31. Relation between readily reducible manganese in soil and manganese content of plants.

Bombuwela soil, the response was marked from 0 to 0.1 g level, but not at higher rates. In Luisiana clay, seedlings responded to applications up to the 1 g level. In Sumber Bandung soil, the response to 0.1 g was marked, but small beyond this with a negative effect at the 1 g level. In Maahas clay (IRRI soil), there was no response up to 0.5 g and then a negative effect from an application of 1 g.

Phosphorus content of the soil solution 3 days after flooding increased

with phosphorus application. In Bomuwela and Sumber Bandung soils, and especially in Maahas clay, the increase was large. However, it was small in Luisiana clay and negligible in Kitakami soil (Fig. 28).

Kitakami soil is an Ando soil formed from volcanic ash. Phosphorus-fixing power is extremely high and a large phosphorus application is necessary for satisfactory growth. It is high in active aluminum and organic matter, but the iron and aluminum contents of plants growing on the soil are not very high.

Bomuwela soil is derived from acidic rocks. The soils have low phosphorus-fixing power and phosphorus response is observed only at low phosphorus applications. The soils are low in active iron and aluminum. Plants growing on these soils are high in iron but rather low in aluminum, and exhibit "bronzing."

Luisiana clay appears to be at an early stage of lateritic weathering from basic rocks. Phosphorus-fixing power is high and responses occur to large applications of phosphorus. The soil contains large amounts of active iron and aluminum, associated plants have moderate contents of these elements.

Sumber Bandung soil has moderate phosphorus-fixing power and responses occur to only moderate phosphorus applications. The soil is high in active iron and moderate in active aluminum. Associated plants are frequently high in iron and aluminum; but bronzing does not develop.

Maahas clay is a young soil formed from basic materials. It is high in active iron but low in active aluminum, and has moderate phosphorus-fixing power. Iron content of associated plants is low, and with heavy phosphorus applications iron chlorosis develops.

Coralline calcareous soils and acid-sulfate soils are also low in available phosphorus as discussed earlier.

From this scattered information obtained by preliminary survey-type experiments, it is impossible to draw a generalized conclusion, but there are indications that interaction between soil phosphorus availability, pH, iron and

Fig. 32. Relation of silica level in leachate to silica content of seedling and acetate buffer (pH 4) soluble silica in soil.

aluminum is an important subject for future research.

Potassium deficiency

Potassium deficiency symptoms were observed in a few cases, and low potassium content without deficiency symptoms was noticed in several others.

Although plant samples were collected at several growth stages, and in some cases potassium fertilizer had been applied, the potassium content of the straw was fairly closely related to the exchangeable soil potassium (Fig. 29).

Rice plants on coralline limestones were low in potassium and suffered from potassium deficiency as described previously. Some soils in Ceylon are low in exchangeable potassium and have small cation exchange capacity; associated plants are deficient as described earlier.

Many soils, apparently latosols with small cation exchange capacities, were frequently low in exchangeable potassium, and associated plants had low potassium contents. On such soils some

response to potassium can be expected (as at Bueno Suerte in Table 26).

"Akagare type I" plants were low in potassium and rather high in calcium. Response of such plants to potassium has been demonstrated by many workers.

Potassium response was demonstrated in a bottle experiment (Table 26) with soils from Ilan and Pingtung in Taiwan. 'Suffocation disease' has been reported on these soils which have low cation exchange capacity and are more or less oversaturated due to relatively

TABLE 26. Response of rice seedlings to potassium in several soils.

Soil	Complete	— K
Maahas	2.28	2.11
Ilan	1.05	0.38
Pingtung	1.82	0.45
Bueno Suerte	2.20	1.54

200 g soil + 0.2 g of $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4$, 0.5 g of $\text{Ca}(\text{H}_2\text{PO}_4)_2 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$, and with and without 0.2 g of K_2SO_4 . Harvested 25 days after growth.

high calcium level. The pH is high. There are several soil features that may be responsible for the disease. At Ilan, the high manganese content may be the cause. Other soil features possibly implicated include the rather high calcium level, rendering the exchange complex oversaturated, combined with a low level of potassium and the increased CO_2 tension under flooded conditions.

Potassium may not be as serious as phosphorus as a practical fertilization problem of rice in the tropics. However, there are soils whose major problem is potassium deficiency though the area may be limited.

Magnesium deficiency

Low magnesium content of rice plants growing on sandy soils in Ceylon has been discussed in relation to "bronzing." The plants on volcanic ash soils in Japan (Kitakami, Mizusawa and Mikatagahara) were also low in magnesium (Table 16).

The relation between exchangeable magnesium in soil and the magnesium content of straw is shown in Fig. 30.

Some of the disorders in Ceylon and Japan (Table 16) may respond to magnesium application. However, except in extreme cases, magnesium deficiency is not likely to become a practical problem in rice cultivation in the near future.

Manganese deficiency

Culture solution experiments conducted at the Institute indicated that deficiency symptoms often develop with less than 20 ppm Mn, toxicity with more than 2,500 ppm Mn in the shoot, but these critical levels vary depending upon other factors.

Manganese content of plant samples collected from the fields ranged from less than 20 to 1,825 ppm. In some cases, the manganese content was suspected to be low enough to cause deficiency. Though manganese deficiency symptoms were observed in the field, response to manganese application may occur. High observed values were not high enough to cause toxicity, but it cannot be concluded that there were no cases of toxicity, since analysis was made only at a certain growth stage.

The manganese content of plant samples was plotted against readily reducible manganese in the soil (Hydroquinone method) (Fig. 31). The points

TABLE 27. Effect of silica level in culture solution on grain yield and element content of straw.

Silica level in culture solution (SiO_2 ppm)	Grain weight (g/plant)	Element content of straw					
		SiO_2 (%)	N (%)	P (%)	K (%)	Fe (ppm)	Mn (ppm)
0	125	0.16	1.84	0.24	2.40	140	215
5	147	1.25	1.74	0.22	2.40	134	205
15	143	1.83	1.74	0.22	2.40	131	120
25	124	2.31	1.66	0.20	2.40	120	115
50	153	3.40	1.44	0.17	2.05	93	65

representing soils from Pusselawa, Bombuwela, Ilan and Himeji, where physiological diseases have been reported, are much above the tentative correlation curve; points for other soils that had high organic matter contents are below the curve.

From a bottle experiment, a close relationship was proved between manganese content of seedlings and manganese level in the soil solution. It is apparent that the manganese level in the soil solution can give a good indication of the manganese-supplying power of the soil. However, readily reducible manganese is not a good indication, as shown by the wide scatter of points in Fig. 30.

Low silica content

Rice seedlings were grown for 3 weeks in bottles of soil supplied with adequate N, P, and K, harvested, and analyzed for available silica by extracting with pH 4 acetate buffer — a well-established method. In a separate experiment 30 g of each soil were leached in glass columns with 60 ml of water. The percolate was analyzed for silica.

Silica contents of seedlings were closely related to percolate silica (Fig. 32, top) which, in turn, was closely related, except for calcareous soil, to silica contents extracted with acetate buf-

fer (Fig. 32, bottom). The percolation method therefore appears adequate for a rapid estimate of the silica-supplying power of soils. The results also suggest that silica is probably absorbed by the plant through the soil solution.

Plant samples collected from various soils contained at least 2.5% silica, and 5% was common. Silica content was often low in plants suffering nutritional disorder, raising the question of whether low levels *per se* were responsible for the disorder.

The possibility was examined with Peta plants grown to maturity in solution cultures with various levels of silica (Table 27).

Plants containing small amounts of silica contained much more iron or manganese than those with normal silica contents, possibly indicating that, when iron or manganese is over-abundant in the soil, high silica plants may be protected against toxicity effects.

Rice plants suffering from various nutritional disorders often contain little silica because the supply from the soil is meager. But low plant silica is not in itself the direct cause of the disorders; a low soil silica supply may be associated with other soil features that are responsible; or a low silica supply may affect the uptake or distribution within the plant of other nutrients.

EFFECT OF ORGANIC SUBSTANCES IN SOILS

Straw application

In an experiment with nine varieties, the effect of applying straw to rice crops was examined during the 1965 dry season at the Institute farm. Straw was applied to 6 ton/ha 30 days and 1 day before transplanting. Two nitrogen treatments, 0 and 100 kg/ha, were superimposed on the straw treatments, and 40 kg/ha of both P_2O_5 and K_2O were applied uniformly.

Applying straw did not affect grain yield, and there were no interactions between varieties or nitrogen with straw application. In terms of grain yield, there were responses to nitrogen, varietal differences, and variety x nitrogen interactions (Table 28).

Possible residual effects of straw and nitrogen fertilizer were investigated during the subsequent wet season. Taichung (Native) 1 was grown over the experimental site but grain yields revealed no residual effects (Table 28).

During the 1965 wet season, the effect of larger quantities of straw, 12 and 24 ton/ha, was tested with six varieties. The straw was incorporated just before transplanting, and fertilizers were applied uniformly: 60 kg/ha N, and 40 kg/ha of both P_2O_5 and K_2O . With early maturing varieties, grain yields were depressed by applying straw, but there was no effect on late-maturing ones. The yield of Peta, an active vegetative variety, was increased by straw application (Table 29).

TABLE 28. Effect of straw application on rice grain yield in Maahas clay (ton/ha), 1965 dry season.

N level (kg/ha)	Straw application (6 ton/ha)		
	None	1 day before transplanting	30 days before transplanting
Effect of straw applied to the crop ^a			
0	3.63	3.64	3.61
100	4.26	4.24	4.40
Residual effect of straw applied to the previous crop ^b			
0 (0 ^c)	4.26	4.55	4.27
0 (100 ^c)	4.33	4.79	4.18

^a Average of 9 varieties.

^b Taichung (Native) 1 only.

^c The level of nitrogen application to previous crop.

As measured by height, tiller number, and plant weight, growth in the early stages appeared to be retarded where straw was applied (Table 30). As the amount of straw applied increased, the mineral content of the plant altered: iron increased, manganese decreased, phosphorus and potassium increased slightly, and the nitrogen and calcium contents were unchanged.

From the data collected, it is concluded that growth during the early stages is retarded by applying straw. In early maturing varieties retardation is manifested by lower grain yields but, apparently because the depressive effect diminishes with time, yields of late varieties are not affected. With vigorous vegetative varieties such as Peta, early depression of growth lessens mutual shading, delays lodging, and results in higher grain yields.

Growth-retarding factors caused by straw application

The depressive effect on growth, diminishing with time, of adding straw to the soil was further investigated in the greenhouse. Graded amounts of straw were applied to pots of Maahas and Louisiana clay uniformly treated with N, P, and K. The soils were then submerged for 0, 3, or 6 weeks; seedlings were planted and harvested 3 weeks later.

Figure 33 shows the dry weight of harvested seedlings as a percentage of the weight of the respective no-straw treatment. Without straw, seedling growth in Maahas clay was much better than in Louisiana clay. Without pre-submergence, growth was retarded progressively with increased straw application. After 3 and 6 weeks of submergence with Maahas clay, although there was a slight increase in the actual dry

TABLE 29. Effect of heavy straw application just before transplanting on grain yield of 6 varieties in Maahas clay, 1965 rainy season.

Variety	Days from transplanting to harvest	Straw application (ton/ha)		
		0	12	24
B5580 Al-15	92	4.78	3.24	3.18
Chianung 242	98	4.80	4.01	3.46
Taichung 65	98	4.60	4.24	2.94
Sukanandi	113	5.07	4.76	4.19
Peta	124	3.27	4.03	5.00
BPI-76	136	6.50	6.92	6.41

weight per plant over those plants transplanted without prior submergence, the percentage decrease at the various straw levels was nearly identical.

Fig. 33. Effect of straw application on rice growth as affected by submergence period after straw application in Maahas clay and Louisiana clay.

With Louisiana clay, however, a different trend was observed. With the no-straw treatments the dry weight was nearly the same but at all levels of added straw the actual dry weight greatly increased. On a percentage basis, the adverse effect of the lower straw treatments had disappeared aft-

er 3 weeks of pre-submergence. At higher levels of straw application the effects were greatly reduced. After 6 weeks of pre-submergence, there was no adverse effect of straw even at the highest straw treatment. At lower straw concentration growth of the seedlings increased from 150 to 180% over the control.

Soil solutions from the pots with no plants were collected at 0, 3, and 6 weeks after submergence and analyzed for iron, manganese, total organic acids and sulfide. No sulfide was detected at any time. The concentrations of iron, manganese and organic acids in the soil solution were higher at 3 weeks than at 6 weeks of submergence and also were higher with higher straw application (Table 31). Iron concentration was much higher in Louisiana clay than in Maahas clay.

The high concentration of iron after 3 weeks of submergence could have been one of the causes of the retarded growth in Louisiana clay. Manganese and organic acid concentrations of the soil solution after 3 weeks of submergence were also quite high in all cases with straw. However, these data did not give any conclusive evidence to indicate which of these changes caused the retardation; it could have been the combined effect of the high concentrations or some other factors which were not considered in this experiment.

These results indicate that with straw application some retarding factor(s) is produced in the soil. The retarding effect decreases with time.

TABLE 30. Dry weight and element content of plants 33 days after planting affected by straw application (average of 6 varieties, 1965 rainy season).

	Straw level (ton/ha)		
	0	12	24
Height (cm)	66.0	62.0	58.0
Tiller number/hill	11.1	7.2	6.3
Dry weight (g/plant)	4.90	2.97	2.27
N (%)	2.09	2.09	1.93
P (%)	0.26	0.30	0.31
K (%)	3.32	3.61	3.59
Ca (%)	0.29	0.29	0.30
Fe (ppm)	664.00	877.00	1065.00
Mn (ppm)	455.00	294.00	318.00

TABLE 31. Concentration of iron, manganese and organic acids in soil solution of Maahas and Luisiana clays with different levels of straw application at 3 and 6 weeks after submergence.

Straw level (ton/ha)	Soil					
	Maahas clay			Luisiana clay		
	Time of submergence (weeks)					
	0	3	6	0	3	6
	Fe (ppm)					
0	0.6	7	16	0.4	324	265
12	0.3	102	82	2.4	422	148
96	0.8	147	91	1.2	869	357
	Mn (ppm)					
0	0.9	21	53	4.7	67	62
12	1.2	66	48	5.0	73	18
96	4.7	105	44	5.9	136	38
	Organic acids (millinormal)					
0	3.3	4.7	5.7	1.7	4.4	4.9
12	5.3	9.8	3.6	2.3	11.1	3.5
96	3.5	20.3	3.5	6.0	25.0	9.9

At a practical level, i.e., 10 ton/ha or less, incorporation of straw into soil may cause retardation at early growth stages of rice plants and result in a decreased grain yield in short duration, but not long duration, varieties. Since the retarding effect disappears with time, if incorporation of straw is made ahead of transplanting there is probably little risk of reduced grain yield at least with the soils tested. There may be a cumulative effect of straw if it is applied every season continuously. Such effect was not the subject of the present study.

Effect of CO₂

From the field to which a large amount of straw was incorporated, there was vigorous bubbling from the soil. With an infrared gas analyzer, it was determined that a large volume of CO₂ was included in the evolving gas.

During the decomposition of organic substances in soils, CO₂ is produced and under flooded condition CO₂ tension in the soil increases more than under upland condition because of slower gas exchange with the air. High tension of CO₂ in submerged soils is frequently

considered to be one of the factors causing troubles of lowland rice.

To examine the effect of CO₂ on rice plants, a culture solution experiment was conducted. Peta seedlings were grown for one month in a standard culture solution through which CO₂ or N₂ were bubbled during the growing period. The culture solutions were maintained at either pH 4 or 6.0.

Growth of the plants with CO₂ bubbling was slightly inferior to that with N₂ bubbling. The plants bubbled with CO₂ generally contained smaller amounts of nutrient elements, especially potassium, than plants bubbled with N₂. The effect was greater at low pH (Table 32). However, the effect of CO₂ was not drastic though pure CO₂ was used. This implies that the CO₂ tension existing in flooded soils does not cause any striking harmful effect.

TABLE 32. Effect of CO₂ and N₂ bubbling on the growth and element content of rice plants.

pH	Bubbled gas	Plant weight (g/plant)	Element content (%)			
			N	P	K	Ca
4.0	CO ₂	9.8	4.3	0.35	2.3	0.35
	N ₂	12.8	5.4	0.42	4.0	0.37
6.0	CO ₂	10.0	5.1	0.50	3.5	0.35
	N ₂	12.3	5.1	0.56	5.1	0.38

To test whether CO₂ can be utilized by the root or not, excised rice roots were suspended in culture solutions containing C¹⁴O₂ kept at different pH values. After 4 hours the amount of C¹⁴ in the roots was determined. It increased from pH 3 to about pH 5 and above this it decreased (Fig. 34). At a low pH the C¹⁴ uptake was fast at the beginning but slowed down with time. On the other hand, at a high pH a slow uptake was maintained for a long time. These observations suggest that C¹⁴ is absorbed as H₂CO₃ and that the uptake is less at high pH values.

CO₂ uptake was inhibited by KCN (Table 33). Roots containing C¹⁴ were extracted with ethyl ether and ethyl alcohol, consecutively. C¹⁴ in the ether extract was small but the alcohol extract and the residue contained a large amount. These facts indicate that if

Fig. 34. Effect of pH on $C^{14}O_2$ uptake by excised roots (4-hour period).

there is H_2CO_3 in the growth media, it will be absorbed by the roots, but if the roots are kept active, the absorbed H_2CO_3 will be converted into organic substances and will not cause any disturbance to the plants.

TABLE 33. Effect of KCN on CO_2 uptake and respiration by excised rice roots.

	KCN concentration (M)			
	0	0.001	0.01	0.1
CO_2 absorbed (cpm/100 mg fresh roots)	606	339	199	54
Respiration ($\mu l O_2/hr/mg$ DW)	3.20	2.08	1.48	Nil

As previously discussed, it is possible that with a high tension of CO_2 in submerged soils a large amount of calcium or iron may, under certain conditions, enter the soil solution and cause troubles, but these cannot be attributed to the effect of CO_2 itself.

Effect of organic acids

Organic acids are produced by the de-

Fig. 35. Effect of pH on acetate-1- C^{14} uptake by excised roots (concentration of acetate was 10^{-6} M, 4-hour period).

composition of organic substances, as described previously. Acetate is the major acid, and butyrate and propionate are always produced. These acids, especially butyrate, are, reportedly, toxic to the rice plant.

A culture solution experiment was conducted to examine the effect of organic acids in relation to pH. Peta plants growing for 3 weeks in a standard culture solution were subjected to various levels of acetate or butyrate at three pH values, 4, 6, and 8.

TABLE 34. Effect of acetate and butyrate on the growth of Peta rice (g/plant).

pH	Concentration of acid (mN)			
	0	10	20	40
	Acetate			
4	7.6	2.2	1.3	0.4
6	4.7	5.3	5.8	4.6
8	3.1	5.1	6.2	4.7
	Butyrate			
4	7.6	1.2	0.8	0.4
6	4.7	5.7	4.5	3.5
8	3.1	5.3	5.7	4.6

At pH 4, acetate as well as butyrate was toxic at 10 millinormal concentration. Butyrate was more toxic than acetate. However, at pH 6 and 8, organic acids at 10 millinormal were apparently beneficial because, in their absence, plants become chlorotic. There was a slight decrease in plant weight with concentrations of 40 millinormal in the culture solution (Table 34).

Excised roots were suspended in a culture solution containing acetate-1-C¹⁴ at various pH values. The amount of C¹⁴

absorbed by the roots, was found to decrease with increase of pH (Fig. 35). The data strongly suggested that undissociated acetic acid is absorbed by the roots.

From these results it can be concluded that at a low pH organic acids are in undissociated form, absorbed by the root, and cause disturbances. However, at a high pH the acids are mainly ionized, absorbed with difficulties, and do not cause serious trouble.

Biochemistry

The new biochemist, who joined the staff in July, continued to study Fraction-I protein of rice leaves and initiated new biochemical studies on morphogenesis.

FRACTION-I PROTEIN OF NORMAL AND DISEASED RICE LEAVES

Previous investigations in these laboratories have shown that the high molecular weight Fraction-I protein from leaves infected with rice blast is electrophoretically different from the proteins of normal rice leaves. Assay of enzymic activity of the protein using radioactive C^{14} revealed that the amount of radioactive CO_2 fixed by the diseased fraction was reduced to almost half the amount fixed by the normal fraction. As three enzymes are known to be associated with this partially purified protein, it is not yet known which of the enzyme or enzymes are affected by pathogenesis. It is likely, however, that carboxydismutase, which is reported to form most of the molecular bulk of the protein, has undergone some change.

The migratory difference between the normal and diseased protein in an electric field was further confirmed using agar gel, a medium known to be more inert than acrylamide or starch. Immunoelectrophoretic studies, using the same medium, of the proteins from the two sources appear to show some difference in the nature of precipitation lines formed. Experiments involving rice plants infected by tungro virus, showed that in electrophoresis Fraction-I protein from the virus-diseased leaves behaves in a way similar to that of protein from leaves infected with blast, indicating that the change induced on this protein by pathogenesis is presumably nonspecific in relation to the causal organism. Further, the amount of Fraction-I protein in virus-infected leaves was much less than in normal leaves. This observation is significant as it has been shown in the case of TMV that virus multiplication takes place at the expense of Fraction-I protein.

The glycoprotein nature of Fraction-I protein was also investigated in normal and diseased rice leaves. The carbohydrate components of the protein were analyzed after enzymic hydrolysis and gel filtration. The analysis revealed that the diseased protein contained two distinct groups of carbohydrates compared with one in the healthy leaf pro-

tein. The carbohydrates were positive to tests for both hexoses and pentoses.

Since the two proteins (from normal and diseased rice leaves) appeared to have the same percentage composition of amino acids, and apparently the same molecular weight as shown by ultracentrifugation studies, the possibility was investigated that the protein was composed of a number of subunits. Consequently, an attempt was made to dissociate the protein with reagents such as sodium dodecyl sulfate (SDS), urea and guanidine HCl. Urea and guanidine HCl did not show any evidence of dissociating the protein to smaller subunits, but analytical ultracentrifugation studies showed that a considerable reduction in its concentration had occurred. The significance of this is not clear. SDS (an ionic detergent), on the other hand, did dissociate the protein, and the product had an approximate *S* value of 3.5 compared with 18s for native protein. Both the normal and diseased proteins were capable of being dissociated to the same degree.

The behavior of the protein was further investigated by gel electrophoresis performed with varying concentrations of SDS in the buffer as well as in the gel. The pattern of electrophoresis varied with the concentration of SDS used: with no SDS, the protein gave a very diffused pattern; with $10^{-3}M$ and $10^{-2}M$ concentration, both the normal and diseased proteins showed many bands, one corresponding to the original Fraction-I protein; with still higher concentrations ($5 \times 10^{-2}M$) of SDS, only a single band was observed to move at a faster rate than that of original undissociated Fraction-I protein. In all cases the difference in mobility between the normal and diseased species of protein was maintained.

Although the significance of these results is not clear, it appears that the Fraction-I protein displays properties of reaggregation even after it is dissociated. The nature of this reaggregated protein, however, has yet to be fully investigated.

Biochemical studies on morphogenesis of the rice plant

It has recently been observed by a visiting scientist that water-culturing the rice plant in a defined medium containing *L*-histidine as a sole source of nitrogen specifically inhibits morphogenesis at the stage of grain maturation. This observation is being utilized to examine the possibility that histidine is a specific inhibitor of starch biosynthesis in the grain.

Various analytical methods are being developed to study several intermediates and enzymes that are related to starch biosynthesis.

Preliminary work was initiated on the isolation and characterization of

nucleic acids from rice plants. RNA was isolated from leaves by phenol-SDS method and chromatographed on the methylated albumin column. Its base composition and metabolic behavior is being investigated with the use of radioactive tracers in the hope of isolating "messenger-type" RNA from the plant. This information will be used in the study of specific "messages" at various development stages of the plant.

MISCELLANEOUS

The biochemist taught a graduate course Agricultural Chemistry 230 "Advanced Biochemistry" during the first semester 1965-1966 at the UPCA.

THE BIOCHEMIST in discussion with a visiting scientist and a research assistant.

Cereal Chemistry

Basic information on the physicochemical nature of the rice grain is meager. Such information is essential if the reasons for the divergent processing, eating, and nutritional qualities of rice are to be understood. Consequently, the work in cereal chemistry has centered around a systematic characterization of these qualities of rice grain, particularly as regards the starch and protein fractions. The principal studies this year were on (a) the relationship of amylose to eating quality, (b) the physical structure and hardness of the rice grain, and (c) the physicochemical characterization of starch and proteins.

AMYLOSE AND EATING QUALITY OF RICE

Previous studies with varieties in which the amylose content of the milled rice ranged from 16 to 33 percent have shown amylose content to be the principal factor affecting the textural characteristics of cooked rice. However, the varieties used were of diverse genetic background and varied in a number of constituents other than starch. Better materials for such a study are available in a number of lines developed by the College of Agriculture, University of the Philippines (UPCA) through crosses of various waxy and nonwaxy varieties from the Philippines. Pairs of samples are available which are of similar genetic makeup but which differ markedly in amylose content. The starch of waxy rice is essentially all amylopectin, thus it is possible to extend the range of amylose content to the lower extreme.

Samples of rice of three hybrid waxy lines and their respective nonwaxy parents were cooked with the same quantity of water and evaluated by a taste panel in cooperation with the Home Technology Department of the UPCA (Table 1). The data verified a relationship between amount of amylose and tenderness, cohesiveness, and gloss scores of cooked rice. The waxy samples were more tender, cohesive, and glossy than the nonwaxy parents.

Two out of the three nonwaxy parents had lower flavor scores than their waxy lines. BPI-76 had the same flavor scores as its waxy line and had tenderness, cohesiveness, and gloss scores which were intermediate between the waxy samples and the other nonwaxy but higher-amylose samples. The slight discoloration of the waxy samples may explain their higher color scores. All the samples had the same aroma scores.

Protein content has been shown to be negatively correlated with the tenderness and cohesiveness scores but a suggestion was noted in these data that this is a minor factor compared with starch type. Two of the waxy samples had higher protein contents than their nonwaxy counterparts but were also more tender.

Compilation of the physicochemical data of rice of various countries continues. Data are available from 145 varieties which had been grown in the country of origin, at the Institute, or at both locations. Samples of these leading and recommended varieties were obtained through the agricultural ministries, except the commercial samples of rice from China. Nonwaxy samples of milled rice obtained from 18 countries varied widely in amylose content (Fig. 1).

TABLE 1. Some physicochemical properties and eating quality scores of milled rice of three waxy lines and of their nonwaxy parents.

	Protein content (%)	Amylose content (%)	Gel. temp. (°C)	Eating quality scores (warm rice) ^a				
				Flavor	Tender-ness	Cohesive-ness	Color	Gloss
Pilit Morado X BPI-76	10.48	waxy	72	4.8	7.4	6.5	3.9	7.1
BPI-76	8.93	24.5	71	5.5	6.3	4.1	1.5	4.9
Pangasinan X Peta	10.49	waxy	71	5.2	7.6	6.8	3.6	7.4
Peta	6.96	28.8	70.5	4.2	4.0	2.9	1.2	3.1
Pangasinan X Tjere Mas	9.47	waxy	71.5	5.3	7.6	7.1	3.8	7.2
Tjere Mas	11.85	26.3	71.5	3.8	2.2	1.8	2.2	2.1
<i>Analysis of variance (variety)</i>								
F-value				3.86**	60.70**	116.57**	24.8*	94.00**
Standard error (X)				0.34	0.29	0.21	0.24	0.25
LSD (5%)				0.97	0.81	0.59	0.67	0.70

^a Numerical scores from 1 to 9 were assigned, a score of "1" representing the lowest expression of the property in question and a score of "9" the highest expression.

Fig. 1. The wide range in amylose content of nonwaxy rice varieties reflects the different preferences for cooking and eating qualities in the world.

GRAIN HARDNESS AND GRAIN STRUCTURE

Alkali digestibility values have been claimed by some rice workers to be negatively related to grain hardness, and hence to breakage during milling. It is thought that the alkali values reflect the relative porosity of the grain. To determine the general applicability of this relationship, brown rice of 78 nonwaxy samples from Asia, 41 waxy lines from the UPCA, and a strain of crumbly rice (No. 7154) from the United States, were screened for grain hardness with a Kiya grain hardness tester. Breaking hardness refers to the pressure necessary to cause the grain to crack, and crushing hardness to that which causes the grain to crumble.

The results showed contrasting behavior for the waxy and nonwaxy lines. Thus, negative correlations existed for

the waxy lines, as predicted, but positive correlations were found for the nonwaxy lines from Asia. The crumbly rice sample followed the pattern of the nonwaxy samples in that it had low values for alkali digestibility and also a low degree of hardness. This relationship for nonwaxy rice was, of course, contrary to that noted by other workers. Presumably the correlation between alkali digestibility and grain hardness is complex (Table 2).

Protein content was generally not linearly related to grain hardness. The crumbly rice sample used here was opaque and nonwaxy with a very soft kernel which crumbles on milling. The sample received from the USDA contained 19.5 percent amylose and 10.3 percent protein (both on a dry brown

Fig. 2. The loose arrangement of the starch granules in the white core portion (left) of Taichung (Native) 1 endosperm contrasts with their compact packing in the translucent portion (right). Stain: Fast Green — iodine.

rice basis), and had a gelatinization temperature of 71°C. The quantity of protein extracted from it was not very different from other nonwaxy varieties. Amino acid analyses indicated no unusual aminogram for this variety. Lysine content, 4.26 percent of its protein, indicates that its opaqueness is not associated with any unusual amount of this amino acid.

Since data from physicochemical studies of the rice grain have so far been inadequate to explain such properties as grain hardness and milling quality, histological studies of grain structure and the distribution of chemical constituents were initiated.

Rice processors have claimed that opaque portions, such as white belly

and white core in nonwaxy rice, are associated with high grain breakage. Hence studies have been initiated recently on opaque samples, including crumbly and waxy types. Sections are being stained for starch, cell wall constituents, and protein. In crumbly rice and the opaque portion of the endosperm of nonwaxy varieties, the starch granules were found to be randomly arranged. This resulted in loose packing in the starch granules (Fig. 2), contrasting with the compact arrangement of cell contents in the translucent portion of the endosperm. To complement these studies with light microscopy, a cooperative project using an electron microscope has been initiated with the UPCA Department of Chemistry.

TABLE 2. Range of hardness and alkali digestibility values and protein content of brown rice samples and their correlations.

Property	Crumbly rice	Nonwaxy Asian samples	Waxy lines
Hardness ^a			
Breaking (kg)	3.5	3.8 - 8.8	5.0 - 6.9
Crushing (kg)	4.6	4.8 - 10.9	7.3 - 12.4
Alkali digestibility ^b			
Spreading values	3.9	4.0 - 7.0	2.5 - 6.0
Clearing values	2.5	3.0 - 6.7	1.6 - 5.0
Protein content (%)	10.28	6.54-13.84	6.19-13.63
<i>Correlation coefficients (r)</i>			
Breaking hardness vs. alkali spreading		0.433** (n = 78)	-0.543** (n = 41)
Breaking hardness vs. alkali clearing		0.448** (n = 78)	-0.513** (n = 41)
Breaking hardness vs. protein content		0.075 (n = 58)	-0.642** (n = 41)
Crushing hardness vs. alkali spreading		0.449** (n = 78)	-0.592** (n = 41)
Crushing hardness vs. alkali clearing		0.423** (n = 78)	-0.620** (n = 41)
Crushing hardness vs. protein content		0.097 (n = 58)	-0.276 (n = 41)

^a Mean for 10 grains.

^b Values of 1.0 to 7.0 in the order of increasing alkali digestibility.

PHYSICOCHEMICAL STUDIES OF RICE STARCH

Gelatinization of granular starch may depend upon granular size, percentage of amylose, molecular weight of the components, and the corresponding micellar organization and degree of crystallinity of the granule. In terms of granular size, 4 waxy and 10 nonwaxy samples ranged from 4.1 to 5.6 and 3.8 to 5.7 microns, respectively. However, granule size and gelatinization tem-

perature of the samples were not linearly correlated.

Subfractionation studies were performed on two amylose and one amylopectin preparations to verify their homogeneity. Subfractionation of amylose, by stepwise precipitation from dimethylsulfoxide solution with ethanol, indicated essentially a molecular weight fractionation of Taichung (Native) 1

Fig. 3. The purity of the rice amylose and amylopectin preparations was verified by the presence of only one peak during ultracentrifugation in dimethylsulfoxide.

and Century Patna 231 amyloses. The β -amylolysis limit of the subfractions was less affected than intrinsic viscosity. This narrow range of β -amylolysis value may be due in part to subfractionation during the two crystallizations from aqueous *n*-butanol solution in the preparation of these amylose samples.

The amylopectin of Taichung (Native) 1 shows a high iodine binding capacity value, although it has normal unit chain length. To determine the reason for this property the amylopectin was subfractionated from aqueous solution by centrifugation and by precipitation with 2-nitropropane. The result indicated that the high iodine coloration of the amylopectin of Taichung (Native) 1 is probably due to the presence in the molecule of long blue-coloring branches, and not to contaminant degraded amylose.

Sedimentation constants of 7 amylose and 9 amylopectin samples were determined to complement the viscometric

data and check further varietal differences in the molecular weight of the fractions. The constant is an index of molecular size. All the samples gave only one main peak (Fig. 3), indicating a high degree of purity.

The Samylose values of seven samples showed a narrow range of 1.4 to 2.3 Svedbergs. Samylose showed a negative trend with gelatinization temperature of the starch, except for Peta (Table 3). When related with degree of crystallinity for these samples as indexed by their x-ray diffraction intensity at $2\theta = 20.25^\circ$, Century Patna 231 amylose had the lowest Samylose value and was the most crystalline sample. The relation between crystallinity and Samylose was poor for the four amylose S with S values of at least 2.0.

The seven nonwaxy and two waxy amylopectins were of greater molecular size than the amyloses and their range of S values was wider: 11 to 550. The low-gelatinization-temperature starches

TABLE 3. Sedimentation constants of amylose and amylopectins of rice starch in dimethylsulfoxide at 20°C in relation to gelatinization temperature of the starch and the crystallinity of amylose.

Variety	S amylose (Svedberg)	S amylopectin (Svedberg)	Gelatinization temperature of starch (°C)	X-ray diffraction intensity at 2θ=20.25° (amylose) (cps) ^a
Leuang Yai 34	2.1	120	52.5-59	1130
Nahng Mon S-4	2.2	44	53 -59.5	807
Malagkit Sungsong Puti	—	11	59.5-61	—
Taichung (Native) 1	2.3	12	55 -63	1180
Taichung 65	1.7	59	59.5-65	1380
Bengawan	1.8	150	55 -66.5	1400
Peta	2.0	53	64 -71	711
Century Patna 231	1.4	550	66 -74.5	1570
Crowley 2585-6-1	—	220	67 -75	

^a Counts per second.

tended to have lower $S_{\text{amylopectin}}$ values. The high-molecular-weight amylopectins of Century Patna 231 and Crowley 2585-6-1 were also derived from high-gelatinization-temperature starch. Again Peta was the exception. Taichung (Native) 1 had the lowest molecular weight among the nonwaxy amylopectins studied, although it gave the highest intrinsic viscosity value of 168 among the samples. One possible cause for this lack of correlation between intrinsic viscosity in alkali solution and sedimentation constant in dimethylsulfoxide for these starch fractions is that dimethylsulfoxide is a better solvent for these starch fractions than 0.5 N sodium hydroxide. With the waxy samples, the low gelatinization-temperature variety, Malagkit Sungsong Puti, has a lower molecular weight than the high-gelatinization-tempera-

ture variety, Crowley 2585-6-1. This is in line with the general observation that decreases in solubility are associated with the increase in molecular weight. The generality of this relationship for waxy rice is being investigated.

Studies of the influence of the waxy gene on such physicochemical properties as protein and fat contents of the grain have given contradictory results. To resolve this problem, three pairs of isogenic lines, differing essentially only in the *waxy* gene, were studied. The results indicate that these samples did not differ markedly in protein and fat contents (Table 4). Amino acid analysis of brown rice indicated minor differences in composition due to the *waxy* gene. The waxy lines had lower contents of tyrosine and aspartic acid than their nonwaxy counterparts.

TABLE 4. Physicochemical data of some isogenic lines.

Lines	Rough rice			Brown rice	
	Length (cm)	Width (cm)	Hull (%)	Protein (%)	Fat (%)
Taichung 65	7.2	3.6	20.5	12.37	2.22
Glutinous Taichung 65	7.5	3.6	19.6	11.23	2.59
Caloro	7.4	3.6	19.8	12.79	2.25
Cal 5563A1	7.7	3.7	20.9	13.45	2.53
Century Patna 231	9.2	2.5	22.2	13.41	2.95
Waxy Century Patna 231	10.0	3.0	21.3	12.12	2.52

PHYSICOCHEMICAL STUDIES OF RICE PROTEINS

Rice protein is a principal source of the dietary protein in Asia. It is the principal substance occupying the spaces between the compound starch granules in the rice endosperm cells. Chemists have made considerable progress toward understanding the nature of seed proteins but they seldom have used rice as the experimental material.

Electrophoresis, ion-exchange cellulose chromatography, and immunoelectrophoretic techniques have been used in the study of barley and wheat proteins. Preliminary results indicated that gel electrophoresis may be employed for the characterization of rice proteins with some modifications of the techniques.

Amino acid analysis of the crude

prolamin. The rice prolamin preparation was relatively high in carbohydrate contamination identified, by paper chromatography of its hydrolyzate, as being mainly glucose.

The highly organized nature of the cell protoplasm has become quite apparent in recent years. In the endosperm cells of some seeds such as corn, barley, wheat and peanut, light and electron micrography has shown the protein to occur in the form of discrete structures termed protein bodies. Histochemical studies of BPI-76 milled rice with the light microscope indicated the occurrence of protein in the endosperm in the form of discrete particles or bodies (Fig. 4). The higher protein sample of BPI-76 had more protein

Fig. 4. Compound starch granules and stained protein bodies are the main constituents seen in the cross section of the endosperm cells of rice.

preparations of salt-soluble protein, prolamin, and glutelin from BPI-76 brown rice verified the reported low lysine and tryptophan contents of rice prolamin. The levels of these two amino acids were less than 1 percent in the

bodies than the lower protein sample. Using electron microscopy, Raison has noted the protein of the developing grain to be also essentially in the form of protein bodies.

The protein particles of a few seeds

such as wheat and corn have been analyzed. These particle-bound proteins generally are less soluble and have a lower nutritive value than the smaller proportion of proteins which are apparently free in the cytoplasm. Such intact protein particles have been successfully isolated by non-aqueous flotation or aqueous extraction in the presence of a high molecular weight osmotic agent such as polyethylene glycol. Protein characterization would be greatly simplified if protein particles could be physically separated without resorting to chemical extraction. The nutritive value of the particle proteins of rice will be important to determine as they are the major form of protein in the grain.

Attempts to isolate protein-rich fractions from rice by the flotation method indicated that physical separation of these particles is rendered feasible by differences in densities of protein and starch. Preliminary work at a density of 1.39 with a milled rice BPI-76 sample of 14 percent protein produced a 1-percent fraction with 52 percent protein. From BPI-76 brown rice of 14 percent protein, flotation at a density of 1.37 yielded a 3.5-percent fraction with 48 percent protein. Subsequent flotation at a density of 1.39 gave a 3.0-percent fraction with 39 percent protein.

These protein values are lower than the 80 percent protein fractions obtained from wheat flours.

Red pericarped varieties have been claimed to have higher protein contents than the unpigmented rices. Red Century Patna 231 obtained from Varietal Improvement had the same protein content and amino acid as unpigmented Century Patna 231. Presumably, the claimed higher protein content of colored varieties is not due to the color *per se*, which is anthocyanin in nature.

MISCELLANEOUS

The associate chemist conducted the graduate course Agricultural Chemistry 268 Cereal Chemistry during the second semester 1964-65 at the UPCA. He presented a paper, "Physicochemical investigations of the rice grain," at the Technical Symposium of the Chemical Society of the Philippines in Manila in March, and a review article, "Proteins of Rice Grain," at the Third Scientific Meeting of the Philippine Association of Nutrition in Manila in October.

Four rice chemists reviewed the draft of the compiled handbook of physicochemical data on the rice grain, and it is being reproduced as a technical bulletin.

Varietal Improvement

Activities to develop improved lines were further intensified to meet the need for higher grain yields in the tropics. A total of 570 crosses have been processed since the initiation of the hybridization program in 1962. Four plantings of pedigree lines numbering over 23,000 were made during the year. Over 1,400 F_2 backcross populations from 71 different crosses were grown and selected. True-breeding F_6 or F_7 lines were planted at a number of locations in Southeast Asia for observation. A few short-statured, early maturing, non-lodging, nitrogen-responsive lines showed good promise at several locations. Additional crosses were initiated to improve further the disease resistance and grain quality of these lines.

Studies on breeding methods, inheritance of physiologic and quantitative traits, cytogenetic basis of sterility, and nature of lodging resistance were continued to provide basic information of vital interest to breeders.

VARIETAL TESTING AND DEVELOPMENT

World collection

The description and preservation of rice germ plasm has been assisted with a four-year grant of \$55,200 from the United States National Science Foundation. The addition of 134 cultivated varieties during the year increased the total collection to 9,913 accessions. A detailed morphologic-agronomic description has been recorded for all varieties in the collection. The process of organizing the varietal description into a useful varietal stock catalog has been started.

An additional 2,606 duplicate accessions were sent to the United States National Seed Storage Laboratory at Fort Collins, Colorado for storage. The entire world collection will be eventually deposited there for increased protection.

During the year, 1,608 varieties from the collection were sent upon request to 56 institutions in 26 countries. An additional 3,033 samples of breeding material developed at the Institute were shipped for evaluation in other countries. Another 227 samples of wild taxa in the genus *Oryza* were supplied to 7 institutions in 4 countries.

Taxonomy in the "*O. glaberrima* complex"

Closely related to the cultivated species of Africa, *O. glaberrima* Steud., are two other diploid forms, *O. breviligulata* A. Chev. et Roehr. and *O. Stapfii* Roschev. These three taxa form the "*O. glaberrima* complex." Based on morphological and taxonomic evidence, the African diploid taxon, *Oryza Stapfii* Roschev., does not warrant a species rank. It should not be treated as a variety of either *O. glaberrima* Steud. or *O. breviligulata* A. Chev. et Roehr. but as a synonym to *O. breviligulata*. Distinct differences in morphological features such as grain length, pubescence of the lemma and palea, texture of awn, panicle branching and form, and growth habit of the juvenile plants were observed which aid in delimiting the two valid species, *O. glaberrima* and *O. breviligulata*.

Economic value of the cultivated African species, *O. glaberrima*

Several rice researchers have mentioned the possibility of utilizing *O. glaberrima* as a source of germ plasm for improving the disease resistance, flood tolerance, and grain quality of *O. sativa*. The ratings of gelatinization temperatures on 21 strains in the 3 taxa of the "*O. glaberrima* complex" were given in the 1964 Annual Report.

Studies on other economic traits indicated that the glabrous leaves and grains of *O. glaberrima* is a desirable trait, especially when this crop is mechanically harvested, threshed, dried, and milled. Very low incidence of stem borer infestation was noted among plants of the 3 taxa during the two seasons. However, all strains included were highly susceptible to the "tungro" virus disease. Nearly all lines had pronounced grain dormancy and the caryopses had a red pericarp. The plants generally exhibited a rapid rate of plant tissue senescence near maturity and no ratoon crop was possible. Resistance to blast, nematodes, bacterial leaf blight and other diseases might be present in these strains and could be sought in further tests.

Eleven strains of *O. glaberrima* and eight lines of *O. breviligulata* were analyzed for amylose, protein, and alkali digestibility values by the Institute's cereal chemists. The samples had high protein and amylose contents, and intermediate or high alkali digestibility values (Table 1). On the basis of amylose content, cooked rice of these African

TABLE 1. Range of protein and amylose contents and alkali digestibility values of milled rice samples of *Oryza glaberrima* and *Oryza breviligulata*.

Property	<i>Oryza glaberrima</i> (n=11)	<i>Oryza breviligulata</i> (n=8)
Protein (%)	9.49-13.80	13.35-17.27
Amylose (%)	24.0 -29.2	25.4 -30.4
Alkali spreading	5.0 - 5.5	4.8 - 5.6
Alkali clearing	4.0 - 4.5	3.2 - 4.4

species may be classified as dry and flaky.

The *sativa* x *glaberrima* hybrids are known to be highly sterile. Therefore, the promise of *O. glaberrima* as a source of germ plasm for the improvement of *O. sativa* appears rather limited.

Objectives of the breeding program

In irrigated areas of tropical Asia, nitrogen responsive, non-lodging, and high-yielding varieties are urgently needed to meet increasing demands for food. The Institute breeding program is designed to develop a range of varietal types of wide adaptability that would meet the requirements of a large number of Asian farmers. The following varietal characteristics are considered essential in developing the improved lines.

1. Early maturity and insensitivity to photoperiod.
2. Relatively short, erect, narrow, thick, dark-green leaves, which permit the penetration and efficient utilization of sunlight.
3. Short, sturdy culms to reduce lodging at high fertility levels.
4. Resistance to the more prevalent diseases of economic importance.
5. Grain dormancy at time of harvest to reduce losses from sprouting on the panicle.
6. Moderately firm threshability to reduce losses from shattering before and during harvest.
7. High grain yield with high milling recovery.
8. A range of grain types and cooking characteristics acceptable to consumers in different regions.

Hybridization program

Approximately 70 varieties have so far been used in the crossing program. As mentioned in previous reports the varieties selected for parents were screened from the world collection of varieties maintained at the Institute. In some of the more recent crosses, promising hybrid lines developed in the breeding program were used as parents.

The Institute pathologists are continuously screening the world collection

for improved sources of resistance to diseases. As varieties possessing superior levels of resistance are identified, they are immediately included in the hybridization program. Screening of hybrid populations and line selections for disease resistance is continually made in close cooperation with plant pathologists.

During the year, 122 new single cross-combinations were made. Backcrosses of 26 combinations, some for the third, fourth, or fifth backcross to the recurrent parents, were accomplished. The total number of crosses made since 1962 now exceeds 570.

Most of the single-cross combinations were grown as bulk-hybrid populations in the F₂ and F₃ generations. Later generations were grown in 5-meter pedigree rows. Intense selection for desired plant type was practiced within the bulk populations. In tall x short-statured crosses most of the tall segregates were removed prior to blooming or as soon as height differences were detected.

Over 1,750 single-backcross F₂ populations from some 100 different crosses were grown. Important recurrent parents used in the single backcrosses were Peta, Sigadis, BPI-76, Chianung 242, Acc. 6993 (CP 231 x SLO-17), and Acc. 6973 (B58-A6-545). Donor parents included Peta, Sigadis and Mas for tungro resistance, Leuang Yai 34 and Nahng Mon S-4 for long-grain shape and cooking qualities, 81B-25 for plant type, CI 9534 (CP 231 x HO-12) for blast resistance, and Belle Patna and CI 9544 for early maturity.

A multiple backcrossing technique is being effectively used in transferring to tropical varieties simply inherited genetic traits such as reduced plant height, earlier maturity, photoperiod insensitivity, disease resistance, and certain endosperm characteristics. Donor parents were Taichung (Native) 1 for short stature, Belle Patna for early maturity, and CI 9534 for blast resistance.

This breeding method is also being used in the development of *japonica* type varieties suitable for growing in the tropics. Chianung 242, a Taiwan *japonica* variety, was used as the recurrent parent in this series of crosses

TABLE 2. Plant and grain characteristics being transferred to tropical *indica* and Taiwan *japonica* varieties through multiple backcross programs.

Backcross and combination	Traits obtained from donor parent
Peta/6 x Taichung (Native) 1	Short stature, early maturity, low gelatinization temperature of milled rice
Peta/5 x Belle Patna	Early maturity (100-105 days)
Peta/3 x CI 9534	Blast resistance
Sigadis/4 x Taichung (Native) 1	Short stature, early maturity, low gelatinization temperature of milled rice
Sigadis/2 x CI 9534	Blast resistance
Sigadis/2 x CI 9544	Early maturity (100-105 days)
Basmati 370/2 x Taichung (Native) 1	Short stature, early maturity
Leuang Yai 34/2 x Taichung (Native) 1	"
Nahng Mon S-4/2 x Taichung (Native) 1	"
Gam Pai/3 x Taichung (Native) 1	"
Pah Leuad/3 x Taichung (Native) 1	"
Chianung 242/ x [(CP 231 x SLO-17) x PI 215936]	Grain dormancy
Chianung 242/2 x Peta	Tungro virus resistance
Chianung 242/2 x (Mo. R-500 x Nato)	Blast resistance and 100-day maturity
Chianung 242/2 x [Ch. 242 x T(N)1 x Tainan 3]	Short stature

Chianung 242 is adapted to the tropical environment but lacks seed dormancy and resistance to blast and the tungro virus disease. The more important multiple backcross programs underway are shown in Table 2.

Pedigree nurseries

A total of 23,438 line selections and their parents were grown in 5-meter pedigree rows. They were distributed among 5 planting dates (October 1964, and January, March, June, and October 1965). The pedigree lines were selected from over 200 crosses involving about 37 different varieties. These totals include both single and backcross combinations.

Included in the October 1965 pedigree nursery were the F₆ and F₇ generations of lines selected from the first group of IRRI crosses. These were crosses between the Taiwan short-statured *indica* varieties (I-geo-tze and Dee-geo-woogen) and tall tropical *indica* varieties such as Peta, Siam 29, FB-24, H-105, BPI-76 and others. They also include *japonica* x *indica* crosses involving the same tropical *indica* varieties and the Taiwan *japonicas* (ponlais), Chianung 242, Taichung 172, Taichung 176, and Chianan 8. Other combinations were

single backcrosses between BPI-76, as the recurrent parent, and several ponlai varieties. After the F₄ generation, a number of these lines were grown in yield trials and the results are reported elsewhere.

The F₃ and F₄ generations of many new crosses were grown in pedigree rows during 1965. The F₅ generation of a few of the earlier maturing lines of this group of crosses was also grown. This series included crosses between U.S. varieties and tropical *indica* varieties such as Sigadis, Peta, Mas, BPI-76, 81B-25, Taichung (Native) 1, Leuang Yai 34, and Nahng Mon S-4. Many F₃ and a few F₄ line selections from the single backcross combinations previously described were grown in June- and/or October-seeded pedigree nurseries.

Pedigree line selections are evaluated for maturity, photoperiod sensitivity, plant type, reaction to diseases, grain dormancy and threshability, grain size, shape and appearance, and cooking behavior based on alkali digestion and analytical amylose tests.

Progress toward achieving breeding objectives

Maturity. With respect to time of maturity, the major effort is directed

toward the development of photoperiod-insensitive or weakly sensitive varieties maturing in 115 to 135 days from seeding to maturity. The maturity of insensitive lines ranges from 85 to over 140 days (seeding to maturity). The development of 85- to 100-day *indica* lines is underway. The early and heavy tillering short-statured *indica* lines have been crossed with northern Japan and U.S. varieties of about 85- and 100-day maturity, respectively. It is possible that 100-day strains possessing the seedling vigor (expressed as early and heavy tillering ability) of the short-statured *indicas* may produce satisfactory yields when transplanted, particularly if early transplanting is practiced. Varieties maturing in 85 days may not yield satisfactorily when transplanted but probably have value in a direct seeded culture.

Several backcrosses to the *indica* parent lines will be used in transferring the desired maturity to tropical *indica* varieties.

The development of 85- and 100-day ponlai lines is also underway using similar sources of early maturity and breeding procedures. In addition to early maturity, other desired traits being transferred to the ponlai varieties are shorter stature, blast and tungro resistance.

Plant type. Collectively, the many plant characteristics that make up plant type cannot be measured precisely and must be evaluated visually. The breeder must be able to identify at a glance the desirable plant types in mixed populations or pedigreed line rows. Consequently, diligent field observations are made throughout the growing season.

Promising short-statured *indica* types have been selected from single crosses between Peta and the short-statured I-geo-tze and Dee-geo-woo-gen. Examples of lines selected from these crosses are IR9-60 and IR8-288-3, selected from I-geo-tze and Dee-geo-woo-gen crosses, respectively. Extensive testing under a wide range of conditions will be required to determine the range of adaptability of IR9-60, IR8-288-3, and similar lines selected from other crosses. To date, these lines have shown much

promise with respect to seedling vigor, early tillering, erect leaf habit, general vegetative vigor, resistance to lodging, and nitrogen responsiveness as indicated by grain-yielding capacity.

Plant height. The Taiwan short-statured *indica* varieties, represented by Taichung (Native) 1, I-geo-tze, and Dee-geo-woo-gen are important sources of short stature. Another promising short-statured parent is Acc. 6993 (Century Patna 231 x SLO-17), a hybrid line developed in the U.S.A. Crosses between this line and tall tropical *indica* varieties have been made and selection is in progress. The Century Patna 231 x SLO-17 line has earlier maturity and lower tillering capacity than most tropical varieties.

Blast resistance. A number of the varieties used in the crossing program have produced progenies resistant to blast. As of this date, the parent varieties which have exhibited resistance to blast under a wide range of conditions and from which resistant progenies have been selected are Acc. 6741 (Century Patna 231 x HO-12), Acc. 9914 (Mo. R-500 x Nato), H-105, Taichung 172 and 176, and Chianan 8. Kataktara, a Pakistani variety showing a high degree of blast resistance, has been used in recent crosses. H-105 when crossed with short-statured *indicas* produced short-statured, blast resistant lines. These lines have been crossed with the improved short-statured lines such as IR9-60 and IR8-288-3.

Bacterial leaf blight. Varieties from which bacterial leaf blight resistant progenies have been obtained are Kaohsiung 68, Chianan 8, Taichung 172 and 176, Acc. 6973 (B581-A6-545), Acc. 9797 (B589-A4-18), and Sigadis. The cross of Sigadis x Taichung (Native) 1 has given short-statured lines possessing the bacterial leaf blight resistance of Sigadis.

Tungro and other virus diseases. Peta, Sigadis, and FB-24 are the sources of resistance to the tungro virus used to date. At least moderate resistance to the disease has been transferred to short-statured lines. IR8-288-3 appears to be in this group. Other and possibly improved sources of tungro resistance

are being investigated by plant pathologists and will be immediately used in the crossing program.

Based upon field counts of affected plants, all varieties used in the crossing program appear susceptible to grassy stunt. It is possible that the degree of susceptibility may vary among varieties but this has not been determined.

Stem rot and sheath blight. Varieties which have been reported to possess tolerance to stem rot are BPI-76, Peta, and several of the ponlai varieties. Most of the information concerning resistance to sheath blight has been obtained from Taiwan. Taiwan scientists report that Peta appears to have some resistance to the disease. From local observations most of the ponlai varieties appear to be rather susceptible. Improved testing techniques for determining reaction to sheath blight are needed before any large-scale evaluation can be undertaken.

Slow leaf senescence. It is believed that slow leaf senescence at maturity, common to most *japonica* varieties, would be desirable in tropical *indica* varieties. In crosses between BPI-76 and ponlai varieties, several BPI-76 type lines have been selected which have slow leaf senescence. These lines have been used as parents in crosses with IR9-60, IR8-288-3, and similar types. It is too early to predict whether or not this breeding objective can be easily accomplished. Some of the U.S. varieties possess slow leaf senescence and are being used in crosses with the improved short-statured lines.

Grain milling and cooking quality tests

Plant selections saved for growing in pedigree nurseries are usually milled in a test-tube miller (described in Annual Report, 1964), using 5- to 10-gram rough rice samples. Data on head and total milled rice yields are obtained on many of the selections. Percentage of hulls appears to be a reliable index of total milled rice, based on weighing 10-gram rough rice samples before and after hulling.

Milled rice grains are visually classified as to grain size and shape according to the following scale:

Size (length)	Shape (length/ width ratio)
Long — 6.61 to 7.50 mm	Bold — 2.0 or less
Medium — 5.51 to 6.60 mm	Medium — 2.1-3.0
Short — 5.50 mm or less	Slender — over 3.0

Milled grains are visually scored for presence or absence of white center and white belly, degree of translucency, and breakage at the basal-ventral end of grain, referred to as the condition of the "eye". The above determinations are scored on a 0 to 5 scale as illustrated in Fig. 1.

An alkali digestion test for determining gelatinization temperature and an analytical amylose determination are used as indices of cooking behavior. The empirical iodine-blue test has been discontinued for the most part as it has been possible to conduct as many as 500 analytical amylose determinations per week.

Most of the breeding lines grown in the pedigree nurseries were tested for gelatinization temperature and many were tested for amylose content. Most of the tropical *indica* varieties used as parents in the crossing program vary from 25 to over 30 percent amylose. Most *japonica* varieties show an amylose content of 20 percent or below, and U.S. varieties vary from 15 to 27 percent. Most of the tropical *indica* parent varieties show either a low or an intermediate gelatinization temperature, the *japonica* varieties are essentially all low, and the U.S. varieties have high, intermediate, and low gelatinization temperatures.

Within the short-statured *indica* hybrid selections developed, both low and intermediate gelatinization temperature lines were saved. For example, in the Peta x Taichung (Native) 1 backcross program the low gelatinization temperature of Taichung (Native) 1 has been retained through four backcrosses to Peta. Milled grains showing a low gelatinization temperature tend to cook faster than other types. For this reason, the low gelatinizing types may be more generally acceptable in tropical Asia than the intermediate or high gelatinizing types.

Most of the short-statured *indica* lines, like their parents, show amylose

Fig. 1. Variations in the appearance of milled rice. (A) translucency, (B) white core, (C) white belly, and (D) condition of the "eye."

contents varying from 25 to over 30 percent. By crossing with U.S. or *japonica* varieties, low amylose content (15 to 20 percent) is being introduced into the short-statured *indica* lines. Hybrid lines showing a wide range of amylose content are being developed since quality preferences vary in the different countries.

Yield trials

Replicated yield trials of the Institute breeding lines and selected check varieties were grown in 3 plantings: October 1964, and January, and June 1965. A basal dressing of nitrogen was usually applied (60 kg/ha) followed by a dressing of 30 kg/ha or more. Supplementary data were obtained from observational yield trials planted in January, March, and June of 1965.

The mean yields of several of the hybrid lines over 2 or 3 crops clearly indicate that they are superior to the widely grown tropical *indicas*, temperate *japonicas*, and southern U.S. varieties and lines. Some of the lines have the desired cooking characteristics. However, the lines are deficient in re-

sistance to one or more of the major diseases (blast, bacterial leaf blight, and tungro virus).

A partial listing of yield data and other traits of established varieties of diverse origin and of the more promising hybrid lines, summarized over 3 plantings, is given in Table 3. The tungro virus reactions were obtained from seedling tests by plant pathologists and may differ from the field reactions of adult plants. The data on reaction to blast were obtained from seedlings grown in disease nurseries. The bacterial leaf blight readings were based on flag leaf inoculations conducted in the field. Seed dormancy scores were based on the germination of 100 grains immediately following harvest and drying. Milled rice yields were based on 125-gram rough rice samples processed in a McGill sheller and a small McGill miller.

Cooperative variety testing in tropical Asia

To collect information on the performance of IRRI-bred, early-generation lines under a variety of environ-

TABLE 3. Agronomic, disease, and grain quality data on selected varieties and lines grown in replicated yield trials at 3 planting dates (October 1964, January and June 1965), IRRI.

IRRI Acc. Variety or No. selection	Grain yield (kg/ha)			Maturity (days seedling- harvest)		Mean no. panicles/plant	Mean plant ht (cm)	Mean lodging (%)	Disease			Seed Milled rice		Gelat. Amylose temp. (%)				
	Seeding date			Jan.	June				Tun- gro virus	Bact. leaf blight	Blast	maney	Head		Total			
	Oct. 64	Jan. 65	June 65													3 crops	Jan.	June
35 Peta	2980	2911	1426	2439	2168	152	135	17	159	95	R	S	S	92	49.6	72.7	I	28.5
39 BPI-76	3072		4453			(114) ^a	150	10	128	35	S	S	S	77	65.4	71.2	H	24.1
4095 Sigadis	3866	3857	3542	3755	3700	149	135	16	158	73	R	R	MR	77	47.6	72.9	I	29.0
259 81B-25	4058	4032	4385	4158	4208	155	143	16	186	93	R	S	MS	91	42.2	65.6	I	25.9
146 PI 215936	3738	4063	5239	4347	4651	127	113	13	124	0	S	R	S	4	67.8	70.7	L	20.2
92 Tainan 3	2896	4630	5074	4200	4852	131	113	13	127	32	S	R	S	1	65.9	75.6	L	17.9
87 Chianung 242	2965	5272	5300	4512	5286	135	113	11	132	12	S	R	MS	10	68.4	73.6	L	16.7
6993 CP 231 x SLO-17	3496	5331	4419	4415	4875	127	110	13	102	0	S	R	S	21	60.9	70.9	H	19.5
6973 A6-545, (CP 281/3 x Bbt)/2 x PI 215936	2968	6118	4855	4644	5487	134	113	13	117	2	I	R	R	9	61.8	72.4	H	25.6
6974 A3-47-15, PI 215936 x CI 9214	2067	5159	5047	4091	5103	132	113	12	140	27	S	R	S	3	54.4	70.6	I	26.8
9800 A3-47-15-1-2, PI 215936 x D-g-w-g	6934	5398	5398	6166		136	113	12	138	13	I	S	S	5	62.3	71.8	I	27.5
9792 A3-47-3-1, PI 215936 x CI 9214b	3574	4891	4517	4327	4704	135	112	12	144	34	S	R	S	6	56.6	70.2	I	25.7
9795 A3-47-4P-2P, PI 215936 x CI 9214	2823	5368	4412	4201	4890	128	110	12	135	34	S	S	MR	6	42.4	72.6	I	26.8
730 Milfor-6(2)	3799	4459	5381	4546	4920	137	126	11	162	20	S	I	S	55	47.6	71.9	I	24.1
105 Taichung (N) 1	4207	6811	5231	5416	6021	135	116	18	99	33	S	S	S	11	61.9	72.7	L	29.5

IR3-66, BPI-76 x D-g-w-g	3692	5644	5230	4855	5437	135	128	15	101	0	S	S	S	S	23	57.5	70.0	L	30.2
IR4-2, H-105 x D-g-w-g	4270	6526	5128	5308	5827	129	118	14	101	0	S	S	S	S	31	58.0	70.6	I	28.6
IR4-11, H-105 x D-g-w-g	3579	6073	5643	5098	5858	138	125	16	103	23	S	S	S	S	58	45.8	70.4	I/L	29.2
IR6-33-2, Siam 29 x D-g-w-g ^c	(5476)	5248	(5362)	130	133	14	111	0	S	S	S	S	S	30	53.0	70.6	I	29.1	
IR8-36, Peta x D-g-w-g	5074	6325	5760	5719	6047	135	126	16	110	23	S	S	S	17	54.6	70.6	I	29.0	
IR8-246, Peta x D-g-w-g	4621	7092	5115	5609	6104	138	127	16	106	15	S	S	S	35	51.3	71.8	I/L	29.0	
IR8-288-3, Peta x D-g-w-g ^c	(6511)	5610	(6060)	128	129	13	111	3	I	S	S	S	31	46.5	71.8	L	30.0		
IR9-60, Peta x I-g-t	4817	6783	5011	5534	5897	138	125	16	96	0	S	S	S	63	60.7	73.6	I	27.6	

^a October seeding.

^b January and June averages for all headings.

^c March and June averages for all headings except dormancy and quality data (March was observational yield trial).

ments in Southeast Asia, a number of F_3 or F_4 bulk populations and/or pedigree lines were sent to breeders in Hongkong, the Philippines, Malaysia, Taiwan, and Thailand for observation and selection. Most of the experimental lines were progenies of crosses involving a short-statured *indica* from Taiwan and a tall tropical *indica*. Other lines were derived from crosses of a U.S. line with a tropical *indica*, tropical *indica* with a *japonica* variety, or progenies of a *japonica* and a tropical *indica* backcrossed to the *indica* parent. Individual plant or panicle selections from such populations were made at the Bicol Rice and Corn Experiment Station (Philippines), Bukit Merah Padi Experiment Station (Malaysia), Bangkhen Experiment Station (Thailand), and San Pah Tong Experiment Station (Thailand). At Bukit Merah, a number of the short-statured selections were entered in a preliminary yield trial near the end of the year. In Thailand, pedigree nurseries of the above selections will be planted early in 1966 at Bangkhen. Near the end of the year, the Institute also furnished a set each of 303 selections and parent varieties for testing in Colombia, East Pakistan, India, Malaysia, Taiwan, and Thailand as pedigree lines.

During the wet season, 8 selections were entered in the regional lowland performance tests of the Philippine Seed Board at 6 experiment stations (UPCA at Los Baños, Laguna; Maligaya Rice Research & Training Center at Muñoz, Nueva Ecija; Palawan Station at Puerto Princesa, Palawan; Visayas Station at Iloilo City; Mindanao Station at Midsayap, Cotabato City; and Bicol Station at Pili, Camarines Sur). These entries are Taichung (Native) 1, Tainan 3, Acc. 9792 (PI 215936 x CI 9214), Acc. 9795 (PI 215936 x CI 9214), IR3-66 (BPI-76 x D-g-w-g), IR8-36 and, IR8-246 (Peta x D-g-w-g), and IR9-60 (Peta x I-g-t). The 8 selections were divided between 2 yield trials, each of which involved 2 nitrogen levels in replicated plots.

Partial yield data from the above 6 locations showed that at the UPCA, Mindanao Station, and Bicol Station,

the 4 IRRI semi-dwarf lines ranged from 3,247 to 5,029 kg/ha in mean yield and, as a group, surpassed the other tropical *indicas*. Among the 4 short-statured lines, IR9-60 was the highest yielding line among entries of comparable maturity, especially at the higher nitrogen level of 60 kg/ha. At the Maligaya Center and Palawan Station, the leading entries were IR8-246 and several selections developed by the Maligaya Station of the Philippine Bureau of Plant Industry. At Palawan, IR9-60 was heavily infected with bacterial leaf blight and *Helminthosporium* leaf spot. At Maligaya, IR9-60 showed a heavy incidence of bacterial leaf blight and a moderate infection of leaf blast when approaching maturity. As a group the IRRI short-statured lines yielded higher than Taichung (Native) 1, the *japonica* varieties, or the U.S. lines of *indica* x *japonica* parentage.

In another wet season experiment at Maligaya, the yield of 28 IRRI short-statured lines ranged from 1,578 to 6,843 kg/ha in unreplicated plots. The highest yields were obtained from IR5-47-2, (6,843 kg/ha) and IR8-288-3 (6,389 kg/ha), while the local check, BPI-76, yielded 3,497 kg/ha.

As a continuation of the above BPI-IRRI cooperative trials, 3 IRRI lines (IR6-52-3, IR8-288-3 and IR9-60) were entered in the successive series of tests to be grown in the 1965-66 dry season at the same locations.

At the Bangkhen Station of the Thai Rice Department, 26 varieties and lines were included in a replicated yield trial fertilized with 155 kg of nitrogen. The line IR8-288-3 (Peta x D-g-w-g) led the early maturing entries with a mean yield of 6,483 kg/ha, a record figure for Thailand. Another short-statured selection, IR8-188-1, yielded 5,127 kg/ha, whereas the check variety (Leuang Tawng) yielded 3,591 kg/ha. The high yield of IR8-288-3 and IR8-188-1 may be partly attributed to their moderate field resistance to the virus diseases. The *japonica* varieties and the U.S. selections all yielded lower than the check variety, mainly because of heavy virus infections.

This year's initial cooperative trials suggest that the short-statured lines selected from Taiwan's semi-dwarf *indicas* x tall tropical *indicas* generally showed wider adaptability and superior yield performance than the *japonicas*, U.S. selections, or local *indica* varieties under a variety of environments and cultural practices common to tropical areas. From the above preliminary findings, new crosses have been added to further improve the disease resistance and grain quality of these short-statured selections.

Seedling vigor in rice varieties

Seedling vigor expressed as quick emergence from the soil is a required characteristic in directly seeded plantings. In transplanted crops, rapid seedling growth in the early stages is a much desired trait in the tropics. One of the principal features of early growth vigor is the speed at which tillers are produced to cover the space between seedlings.

A preliminary study was made among 28 varieties and lines which differed appreciably in growth characteristics. Measurements on mesocotyl length taken from seeds germinated in darkness showed that the *japonicas* as a group had short mesocotyls. The other 24 strains varied greatly in mesocotyl length. Four semi-dwarf lines, Leuang Yai 34, MTU-15, and Binato had shorter mesocotyls than the *japonicas*. Tai-chung (Native) 1 did not have an elongated mesocotyl. The other *indicas* generally showed longer mesocotyls.

As a group, the *japonica* varieties showed the lowest speed in coleoptile emergence. Most of the semi-dwarf *indicas* were also slow in emergence but a few showed an intermediate speed. Among the U.S. strains, CP 231, which is adapted to direct seeding, showed rapid emergence. Three other U.S. selections also showed rapid emergence, but one line (Acc. 9795) of *indica* x *japonica* parentage was as slow as the *japonicas*. One Philippine upland variety, Palawan, gave the highest speed in emergence. However, the maximum difference in the rate of emergence was about 36 hours.

Three U.S. strains (CP 231, Acc. 9792, Acc. 9795), and Palawan and Mangarez (upland) had the smallest number (about 9) of leaves on the main culm at 52 days following seeding. Other U.S. strains, the *japonicas*, a few of the tropical *indicas*, and three semi-dwarfs had an intermediate number of leaves (range 9.5-10.5). Most of the semi-dwarfs and Peta had nearly 11 leaves. Sigadis led the group with a mean of 11.5 leaves.

The emergence of the 6th, 9th, 12th, and 15th leaves on the young plants was recorded. On this basis the semi-dwarfs, Sigadis, Peta, and Intan showed rapid leaf development, followed by the other tropical *indicas*. The U.S. selections and the upland varieties were among the slowest and the *japonicas* showed an intermediate rate. The maximum difference in the date of the appearance of the 9th leaf among varieties was 5 days, whereas the difference for the 15th leaf was 19 days.

At 35 days following transplanting, the upland varieties, the U.S. selections, one semi-dwarf (IR4-2), and the *japonicas* had 5 to 8 tillers. Most of the tropical *indicas* belonged to the intermediate group (8-9 tillers). Peta and most of the semi-dwarfs had 10 to 13 tillers. The largest number of tillers at the maximum tillering stage was observed in the semi-dwarfs and some of the tropical *indicas* such as Peta and Intan. The lowest number was found in the upland varieties. The U.S. lines and *japonicas* also had low tiller numbers.

The increase in tiller number between the 26th and 44th day following seeding also varied appreciably among varieties. The greatest rate of increase was observed in most of the semi-dwarfs, Peta and Intan. The smallest rate of increase was found in the U.S. selections, the upland varieties, and Chianung 242.

The number of leaves on the main culm and the number of tillers at 35 days following seeding, were found to be positively correlated ($r=0.77$) at a highly significant level.

The above findings suggest that early growth vigor is largely associated with the number of leaves and tillers

and their rate of development in young plants. Although the Institute plant physiologists have observed that heavy tillering in long duration varieties tends to result in overcrowding and mutual shading at the later stages of growth, a vigorous and rapid vegetative growth starting at an early stage and sustained

up to anthesis appears to be a desirable trait in the early maturing strains. Thus, the relatively leafy growth and heavy tillering habit of the short-statured *indicas* may enable the young plants to become fully established before weed competition becomes a problem.

BREEDING METHODS AND TECHNIQUES

Natural selection in bulk populations

The concept of plant type as outlined in previous reports is basic to the breeding of improved varieties for the tropics. Abundant evidence indicates that certain leaf and culm traits and maturity period, alone and in combination, condition nitrogen responsiveness and high grain yield. As most present tropical varieties show an undesirable vegetative plant type, introduced temperate region varieties, which are early in maturity and have small, erect leaves and short, sturdy culms, are used as parental sources of the basic plant type required for high production in the tropics.

The hybridization of two distinct types, to recombine desirable features of each, leads to a profusion of segregates which differ greatly in plant type. Field experience suggests that desirable plant types suffer in competition with the plant types characteristic of tropical varieties. This would clearly limit the usefulness of the bulk breeding method in the selection of improved types for tropical conditions. It also suggests that competitiveness is not equated with yield capacity in pure stands and that the relationship of certain plant traits to competitiveness may be identified, as has been done for the relationships between the same traits to nitrogen responsiveness and yield ability. Two studies were initiated to investigate the relationship between competitive ability and yield potential under different environments.

Competition in varietal mixtures. In 1963, five varieties of contrasting plant types but having equal maturity periods were mixed in equal proportions to form four bulks. The varieties are il-

lustrated in Fig. 2. By transplanting single plants per hill at a 30 x 20 cm spacing, 1,000 plants of each variety were randomly planted in each bulk. Thus, each variety initially constituted 20 percent of each bulk. Each bulk is being grown each year at one of the following environments: wet season at 0 and 50 kg/ha N and dry season at 0 and 100 kg/ha N. A census of each variety is made each planting to establish changes in bulk composition. These changes measure relative competitiveness.

In addition, the 5 varieties are grown each semester in a yield trial consisting of 8-row plots with 6 replications at two nitrogen levels, to provide an estimate of relative yielding ability.

Changing compositions of the 4 bulks are shown in Fig. 3. The two typical tropical varieties, BJ 1 and MTU-15, quickly dominated the bulks and the improved plant types represented by Taichung (Native) 1, Chianung 242, and Milfor-6(2) suffered a severe competitive disadvantage. Although dry season plantings and high nitrogen levels intensify competition, the varieties show the same relative competitiveness over each environment tested.

The yield data from pure stands (Ta-

TABLE 4. Mean yields (ton/ha) of 5 varieties in various environments.

Variety	Wet season (3 years)		Dry season (2 years)	
	0 N	50 N	0 N	100 N
Taichung (Native) 1	4.63	4.46	6.20	6.12
Chianung 242	3.94	3.97	4.90	5.10
Milfor-6(2)	3.81	4.05	4.27	4.53
MTU-15	2.40	1.84	3.40	3.13
BJ 1	2.26	2.21	2.89	2.87

Fig. 2. Five contrasting plant types grown in the study of natural selection in bulk populations.

ble 4) show that the least competitive varieties have the highest yield potential. The highest yielding varieties, Taichung (Native) 1 and Chianung 242, have desirable plant types and are representative of the varieties being developed at the Institute.

Competition in segregating populations. Short stature in the variety Taichung (Native) 1 is conditioned primarily by a single major recessive gene. Short stature is a prerequisite to nitrogen responsiveness and high yield potential. An experiment was designed to study the relationship of plant height to competitiveness and yield capacity.

F_2 seed of the cross Peta x Taichung (Native) 1 was planted in single-plant hills at a spacing of 30 x 30 cm in two bulks grown separately at 0 and a high level of nitrogen. The seed produced was planted as F_3 bulks at the two nitrogen levels and the process is being repeated through F_6 . A census of short

and tall plants in each bulk in each succeeding population is made to measure competition of tall plants versus short plants.

A large number of tall and short plants of equal maturity were selected from homozygous F_3 lines to establish tall and short F_4 populations for entry into a replicated yield trial which will be continued through the F_6 . Differences in yield would measure the influence of the single height locus on

TABLE 5. Expected and observed frequencies of short plants from the cross Peta x Taichung (Native) 1 in bulk populations grown at two nitrogen levels.

Generation	Percent expected	Percent observed	
		0 N	High N
F_2	25.0	24.9	24.9
F_3	37.5	31.2	22.4
F_4	43.8	33.5	18.9

Fig. 3. Changes in varietal composition of 4 bulks grown under differing environments.

yield. The tall and the short populations may be considered as isogenic with the assumption of no linkage.

Changes in frequencies of tall and short plants in the bulks are presented in Table 5. Short plants appeared in expected numbers in the F_2 , but in later generations they were fewer than expected. Thus it appears that short plants are less competitive than tall plants. The addition of nitrogen intensifies the effect of competition against short plants.

TABLE 6. Plant height and yield of short and F_4 bulks and the parents of the cross Peta x Taichung (Native) 1.

Entry	Yield (ton/ha)		Height (cm)	
	0 N	50 N	0 N	50 N
Taichung (Native) 1	5.55	6.09	100	107
Short bulk	4.91	5.34	98	104
Tall bulk	4.86	4.99	167	178
Peta	4.99	3.51	176	181

Short segregates in the F_4 generation yielded less than the short parent (Table 6). This was expected as the short

bulk consists of a mixture of adapted and unadapted plants all of which contribute to yield. The short bulk, however, yielded the same as the tall bulk at 0 nitrogen and was only slightly better at the high nitrogen level. Yield differences might increase in subsequent generations.

Partial sterility in *indica* x *japonica* hybrids

A detailed evaluation of sterility in wide crosses, particularly as it influences breeding objectives and methodology was completed. Detailed data and conclusions are presented in IRRI Technical Bulletin No. 5 and only the major findings are summarized here.

Thirteen *indica* and 14 *japonica* varieties were hybridized to produce 363 crosses, including reciprocals. The study of the fertility of the parent varieties and over 4,900 F_1 plants resulted in the following observations.

- Hybrids of photoperiod-insensitive parents were invariably earlier in maturity than either parent, indicating heterosis and/or dominance of genes for earliness. Hybrids between photoperiod-sensitive and insensitive varieties all showed dominance of photoperiod sensitivity.
- Parent varieties were normally fertile. Taiwanese *japonicas* were somewhat more fertile than Japanese *japonicas*. Pollen and spikelet fertilities were highly significantly correlated ($r=0.415$) in the 27 parent varieties. Coefficients of variability for within-parent pollen and spikelet fertility averaged 2 and 6 percent, respectively.
- Mean F_1 fertility ranged from 6 to 98 percent for pollen and 1 to 92 percent for spikelets. All F_1 plants together averaged 46 percent fertility in both pollen and spikelets.
- Hybrids having Japanese *japonicas* as one parent averaged 43 percent fertility in both pollen and spikelets compared with 48 percent for hybrids having Taiwanese *japonicas* as a parent.

5. No large differences between pollen and spikelet fertility were observed for any hybrid.
 6. There was a pronounced and unexplained tendency for one measure of fertility to exceed the other in sets of crosses grouped by common *indica* parentage. No consistent differences were found when crosses were grouped by common *japonica* parentage.
 7. All hybrids having a common *indica* parent showed comparable fertility irrespective of their *japonica* parentage. Hybrids having a common *japonica* parent showed little consistency in fertility level. Therefore, although fertility depended upon the specific combination of parent varieties, the level of fertility was associated with the *indica* parent of the hybrid.
 8. Coefficients of variability for plant-to-plant differences in fertility within hybrids were usually moderately low and averaged 16 percent (pollen) and 20 percent (spikelet) for all crosses. Percent c.v. showed a negative association with levels of fertility.
 9. A highly significant correlation ($r=0.840$) was calculated for pollen and spikelet fertility for all F_1 plants together.
 10. It was shown that many potentially fertile ovules of hybrids having a high degree of sterility did not set seed because of inadequate pollination, explaining in part the often reported tendency for spikelet sterility to exceed pollen sterility.
 11. Paired hybrids of 181 reciprocal crosses did not differ significantly in fertility.
 12. It was concluded on the basis of varied lines of evidence that pollen and spikelet fertilities do not differ arithmetically, are highly correlated, and have the same basic cause.
 13. Pollen fertility in parent varieties was slightly influenced by environment whereas spikelet fertility often showed considerable environmental variation.
 14. In the partially sterile hybrids, there can be a large and roughly comparable effect of environment on spikelet and pollen fertility, and the effect increases in proportion to the level of sterility.
- Fifteen normally fertile U.S. lines, derived from *indica* x *japonica* hybridizations were crossed with typical *indicas* and *japonicas* and among themselves. In 41 crosses with 11 *indicas* the mean spikelet fertility was 82 percent. Mean spikelet fertility was 92 percent in 7 hybrids with 2 *japonicas*. Eleven intercrosses of the lines had 91 percent spikelet fertility. It was concluded that derived lines having *indica* and *japonica* germ plasm are highly fertile with representative varieties of both variety groups.
- The genetics and consequences of hybrid sterility were studied in four large F_2 populations derived from crosses which differed greatly in F_1 fertility. The significant results are summarized as follows:
1. F_2 populations showed wide and continuous segregation from highly sterile to highly fertile classes; many plants more sterile than the F_1 parent were observed.
 2. Each population was characterized by a single distinct modal class for fertility and each seemed to consist of a large number of genetically distinct classes.
 3. Mean F_2 fertility, and fertility of the modal class, increased as F_1 fertility increased.
 4. Population fertility ranges and F_2 plant frequencies in the more sterile and the more fertile ranges were associated with F_1 fertility.
 5. There is a direct association of F_1 fertility with F_2 fertility, suggesting that F_1 fertility predicts F_2 breeding behavior for fertility.
 6. The association between F_1 and F_2 fertility, and the presence of many F_2 fertility classes, tend to support the hypothesis that sterility in the F_1 and the F_2 is caused by common chromosomal and/or genic mechanisms.

7. F_2 segregation ratios for monogenic and quantitative characters were normal and undisturbed by the degree of sterility.
8. Heterozygotes and homozygotes of two monogenic traits had equal fertility, suggesting that sterility would not cause abnormal gene frequencies in the F_3 or later generations.
9. Recombinants and non-recombinants (parental types) were equally fertile regardless of the degree of hybrid sterility in the population.
10. There was no deficiency of recombinants resulting from hybrid sterility.
11. Although *indica* genes and character associations may progressively dominate hybrid populations, it is suggested that their superior fitness is caused by their greater competitiveness in relation to natural selection and is not caused by increased hybrid fertility.

Heterosis

A preliminary study of heterosis was conducted during the 1964 wet season with 24 *indica* x *japonica* hybrids which showed normal F_1 fertility. The 24 F_1 hybrids (335 plants) were transplanted without replication between their respective parents in single-plant hills at a wide spacing of 30 x 30 cm. A minimal application of 15 kg/ha N was top-dressed at 45 days after sowing. There was slight or no heterosis for plant height. Earliness, total tiller number and percent productive tillers, and grain yield all showed unusually high levels of hybrid vigor. Mean hybrid grain yield, for example, averaged 162 percent of the high parent and 189 percent of the mid-parential yields.

The unusual heterotic values observed led to a detailed study in cooperation with the department of Plant Physiology during the 1965 wet season. Two hybrids, B5711A1-18-6 x Tainan 3 and Chianung 242 x BPI-76, were transplanted in single-plant hills at 25 x 25 cm with three nitrogen levels: 0, 50 and 100 kg/ha. Plots measuring 6.25 m² were replicated twice. Data were recorded at 40 days after transplanting, at flowering, and at harvest.

Percent heterosis for vegetative traits in the F_1 (mid-parent = 100%) is shown in Fig. 4. Data are summarized for both crosses at all nitrogen levels. The plant height, tiller number, dry weight, and LAI data all indicate that the F_1 showed substantial vegetative vigor in the early growth stages. The parent varieties increased in plant size later, so that by flowering the F_1 showed little hybrid vigor. The marked reduction of light penetration into the F_1 population at 40 days after transplanting confirms the exceptional, early vegetative growth of the hybrids.

Grain yield, averaged for both hybrids and three nitrogen levels, was 98 percent of the mid-parent yield. Heterosis in the F_1 for grain-straw ratio was 132 percent.

The extremely vigorous vegetative development of the hybrids during the early growth stages resulted in excessive mutual shading which inhibited net

Fig. 4. Mean heterosis values of two hybrids grown at three nitrogen levels.

assimilation and also reduced the amount of storage products available for translocation to the grain during the period from flowering to maturity. Consequently, no heterosis for yield was observed. The large advantage in grain-straw ratio of the hybrids is related directly to their earlier maturity; one hybrid averaged 5 days earlier than the mean of the parents, and another was 22 days earlier (one parent being photoperiodic).

These data from large, replicated plots are at variance with those from the unreplicated, widely-spaced preliminary study conducted in 1964. They

also confirm the importance of investigating heterosis with field populations and spacing that approximate those of normal agronomic technique.

The indication that heterosis for yield was precluded by the exceptional mutual shading which developed early in the vegetatively vigorous hybrids suggests an area for future study. It is possible that heterosis for yield will be difficult to demonstrate under the low light, high-temperature conditions of the tropics. Identical hybrids grown in temperate regions having a more favorable environment, however, might show increased vigor for grain production.

GENETIC STUDIES

Genetic analysis of the components of growth duration

With the cooperation of the plant physiologists, the inheritance of growth duration is being studied by the component-analysis method. The total growth duration of an individual plant is divisible into four components: (1) the basic vegetative phase, (2) a photoperiod-sensitive phase, (3) a thermosensitive phase, and (4) the reproductive phase from panicle initiation to full maturity. The portion of the fourth component from panicle initiation to panicle emergence (heading) is the least variable portion among varieties and averages about 35 days. By recording the number of days from seeding to heading among hybrid progenies of tropical varieties of

low thermosensitivity, the two major components involved in such crosses are the basic vegetative phase (b.v.p.) and the other portion which is largely comprised of the photoperiod-sensitive phase (p.s.p.).

When vegetative tillers from the same plant are placed under different photoperiods, the basic vegetative phase and the photoperiod-sensitive phase of the same individual can be readily determined in one experimental planting, thereby eliminating the complicating factor of changing photoperiods under natural conditions. The technique consists of starting the parent varieties and hybrid progenies (F_1 and F_2) under a 10-hour photoperiod and separating one of the earliest primary tillers from each plant for growth under a 16-

TABLE 7. F_2 segregation for photoperiod sensitivity and basic vegetative phase in four crosses.

Cross	Photosensitivity			Basic vegetative phase				P of χ^2 and ratio
	Sensitive	Insen- sitive	P of χ^2 and ratio	very short	short	med.	long	
BPI-76 x Tainan 3	97	32	.98-.95 (3:1)		96	24		.95-.90 (12:3:1)
Siam 29 x Tainan 3	206	18	.30-.20 (15:1)	125	46	38	15	.90-.80 (9:3:3:1)
R.S. 3 x Milfor-6(2)	103	29	.50-.30 (3:1)	49	74	7	2	.70-.50 (27:33:3:1)
R.S. 3 x I-g-t	72	69	.30-.20 (9:7)	55	50	24	12	.70-.50 (27:21:12:4)

hour photoperiod. The sensitive individuals exert panicles early under the 10-hour photoperiod but also grow vegetatively for an extended, indefinite period under the 16-hour photoperiod. Non-sensitive plants flower under the 16-hour photoperiod soon after the corresponding primary tiller has flowered under the 10-hour treatment.

Four crosses, each involving a photoperiod-sensitive parent and an essentially insensitive parent, were studied in the above manner. The two parents of each cross also differed appreciably in the length of the b.v.p. The sensitive x insensitive crosses were Raminad Strain 3 x I-geo-tze, Raminad Strain 3 x Milfor-6(2), BPI-76 x Tainan 3, and

with a number of F₁ hybrids from other crosses or of the same crosses.

Photoperiod response of F₂ plants. The F₂ populations of Raminad Strain 3 x Milfor-6(2) and BPI-76 x Tainan 3 each showed a segregation ratio of 3 sensitive to 1 insensitive, indicating that high photoperiod sensitivity in each cross was governed by a single, dominant allele, *Se* (Table 7). The F₂ population of Raminad Strain 3 x I-geo-tze was distributed as 72 sensitive and 69 insensitive plants, showing a significant deviation from the 3:1 ratio. However, the above segregation was compatible with a 9:7 ratio. Since the 10 F₁ plants were also sensitive, it is reasonable to assume that the I-geo-tze parent carried a recessive inhibitor-gene for sensitivity (symbol: *i-Se*) which would result in the 9:7 distribution of F₂ plants. This postulate involving a suppressor gene will be further verified from selected lines in the F₃ generation.

The cross of Siam 29 x Tainan 3 gave a proportion of 206 sensitive to 18 insensitive F₂ plants, indicating a significant deviation from the 3:1 ratio. How-

Fig. 5. Basic vegetative phase (solid line) and photoperiod-sensitive phase (dotted line) of Parents and F₁ plants (days).

Siam 29 x Tainan 3. Plantings included the parents, the F₁ plants, and the F₂ plants.

F₁ behavior. In each of the four crosses, the F₁ hybrids were photoperiod-sensitive and shorter in b.v.p. than either parent (Fig. 5). The results indicated that (1) high photoperiod-sensitivity is dominant to low sensitivity, and (2) short b.v.p. is dominant to long b.v.p. The above data also confirmed the preliminary results reported in 1964

Fig. 6. Distribution and means of parents, F₁ and F₂ plants by the length of the basic vegetative phase (days) in the cross of Raminad Strain 3 x Milfor-6(2). Solid horizontal lines show the range of b.v.p. of parents and F₁ plants about the means (dotted circles).

ever, the observed ratio is compatible with a 15:1 ratio, which would involve two duplicate genes for photoperiod-sensitivity (Se_1 and Se_2).

Basic vegetative phase of F_2 plants. The distribution of the two parents, the F_1 hybrids, and the F_2 plants with respect to b.v.p. in each of the four crosses showed certain similarities: (1) the F_1 plants had a shorter b.v.p. (difference: 6-13 days) than the short, photoperiod-sensitive parent, (2) a number of F_2 plants had an even shorter b.v.p. (difference: 1-13 days) than the short F_1 plants, and (3) a smaller number of plants had a considerably longer b.v.p. (difference: 13-58 days) than the long, insensitive parent. The above results indicated transgressive segregation in each of the four crosses (Figs. 6 and 7).

In the Siam 29 (P_1) x Tainan 3 (P_2) cross, the F_2 distribution with respect to b.v.p. indicated a satisfactory agreement with the 9 (shorter than the short P_1): 3 (similar to P_1): 3 (similar to P_2): 1 (longer than the long P_2). The above distribution suggested that the two parents each carried a dominant allele for short b.v.p. similar to duplicate genes. The short b.v.p. gene (symbol Ef_{11}) in the sensitive (P_1) Siam 29 parent was epistatic (more effective) to the other short b.v.p. gene (Ef_{12}) in the insensitive parent (P_2). The two genes controlling b.v.p. also appeared to be cumulative in action, thus providing F_2 plants which were earlier than the shorter, sensitive parent.

The segregation in the BPI-76 x Tainan 3 cross indicated good agreement with the 12 (shorter than the short P_1 or similar to P_1): 3 (similar to P_2): 1 (longer than P_2). The distribution also indicated that the two parents each carried a dominant allele for short b.v.p., the gene (Ef_{21}) in the sensitive BPI-76 parent (P_1) being epistatic to that (Ef_{22}) in the insensitive parent (P_2).

In the Raminad Strain 3 x Milfor-6(2) cross, the two parents only differed by 10 days in b.v.p. The F_2 plants were largely distributed about the two parents with a number of plants distinctly later than Milfor (Fig. 6). The segregation may be interpreted on the basis of three genes: Raminad Strain

Fig. 7. Distribution and means of parents, F_1 , and F_2 plants by the length of the basic vegetative phase (days) in the cross of Raminad Strain 3 x I-geo-tze. Solid lines show the range of b.v.p. of parents and F_1 plants about the means (dotted circles).

3 had $Ef_{31} Ef_{31} ef_{32} ef_{32} Ef_{34} Ef_{34}$, Milfor-6(2) had $ef_{31} ef_{31} Ef_{32} Ef_{32} ef_{34} ef_{34}$, and the F_2 ratio was compatible with the 27 (earlier than P_1): 33 (similar to P_1 or P_2): 3 (later than P_2): 1 (much later than P_2). The order of epistacy in the three-gene series is then $Ef_{31} > Ef_{32} > Ef_{34}$.

In the Raminad Strain 3 x I-geo-tze cross, a multimodal F_2 distribution was noted (Fig. 7). A large proportion of the F_2 plants was compatible with the postulate that Raminad Strain 3 carried the genic constitution of $Ef_{31} Ef_{31} ef_{33} ef_{33} Ef_{34} Ef_{34}$ and that I-g-t had the genic formula of $ef_{31} ef_{31} Ef_{33} Ef_{33} ef_{34} ef_{34}$, resulting in a segregation ratio of 27 (shorter than P_1): 21 (similar to P_1): 12 (similar to P_2): 4 (later than P_2). The order of epistacy in the three-gene series is $Ef_{31} > Ef_{33} > Ef_{34}$.

TABLE 8. Mean values of plant height, culm length, number of days to heading, tiller and panicle numbers, panicle weight, and size of sample in three semi-dwarfs and their F_1 hybrids.

Trait	Igt	T(N)1 x Igt	Igt x T(N)1	T(N)1	T(N)1 x Dgwg	Dgwg x T(N)1	Dgwg	Igt x Dgwg	Dgwg x Igt
Plant height (cm)	100.0	100.8	103.7	99.8	102.2	101.1	112.3	118.2	116.9
Culm length (cm)	77.3	76.5	78.8	76.1	78.2	77.7	88.3	93.1	92.4
Days to heading	71.0	74.0	74.0	79.0	79.0	79.0	86.0	78.0	75.0
Tiller no.	16.3	32.6	30.7	20.4	21.7	32.0	16.4	26.8	26.3
Panicle no.	15.3	32.1	30.1	19.9	21.7	31.8	16.0	25.8	25.6
Panicle wt (g)	3.2	3.5	3.6	2.9	3.2	3.9	3.2	4.1	4.3
No. plants sampled	10.0	7.0	10.0	8.0	3.0	4.0	9.0	6.0	10.0

In BPI-76 x Tainan 3, those F_2 plants with extremely short b.v.p. were photoperiod-sensitive, whereas those with extremely long b.v.p. were essentially insensitive. A similar pattern was noted in Siam 29 x Tainan 3 and Raminad Strain 3 x Milfor, suggesting an association between high sensitivity and short b.v.p. In R.S. 3 x I-g-t, the above association was not observed since it has been postulated that I-g-t carried the recessive inhibitor gene for sensitivity and that some of the insensitive F_2 plants actually were *Se Se i-Se i-Se*.

The photoperiod-sensitive gene or genes appeared to be more potent than the genes controlling b.v.p. The order of gene expressivity is, therefore, $Se > Ef_{11} > Ef_{12} > Ef_{13}, Ef_{21} > Ef_{22}, Ef_{31} > Ef_{32} > Ef_{34}, Ef_{32} > Ef_{33},$ and $i-Se > Se$.

The segregation of the photosensitivity gene(s) and the b.v.p. genes appeared to be largely independent. This suggests that a breeder would obtain from a sensitive x insensitive cross certain photoperiod-insensitive progenies with short b.v.p., if he could differentiate between sensitive and insensitive individuals. As multiple loci of at least three to five genes would be involved, it is desirable to grow F_2 populations of an adequate size in order to include the desired genotypes.

Allelism of genes for short stature, maturity and other quantitative traits in three semi-dwarf varieties

Dee-geo-woo-gen, I-geo-tze, and Taichung (Native) 1 are three early maturing, nitrogen responsive, semi-dwarf

indicas from Taiwan which are being intensively used in the Institute's breeding program. The short stature in both I-geo-tze and Taichung (Native) 1 is inherited largely as a single-recessive trait as reported in the 1964 Annual Report. Taichung (Native) 1 is a progeny of Tsai-yuan-chung x Dee-geo-woo-gen and presumably derived the short-stature gene from Dee-geo-woo-gen. I-geo-tze is a strain selected from commercial fields and its pedigree is unknown. The allelic relationship of the short-stature genes in I-geo-tze, Taichung (Native) 1, and Dee-geo-woo-gen was not known.

Three intercrosses among the three dwarfs were made in the dry season, and the F_1 hybrids together with their parents were grown in the wet season. Data on mean plant height, culm length, days to heading, tiller number, panicle number, and panicle weight are summarized in Table 8.

Plant height and culm length data showed that the F_1 hybrids in the three intercrosses and their reciprocals and their parents did not differ significantly in these traits. I-g-t x D-g-w-g hybrids in the reciprocal crosses were slightly taller than the taller D-g-w-g parent, probably a sign of heterotic vigor. The T(N)1 x D-g-w-g F_1 plants did not exceed the D-g-w-g parent in either plant height or culm length. It appears that the three varieties have the same dwarf-stature gene since the hybrids were not significantly different from their parents. The F_2 populations and the parents will be grown in the 1966 dry season to detect any segregation for genes controlling plant stature.

The F_1 hybrids were generally intermediate or slightly earlier than the mid-parent value in maturity, suggesting that the slight degree of earliness detected is an expression of heterotic vigor. Heterotic vigor was also expressed by greater tiller number, panicle number, and panicle weight than the parents.

Modifying genes controlling plant height

From the F_2 and F_3 data in the Peta x I-geo-tze cross, it was postulated that in addition to the major gene controlling the difference in plant height between Peta and I-geo-tze, there appeared to be other genes of modifying effect. To verify this point, a number of F_3 lines which were either shorter than the I-g-t parent or taller than the Peta parent were grown as F_4 lines in the 1965 dry season. From these F_4 lines, those which were homozygous for plant height and maturity, and had a mean height either shorter than I-g-t or taller than Peta, were grown as 21-plant rows in the wet season. Among the homozygous F_5 lines, 10 plants per line were measured for plant height. Comparisons with one of the parents were made by using the t test for significance.

Among the 204 semi-dwarf F_5 lines, the mean height ranged from 82.8 to 115.3 cm, whereas the I-g-t parent measured 116.9 cm. Of these, 200 were significantly shorter than I-g-t, ranging from 82.8 to 106.6 cm. The other 4 lines varied from 110.1 to 115.3 cm and did not differ significantly from I-g-t. Among the 587 tall lines, plant height ranged from 163.1 to 214.1 cm, whereas Peta measured 172.1 cm. Within those F_5 lines, 541 lines which varied from 181.4 to 214.1 cm were significantly taller than Peta. The other 46 lines did not differ significantly from Peta and ranged from 163.1 to 185.6 cm; a smaller variance was also noted within the group.

The above findings indicate that in addition to the recessive allele which conditions the semi-dwarf stature in I-g-t, other height genes of a modifying nature are also present to account for the wide and transgressive segregation in the Peta x I-g-t cross. These modifiers would enable a breeder to select in such a cross among an array of short-statured lines, ranging from 80 to 115 cm in the wet seasons. This possibility has been utilized in the Institute's breeding program where a large number of semi-dwarf x tall tropical *indica* crosses have been made and processed.

CYTOGENETIC STUDIES

Cytogenetic studies on the nature of sterility in intervarietal hybrids and irradiated progenies were made to elucidate problems of vital interest to breeders. The investigations were conducted under a cooperative project with the College of Agriculture, the University of the Philippines. Dr. Dolores A. Ramirez of the College cooperated in the cytological investigations.

Cytological study of sterility in *indica* x *japonica* hybrids

A cytological study of sterility in F_1 hybrids from 12 cross-combinations was completed during the year. Five *indica* and six *japonica* parents were included in the study. The pollen and spikelet fertility of the parents ranged from 87.4

to 99.0 and 84.9 to 98.5 percent respectively. Among the hybrids, the pollen and spikelet fertility readings varied from 14.6 to 99.3 and 0.6 to 94.8 percent respectively. The pollen and spikelet fertility readings were positively correlated ($r=0.48$) at the 5 percent level of significance.

"Loose pairing" of chromosomes at the pachytene-diplotene stages were frequently observed in both the F_1 hybrids and the parents. The range of frequency of "loose pairs" found in the parents was from 3.5 to 42.6 percent. In the hybrids, the frequency ranged from 4.5 to 24.2 percent. There were indications that the loosely paired chromosomes were in the process of chiasma formation at the late pachytene or early dip-

plotene stages and may not have indicated true structural differences in the chromosomes.

All the parent varieties showed essentially normal chromosome behavior at diakinesis and metaphase I, except BPI-76 which showed occasional univalents at diakinesis (1.1%) and at metaphase I (1.5%), and Kaohsiung 68 which showed univalents (0.3%) at metaphase I.

Univalents were observed at diakinesis and metaphase I in some of the hybrids studied. In general, more cells with univalents were observed in the hybrids than in the parent varieties. However, the frequency of these unpaired chromosomes was very low: 0.2% (Siam 29 x Kaohsiung 68) to 2.4% (Rikuu 132 x CP 231 and T 1242 x Norin 20). The frequency of univalents in the hybrids was too low to account for the observed incidence of spikelet and pollen sterility. It is believed that the univalents were due to the precocious disjunction of the homologues. One cell with a ring-of-four configuration was observed at diakinesis in the hybrid Norin 17 x BPI-76. This ring might have been due to an exchange of segments between two pairs of chromosomes.

Chromosome bridges without acentric fragments were observed in some of the parent varieties (3-7%) and most of the hybrids (1.3-13.4%) at anaphase I. Two of the hybrids had a low incidence (about 1%) of bridge formation at telophase I. The presence of these bridges in the parent and hybrid varieties was not associated proportionally with the extent of pollen abortion. These bridges might have resulted from a delayed disjunction of the homologues following a delayed terminalization of chiasmata.

Anaphase bridges with acentric fragments were observed at a very low frequency (1.3-5.2%) in four of the hybrids. The nature of the bridges could not be ascertained, as no inversion loops were observed at pachynema. Bridges with fragments were not observed in any of the parent varieties.

There was no distinct cytological evidence of structural differentiation

between the chromosomes of the *indica* and *japonica* varieties. The hybrids exhibited essentially the same meiotic behavior as the parent varieties. Although gross chromosomal aberrations such as univalents and anaphase bridges were observed, the frequency was too low to account for the high pollen and spikelet sterility of the hybrids. There were no basic differences in the type and frequency of chromosome aberrations between the parents and hybrids and among the hybrids exhibiting different degrees of sterility.

The development of the anthers following meiosis was also studied in some hybrids and their parents. The anther sections did not reveal any detectable differences between the fertile parents and the sterile F_1 hybrids in the appearance of the epidermis, endothecium, and tapetum. No obvious abnormality of anther development could be found to be associated with pollen abortion.

While the above findings do not exclude the possibility of cryptic structural differences in the chromosomes of the two parental types including inversions of the included type, the cytological data suggest that the sterility of the F_1 hybrids is more complex than is often assumed and may be attributed to more than one type of causal factor. The data suggest that a mechanism of genetic imbalance, which exerts its deleterious effects upon the gametes of the F_1 hybrids, is probably involved. The disharmonious combinations of genes are reflected in the wide range of sterility readings found in the hybrids as contrasted with a much narrower range of variability in chromosomal aberrations. However, genic sterility and chromosomal sterility are extremely difficult to distinguish experimentally. The segregation for sterility in the F_2 and F_3 generations is being followed to provide additional genetic information on this subject.

Sterility in F_4 plants

A number of F_4 plants showing high sterility in January-February were taken from the pedigree nursery and grown as a ratoon crop. Microspores were collected from these ratooned

plants which were either progenies of (*indica* x *japonica*) or (*indica* x U.S. line) hybrids. The pollen fertility of the F_4 plants ranged from zero to 43 percent.

In four highly sterile lines of Mong Chim Vang A x PI 215936 (0-3% pollen fertility), meiosis was normal in the majority (78-90%) of the pollen mother cells. Two or four univalents were observed with low frequency (2-11%) at diakinesis in a number of cells.

Fig. 8. Laggards and bridges at anaphase I in F_4 line 12339 of Mon Chim Vang A x PI 215936.

Bridges at anaphase (Fig. 8) and laggards at telophase were noted in several others. Twenty-four univalents were found in two lines at metaphase (1.7-2.3%). In three lines, multinucleate cells (syncytes) were observed at frequencies ranging from 2 to 12 percent (Fig. 9), resulting from nuclear division without cytokinesis. In another completely sterile line (#12382), meiosis was normal in 63 cells examined and twelve bivalents were observed at metaphase. In one plant with 43 percent fertility, a chain-of-four was noted in one cell, indicating a chromosomal interchange involving one long segment of one chromosome and a short segment of the other.

In a completely sterile line of Tam Vuot x PI 215936, two univalents were noted at diakinesis and metaphase at a frequency of 4 and 26 percent, respectively. At metaphase, one cell showed four univalents.

In four lines involving an *indica* parent and a U.S. line, chromosome pairing was essentially normal in all of the PMCs with the normal chromosome number. In one plant of the line (CP 231 x SLO-17)/2 x Nahng Mon S-4, 13 bivalents were found in 4 cells from a total of 33. In another plant of the same line, one tetraploid cell was observed at anaphase I, probably as a result of endomitosis. In two other lines, anaphase bridges were noted at a frequency of 2 to 3 percent.

In (CP 231 x HO-12)/2 x BPI-76, the 111 PMCs examined at diakinesis and metaphase all showed normal pairing, although the pollen fertility was only 3.8 percent.

The above findings indicate that hybrid sterility in the F_4 plants was associated in a few pollen mother cells with such gross aberrations as the failure of cytokinesis or chromosomal doubling, in addition to the more prevalent types of meiotic aberrations such as univalent and quadrivalent formation, anaphase bridges, telophase laggards, tetrasomes, and chromosomal interchanges. The low frequency of chromosome aberrations observed compared with the high pollen sterility found in these plants indicates that the structural differences in chromosomes were insufficient to account for all of the sterility observed. It is obvious that other aberrations associated with the meiotic processes, either chromosomal or genic in nature, were operating in the F_4 plants.

Fig. 9. Syncyte formation (multinucleate cells) in line 12339.

Sterility in progenies of crosses involving irradiated dwarf x U.S. variety

Five U.S. lines that are early maturing, short, stiff-strawed, but with noticeable spikelet sterility were obtained from crosses of irradiated dwarf mutants (CP 231 dw) and U.S. varieties of average height (Bbt. 50 and T.P.). Their pollen fertility ranged from 78 to 93 percent; spikelet fertility, from 44 to 60 percent.

Pollen and spikelet fertility were determined at three regions of the panicle: top, middle, and basal. Some variation in pollen fertility was noted in different spikelets of the same panicle. Most of the spikelets which showed extremely low pollen fertility (0-50%) were collected from the basal portion of the panicle. Plants of the CP 231 parent also showed higher sterility on some of the basal panicle branches.

The data on the 1964 wet season material showed lower spikelet fertility (44-60%) than pollen fertility (78-93%). However, pollen and spikelet fertilities were almost the same in the 1965 dry season determinations. In some lines, the spikelet fertility readings of the three portions of the panicle were quite different, as shown in one line of CP 231 x TP: the top portion had 90 percent fertility; the middle portion, 83 percent; and the basal portion, 62 percent.

Spikelet fertility in the 1964 wet season differed from that of the 1965 dry

season. Fertility readings were generally higher in panicles harvested in October, 1964, than those collected in April, 1965. This suggests that spikelet fertility varies under different environmental factors.

Cytological observations showed that at diakinesis and metaphase I, univalents (0.5-2.8%) and quadrivalents (3.6-5.2%) were present in each line. At anaphase I, bridges without fragments were found in two lines at a frequency of 3.4 to 7.1 percent. The bridges seem to be due to the late disjunction of homozygous pairs of the chromosomes. The frequency of univalents and quadrivalents was very low and, therefore, insufficient to account for the high incidence of spikelet sterility in the lines.

The difference between pollen fertility and spikelet fertility may be due to the fact that the dwarf mutant plants had very short culms, and that the panicles were not fully exerted from the flag leaf sheath. It is possible that pollination or ripening of the spikelets was adversely affected by the enveloping leaf sheath.

The difference between pollen fertility and seed fertility may be attributed also to pistil abnormality or low percentage of pollen germination. Studies on pollen germination on artificial medium was undertaken using Yamada's method (1954). It was found, however, that modifications of the artificial medium were necessary since pollen germination was not attained in all the trials.

TABLE 9. Shape, dimensions and density of silica cells in six varieties, 1965 dry season.

Variety	Shape	Mean silica cell dimensions (mm)	Mean area/cell (mm ²)	Average no. silica cells/microscopic field (400x)
1. CP 231 dw x Rex.	rectangular or square	.087 x .044	.0038	101.8
2. Belle Patna	rectangular or ovoid	.100 x .520	.0052	60.0
3. BPI-76	square or ovoid	.063 x .520	.0033	143.3
4. Boegi Inda	rectangular or truncate	.840 x .105	.0882	47.1
5. Peta	rectangular or square	.057 x .390	.0022	67.9
6. MTU-15	rectangular	.070 x .052	.0036	53.4

STUDIES ON LODGING RESISTANCE

Silica cells in culm tissues

The distribution and characteristics of silica cells in culm tissues in six selected varieties were studied in relation to lodging resistance. Among the six, four were lodging-resistant varieties

Fig. 10. (Upper) Silica cells (shown as ovoid and rectangular crystalline structures) in Belle Patna are distributed in the epidermal layer. Twenty-three cells are shown in the section. A nucleus (dark spot) may be seen in some of the cells. The tiny white spots in the lower portion are silica crystals in trichomes. Magnification: x 400.

(Lower) Silica cells in MTU-15 are smaller and fewer (19 cells are shown). Long cells connect the silica cells. A few silicified papillae are also included. Magnification: x 400.

and the other two susceptible. The epidermal strips of the culms were ashed at 400 C, mounted in diaphane, and examined for silica cells. In the transverse sections of the culm, a large number of silica cells were concentrated in the epidermal layers. Only a few silica

cells were found in the sclerenchyma and parenchyma cells. The shape of the silica cells varied from squarish to rectangular, to ovoid. The cells also varied considerably in dimensions and shape (Table 9). A large number of silica cells per microscopic field (400x) was found in the extremely stiff-strawed BPI-76 and CP 231 dwarf x Rexoro. The lowest numbers were noted in the coarse-stemmed Boegi Inda (a bulu variety from Indonesia). Intermediate numbers were found in the stiff-strawed Belle Patna and the relatively weak-strawed, tall Peta (Table 1).

The silica cells were most evenly distributed, uniform in size, and closely spaced in CP 231 dwarf x Rexoro, Belle Patna, and BPI-76. In other relatively weak-strawed varieties the distribution was largely at random and widely spaced (Fig. 10). The lengths of silicified trichomes and papillae on the epidermis were approximately proportional to the culm dimensions. Different nitrogen levels (0 and 120 kg/ha added N) appeared to have little effect on silica cell distribution.

Culm structure in bulu varieties

The coarse-stemmed, bold-grained, and long-awned bulu varieties of Indonesia have been cited frequently by rice workers as desirable sources of lodging resistance. Two bulus, Untung and Rodjolele, considered as promising germ plasm for straw strength, were grown in the wet season at two nitrogen levels (0 and 120 kg/ha added N).

The taller Untung (157-184 cm) lodged prior to heading at both nitrogen levels. Morphological examination showed that its basal elongated internodes were quite long (6.8 cm for BI₁ and 14.4 cm for BI₂) and ovoid in cross section. Most of the plant samples had broken or buckled basal internodes.

The sclerenchyma cells of Untung arranged in 4- to 5-cell layers were thin-walled and loosely packed; lignification was light. The outer vascular bundles were small and largely distributed in the middle portion of the parenchyma

region. They were not fused with the sclerenchyma layer. The inner vascular bundles were asymmetrically arranged and there were about 30 large air spaces (lacunae) in the parenchyma tissues. Silica cells varied in size with a mean dimension of .051 x .054 mm, or .00275 mm² in area. The mean distribution was 45 cells per microscopic field. Silicified trichomes and papillae were observed near the epidermis.

The earlier maturing and shorter Rodjolele (122-150 cm) did not lodge. However, its cL_r values were rather low (.162 for 0-N and .122 for 120-N). The length of the basal internodes in-

The sclerenchyma layer consisted of 5 to 6 thick-walled, compact, and intensely lignified cells. Lignified cells, which seemed to form connections between the inner vascular bundles, were observed in the parenchymatous layer. Inter-cellular air spaces were as numerous as in Untung but were smaller. Silica cells were randomly distributed with mean dimensions of .070 x .087 mm, or a mean area of .00609 mm². The mean distribution was 40 cells per microscopic field. A large number of silica crystals in trichomes and papillae were observed.

The above structural features in the two bulus showed that differences in lodging resistance were essentially associated with the same set of traits described in the reports of previous years. These comparisons and the cL_r readings also indicate that the lodging resistance of bulus is inferior to that of BPI-76, CP 231, CP 231 x SLO-17, the CP 231 dwarf x TP selections, or the CP 231 dwarf x Rexoro selections.

Analysis of plant characters associated with lodging resistance

Investigations with 46 varieties during 1963 to 64 led to the identification of a number of plant characters related to lodging resistance. These were plant height, tiller weight, length of the two basal elongated internodes (BI_1 and BI_2), outer and inner diameters of the two basal elongated internodes, wrapping of leaf sheaths at the lower internodes, culm resistance to buckling and tensile stress, and certain structural features of the culm.

To assess the relative contribution of the above traits to lodging resistance, 10 varieties of different plant types and straw strengths were grown during the dry season and measurements were made on 100 tillers per variety on a number of plant characters. Using the chain method, lodging resistance factor (cL_r) estimates were obtained from the 100 tillers in each variety. The path coefficient analysis method was used to determine the direct and indirect effects of different measurements on the cL_r readings averaged over the 10 varieties. The 10 varieties were BPI-76, CP

Fig. 11. Path diagram and correlation coefficients of 8 factors affecting the lodging resistance factor (cL_r) in 10 varieties in the dry season.

creased with heavy nitrogen application. Rodjolele had thicker culms. The basal internodes were also long, about 6.5 cm for BI_1 and 16.8 cm for BI_2 , but the variety had only 5 elongated internodes compared to 6 in Untung.

The outer vascular bundles of Rodjolele were also small but they were mostly fused with the sclerenchyma layer.

Fig. 12. Internode elongation patterns, culm diameters, and cL_r estimates of 10 varieties, 1965 dry season.

231, Taichung (Native) 1, Chianung 242, MTU-15, Peta, Liuchow, Milfor-6 (2), CP 231 dwarf x Rexoro, and Tangkai Rotan.

The path diagram (Fig. 11) shows that short stature was positively correlated with lodging resistance (high cL_r). The direct contribution of height to cL_r was also one of the greatest and negative in sign. The outer (d_1) and inner (d_2) diameters of the lowermost elongated internode (BI_1) that exceeded 5 cm in length were also among the largest in their direct contributions to the cL_r value. However, the outer diameter had a negative effect on lodging resistance, while the inner diameter showed a positive contribution to cL_r . The correlation coefficients between the cL_r and the two diameters indicated a reversed relationship in each case. The correlation between cL_r and the culm diameters indicated a low degree of association. This pattern of association is rather unusual since a thicker culm is generally associated with greater culm strength. However, the pooled data involved Taichung (Native) 1 and CP 231 dwarf x Rexoro, which have a number of short but thick basal internodes often shorter than 5 cm and three to four much longer and thinner internodes immediately above them. Because of these features, the culm diameters of BI_1 and BI_2 were taken on the thinner internodes above the thickened plant base (Fig. 12). Therefore, the relationship between cL_r and culm diameters was obscured when averaged over a number of

diverse plant types.

The length of the two basal elongated internodes showed a relatively small but negative contribution to the lodging resistance factor. The correlation coefficients were also negative in sign. These values agreed with the previous findings.

Snap score and tiller weight both contributed to the cL_r estimates; the snap score was positively correlated and tiller weight negatively correlated with cL_r . Since tiller weight was incorporated into the cL_r readings on theoretical considerations, its direct effect on cL_r would be relatively small. Snap score is related to the breaking strength of the culms and is, therefore, largely independent of the cL_r on theoretical grounds.

Among the 7 traits measured, the outer and inner diameters showed a high positive correlation ($r = .9498$); as did the outer diameter and length of BI_1 ($r = .5457$); the inner diameter and length of BI_1 ($r = .6696$); tiller weight and outer diameter ($r = .8320$); tiller weight and inner diameter ($r = .7225$); plant height and tiller weight ($r = .5069$); the lengths of BI_1 and BI_2 ($r = .5855$).

Path coefficient analyses were also made for the individual varieties. The analyses indicated that in a tall variety such as Peta variation in height among plants was the major component affecting cL_r . The next important variable was the outer diameter of the BI_1 , followed by the lengths of the BI_2 and BI_1 , in that order. In a stiff-strawed but relatively tall variety such as BPI-76, plant height was again the major component in affecting cL_r , followed by tiller weight, the outer diameter, the snap score, and the lengths of BI_1 and BI_2 . In the short-statured CP 231 dwarf x Rexoro, the major components influencing cL_r were the snap score and the length of BI_2 .

The above analyses generally support the preliminary findings in previous seasons that plant height and the physical features of the culm associated with strength are the major factors in determining varietal resistance to lodging.

Plant Pathology

Varietal resistance offers the most promising means of controlling rice diseases, particularly in the tropics. Consequently, effort was directed toward developing and improving techniques for screening varieties, standardizing resistance evaluation procedures, and understanding more thoroughly the inheritance of resistance. The physiology of causal organisms and their possible relation to the mechanism of resistance were studied further.

Three new techniques for testing varietal resistance have been developed successfully. They are the "cut stem" method for stem rot, the "flag leaf inoculation" technique for bacterial leaf blight, and the "mass screening" method for tungro disease. Using these and other techniques, a large number of varieties were tested for resistance to the major diseases of rice. About 600 varieties and hybrid lines were tested for resistance to stem rot, 6,000 for resistance to bacterial leaf blight, and 1,600 for resistance to tungro disease, in addition to 6,000 tested in the blast nursery for resistance to the rice blast disease.

The investigations on blast resistance included cooperation with other research stations in the Philippines and in other countries, thus allowing resistance to be tested against a range of physiologic races of the fungus and the selection of varieties with a wide spectrum of resistance. Extensive studies on the inheritance of blast resistance indicated that, in most cases, it is simply inherited. Studies on the inheritance of resistance to bacterial leaf blight and tungro disease were also initiated.

As a result of cooperative projects with research stations in other countries, it is now becoming clear that virus diseases are important throughout southeast Asia. The "penyakit merah" disease of Malaysia, for example, formerly ascribed to physiologic causes, was shown during the year to be caused by a virus. The tungro virus was found to be "nonpersistent" in the body of its insect vector.

Another series of projects was concerned with the chemical constitution of the rice plant and its relationship to diseases, the utilization of carbon and nitrogen compounds by the causal organisms of stem rot and bacterial leaf blight, and with the host ranges of these pathogens.

RICE BLAST

Varietal resistance

About 4,500 hybrid lines from the Institute's breeding program have been tested for resistance in the blast nursery. The 700 resistant varieties selected from previous tests were tested again at three different times this year to expose them to the various races of fungus as they occur at Los Baños in different seasons. Although previously found to be resistant, some proved in these tests to be susceptible. About 400 varieties were still identified as highly resistant while others were found to have a degree of resistance somewhat below that previously recorded. Tests were also made on 120 varieties from the USDA blast nurseries.

In cooperation with six stations in the Philippines (five Bureau of Plant Industry regional stations and the Central Mindanao University) the set of 258 varieties used in the International Uniform Blast Nurseries and the 400 varieties previously identified as resistant were tested.

Of the varieties from the International Uniform Blast Nurseries tested in 1964 and 1965 the following were found resistant at all testing stations in the Philippines:

CI 5309	KPF 6
CP 231 x HO 12	Pah-Leuad 111
Dular	Pah-Leuad 29-8-11
D 25-4	Ram Tulasi (Sel)
Kam Bau Ngan	Tadukan
Kanto 51	Taichung 181
Kanto 53	Tetep
Kataktara DA 2	Yakeiko

For the International Uniform Blast Nurseries program, 50 sets of seed samples, each including 258 varieties, were distributed to 20 cooperating countries. Results of the 1964 tests have been received from most of these countries. General observations on these results were as follows:

(1) No variety was resistant at all localities or to all races; many varieties, however, possessed a wide spectrum of resistance which would be valuable in breeding programs; other varieties were resistant at some localities but

susceptible in the remainder; certain varieties were susceptible in all localities or to all races; resistant varieties were found in each of the testing localities and to each race of the organism.

(2) Some regional patterns in reaction were noticed. For example, a variety resistant or susceptible at one place in the temperate region tended to show a similar reaction to the other temperate zone sites. Similar regional trends were noted in the tropics.

(3) There were obvious differences in reaction between the temperate countries and the tropics. Many varieties displayed opposite reactions in the two zones, indicating differences in physiological races.

Inheritance of blast resistance

To obtain more comprehensive information on the mode of inheritance of blast resistance, 106 crosses were made of 25 combinations among 7 resistant and 9 susceptible varieties; 13 different fungus isolates (races) were used for inoculation. Twenty-four backcrosses from 4 resistant and 7 susceptible parents were also tested with 2 isolates. There were three groups: In Group 1, a large number (12) of fungus isolates (races) were used to inoculate each of the cross-combinations; Group 2 consisted of all possible combinations of 3 resistant and 4 susceptible parents and 3 isolates; in Group 3, only 1 resistant parent was combined with 4 susceptible ones and 3 isolates were inoculated.

Resistance or susceptibility was tested at the seedling stage of 4 to 5 leaves. All artificial inoculations followed a standard procedure which took account of soil fertility, age of plants, concentration of spore suspension, temperature of inoculation chamber, etc. Each inoculation test included both resistant and susceptible parents. Resistance and susceptibility were measured by four scales: resistant (scale 1, inconspicuous minute brown specks or none), moderately resistant (scale 2, conspicuous brown specks), moderately susceptible (scale 3, small brown lesion with round-

ish necrotic spots), and susceptible (scale 4, typical large blast lesions). In calculating genetic ratio, scales 1 and 2 were considered resistant, and 3 and 4, as susceptible.

Reaction of F_1 plants. F_1 plants (population varied 5-30) showed resistant reaction irrespective of the cross combinations or isolate used. Only in few cases, when the resistant parents were not highly resistant (scale 2), did the F_1 population show some moderately susceptible or susceptible reaction.

It seems evident that blast resistance is a dominant character.

Fig. 1. Segregation of resistant and susceptible plants in F_2 population; three typical cases.

Reaction of F_2 plants. Each test was made on a population of about 200 to 300 seedlings. The reaction within each F_2 population varied from completely resistant (scale 1), moderately resistant (scale 2), moderately susceptible (scale 3), to completely susceptible (scale 4). The percentage of intermediate reactions (scales 2 and 3) were, however, always smaller (Fig. 1).

The simple genetic ratios (1 and 2 pairs of genes) of the resistant (scales 1 and 2) and susceptible (scales 3 and

4) populations of the 106 tests are summarized in Table 1.

Analysis of the results based upon particular parental varieties (resistant or susceptible) or isolates did not correlate with any particular ratio. The ratios of 15:1, 13:3, and 3:1 were obtained from a single combination when tested separately with different isolates. Even with the same combination and the same isolate, two kinds of ratios were obtained.

TABLE 1. Genetic ratios (R:S) of F_2 population of the 106 crosses.

	15:1	13:3	3:1	9:7
Group 1 materials	4	8	15	—
Group 2 materials	7	—	38	9
Group 3 materials	—	7	18	—
Total	11	15	71	9

In certain cases when the resistant varieties were used as female parents, more resistant individuals were found in the F_2 populations. For instance:

Taichung (Native) 1 x

Ta-poo-cho 2 ----- 3:1

(Native) 1 ----- 13:3

Intan x (CP 231 x HO 12) ---- 3:1

(CP 231 x HO 12) x Intan ---- 13:3

Other reciprocal crosses did not show such differences.

Reaction of backcrosses. The resistant individuals of F_1 and those from backcrosses were further backcrossed to susceptible parents. The population of each of these backcrosses for test varied from 7 to 27 in Group 2 and 23 to 102 in Group 3. All the 24 backcrosses, which involved 4 resistant and 7 susceptible varieties, tested with 3 isolates, showed a 1:1 ratio.

The above data show that in most cases a single pair of dominant genes controls resistance to blast. The reasons for the presence of intermediate reactions (scales 2 and 3) are not known. It may be due to the incomplete expression of gene characters, to the effect of environmental conditions or to interactions with other microorganisms, particularly bacteria (see epiphyllic bacteria, below) present on the leaf surface. A shift of reaction from scale 2 to 3, or vice versa, caused by slight differences

TABLE 2. Reactions of the suggested international differential varieties to isolates of *Piricularia oryzae* from the Philippines.

Variety	Race Group										
	IA-1	IA-2	IA-3	IB-1	IB-2	IC-1	ID-1	ID-2	ID-3	ID-4	ID-5
Raminad Str. 3 (PI 231128)	S	S	S	R	R	R	R	R	R	R	R
Zenith (CI 7787)	S	R	R	S	S	R	R	R	R	R	R
NP 125 (PI 201902)	R	R	R	R	R	S	R	R	R	R	R
Usen	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S
Dular (PI 180061)	R	R	R	R	R	S	R	R	R	R	R
Kanto 51	R	R	R	R	R	R	S	R	R	R	R
CI 8970-S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	R	R
Caloro (CI 1561-1)	S	S	R	S	R	S	S	S	R	S	R
No. of isolates (Total, 100)	3	50	4	5	2	1	2	16	11	3	3

in these biological and physical environmental conditions, may have resulted in the segregation ratios other than 3:1. The possibility of 2 pairs of genes, as indicated by 15:1, 13:3, and 9:7 segregation ratios, was not supported by the tests on the backcrosses so far made. While further detailed studies on the inheritance have to be made, the above data give reason to believe that breeding for blast resistance may be relatively rapid and less complex than generally supposed.

Physiological races

During the meeting of the US-Japan cooperative project held in Tokyo, October 1965, on the study of physiologic races of *P. oryzae*, eight differential varieties were suggested for international use to differentiate race groups. According to these differentials, the 100 Philippine isolates tested may be separated into 11 race groups, as in Table 2. Additional varieties from each country are to be used for further differentiation of races. An official report of the meeting will be published.

Longevity and stability of *P. oryzae* cultures

One of the problems in studying the blast fungus is the maintenance of stock cultures. The fungus, like others, is apt to change after frequent transfers. To reduce the variability to a minimum, cultures were stored at low temperature to avoid frequent transfers. Six isolates in PDA tube slants were kept in a deep freezer at about -30 C and transfers

were made each month. The observations commenced in June, 1964, and one of the six isolates lost its viability 10 months later. The other five were still growing well after 16 months. Testing is continuing.

Meanwhile, the stability of cultural characters and pathogenicity of two isolates, I-42 and I-129, are being studied. Isolate I-42 is considered a variable culture and I-129 a stable one. Four conidial generations, 50 conidia from each monoconidial culture in each generation, were studied. Segregation in color of colony, dark and light, was readily observed in I-42 in each generation. No change in color and other cultural characters were noticed in I-129 among the 500 tubes. Changes in pathogenicity are being studied.

Free amino-acid contents of rice leaves

Early experiments showed that isolates (races) of *P. oryzae* differ strikingly in their utilization of amino acids *in vitro*. Some isolates utilized certain amino acids well while others could not use them. Some utilized many kinds of amino acids, others only a few. Leaves were analyzed to discover whether this difference in ability to utilize amino acids had any correlation with the amino acids contained in rice varieties resistant or susceptible to specific physiologic races. Leaves of three rice varieties, (1) Kataktara DA 2, resistant to all known races in the Philippines, (2) Khao Tah Haeng 17, susceptible to all races, and (3) Peta, resistant to some races but susceptible to others, were ob-

TABLE 3. Major amino acids and related compounds in rice leaves resistant or susceptible to *P. oryzae* at seedling stage grown at high and low levels of NH_4NO_3 nitrogen (μg fresh weight).

	Nitrogen level					
	20 ppm			120 ppm		
	Kataktara DA 2 (R)	Peta (R & S)	Khao Tah Haeng 17 (S)	Kataktara DA 2 (R)	Peta (R & S)	Khao Tah Haeng 17 (S)
Urea	9.9	67.5	70.2	27.3	98.4	35.7
Hydroxyproline	32.9	56.5	155.0	58.4	33.4	59.0
Aspartic acid	464.3	300.7	373.3	336.5	593.2	537.5
Threonine	59.4	49.1	61.5	272.4	96.8	74.8
Serine	137.7	265.1	272.7	158.0	250.4	271.3
Asparagine	86.4	144.3	110.3	159.6	424.4	239.4
Proline	28.8	30.2	19.9	22.5	17.8	23.9
Glutamic acid	489.4	1,076.7	930.6	484.6	1,376.3	1,217.8
Glycine	36.9	57.1	69.2	32.0	53.3	53.5
Alanine	148.7	309.5	259.4	271.2	312.5	288.9
Valine	18.5	32.8	24.5	25.3	24.1	20.5
Cystathionine	1.3	5.8	58.2	6.7	20.0	22.9
Methionine	14.5	18.1	22.4	25.4	22.5	25.2
Isoleucine	550.3	629.6	988.2	560.0	788.1	621.1
Leucine	7.0	21.8	20.2	21.6	12.2	18.5
Tyrosine	7.2	14.0	10.3	9.2	11.2	7.6
Phenylalanine	14.4	20.8	11.9	12.4	8.4	9.1
Gamma-aminobutyric acid	5.8	19.7	15.3	13.3	25.7	10.0
Ethanolamine	8.9	23.2	19.8	19.6	26.2	21.2
Ammonia	7.9	21.0	25.0	15.2	23.6	17.8
Lysine	10.1	11.0	8.9	6.4	5.8	1.6
Total	2,140.3	3,174.5	3,526.8	2,537.6	4,224.3	3,577.3

tained from plants grown in water culture with high and low nitrogen levels, and were analyzed for amino acid content. Water-soluble alcohol extraction was used to obtain the amino acid acids which were then analyzed by the Beckman-Spinco amino acid analyzer Mod. 120. The results are shown in Table 3.

The data show that the kinds of amino acid and their relative quantities in the leaves of resistant varieties were similar to those of susceptible ones. The absolute quantities were, however, higher in susceptible than in resistant varieties, and they increased at higher levels of nitrogen in the culture solution. It seems, therefore, that specific amino acids required by particular isolates of the organism cannot account directly for their specific pathogenicity to rice varieties.

Epiphylllic bacteria on rice leaves

When rice leaves were inoculated with a spore suspension of *P. oryzae*, hundreds of spores were lodged on each leaf. Often, however, only a few lesions of blast developed and as a result the

Fig. 2. Effect of epiphylllic bacteria of rice leaves on growth of *Piricularia oryzae* in culture.

reading reactions were sometimes uncertain. Epiphyllic bacteria on the rice leaves were isolated from old and young leaves from the greenhouse and field to study their effect on infection by blast fungus.

Preliminary results showed that there were 20 to as many as 6,600 bacterial cells on each cm² of rice leaves. Older leaves carried more bacteria than young

ones. Many types of colonies were isolated, most of which demonstrated various degrees of antibiotic effects against *P. oryzae* in culture (Fig. 2). The filtrates of these cultures inhibited and/or retarded the elongation of germ tubes of *P. oryzae* spores. Complete inhibition was observed in undiluted filtrate and was still noticeable in 1:100 dilution.

STEM ROT

Mode of infection

Stem rot is a common disease in the tropics, present in almost every rice field. To obtain more information on the extent of damage caused by the disease, further observations and experiments were made on the mode of infection by the two causal organisms, *Helminthosporium sigmoideum* (*Leptospheria salvinii*) and *H. sigmoideum* var. *irregulare*, one or the other or both of which are universally present in rice fields. In spite of the pressure of the organisms, however, infection on the stem was rarely observed up to time of maturity. Blackish lesions were often found on the leaf sheaths near the water line and infection cushions of the *H. sigmoideum* sometimes found on the lower internodes. In neither case, however, were the stems seriously affected, although after harvest sclerotia of the organisms (Fig. 3) were found in most of the stubble.

In artificial inoculation experiments, neither organism was able to infect unwounded internodes or even the leaf sheath when small pieces of fungous culture on PDA were used as inoculum. However, if the internodes were wounded, both organisms grew rapidly; the entire internode often became rotten, and numerous sclerotia formed within 10 days. Infection of the leaf sheath sometimes occurred through the growth cracks at the thin margin of the leaf sheath. The organisms also grew in dead stems and other tissues. These observations and experiments suggest that the fungi are aggressive wound parasites.

In other artificial inoculation experiments, infections on the unwounded

Fig. 3. Sclerotia of *Helminthosporium sigmoideum* (A) and *H. sigmoideum* var. *irregulare* (B).

stems occurred, at least in certain susceptible varieties, when the green leaf sheaths were wounded and inoculated. The organism grew in the leaf sheath and further infected the unwounded stems underneath. With *H. sigmoideum*, infection cushions were formed on the stem surface (Fig. 4, B) before penetration, but with *H. sigmoideum* var. *irregulare* only appressoria were formed. When the dying or dead leaf sheaths were similarly inoculated, however, no infection occurred on the stem, 10 days after inoculation, even though the organisms grew profusely on the dead leaf sheaths. The growth in the green leaf sheaths seems to support the infection of the stems particularly for *H. sigmoideum*. The exact reason is not yet known. When large pieces of mycelial mat from liquid cultures were used as

Fig. 4. Appressoria of stem rot organism formed on rice culm in field (A), and infection cushion of *H. sigmoideum* (B).

inoculum, infections on unwounded stems also occurred. The large quantity of inoculum and the presence of leaf sheath seem to effect the infection on unwounded stems. Further studies are under way.

From these observations and experiments, it seems that the organisms are common but cause no great damage before harvest. However, damage could be severe if numerous wounds are inflicted through lodging, insect injury, or other causes.

Methods of artificial inoculation

A quick method has been developed to test varietal resistance to the disease. Ten elongated lower internodes, with nodes at each end, were cut from each variety at the time of flowering. The leaf sheaths were removed and the internodes wounded by needle punctures.

A small piece of the fungous culture on agar medium was placed on the wounds and held in position by scotch tape. The entire cut stems were covered by a plastic bag, placed over a pan of shallow water to keep high humidity, and held in a plant growth chamber at 28 C. Readings were made 10 days after inoculation. In resistant varieties small lesions (discolorations) appeared around the wounds, whereas in susceptible varieties the entire internodes rotted and

Fig. 5. Comparison of lesions of stem rot developed on cut stems (right) and standing stems (left) of three varieties.

Standard for measuring resistance

The results of inoculation showed a wide range of resistance among varieties: on flag leaves, from immunity to death of the leaf blade and leaf sheath; and on seedlings, from immunity to death of the entire seedling. The standard scales for classifying degree of resistance suggested earlier did not adequately separate the various degrees. It is obvious that one scale is inadequate to cover the ranges of reaction in both flag leaf and seedling.

A new standard of scales is proposed in which the scales for one growth stage correspond to an appropriate reaction

of the other stage. For instance, a reaction of scale 1 on flag leaves indicates restricted lesions, and the same scale applied to the seedling stage also indicates a restricted lesion. In severely affected plants, a reaction of scale 9, indicating the destruction of the leaf blade and leaf sheath by the organism, corresponds to a seedling scale 9 in which many seedlings are killed. The same scale of reaction corresponds to more severe symptoms in the seedling stage, in which plants are killed, and in this sense, seedlings are more susceptible than the maturing plants. The scale readings are described in detail as follows:

**Standard of Scales for Indicating Degree
of Resistance to Bacterial Leaf Blight**

<i>Scale</i>	<i>Seedling Stage</i>	<i>(Flowering Stage (Flag Leaf))</i>
0	No lesion observable (immune)	Same
1	Lesions restricted to 1-2 mm around the points of inoculation.	Same
2	Lesions more or less elliptical not more than 2-3 cm long.	Same
3	Lesions elongated, extend to about 1/2 length of leaf blade or less.	Lesions elongated, less than 1/4 of leaf length.
4	Lesions extend to and destroy 3/4 of leaf blade.	Lesions broad and coalesce, the upper portion of the leaves often dead, lesions extend to about 1/4 of the lower half of leaf surface below the points of inoculation.
5	Lesions extend to and destroy the entire leaf blade.	Lesions coalesce and upper portion of leaves dead, lesions extend to about 1/2 of the lower half of leaf surface.
6	Lesions extend to and destroy the entire leaf blade and less than 1/2 of leaf sheath.	Lesions extend to about 3/4 of the lower half of the leaf blade.
7	Entire leaf blade and more than 1/2 leaf sheath destroyed and a few pale yellow symptoms appear.	Lesions extend to the base and destroy the entire leaf blade.
8	Leaf blade and leaf sheath destroyed, many pale yellow plants, and less than 25 seedlings completely killed (kresek).	Lesions destroy the entire leaf blade and extend to about 1/2 of leaf sheath.
9	About 50% or more seedlings entirely killed (kresek).	Lesions completely destroy the leaf blade and sheath.

Fig. 6. Inoculation pads and bacterial suspension for bacterial leaf blight inoculation in the field.

rows; the other is a cushion of cotton and cheese cloth soaked with the bacterial suspension (Fig. 6). The pads were held on the thumb and middle finger of one hand. The flag leaves were punctured midway between base and tip, 20 flag leaves being inoculated for each variety. Statistical analysis of tests made on 109 varieties showed that readings from 10 leaves of each variety were sufficient to give reliable data.

Resistant varieties were confirmed by inoculation at the seedling stage. Two needle punctures were made at the middle of each of three expanded leaves when the seedlings were at the 4- to 5-leaf stage.

Expansion of lesions

The rate of expansion of resistant, moderate and susceptible types of lesions was studied to determine a suitable date to read reactions on flag leaves. One hundred and nine varieties of the three groups were inoculated and

lesions measured at 14, 20, and 30 days after inoculation. The results were analyzed statistically. It was found that in the moderate and susceptible groups, the rate of expansion within each group was similar. Within the resistant group, however, lesions on some varieties expanded faster after 20 days than on others and the differences were statistically significant. Reading at 30 days after inoculation may, therefore, be preferred. Because of other factors, however, such as the early senescence of leaves in certain varieties, readings were made 20 days after inoculation and the resistant varieties were confirmed by further tests.

In the seedling stage the 'kresek' symptom was observed on susceptible varieties at 20 days, but there were more plants showing the symptom after 30 days. Therefore, the method adapted for preliminary screening was to make initial readings 20 days after inoculation and to make more detailed studies after 30 days.

Standard for measuring resistance

The results of inoculation showed a wide range of resistance among varieties: on flag leaves, from immunity to death of the leaf blade and leaf sheath; and on seedlings, from immunity to death of the entire seedling. The standard scales for classifying degree of resistance suggested earlier did not adequately separate the various degrees. It is obvious that one scale is inadequate to cover the ranges of reaction in both flag leaf and seedling.

A new standard of scales is proposed in which the scales for one growth stage correspond to an appropriate reaction

of the other stage. For instance, a reaction of scale 1 on flag leaves indicates restricted lesions, and the same scale applied to the seedling stage also indicates a restricted lesion. In severely affected plants, a reaction of scale 9, indicating the destruction of the leaf blade and leaf sheath by the organism, corresponds to a seedling scale 9 in which many seedlings are killed. The same scale of reaction corresponds to more severe symptoms in the seedling stage, in which plants are killed, and in this sense, seedlings are more susceptible than the maturing plants. The scale readings are described in detail as follows:

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4	Lesions extend to and destroy 3/4 of leaf blade.	Lesions broad and coalesce, the upper portion of the leaves often dead, lesions extend to about 1/4 of the lower half of leaf surface below the points of inoculation.
5	Lesions extend to and destroy the entire leaf blade.	Lesions coalesce and upper portion of leaves dead, lesions extend to about 1/2 of the lower half of leaf surface.
6	Lesions extend to and destroy the entire leaf blade and less than 1/2 of leaf sheath.	Lesions extend to about 3/4 of the lower half of the leaf blade.
7	Entire leaf blade and more than 1/2 leaf sheath destroyed and a few pale yellow symptoms appear.	Lesions extend to the base and destroy the entire leaf blade.
8	Leaf blade and leaf sheath destroyed, many pale yellow plants, and less than 25 seedlings completely killed (kresek).	Lesions destroy the entire leaf blade and extend to about 1/2 of leaf sheath.
9	About 50% or more seedlings entirely killed (kresek).	Lesions completely destroy the leaf blade and sheath.

Scale 1, 2, and 3 may be considered as resistant; 4, 5, and 6, intermediate; and 7, 8, and 9, susceptible.

Correlation of resistance between seedling and flowering stages

To investigate whether reaction to bacterial leaf blight would be different at the seedling stage from that at the flowering stage, data were compiled from 98 resistant, moderate and susceptible varieties which had been inoculated with the same isolate of the bacterium at both stages. The results (Fig. 7) showed a positive correlation with the "r" value at 0.8495. None of the 98 varieties showed striking differences at the two stages. Reaction at either stage appears to indicate the resistance of a variety. The absence of a close positive correlation with some varieties in the resistant group may have been related to the time of reading as discussed earlier. In the data presented, readings were made 20 days after inoculation.

Fig. 7. Resistance to bacterial leaf blight; correlation between seedling and flowering stages.

Varietal resistance

About 700 blast resistant varieties were tested for bacterial leaf blight resistance in the dry season at the flowering stage using the flag leaf method. Many were found resistant and were further tested at the seedling stage. About 2,500 varieties from the world collection were inoculated during the

TABLE 4. Summary of the reaction of varieties from the world collection to the bacterial leaf blight organism (isolate B 72) in the flowering stage (flag leaf).

Reactions	No. of varieties	Percentage
0	121	3.70
1 } Resistant	327	9.99
2	435	13.28
3	1,177	35.94
4 } Intermediate	377	11.51
5	283	8.64
6	83	2.53
7 } Susceptible	46	1.40
8	404	12.34
9	22	0.67
	3,275	100.00

rainy season. One of the most virulent strains, B 72, was used as an inoculum. Table 4 gives the summarized results. A partial list of resistant varieties is given below:

1. Varieties resistant to bacterial leaf blight tested at both the seedling and the flowering stages (these are also resistant to blast in the Philippines).

Athikraya Ptb 9	M 302
Adt 25	Remadja
Ca 902/b/2/1	Secano do Brazil
D 44-1	221b/57/1/4
E. L. Gopher	Sigadis
Hsinchu 56	Sonocalif
PI 209938	Tainan 1
Zenith	Tainan 9
Khao Tah Oo	Tainan iku 512
Kwangfu 1	Tainan iku 516
Lantjang	Takao No. 21
Mean-don-tsi	

2. Varieties tested at flowering stage only.

Agulha E.S.A. (IRGA)	Lalka
Bony	Puebla Larga
Casca Branco 3-1-P	Reis (Lonisiana)
Chu-Kame	Subhubalawee
Dourado Liso No. 2	Taichung 65
DV 32	Taichung 186
DV 85	T 5
DV 86	Vary Lava 16
DV 139	Wa Chan
Goiano	Zenith (E.U.) nova
Kirikunda	

TABLE 5. Effect of nitrogen sources on the growth of five isolates of *Xanthomonas oryzae* (growth as optical density at 620 m μ at fifth day).^a

Nitrogen Compound (800 ppm)	Isolate				
	B2	B72	B69	B10	B46
DL-isoleucine	0.0066	0.0066	0	0	0
L-leucine	0.0079	0.0555	0.1770	0.0292	0.0088
DL-serine	0	0.0066	0	0	0
L-phenylalanine	0	0.0830	0.0066	0.0066	0.0132
DL-tryptophan	0	0.0141	0	0	0
L-cystine	0	0	0	0	0
DL-methionine	0	0	0	0	0
L-aspartic acid	0.2007	0.9318	0.2924	0.8962	0.9208
L-asparagine	0	0.0110	0	0	0
L-glutamic acid	0.0410	1.3010	0.6440	0.3279	0.1337
L(+)-histidine . HCl . H ₂ O	0	0.0223	0.0223	0	0
DL-lysine HCl	0	0.1550	0.0074	0	0
Casamino acids	0.0580	1.9210	0.4609	1.0220	0.0706
Control	0	0	0	0	0

^a No growth in DL-alanine, glycine, L-threonine, DL-valine, L-proline, L-hydroxyproline, L-glutamine, L-arginine, Gamma-amino n butyric acid, L-ornithine Hcl, urea, KNO₃, NH₄NO₃, (NH₄)₂SO₄ and (NH₄)₂HPO₄.

Nitrogen nutrition in vitro

In studying the mechanism of disease resistance, the effect of various nitrogen sources on the growth of the organism was tested. Twenty-nine nitrogen sources were used separately and in some combinations to study the utilization of nitrogen by five strains of the organism in a synthetic medium. Growth was measured by optical density at 620 m μ on the fifth day of growth. The results (Table 5) show that the organism grew best in gluta-

mic acid, and aspartic acid, but there was some growth in DL-lysine HCl. Little or no growth was observed in many other nitrogen sources. Other workers have reported that sulfur-containing amino acids are essential for growth of the bacterium.

Although no growth was obtained with L-cystine and DL-methionine at 800 ppm, a separate test showed that the organism could use these amino acids slightly where they were in low concentrations (< 100 ppm).

VIRUS DISEASES

Testing for tungro resistance

As it has been difficult to test varietal resistance to the tungro disease under field conditions, studies using artificial inoculation were intensified. Previously, a cage method was used in which viruliferous insects were confined in a small Mylar cage enclosing seven seedlings. Duplicate tests were made for each variety. The insects were killed after inoculation feeding. This year, to improve the efficiency of the technique, the insects were used repeatedly. To increase accuracy, the number of test seedlings was increased. By rearing a large population of insects a meth-

od for mass-screening varieties was developed.

Using this method it was possible to inoculate 16 varieties, replicated twice, involving 928 seedlings, each day. Key features of this method are as follows:

(1) An efficient insect rearing procedure from which a new batch of adult insects is available every two days. As the insects require approximately 26 days to reach maturity, some 13 cages are used to confine the insects at various stages of development.

(2) Diseased plants for insect acquisition feeding must be available at all times. Daily re-acquisition feeding is necessary to insure that the insects re-

main infective because the virus is non-persistent, as will be discussed later.

(3) Seedlings to be tested are germinated in Petri dishes and transplanted to pots (29 per pot) and at 2- to 3-leaf stage (11-13 days old) are subjected to inoculation.

(4) Each inoculation cage, measuring 20 x 20 x 20 inches hold 16 pots, and therefore, about 460 seedlings, and to inoculate this number of plants about 1,000 viruliferous insects are confined. These seedlings are exposed to the insects for about 8 hours.

(5) Integration of all operations to permit a steady flow of testing.

To evaluate the accuracy of the "mass screening" method, 150 entries of IR 9-60, a selection susceptible to tungro disease, were used to test the reproducibility of results obtained by the method. Analysis showed that in terms of percentage seedlings infected, the variation was from 84.5 to 100% with an average value of 97.2% (standard deviation, 2.94; coefficient of variation, 3.03%). Differences within entries were not statistically significant. The

differences between two replicates of a single entry varied from 0 to 17.9%, average 3.6%. The differences of average percentage of infected seedlings between two cages of the same date were 0.6 to 4.1%. Only the extreme value reached significant level (LSD 5% = 4.07). The means of percentages of infected seedlings from each date were 95.4, 96.0, 96.2, 96.8, 96.9, 97.5, 97.7, 98.1, and 99.1% with LSD values of 2.18 and 2.89 for 5 and 1% levels respectively, indicating that differences between dates were, in some cases, statistically significant. Therefore, additional replications are needed only if a more precise figure of percentage of infected seedlings is required.

A total of 1,645 varieties, lines, or entries were tested from April to November by the "mass screening" technique.

Classifying tungro resistance

Of rice varieties so far tested by the "mass screening" technique, percentages of infection have varied from less than 10 to 100%. The percentage of infection therefore has been used directly

Fig. 8. Degree of severity of rice varieties affected by the tungro disease. From left to right, the rating scales are S3, S2, S1, and S0-1 for each pair of pots. Seedlings tied with white strings are healthy.

to indicate the degree of susceptibility to the tungro disease. Varieties with less than 30% are generally considered as resistant; those with more than 60%, susceptible, and others, intermediate. The varieties in the resistant group, such as Peta and Tjeremas, would usually have only a few plants infected in field plantings.

Varieties vary also in tolerance to the disease after infection as shown by their subsequent growth (Fig. 8). Infected plants of some varieties, such as Taichung (Native) 1, continued to show discoloration and retardation of growth, resulting in severely stunted plants, while in others, such as BPI-76 and TKM 6, the discoloration gradually disappeared and normal growth was more or less resumed, resulting in only slight stunting. The tolerant varieties would usually suffer only slight damage in field planting. Between the two extremes there are gradations. This tolerance to or severity of disease has to be considered in classifying the reaction of varieties. The degrees of severity are tentatively classified into four rating scales of increasing severity as follows: S0, S1, S2, and S3. For intermediates between adjacent categories S0-1, S1-2, and S2-3 are used (Fig. 8).

Varietal resistance to tungro

Seed board varieties. Philippine Seed Board Varieties were tested three times

221/BCIIIA/81/2/1	Fadjar	Pekahok-Kimkan
221b/57/1/4	FB 24	Peta
221b/212/2/2/2/1	Gam Pai 30-12-15	PI 184675-2
221b/236/2/3/2/1	Indrasail	PI 184676
221c/53/1/3/1	JC-170	Red Rice
221c/391/1/3/3	Ladang	Salak 2885
221e/20/3	Lantjang	Seri-Raja
Andi from N. Pokhara	Latisail	Tjahaja
Badshabhog T 412	Latisail (T. Aman)	Tjeremas
Bengawan	Pankhari 203	TP x Rexoro-SB
DV 29		

Nonpersistence of tungro virus in its vector

The infectivity of a vector can be tested by exposing healthy seedlings of a susceptible variety to individual insects for a certain period of time. If the

by the "mass screening" technique. The average percentages of infected seedlings were Peta, 9.8; Tjeremas, 13.1; Bengawan, 18.5; BE-3, 68.8; Dinalaga, 77.5; FB-121, 77.6; Azucena, 80.0; Raminad Str. 3, 80.5; BPI-76, 86.3; Palawan, 87.0; and Mangarez, 91.6%. Peta, Tjeremas, and Bengawan are classified in the resistant group.

IR lines. A total of 305 hybrid lines from the Institute have been tested. The results showed that 254 lines, 82.6% of the total, may be considered susceptible to the tungro disease since their percentages of infected seedlings were over 60%, and 181 lines showed a degree of severity higher than the scale unit S1. Other lines were moderately susceptible or intermediate.

The results also indicated that more resistant lines were found from crosses involving resistant parents, and that it may be possible to obtain a tungro resistant variety of desirable plant type through breeding. Studies on the mode of inheritance of tungro resistance are being initiated.

Other rice varieties. The screening of rice varieties for tungro resistance was primarily aimed at identifying those with high resistance for breeding materials. A total of 690 varieties have been tested. More than 80% of them had over 60% infected seedlings. However, the following varieties, with a percentage of infected seedlings less than 30%, are considered to be resistant:

exposed seedlings become infected, the insects were infective during the period when the seedlings were exposed. To study the infectivity of the vector of tungro virus, a test tube method was developed. Single seedlings were inserted in test tubes containing moist soil and

single insects were confined. The tubes were covered by a perforated cap which could be removed easily. Transference of insect was effected by an aspirator at any time desired; transference of seedlings, by adding more water to the tube. This method has been found convenient for this and similar studies.

Loss of infectivity. Insects acquire the tungro virus from diseased plants and become infective. But they remain infective for only a short period. As shown in Table 6, only one insect retained the infectivity for 5 days after the termination of an acquisition feeding period, and this was the longest period recorded of virus retention in the insects. A few insects retained their infectivity for 4 days but more than 50% of the infective insects lost their infectivity 24 hours after acquisition feeding (Table 6). A similar loss of infectivity has also been observed following re-acquisition feeding on diseased plants. Once the insects lost the infectivity, they remained non-infective until death unless given access to another virus source.

TABLE 6. Daily infectivity of *N. impicticeps* after acquisition feeding on tungro diseased plants.

No. daily serial transfers after acquisition feeding	No. infective insects/no. survivors tested	Percentage of infective insects
1	243/521	46.6
2	107/501	21.4
3	34/485	7.0
4	9/464	1.9
5	1/430	0.2
6 ^a	0/399	0

^a None remained infective thereafter although test was continued until death of insects (insects remained alive for a maximum of 51 days).

The percentage of insects losing infectivity were 56.0, 86.0, 96.3, 99.6, and 100% on the second, third, fourth, fifth, and sixth day, respectively, after acquisition feeding, indicating that the infectivity gradually decreased with time in days. Experimental results showed that the decrease of infectivity was not due to the number of seedlings inoculated by the insect. Loss of infectivity could not be attributed to aging of the

leafhoppers because infectivity could be restored by re-acquisition feeding, regardless of when the re-acquisition feeding was made. Some insects retained their infectivity for as long as they were alive if they had a daily re-acquisition feeding. The loss of infectivity is, therefore, related only to the time elapsing since the termination of acquisition feeding.

No demonstratable incubation period in the vector. An incubation period, the time elapsing between ingestion of an infectious agent by an insect and the time when the insect becomes infective, is required by all known leafhopper-transmitted viruses and is related to the multiplication and circulation of the virus within the vector. With the tungro virus several experiments were made to determine the incubation period of the virus in the vector but no appreciable length of time could be detected. The insects transmitted the disease agent immediately after acquisition. By shortening the acquisition period, the insects were then not infective. Some insects were able to transmit the disease following an hour of acquisition feeding and an hour of inoculation feeding. If there was a latent period in the insect, it could not, therefore, have been longer than 2 hours, which is shorter than any incubation period of leafhopper-borne viruses reported.

Effect of length of acquisition on infectivity. Generally, the length of acquisition feeding does not affect the infective capacity or the retention of virus by a vector in the propagative group of leafhopper-borne viruses. But a longer feeding period is necessary to enable the vectors to acquire their maximum charge of the circulative group of leafhopper-borne viruses. With the tungro virus, experimental results indicated that both the percentage of infective insects and the duration of retention of infectivity increased as the acquisition feeding period was increased up to 4 days.

Loss of infectivity after molting. It is generally accepted that leafhopper-borne viruses are retained by the vector through the molting stage. Experiments were made to determine whether

this was so with tungro virus. To guard against the normal loss of infectivity with time, nymphs were confined on diseased plants until molting had been completed. The results (Table 7) indicated that not a single viruliferous

TABLE 7. Infectivity of *Nephotettix impicticeps* before and after molting.

Treatment	Experiment	No. of infective	No. of non-infective
Before molting	I	3	3
	II	5	3
	III	17	14
Total		25	20
After molting	I	0	6
	II	0	8
	III	0	31
Total		0	45

nymph remained infective after molting. Loss of infectivity during molting is one of the major characteristics of nonpersistent viruses.

Leafhopper-borne viruses have been thought to be either propagative or circulative, the only two known groups. Evidence on the tungro virus, however, does not support its inclusion in either group. The term 'nonpersistence,' generally applied when transmission time is short and the vector cannot transmit after molting, is an appropriate term for the interaction of the tungro virus and its leafhopper vector, *Nephotettix impicticeps*. This appears to be the first exception to the statement by K. M. Smith that 'leafhopper-borne viruses are always persistent and are usually carried by the insect for the rest of its life.'

To remain infective, the tungro vector requires constant access to diseased plants. The transmission cycle should therefore be broken if diseased plants of rice and the other grass hosts (*Eleusine indica*, *Echinochloa crus-galli*, and *E. colonum*) are rogued from the crop. This procedure is suggested as a method of reducing the incidence of the disease in the field.

Electron microscopic study of rice viruses

In collaboration with Dr. K. Maramorosch, Boyce Thompson Institute for Plant Research, U.S.A., and Dr. E. Shikata, Botanical Institute, Faculty of Agriculture, Hokkaido University, Japan, studies are proceeding on the morphology of particles of rice viruses, both in plants and in insects, by the ultra-thin section technique and electron microscopic examination. The preliminary results indicated that the virus particles of grassy stunt (Fig. 9) are similar to those of the rice dwarf in Japan. They are 70 millimicrons in diameter and multiply in a "viroplasmic matrix" in the fat body cell cytoplasm of *Nilaparvata lugens*.

Fig. 9. Virus particles of grassy stunt of rice in *Nilaparvata lugens*. (A.) engulfed virus particles. (B.) virus particles in tubular structure.

Effect of viruses on rice plants inoculated at different ages

Preliminary findings of studies on the effect of rice viruses on the growth and yield of rice plants indicate a gen-

Fig. 10. Effect of tungro virus on the growth of IR9-60 inoculated at different ages of seedlings. From left, plant inoculated at 15, 30, 45, 60, 90 days after sowing, and two controls: one exposed to virus-free insects at 90 days, and the other, un-inoculated. There are four seedlings per pot; all tillers except one from each plant were removed at the time of inoculation.

eral tendency for the percentage of infected plants to decrease and degree of severity to lessen as the plants grow older. As shown in Fig. 10, the degree of severity on IR9-60 infected by the tungro virus lessened gradually as the time between sowing and inoculation increased.

Seedlings of BPI-76 were inoculated with tungro, grassy stunt, and yellow dwarf viruses at 10, 30, and 60 days after sowing. The results indicated that the loss due to any of the viruses was negligible if seedlings were infected after 60 days. Thus it may be important to protect seedlings during the early stages of growth.

Viral nature of "penyakit merah" disease

The "penyakit merah" disease of rice in Malaysia has long been considered a physiological disease. The characteristic symptoms are a stunting of the plant and discoloration of the leaves. These symptoms are similar to those of tungro

disease. "Penyakit merah" was investigated with the collaboration of the Department of Agriculture, States of Malaya, at Parit Buntar in Perak State where the disease has been prevalent for many years. The main purpose of the investigation was to determine whether, as with tungro virus, the causal agent of "penyakit merah" was transmissible by the rice green leafhopper, *Nephotettix impicticeps*.

Rice green leafhoppers were collected from fields in six different localities in the Krian District and confined on healthy seedlings. Some of the seedlings became infected and displayed symptoms similar to those appearing in the fields, thus indicating that the disease principal was associated with the leafhopper in the field.

Virus-free insects reared from eggs, and adult insects collected directly from the field, were confined for acquisition feeding on diseased plants collected from eight different localities. They were subsequently transferred to cages

containing healthy seedlings. Insects which had not fed on any diseased plants served as a control. A high percentage of seedlings exposed to viruliferous insects became infected whereas the controls remained healthy. The experiments also showed that the virus was recovered by the insects from 58 of 64 diseased samples.

From the evidence on the transmissibility of the disease principal by *N. impicticeps*, it has been concluded that "penyakit merah" is caused by a virus and that the leafhopper is the vector. Further experiments are being carried out to discover whether other environmental factors affect the development and severity of the disease.

In some varietal resistance tests, the Malaysian varieties Machang, Malinja, Mayang Kelantan, Mayang Sibatil, Seraup 50, Seri Raja, Seri Raja 712, and Seri Raja 949 were found susceptible. Tests on other varieties showed that Bengawan, FB 24, Gam Pai, Intan, Latisail, Peta, Tjeremas, and Tjina were resistant and that Aceh, CP 231 x HO

12 and Taichung (Native) 1 were susceptible. The reactions of susceptible varieties to "penyakit merah" are similar to the reactions to tungro.

Because the symptoms and varietal reactions are similar, a close relationship between the "penyakit merah" virus and the tungro virus is suspected. The results of the "penyakit merah" study have been published.

The discovery of the viral nature of "penyakit merah" suggests that the "mentek" disease of Indonesia may also be caused by a virus. These, together with the newly reported virus diseases in Taiwan and Thailand, indicate the importance of these diseases in the tropics. It is possible, of course, that at times the same names have been used for other diseases of similar symptomatology but of non-viral origin. None has been identified so far in these studies, but until further work has been done, the investigator should explicitly describe the disorder which he is studying.

Soil Chemistry

Further advances in soil chemistry during the year included: (a) the application of physical chemistry to the study of flooded soils, (b) the description and interpretation of chemical and electrochemical changes in flooded soils, (c) the appraisal of the chemical benefits of flooding rice soils, and (d) the diagnosis and correction of physiological disorders of the rice plant associated with injurious soil conditions.

The apparent standard free energies of formation of three metastable substances involved in mineral equilibria in flooded soils were determined, and a relationship established between ionic strength and specific conductance. The main redox and carbonate equilibria in submerged soils were identified and quantitatively characterized. Nitrate and sulfate reductions were found to be first order reactions. Mercaptans, amines, aldehydes and ketones, fatty acids, amino acids, and sugars in the solutions of flooded soils were isolated and identified.

In the applied field, it was confirmed that one of the principal benefits of flooding rice soils was increased availability of iron, especially in the reproductive phase of the plant's development and that (a) suffocation disease was caused by reduction products and was corrected by nitrate and manganese dioxide, (b) a physiological disorder of rice on a soil from Taiwan was boron toxicity, and (c) the toxicity of an acid-sulfate soil from Vietnam was due chiefly to excess ferrous iron in the soil solution which was overcome by lime and manganese dioxide.

These findings are described under: (a) thermodynamics of flooded soils, (b) redox systems in flooded soils, (c) carbonate equilibria in submerged soils, (d) chemical kinetics of flooded soils, (e) the organic components of anaerobic soil solutions, (f) water regime in flooded soils, and (g) physiological disorders of the rice plant.

THERMODYNAMICS OF FLOODED SOILS

Although the principal chemical and electrochemical changes in flooded soils have been known for decades, no one had attempted to explain and interpret them in terms of thermodynamics. The deterrents, apparently, were: (a) the dynamic nature of flooded soils which prevents the attainment of true equilibrium, (b) the irreversibility of some of the changes, (c) the heterogeneity of the soil system, (d) the variety and multitude of equilibria, both organic and inorganic, (e) the complications caused by bacteria and their metabolites, (f) the large number of chemical analyses required to calculate the activities of ions in anaerobic soil solutions, and (g) the practical problems with which soil chemists were preoccupied. But it has been found in these laboratories that thermodynamics can be applied successfully to flooded soils, open new vistas in the study of their chemistry, and throw considerable light on ecologically important chemical and electrochemical changes in flooded rice soils.

Success in the present investigations was due primarily to (a) the consideration of the soil solution as the phase representing the equilibrium in flooded soils, (b) the use of experimental apparent standard free energies of formation of metastable substances found in a medium that undergoes oxidation-reduction over short periods of time, instead of the values for their stable, crystalline counterparts, and (c) an empirical discovery that dramatically simplified the calculation of activity coefficients of the ions involved in equilibria in so complex a medium as the soil solution of a reduced soil.

The equilibrium soil solution

The soil solution of a flooded soil may be regarded as its equilibrium solution. It consists of thick films of water between the soil particles, contains dissolved and suspended matter in dynamic equilibrium with the solid and gas phases of the soil, and is the solution of unique composition in the context of

the Gouy theory. Thus, despite the heterogeneity caused by the uneven distribution of organic matter and soil minerals, the soil solution drawn by gravity should represent the average equilibrium soil solution at sampling. An integrated study of Eh, pH and the chemical composition of the soil solutions of 31 soils kept flooded for 16 weeks showed that the soil solution of a flooded soil is the thermodynamically meaningful phase (Annual Report, 1964). Subsequent studies confirmed this.

Standard free energy of formation of $\text{Fe}_3(\text{OH})_8$

One of the biggest obstacles to the application of thermodynamics to flooded soils is the absence of thermochemical data for substances (probably hydrated variants of stable crystalline species) that undergo oxidation-reduction or precipitation and solution over short periods of time in a medium that is alternately saturated and moist, but seldom desiccated. Of such substances, $\text{Fe}_3(\text{OH})_8$, the hydrated metastable variant of magnetite (Fe_3O_4), is perhaps the most important because of its abundance and reactivity. A knowledge of the standard free energy of formation of this substance is necessary for the quantitative study of redox, carbonate, and hydroxide equilibria in flooded soils.

The standard free energy of formation of ferrosiferic hydroxide ($\Delta F_{\text{Fe}_3(\text{OH})_8}^\circ$) at 25 C was calculated by

five methods using the solubility product of $\text{Fe}_3(\text{OH})_8$ and pH, Eh and Fe^{++} activity of the solution phase of sand, containing 0.1% $\text{Fe}(\text{OH})_3$ and 0.1% of a 1:1 mixture of dried straw and green manure, kept submerged with water for 16 weeks.

$$\Delta F_{\text{Fe}_3(\text{OH})_8}^\circ \text{ from } K_s.$$

The precipitation of $\text{Fe}_3(\text{OH})_8$ from aqueous solutions may be represented by the equation,

$$\begin{array}{ccccccc} -20.3 & & 2(-166.0) & & 2(-37.6) & & x \end{array}$$

$$\text{with } K_s = \frac{(\text{Fe}_3(\text{OH})_8)}{(\text{Fe}^{++}) (\text{OH}^-)^2 (\text{Fe}(\text{OH})_3)^2} = \frac{1}{(\text{Fe}^{++}) (\text{OH}^-)^2} = 10^{17.56}$$

(which is the reciprocal of Arden's value of 6.4×10^{-18} for K 's for $\text{Fe}_3(\text{OH})_8$, corrected for the activity coefficient of Fe^{++}).

$$\Delta F_R^\circ = -RT \ln K_s = -1.364 \times 17.56 = -24.4 \text{ kcal}$$

$$\text{Also } \Delta F_R^\circ = x - (-20.3) - 2(-166.0) - 2(-37.6) = x + 427.5$$

$$\text{or } x = \Delta F_{\text{Fe}_3(\text{OH})_8}^\circ = -451.5 \text{ kcal per mole at } 25^\circ\text{C}.$$

If the experimental figure of $10^{-17.4}$ is used for K_s , $\Delta F_{\text{Fe}_3(\text{OH})_8}^\circ = -451.2$.

$\Delta F_{\text{Fe}_3(\text{OH})_8}^\circ$ from E_o of the system $\text{Fe}(\text{OH})_3 - \text{Fe}_3(\text{OH})_8$.

Experimentally E_o was 0.433 ± 0.003 $\text{Fe}(\text{OH})_3$, and organic matter, incubated from peak water-soluble Fe^{++} on-wards, for the solutions from sand, ed anaerobically with water.

$$\text{or } \begin{array}{l} \therefore x + 441.3 = -0.433 \times 23.06 = -10.0 \\ \Delta F_{\text{Fe}_3(\text{OH})_8}^\circ = -451.3 \text{ kcal per mole at } 25^\circ\text{C} \end{array}$$

$\Delta F_{\text{Fe}_3(\text{OH})_8}^\circ$ from E_o of the system $\text{Fe}_3(\text{OH})_8 - \text{Fe}^{++}$.

Experimentally, E_o was 1.394 ± 0.004 for sand, $\text{Fe}(\text{OH})_3$, organic matter, and water, incubated anaerobically.

$$\Delta F_R^\circ = -46.12 \times 1.394 = -64.3$$

$$\therefore \Delta F_{\text{Fe}_3(\text{OH})_8}^\circ = -450.2 \text{ kcal per mole at } 25^\circ\text{C}.$$

$\Delta F^\circ \text{Fe}_3(\text{OH})_8$ from the equilibrium constant of the $\text{Fe}_3(\text{OH})_8 - \text{Fe}^{++}$ reaction.

$$\frac{(\text{Fe}^{++})^3 (\text{H}_2\text{O})^8}{(\text{Fe}_3(\text{OH})_8) (\text{H}^+)^8} = K$$

i.e. $3 \log(\text{Fe}^{++}) + 8\text{pH} = \log K = 45.8$ (experimentally).
 $-514.5 - x = \Delta F^\circ_{\text{R}} = -1.364 \log K = -62.5$
 $x = -452.0$

or $\Delta F^\circ \text{Fe}_3(\text{OH})_8 = -452.0$ kcal per mole at 25°C .

Comparison of $\Delta F^\circ \text{Fe}_3(\text{OH})_8$ (kcal per mole at 25°C) by five methods.

1. Using Arden's value for the solubility product of $\text{Fe}_3(\text{OH})_8$, corrected for γFe^{++} and the following experimental values obtained in these laboratories:	-451.5
2. Ks for $\text{Fe}_3(\text{OH})_8$.	-451.2
3. Eo for the system, $\text{Fe}(\text{OH})_3 - \text{Fe}_3(\text{OH})_8$	-451.3
4. Eo of the system, $\text{Fe}_3(\text{OH})_8 - \text{Fe}^{++}$	-450.2
5. K for the equilibrium, $\text{Fe}_3(\text{OH})_8 - \text{Fe}^{++}$	-452.0
Mean	-451.2 $\pm$ 0.3

Apparent standard free energy of formation of Mn_3O_4

The close agreement of the values of the standard free energy of formation of $\text{Fe}_3(\text{OH})_8$ by five different methods indicates that (a) the green precipitate that forms when an anaerobic soil solution is made alkaline is a substance with definite thermochemical properties and (b) the postulated equilibria operate in aqueous ferrous systems.

By the same methods, the mean apparent standard free energy of formation of the freshly precipitated form of Fe_3O_4 was -224.4 kcal per mole, compared with -242.2 for magnetite.

The standard free energy of formation of Mn_3O_4 under mild aqueous conditions (hydro hausmannite?) must be known for the quantitative study of redox and carbonate equilibria in flooded soils high in manganese. As a satisfactory figure was not available, a calculation was made of the apparent standard free energy of formation of Mn_3O_4 from Eh, pH, and Mn^{++} activity determinations of a suspension of freshly precipitated MnCO_3 , at several partial pressures of CO_2 , in the laboratory.

$\Delta F^\circ \text{Mn}_3\text{O}_4$ from Eo of the system $\text{Mn}_3\text{O}_4 - \text{Mn}^{++}$

$$\Delta F^\circ_{\text{R}} = -390.0 - x$$

$$\text{Eo} = \text{Eh} + 0.0885 \log \text{Mn}^{++} + 0.236 \text{pH}$$

$$= 1.420 \text{ (experimentally)}$$

$$\Delta F^\circ_{\text{R}} = -1.42 \times 2 \times 23.06 = -65.5$$

$$\Delta F^\circ \text{Mn}_3\text{O}_4 = -324.5 \text{ kcal per mole at } 25^\circ\text{C}$$

$\Delta F^\circ_{\text{Mn}_3\text{O}_4}$ from (E_o) of the system $\text{Mn}_3\text{O}_4 - \text{MnCO}_3$.

$$\Delta F^\circ_{\text{R}} = -356.7 - x$$

$$\begin{aligned} E_o &= E_h - 0.0885 \log P_{\text{CO}_2} + 0.059 \text{ pH} \\ &= 0.680 \text{ (experimentally)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta F^\circ_{\text{R}} &= -2 \times 23.06 \times 0.68 \\ &= -31.4 \end{aligned}$$

$$\therefore \Delta F^\circ_{\text{Mn}_3\text{O}_4} = -325.3 \text{ kcal per mole at } 25^\circ\text{C}$$

The near identity of $\Delta F^\circ_{\text{Mn}_3\text{O}_4}$ by two different methods suggests that Mn_3O_4 precipitated under mild aqueous conditions has a definite standard free energy of formation which is different from that of hausmannite.

Standard free energy of formation of $\text{Mn}(\text{OH})_3$

The use of the published value (-181.0 kcal/mole) of the standard free energy of formation of $\text{Mn}(\text{OH})_3$ in redox equilibria based on it yields unusually high E_o 's, as shown below:

System	E_o (volts)
$3\text{Mn}(\text{OH})_3 + \text{H}^+ + \text{e} = \text{Mn}_3\text{O}_4 + 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$	2.11
$\text{Mn}(\text{OH})_3 + 3\text{H}^+ + \text{e} = \text{Mn}^{++} + 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$	1.89
$\text{Mn}(\text{OH})_3 + \text{CO}_2 + \text{H}^+ + \text{e} = \text{MnCO}_3 + 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$	1.41

Because the observed E_o 's for these systems for soils high in Mn were considerably lower, the standard free energy of formation of $\text{Mn}(\text{OH})_3$ was re-

calculated from E_h , pH, and Mn^{++} activity of a system of manganous carbonate equilibrated with CO_2 at different partial pressures in the laboratory.

$\Delta F^\circ_{\text{Mn}(\text{OH})_3}$ from E_o of the $\text{Mn}(\text{OH})_3 - \text{MnCO}_3$ system.

$$\Delta F^\circ_{\text{R}} = -213.4 - x$$

$$E_h = E_o + 0.59 \log P_{\text{CO}_2} - 0.059 \text{ pH}$$

$$E_o = 0.688 \text{ (experimentally)}$$

$$\Delta F^\circ_{\text{R}} = -23.06 \times E_o = -15.9$$

$$\Delta F^\circ_{\text{Mn}(\text{OH})_3} = -197.5 \text{ kcal per mole}$$

$\Delta F^\circ_{\text{Mn(OH)}_3}$ from E_o of the $\text{Mn(OH)}_3 - \text{Mn}^{++}$ system.

$$E_h = E_o - 0.059 \log \text{Mn}^{++} - 0.177 \text{ pH}$$

$$E_o = 1.163 \text{ (experimentally)}$$

$$\Delta F^\circ_{\text{R}} = -224.5 - x$$

$$\Delta F^\circ_{\text{R}} = -23.06 \times 1.163 = -26.8$$

and $\Delta F^\circ_{\text{Mn(OH)}_3} = -197.7 \text{ kcal per mole at } 25^\circ\text{C}$

Activity coefficients from specific conductance

A knowledge of the activity coefficients of ions is a prerequisite to the application of thermodynamics to ionic equilibria in flooded soils. The current method of deriving them from the concentrations of the ions and the ionic strength ($\frac{1}{2} \sum c_i Z_i^2$) of the solutions necessitates the chemical assay of Ca^{++} , Mg^{++} , Fe^{++} , NH_4^+ , Na^+ , K^+ , HCO_3^- , Cl^- , NO_3^- , NO_2^- and SO_4^{--} in the solutions. A simpler method of determining ionic strength would enormously simplify the study of ionic equilibria in flooded soils.

The previous year's work (Annual

Report, 1964) suggested that the empirical relationship, $\mu = 16 \kappa$ between ionic strength, μ , in moles per liter, and specific conductance, κ , in mhos per cm, might provide a simple, rapid, and sufficiently accurate method of determining the ionic strength of the soil solutions of flooded soils. This year, the limitations of the relationship were examined, its general validity for the soil solutions of flooded soils was confirmed, and a theoretical explanation found based on the Debye-Hückel-Onsager equation.

The empirical relationship, $\mu \approx 16 \kappa$, was confirmed for (a) 22 samples of the soil solutions of 17 flooded soils from submergence to 16 weeks later (excluding the samples which were ex-

Fig. 1. Relationship between μ and κ in the solutions of soils kept flooded for 16 weeks.

traordinarily high in nitrate or sulfate) (Fig. 1), (b) 196 samples from disappearance of nitrate to 16 weeks after submergence and (c) 121 soil solutions from peak water-soluble iron onwards. The regressions of μ on κ were:

	$\mu = 0.0014 \pm 0.0005 + (16.0 \pm 0.9) \kappa$	$r = 0.90^{**}$
or	$\mu = 16 \kappa$ (all 17 soils: start to finish)	
	$\mu = 0.0008 \pm 0.0009 + (15.8 \pm 0.5) \kappa$	$r = 0.91^{**}$
or	$\mu = 15.8 \kappa$ (all 17 soils: NO_3^- disappearance onwards)	
	$\mu = 0.0007 \pm 0.0010 + (15.9 \pm 0.6) \kappa$	$r = 0.93^{**}$
or	$\mu = 15.9 \kappa$ (all 17 soils: peak Fe onwards)	

Thus, despite the changes in the composition of the soil solutions caused by disappearance of nitrate, release and subsequent removal of water-soluble Fe^{++} , and other reactions, the ionic strength was very nearly 16 times the specific conductance.

The regressions of μ on κ for 3 flooded calcareous soils and for the solutions of $\text{Fe}(\text{OH})_3$ fermented anaerobically with straw plus green manure were respectively:

$$\mu = 0.0011 + 17.4 \kappa \quad r = 0.89^{**}$$

$$\mu = -0.009 + 17.6 \kappa \quad r = 0.98^{**}$$

The relative constancy of the $\mu - \kappa$ relationship under varying conditions suggested that it might hold also for aerobic soil solutions. The regression of

μ on κ for 25 samples of irrigation water, whose chemical analysis and κ are reported in "Diagnosis and Improvement of Saline and Alkaline Soils" (USDA Handbook No. 60, 1954), with ionic strengths ranging from 0.0013 to 0.0629 moles per liter confirmed this surmise. Thus:

$$\mu = -0.0012 + 16.9 \kappa \quad r = 0.96^{**}$$

Because of the remarkable constancy of the relationship between μ and κ for mixed electrolytes, the behavior of single salt solutions was examined using published values of equivalent conductivities and concentrations. Converting equivalent conductivities to specific conductivities, and concentrations to ionic strengths, the following expressions were obtained:

<i>Salt</i>	<i>Regression</i>	<i>Limit of μ moles/liter</i>
NaCl	$\mu = 0.0002 + 8.67 \kappa$	0.05
NaHCO_3	$\mu = -0.0002 + 11.7 \kappa$	0.02
Na_2SO_4	$\mu = 0.0006 + 14.4 \kappa$	0.05
MnCl_2	$\mu = 0.0006 + 14.6 \kappa$	0.05
$\text{Ca}(\text{HCO}_3)_2$	$\mu = -0.0003 + 17.4 \kappa$	0.15
CaSO_4	$\mu = 0.0009 + 22.8 \kappa$	0.02
MgSO_4	$\mu = 0.0016 + 25.7 \kappa$	0.02

traordinarily high in nitrate or sulfate) (Fig. 1), (b) 196 samples from disappearance of nitrate to 16 weeks after submergence and (c) 121 soil solutions from peak water-soluble iron onwards. The regressions of μ on κ were:

	$\mu = 0.0014 \pm 0.0005 + (16.0 \pm 0.9) \kappa$	$r = 0.90^{**}$
or	$\mu = 16 \kappa$ (all 17 soils: start to finish)	
	$\mu = 0.0008 \pm 0.0009 + (15.8 \pm 0.5) \kappa$	$r = 0.91^{**}$
or	$\mu = 15.8 \kappa$ (all 17 soils: NO_3^- disappearance onwards)	
	$\mu = 0.0007 \pm 0.0010 + (15.9 \pm 0.6) \kappa$	$r = 0.93^{**}$
or	$\mu = 15.9 \kappa$ (all 17 soils: peak Fe onwards)	

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NaHCO_3	$\mu = -0.0002 + 11.7 \kappa$	0.02
Na_2SO_4	$\mu = 0.0006 + 14.4 \kappa$	0.05
MnCl_2	$\mu = 0.0006 + 14.6 \kappa$	0.05
$\text{Ca}(\text{HCO}_3)_2$	$\mu = -0.0003 + 17.4 \kappa$	0.15
CaSO_4	$\mu = 0.0009 + 22.8 \kappa$	0.02
MgSO_4	$\mu = 0.0016 + 25.7 \kappa$	0.02

TABLE 1. Comparison of the activities (millimoles/l) of HCO_3^- and Fe^{++} derived from the observed ionic strengths and ionic strengths computed from specific conductance ($\mu = 16 \lambda$) in the soil solutions of three flooded soils.

Weeks submerged	Louisiana clay pH 4.6, O.M. 4.1% $\alpha_{\text{HCO}_3^-}$			Maahas clay pH 6.6, O.M. 2.0% $\alpha_{\text{HCO}_3^-}$			Calcareous clay pH 7.6, O.M. 1.5% $\alpha_{\text{HCO}_3^-}$		
	obs.	cal.	$\alpha_{\text{Fe}^{++}}$	obs.	cal.	$\alpha_{\text{Fe}^{++}}$	obs.	cal.	$\alpha_{\text{Fe}^{++}}$
0.5	2.45	2.43	0.02	7.05	7.10	.003	14.3	14.3	.003
1	8.14	8.22	0.91	11.4	11.7	.004	17.5	17.7	.002
2	20.7	20.9	3.23	17.6	17.8	.015	20.0	20.2	.022
3	11.4	11.3	1.02	20.1	20.3	.026	20.9	21.0	.031
4	9.78	9.65	0.53	18.9	18.9	.039	21.1	21.3	.043
5	9.43	9.32	1.02	16.2	15.7	.069	21.0	21.0	.052
9	8.43	8.35	0.91	12.6	12.6	.133	19.3	19.4	.069
13	8.34	8.23	0.85	11.5	11.5	.167	16.0	16.0	.067
17	7.92	7.97	0.73	11.1	11.2	.175	14.5	14.6	.057

The plots of μ and κ show an excellent linear relationship between μ and κ up to ionic strengths of 0.02 and a remarkably good relationship even up to 0.05 μ . The slopes are least for uni-univalent electrolytes, medium for uni-bivalent and biunivalent electrolytes and highest for bivalent salts. The empirical μ/κ slope of 16 for soil solutions of flooded soils and natural waters appears to be a fortuitous mean for a mixture of the four types of electrolytes.

A theoretical basis for the association between ionic strength (which is a measure of the intensity of the electric field in a solution) and specific conductance (which depends on the number of ions per unit volume, their electric charges, and the intensity of the electric field) was found in the Debye-Hückel-Onsager conductance equation which may be written for an aqueous solution of a uniunivalent electrolyte as:

$$\Lambda = \Lambda_0 - (A + B \Lambda_0) \sqrt{c}$$

Substituting the numerical values of A and B for water and of Λ_0 for KCl, and converting Λ to κ , the following relationship for KCl for ionic strengths up to 0.05 was obtained:

$$\mu = -0.001 + 7.91 \kappa \quad r = 0.98^{**}$$

Ionic strengths derived from specific conductance were sufficiently accurate for the calculation of ion activities in flooded soils. Table 1 shows an excellent agreement between activities of HCO_3^- and Fe^{++} calculated from γHCO_3^- and γFe^{++} derived from μ observed and μ computed from κ .

REDOX SYSTEMS IN FLOODED SOILS

The redox systems in flooded soils cover the entire potential range from the oxygen system to the hydrogen system. They include such a large number and variety of inorganic, organic, and bacterial systems in simultaneous dynamic equilibrium that their identification and characterization is, indeed, a difficult task. The difficulty is aggravated by the lack of thermochemical data for the transitory substances involved in redox equilibria in flooded soils. Some of these obstacles were cir-

cumvented by (a) considering the reduction process in stages, (b) testing the presence of systems suspected on chemical or thermodynamic grounds, and (c) using the apparent standard free energies of formation of some of the substances involved in redox equilibria, instead of the values for their crystalline counterparts.

The following mineral systems in the flooded soils studied were identified and characterized:

1. $O_2 + 4H^+ + 4e = 2H_2O$
2. $Fe(OH)_3 + 3H^+ + e = Fe^{++} + 3H_2O$
3. $3Fe(OH)_3 + H^+ + e = Fe_3(OH)_8 + H_2O$
4. $Fe_3(OH)_8 + 8H^+ + 2e = 3Fe^{++} + 8H_2O$
5. $Mn(OH)_3 + 3H^+ + e = Mn^{++} + 3H_2O$
6. $3Mn(OH)_3 + H^+ + e = Mn_3O_4 + 5H_2O$
7. $Mn(OH)_3 + CO_2 + H^+ + e = MnCO_3 + 2H_2O$
8. $Mn_3O_4 + 8H^+ + 2e = 3Mn^{++} + 4H_2O$
9. $Mn_3O_4 + 3CO_2 + 2H^+ + 2e = 3MnCO_3 + H_2O$

The oxygen system is the dominant system in natural aqueous media in equilibrium with air and, therefore, is the system determining the potential of a soil at the instant of flooding (Annual Report, 1963). However, within a few hours, the oxygen concentration is reduced to such a low value that the oxygen system no longer controls the potential of the soil. Other substances in a high state of oxidation, such as NO_3^- then function as electron acceptors in microbial respiration and prevent a further decrease in redox potential, but no proof was found that the $NO_3^- - NO_2^-$ system functioned as a thermodynamically reversible redox system.

The iron systems

The $Fe(OH)_3 - Fe^{++}$ system. With the disappearance of NO_3^- , a soil rapidly undergoes reduction, producing reduced iron and manganese in the solid and the solution phases. Because all soils contain considerably more iron than manganese, the iron systems should exercise a dominant role in the redox potentials of flooded soils. Of the iron systems, $Fe(OH)_3 - Fe^{++}$ is one of the most important because both Fe^{++} and some $Fe(OH)_3$ are always present in reduced soils.

The electrochemical equation for the $Fe(OH)_3 - Fe^{++}$ system is

or $\Delta F_R^\circ = -24.4 = -23.06 E_o$

$$E_o = 1.058$$

and $E_h = 1.058 - 0.059 \log (Fe^{++}) - 0.177 \text{ pH}$

The test for the presence of this system is a linear regression of (Eh+0.177 pH) on log (Fe⁺⁺) with a slope of -0.059 and an intercept of 1.06 volts or constancy and equality of the sum (Eh

+0.177 pH+0.059 log Fe) to 1.06. The experimental observations were as follows:

1. The regression of (Eh+0.177 pH) on log Fe⁺⁺ was

$$(Eh + 0.177 \text{ pH}) = 1.059 \pm 0.014 - (0.0605 \pm 0.036) \log \text{Fe}^{++} \quad r = -0.75^{**}$$

for 14 soils whose Eh, pH, and log Fe⁺⁺ were determined weekly from 0 to 17 weeks of submergence.

or

$$Eh = 1.06 - 0.06 \log \text{Fe}^{++} - 0.177 \text{ pH}$$

cf. with the theoretical equation,

$$Eh = 1.06 - 0.059 \log \text{Fe}^{++} - 0.177 \text{ pH}$$

- Experimental values of Eo for typical soils averaged over 17 weeks of submergence (Table 2) approached 1.06, closely; and
- Sand, Fe(OH)₃, and straw+green manure, incubated anaerobically in the laboratory and greenhouse, gave Eo values of 1.061±0.003 and 1.064±0.005 respectively.

for which
and

$$E_o = 0.429 \text{ volts}$$

$$Eh = 0.429 - 0.059 \text{ pH.}$$

Experimentally, Eo (derived from Eh and pH of the 13 solution samples of sand, Fe(OH)₃, organic matter, and water incubated anaerobically) was 0.433±0.003 volts. This indicated the presence of the system, Fe(OH)₃-Fe₃(OH)₈, in the anaerobic

Table 2 shows that although the Fe(OH)₃-Fe⁺⁺ system operates over a wide range of flooded soils, the three acid soils low in Mn (Soils 10, 21, 24) gave Eo values closest to the theoretical Eo. The near identity of the observed Eo's with Eo calculated from standard free energy of formation of Fe(OH)₃ indicates that "ferric hydroxide" and not Fe₂O₃ (haematite) is the solid ferric phase involved in flooded soils.

The Fe(OH)₃-Fe₃(OH)₈ system. This system comes into operation in flooded soils with the precipitation of Fe₃(OH)₈, after the peak of water-soluble Fe⁺⁺ (Annual Report, 1964). The standard potential of this system can be calculated from the reaction,

system containing Fe(OH)₃.

Eo of flooded soils, derived from Eh and pH of the soil solutions from peak water-soluble Fe⁺⁺ onwards, varied with soil. Mean Eo tended towards 0.43 volt in soils low in Mn and high in Fe; it exceeded 0.5 volt in soils high in Mn

TABLE 2. Eo=Eh+0.059 log Fe⁺⁺+0.177 pH, derived from Eh, pH and $\alpha_{\text{Fe}^{++}}$ of the soil solutions of anaerobic soils.

Soil no.	pH	O.M. (%)	Active Fe (%)	Active Mn (%)	Eo (volts)
4	6.9	2.0	0.91	0.24	1.08 ±0.01
10	5.4	1.5	1.67	0.20	1.07 ±0.01
17	7.0	1.8	1.03	0.15	1.08 ±0.01
21	4.6	4.1	2.78	0.02	1.069±0.004
24	5.3	3.8	1.32	0.01	1.058±0.007
26	7.6	1.5	0.30	0.06	1.08 ±0.01
27	6.6	2.0	1.60	0.31	1.08 ±0.01

and low in Fe as shown in Table 3.

The experimental values of $E_o = E_h + 0.059$ pH, apparently represent a mean between the 0.43 volt, the E_o of the $Fe(OH)_3-Fe_3(OH)_8$ system and

0.66, E_o of the $Mn(OH)_3-Mn_3O_4$ system.

The $Fe_3(OH)_8-Fe^{++}$ system. Since water-soluble Fe^{++} is always present in reduced soils, the system,

should operate after the precipitation of $Fe_3(OH)_8$,

with

$$E_o = \frac{63.3}{2 \times 23.06} = 1.373 \text{ volts}$$

or

$$E_h = 1.37 - 0.0885 \log Fe^{++} - 0.236 \text{ pH}$$

water-soluble Fe for the following 4 to 12 weeks came remarkably close to the theoretical value of 1.37 (Table 4). Agreement was closest with the soils high in Fe (Soils 14, 21, 28), and least in soils low in Fe or high in Mn. The system $Fe(OH)_3-Fe_3(OH)_8$ clearly operates in flooded soils high in active iron.

It may be concluded that: (a) the

TABLE 3. Influence of soil properties on $E_o = E_h + 0.059$ pH in flooded soils from peak water-soluble Fe^{++} onwards.

Soil no.	pH	O.M. (%)	Active Mn (%)	Active Fe (%)	E_o (volts)
21	4.7	4.1	0.02	2.78	0.44
24	5.3	3.8	0.01	1.32	0.45
14	4.6	2.8	0.06	2.13	0.46
28	4.7	3.2	0.05	2.91	0.47
10	5.4	1.5	0.20	1.67	0.51
27	6.6	2.0	0.31	1.60	0.53
7	5.9	3.3	0.33	1.67	0.54
4	6.9	2.0	0.24	0.91	0.56
3	5.7	1.3	0.36	0.79	0.59

Experimentally E_o was 1.394 ± 0.004 for 12 solution samples of the anaerobically fermented $Fe(OH)_3$ from peak water-soluble Fe^{++} , onwards. The mean E_o 's for flooded soils from peak

$Fe(OH)_3-Fe^{++}$ system operates throughout submergence and (b) the $Fe(OH)_3-Fe_3(OH)_8$ and $Fe_3(OH)_8-Fe^{++}$ systems operate after a few weeks of flooding.

TABLE 4. Influence of soil properties on $E_o = E_h + 0.0885 \log Fe^{++} + 0.236$ pH of flooded soils from peak water-soluble Fe^{++} onwards.

Soil no.	pH	O.M. (%)	Active Mn (%)	Active Fe (%)	Mean E_o (volts)
14	4.6	2.8	0.06	2.13	1.373 ± 0.013
21	4.6	4.1	0.02	2.78	1.384 ± 0.004
28	4.7	3.2	0.05	2.91	1.384 ± 0.005
24	5.3	3.8	0.01	1.32	1.36 ± 0.01
10	5.4	1.5	0.20	1.67	1.36 ± 0.02
1	7.6	2.3	0.03	0.18	1.34 ± 0.01
3	5.7	1.3	0.36	0.79	1.33 ± 0.02
4	6.9	2.0	0.24	0.91	1.34 ± 0.02
25	4.8	4.4	0.005	0.18	1.32 ± 0.01

The manganese systems in flooded soils

The identification of the Mn systems in flooded soils was difficult because of (a) the multiplicity of possible equilibria and (b) the absence of thermochemical data for the metastable sub-

stances involved in these systems. However, applying the criteria adopted earlier and using the standard free energies of formation of $Mn(OH)_3$ and Mn_3O_4 determined in the laboratory, instead of the published ΔF° 's, the following systems in flooded soils were identified:

but no evidence was found for any of the following systems based on MnO_2 , even 3 days after flooding: MnO_2 - Mn_2O_3 , MnO_2 - Mn_3O_4 , MnO_2 - Mn^{++} , and MnO_2 - $MnCO_3$.

The $Mn(OH)_3$ - Mn^{++} system. As $Mn(OH)_3$ is present in soils and water-soluble Mn^{++} is released within a few hours or days of flooding, the $Mn(OH)_3$ - Mn^{++} system should operate in flooded soils thus:

$$Eh = 1.16 - 0.059 \log Mn^{++}$$

$$-0.177 \text{ pH}$$

If $E_o = Eh + 0.059 \log Mn^{++} + 0.177 \text{ pH}$ is reasonably constant and nearly equal to 1.16, the $Mn(OH)_3$ - Mn^{++} system operates over the period and in the media considered. Table 5 shows how close the observed E_o 's are to 1.16 in the flooded soils high in Mn; they are less than 1.16 for soils high in Fe and low in Mn.

The $Mn(OH)_3$ - Mn_3O_4 system. Thermodynamically, at Eh values below +0.244 at pH 7, Mn_3O_4 should co-exist with $Mn(OH)_3$. As the E_7 values of flooded soils are considerably less than these, this system should operate in

TABLE 5. Experimental values of E_o for the system $Mn(OH)_3$ - Mn^{++} in soils from submergence to 16 weeks later.

Soil no.	pH	O.M. (%)	Active Mn (%)	Active Fe (%)	E_o (volts) (+0.01)
3	5.7	1.3	0.36	0.79	1.17
4	6.9	2.0	0.24	0.91	1.17
7	5.9	3.3	0.33	1.67	1.13
26	7.6	1.5	0.06	0.30	1.12
27	6.6	2.0	0.31	1.60	1.12
10	5.4	1.5	0.20	1.67	1.09
21	4.6	4.1	0.02	2.78	0.97
24	5.3	3.8	0.01	1.32	0.98
28	4.7	3.2	0.05	2.91	0.99

flooded soils which contain sufficient $\text{Mn}(\text{OH})_3$.

The criterion for the presence of the system,

whose $\text{Eh} = \text{Eo} - 0.059 \text{ pH}$, is the relative constancy of $\text{Eh} + 0.059 \text{ pH}$ around 0.662 volt in spite of Eh and pH variations.

Table 3 shows (a) how close the Eo 's of the Mn-rich soils (Soils 3, 4, 7 and 27) are to 0.66 and (b) how Eo decreases as the Fe content of the soil increases.

The $\text{Mn}_3\text{O}_4\text{-Mn}^{++}$ system. Redox potentials and chemical analysis of reduced soil solutions suggest the presence of the $\text{Mn}_3\text{O}_4\text{-Mn}^{++}$ system in flooded soils. The electrochemical equations for the system are:

$$\text{Eh} = 1.42 - 0.0885 \log (\text{Mn}^{++}) - 0.236 \text{ pH}$$

1.42. The soils low in Mn and high in Fe gave markedly lower Eo 's.

The $\text{Mn}_3\text{O}_4\text{-Mn}^{++}$ system apparently operated in the Mn-rich soils.

The $\text{Mn}_3\text{O}_4\text{-MnCO}_3$ system. The precipitation of MnCO_3 in reduced soils (Annual Report, 1964) implies the production of the system,

$$\text{with Eh} = 0.68 + 0.0885 \log \text{PCO}_2 - 0.059 \text{ pH}$$

For the pure system, $\text{Eh} - 0.0885 \log \text{PCO}_2 + 0.059 \text{ pH}$ should equal 0.68 under varying pH and PCO_2 . If this system operates in flooded soils, Eo of reduced soils will lie between 0.51 (Eo for the $\text{Fe}_3(\text{OH})_8\text{-FeCO}_3$ system) and 0.68, (Eo for the $\text{Mn}_3\text{O}_4\text{-MnCO}_3$ system) because all soils contain both Mn and Fe. Table 6 shows that in Soil 3, which is high in Mn and relatively low in Fe, the system appears to operate. The lower values of Eo for the other soils mean that a mixed $\text{MnCO}_3\text{-FeCO}_3$ system probably op-

TABLE 6. Experimental Eo values for the systems $\text{Mn}_3\text{O}_4\text{-Mn}^{++}$ and $\text{Mn}_3\text{O}_4\text{-MnCO}_3$ in soils from peak water-soluble Mn^{++} onwards.

Soil no.	pH	O.M. (%)	Active Mn (%)	Active Fe (%)	$\text{Mn}_3\text{O}_4\text{-Mn}^{++}$ Eo (volts)	$\text{Mn}_3\text{O}_4\text{-MnCO}_3$ Eo (volts)
3	5.7	1.3	0.36	0.79	1.46	0.64
4	6.9	2.0	0.24	0.91	1.46	0.62
7	5.9	3.3	0.33	1.67	1.42	0.57
27	6.6	2.0	0.31	1.60	1.41	0.57
10	5.4	1.5	0.20	1.67	1.37	0.54
21	4.6	4.1	0.02	2.78	1.23	0.54
24	5.3	3.8	0.01	1.32	1.20	0.51
28	4.7	3.2	0.05	2.90	1.24	0.51

The test for the presence of the system is the approximation of $\text{Eh} + 0.0885 \log \text{Mn}^{++} + 0.236 \text{ pH}$ to 1.42 under varying Eh , pH and Mn^{++} activity. Table 6 shows that the soils high in Mn or low in Fe (Soils 3, 4, 7, 26, 27) gave Eo 's not appreciably different from

erates.

The manganese systems, $\text{Mn}(\text{OH})_3\text{-Mn}^{++}$, $\text{Mn}(\text{OH})_3\text{-Mn}_3\text{O}_4$, $\text{Mn}(\text{OH})_3\text{-MnCO}_3$, $\text{Mn}_3\text{O}_4\text{-Mn}^{++}$, and $\text{Mn}_3\text{O}_4\text{-MnCO}_3$, appear to control the redox potentials of flooded soils relatively high in manganese and low in iron.

CARBONATE EQUILIBRIA IN FLOODED SOILS

Last year (Annual Report, 1964), the tremendous role that carbon dioxide plays in mineral equilibria in flooded soils was stressed, and theoretical equations to describe the effects of CO_2 on the pH and redox potentials of reduced soils were derived. This year the theoretical treatment of aqueous carbonate equilibria was elaborated, the validity of the theoretical equations was tested experimentally with pure systems, and the equations were used to identify the carbonate systems in flooded soils.

The $\text{Na}_2\text{CO}_3\text{-H}_2\text{O-CO}_2$ system

The partial pressure of carbon dioxide (PCO_2) markedly influences the pH values of sodic soils. Although this fact was recognized and the empirical

relationship, $\text{pH} = a - b \log \text{PCO}_2$, established decades ago, no quantitative theoretical explanation was offered. In these laboratories it was found that the pH decrease of several units caused by flooding a sodic soil can be explained almost quantitatively in terms of the $\text{Na}_2\text{CO}_3\text{-H}_2\text{O-CO}_2$ system.

Using the equilibria

the expression was derived:

$$[\text{H}^+] = \frac{K_1[\text{H}_2\text{CO}_3] \pm \sqrt{K_1^2[\text{H}_2\text{CO}_3]^2 + 8\text{Na}K_1K_2[\text{H}_2\text{CO}_3]}}{2[\text{Na}^+]}$$

Because $8 \text{Na}K_1K_2[\text{H}_2\text{CO}_3]$ is negligible cf with $K_1^2[\text{H}_2\text{CO}_3]^2$ for $[\text{Na}^+]$ not exceeding 10^{-2} M and PCO_2 in the range 0.01 to 1.0 atmospheres,

$$\begin{aligned} [\text{H}^+][\text{Na}^+] &= K_1[\text{H}_2\text{CO}_3] \\ &= K_1 k \text{PCO}_2 \end{aligned}$$

Correcting for activity coefficients, we have

$$\frac{(\text{H}^+)}{\gamma_{\text{H}^+}} [\text{Na}^+] = \frac{K_1}{\gamma_{\text{H}^+} \gamma_{\text{HCO}_3^-}} k \text{PCO}_2$$

or $\text{pH} = \text{p}K_1 + \text{pk} + \log [\text{Na}^+] - \log \text{PCO}_2 + \log \gamma_{\text{HCO}_3^-}$

Fig. 2. Relationship between pH and PCO_2 of aqueous sodium carbonate solutions.

i.e.

$$\text{pH} = \text{p}K_1 + \text{p}k + \log[\text{Na}^+] - \log P\text{CO}_2 - 0.51\sqrt{\mu}$$

or

$$\text{pH} = 4.82 - \log P\text{CO}_2 \text{ for } 10^{-3} \text{ N Na}_2\text{CO}_3$$

and

$$\text{pH} = 5.79 - \log P\text{CO}_2 \text{ for } 10^{-2} \text{ N Na}_2\text{CO}_3$$

(assuming complete dissociation of the salt).

To test the validity of the theoretical equations, 10^{-2} and 10^{-3} N Na_2CO_3 solutions were equilibrated with CO_2 - N_2 mixtures whose composition was previously determined by gas chromatography. The regressions of pH on $P\text{CO}_2$ (Fig. 2) were:

$$\text{pH} = 4.84 - 1.00 \log P\text{CO}_2 \quad (0.0005 \text{ M Na}_2\text{CO}_3)$$

$$\text{pH} = 5.79 - 1.03 \log P\text{CO}_2 \quad (0.005 \text{ M Na}_2\text{CO}_3)$$

To test the effect of the ionic strength

Soil only	pH = 6.06 - 0.87 log $P\text{CO}_2$	$r = 0.997^{**}$
Soil + 0.01 M NaHCO_3	pH = 6.17 - 0.95 log $P\text{CO}_2$	$r = 0.995^{**}$
Soil + 0.01 M Na_2CO_3	pH = 6.28 - 0.95 log $P\text{CO}_2$	$r = 0.998^{**}$

compared with the following theoretical equations:

$$0.01 \text{ M NaHCO}_3 \quad \text{pH} = 5.79 - \log P\text{CO}_2$$

$$0.01 \text{ M Na}_2\text{CO}_3 \quad \text{pH} = 6.11 - \log P\text{CO}_2$$

Since the variation of the pH of an alkali soil with $P\text{CO}_2$ is not dependent

Aerobic soil only	pH = 6.14 - 0.85 log $P\text{CO}_2$	$r = -0.998^{**}$
Aerobic soil + 0.01 M NaHCO_3	pH = 6.19 - 0.85 log $P\text{CO}_2$	$r = -0.998^{**}$
Aerobic soil + 0.01 M Na_2CO_3	pH = 6.34 - 0.87 log $P\text{CO}_2$	$r = -0.999^{**}$

The small deviations may be due to differences in ionic strengths between the anaerobic and aerobic treatments.

It was concluded that the pH values of sodic soils is controlled by the partial pressure of CO_2 through the Na_2CO_3 - H_2O - CO_2 equilibrium and is described approximately by the equation

0.001 N Na_2CO_3 (without CaCO_3)	:	pH = 4.84 - 1.00 log $P\text{CO}_2$
0.001 N Na_2CO_3 (with CaCO_3)	:	pH = 5.95 - 0.72 log $P\text{CO}_2$
0.01 N Na_2CO_3 (without CaCO_3)	:	pH = 5.79 - 1.03 log $P\text{CO}_2$
0.01 N Na_2CO_3 (with CaCO_3)	:	pH = 6.00 - 0.91 log $P\text{CO}_2$

on the pH of the Na_2CO_3 - H_2O - CO_2 system over a wider range of ionic strength than in the two preceding instances, 0.0005 M Na_2CO_3 was equilibrated with CO_2 at 0.023 atmospheres in 0.0 to 0.1 molar NaCl. Fig. 3 shows a straight line for the plot of pH on $\sqrt{\mu}$ with a gradient approaching 0.5 and an intercept of 6.78 (4.84 - -1.94) as required by the equation,

$$\text{pH} = 4.84 - \log P\text{CO}_2 - 0.5 \sqrt{\mu}$$

The applicability of the equation

$$\text{pH} = 7.84 + \log \text{Na}^+ - \log P\text{CO}_2 - 0.51 \sqrt{\mu}$$

to reduced soils was tested with the soil with the highest pH available in our collection — a slightly saline alkali soil with an aerobic pH of 8.4. The soil was incubated anaerobically with and without 0.01 M NaHCO_3 and Na_2CO_3 and equilibrated with CO_2 - N_2 mixtures ranging from 0.1 to 100%. The regressions of pH on log $P\text{CO}_2$ were:

on soil reduction but on CO_2 accumulation, the aerobic soil should behave similarly, as the following regressions for the same soil without anaerobic incubation show:

$$\text{pH} = 7.84 + \log \text{Na}^+ - \log P\text{CO}_2 - 0.5 \sqrt{\mu}$$

The slightly higher values of the constant "a" and the lower values of "b" in the observed regressions may be due to CaCO_3 , as shown below:

From the practical standpoint, the decrease in pH of alkali soils caused by flooding can be accentuated by the incorporation of organic matter. Organic matter, not iron salts, may be the remedy for iron deficiency on flooded alkali rice soils.

The $\text{MCO}_3\text{-H}_2\text{O-CO}_2$ systems

The partial pressure of CO_2 deter-

$$\begin{aligned} \text{pH} &= \frac{2}{3} (\text{pk} + \text{pK}_1) + \frac{1}{3} (\log 2 + \text{pK}_2 - \text{pK}_3) - \frac{2}{3} \log P_{\text{CO}_2} + \frac{1}{3} (\log \gamma_{\text{HCO}_3^-} - \log \gamma_{\text{M}^{++}}) \\ \text{pH} - \frac{1}{2} \text{pM}^{++} &= \frac{2}{3} (\text{pk} + \text{pK}_1 + \text{pK}_2 - \text{pK}_3) - \frac{2}{3} \log P_{\text{CO}_2} \\ \text{pM}^{++} &= \frac{2}{3} (\text{pk} + \text{pK}_1 - \text{pK}_2 - \text{pK}_3) + \frac{2}{3} \log 2 - \frac{2}{3} \log P_{\text{CO}_2} + \frac{2}{3} (\log \gamma_{\text{HCO}_3^-} - \log \gamma_{\text{M}^{++}}) \end{aligned}$$

For the $\text{CaCO}_3\text{-H}_2\text{O-CO}_2$ system the equations reduce to:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{pH} &= 6.00 - \frac{2}{3} \log P_{\text{CO}_2} + \frac{1}{3} (\log \gamma_{\text{HCO}_3^-} - \log \gamma_{\text{Ca}^{++}}) \\ \text{pH} + \frac{1}{2} \log \text{Ca}^{++} &= 4.92 - \frac{2}{3} \log P_{\text{CO}_2} \\ \log (\text{Ca}^{++}) &= -2.15 + \frac{1}{3} \log P_{\text{CO}_2} - \frac{2}{3} \sqrt{\mu} \end{aligned}$$

The corresponding equations for the $\text{MnCO}_3\text{-H}_2\text{O-CO}_2$ system are:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{pH} &= 5.42 - \frac{2}{3} \log P_{\text{CO}_2} - \frac{1}{3} (\log \gamma_{\text{HCO}_3^-} - \log \gamma_{\text{Mn}^{++}}) \\ \text{pH} + \frac{1}{2} \log \text{Mn}^{++} &= 4.02 - \frac{2}{3} \log P_{\text{CO}_2} \\ \log (\text{Mn}^{++}) &= -2.80 + \frac{1}{3} \log P_{\text{CO}_2} - \frac{2}{3} \sqrt{\mu} \end{aligned}$$

These equations show that, at constant temperature, the partial pressure of CO_2 uniquely determines the pH, the hydroxide potential, and the activity of M^{++} as required by the phase rule for a three-phase, three-component system.

To test the validity of these expressions, aqueous suspensions of CaCO_3 and MnCO_3 were equilibrated with CO_2 at several partial pressures at 25 C and pH, and the concentrations of Ca^{++} and Mn^{++} determined. The results are

summarized and discussed below: pH was a linear function of $\log P_{\text{CO}_2}$ with a slope of approximately 0.67 (Fig. 4). The regressions were:

The following equations were derived to describe these equilibria:

summarized and discussed below:

pH was a linear function of $\log P_{\text{CO}_2}$ with a slope of approximately 0.67 (Fig. 4). The regressions were:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{CaCO}_3: \quad \text{pH} &= 6.02 - 0.67 \log P_{\text{CO}_2} \\ \text{MnCO}_3: \quad \text{pH} &= 5.40 - 0.66 \log P_{\text{CO}_2} \end{aligned}$$

The close agreement of the intercepts and the slope with the theoretical values, in spite of the omission of the correction for activity coefficients, is due to its small value — 0.01 to 0.05 for

Fig. 3. Influences of ionic strength of the solution on the pH value of 0.0005M Na_2CO_3 equilibrated with 0.023 atmosphere CO_2 .

CaCO_3 in the PCO_2 range 0.03 to 100%. The $\text{MgCO}_3\text{-H}_2\text{O-CO}_2$ system gave a regression that deviated from the theoretical because of the high activity coefficient error caused by its greater ionic

Fig. 4. Influence of PCO_2 on the pH values of aqueous divalent carbonate systems.

Soil no.	pH	O.M. %	State	$\text{pH} = f(\text{PCO}_2)$	
1	7.6	2.3	reduced	$\text{pH} = 6.36 - 0.62 \log \text{PCO}_2$	
17	7.0	1.8	reduced	$\text{pH} = 6.32 - 0.62 \log \text{PCO}_2$	
26	7.6	1.5	reduced	$\text{pH} = 6.24 - 0.76 \log \text{PCO}_2$	
26	7.6	1.5	non-reduced	$\text{pH} = 6.13 - 0.71 \log \text{PCO}_2$	
Soil no.	$\text{pH} + \frac{1}{2} \log \text{Ca}^{++} + \frac{1}{2} \log \text{PCO}_2$		$\log \text{Ca}^{++} - \frac{1}{3} \log \text{PCO}_2 + \frac{2}{3} \sqrt{\mu}$		
1	5.21 ± 0.02		-2.14 ± 0.02		
17	5.20 ± 0.02		-2.06 ± 0.04		
26	5.16 ± 0.02		-2.14 ± 0.02		

The $\text{pH}/\log \text{PCO}_2$ slopes are sufficiently close to 0.67 to show the presence of the $\text{CaCO}_3\text{-CO}_2\text{-H}_2\text{O}$ system but the intercepts are a little too high. This is due probably to (a) the presence of MgCO_3 , (b) the omission of the correction for activity coefficients, (c) sluggish equilibrium, and (d) the presence of calcium salts of organic acids. For the last reason, the value of the constant for the hydroxide potential and for calcium activity are also slightly

strength, as seen below:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Theoretical: } \text{pH} &= 7.11 - \frac{2}{3} \log \text{PCO}_2 \\ &\quad - \frac{1}{3} (\log \gamma_{\text{HCO}_3^-} - \log \gamma_{\text{Mg}^{++}}) \\ \text{Observed : } \text{pH} &= 7.00 - 0.68 \log \text{PCO}_2 \end{aligned}$$

A test for the validity of the equations for the hydroxide potentials is the constancy of the sum of $\text{pH} + \frac{1}{2} \log \text{M}^{++} + \frac{1}{2} \log \text{PCO}_2$ and its approximation to K over a range of PCO_2 . The observed values of K were:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{pH} + \frac{1}{2} \log \text{Ca}^{++} + \frac{1}{2} \log \text{PCO}_2 &= 4.88 \pm 0.04 \\ \text{pH} + \frac{1}{2} \log \text{Mn}^{++} + \frac{1}{2} \log \text{PCO}_2 &= 3.88 \pm 0.03 \end{aligned}$$

The closeness of these K 's to the theoretical indicates that PCO_2 uniquely determines the hydroxide potential according to the theoretical equations.

Some data reported by Frear and Johnston (1929) was used to test the validity of

$$\log (\text{Ca}^{++}) = -2.15 + \frac{1}{3} \log \text{PCO}_2 - \frac{2}{3} \sqrt{\mu}$$

The last column in Table 7 shows the remarkable constancy of K and its closeness to -2.15 over a wide range of PCO_2 .

Flooded calcareous soils behaved remarkably like the $\text{CaCO}_3\text{-H}_2\text{O-CO}_2$ system as shown below:

higher than the theoretical values of 4.92 and -2.15, respectively.

In terms of rice culture, iron deficiency on flooded calcareous soils low in organic matter can be corrected by adding organic matter to raise the partial pressure of CO_2 .

The application of similar tests for the presence of the $\text{MnCO}_3\text{-H}_2\text{O-CO}_2$ system in reduced soils gave the following results:

Soil No.	pH	Active Mn (%)	Active Fe (%)	pH = f (PCO ₂)
3	5.7	0.36	0.79	pH = 5.86 - 0.67 log PCO ₂
7	5.9	0.33	1.67	pH = 5.86 - 0.72 log PCO ₂
27	6.6	0.31	1.67	pH = 5.93 - 0.64 log PCO ₂
21	4.7	0.02	2.78	pH = 5.96 - 0.53 log PCO ₂
28	4.6	0.05	2.91	pH = 5.94 - 0.59 log PCO ₂

The soils high in Mn and low in Fe gave pH/log PCO₂ slopes of approximately 0.67 as required by the MnCO₃-H₂O-CO₂ equilibrium. The intercepts, however, were considerably higher than the theoretical. Co-precipitation of CaCO₃ with MnCO₃ or supersaturation

of the solution may explain this.

Manganous hydroxide potential and Mn⁺⁺ activity criteria also suggest the presence of the MnCO₃-H₂O-CO₂ in reduced soils high in manganese as shown below:

Soil no.	Mn %	pH + $\frac{1}{2}$ log Mn ⁺⁺ + $\frac{1}{2}$ log PCO ₂	log Mn ⁺⁺ - $\frac{1}{3}$ log PCO ₂ + $\frac{2}{3}\sqrt{\mu}$
3	0.36	4.59 ± 0.08	-2.93 ± 0.06
7	0.33	4.65 ± 0.03	-2.95 ± 0.03

TABLE 7. The influence of varying PCO₂ and calcium ion activity on the value of the expression, log (Ca⁺⁺) - $\frac{1}{3}$ log (PCO₂) + $\frac{2}{3}\sqrt{\mu} = K$

log (Ca ⁺⁺)	PCO ₂ , atm	$\frac{1}{3}$ log PCO ₂	$\frac{2}{3}\sqrt{\mu}$	K
-3.337	0.00031	-1.170	0.027	-2.14
-3.307	0.00038	-1.140	0.028	-2.14
-3.183	0.00093	-1.011	0.032	-2.14
-3.010	0.00334	-0.825	0.040	-2.15
-2.909	0.00690	-0.720	0.045	-2.14
-2.796	0.0160	-0.599	0.052	-2.15
-2.609	0.0432	-0.455	0.062	-2.14
-2.531	0.1116	-0.318	0.074	-2.14
-2.243	0.9684	-0.005	0.110	-2.13

Carbonate equilibria criteria clearly indicate that: (a) the Na₂CO₃-H₂O-CO₂ system influences the pH values of sodic soils; (b) the CaCO₃-H₂O-CO₂ system regulates the pH, hydroxide potential, and Ca⁺⁺ activity of calcareous soils; (c) the MnCO₃-H₂O-CO₂ system

influences the pH of reduced soils high in manganese. By the same criteria, no FeCO₃-H₂O-CO₂ system was detectable, thus confirming the earlier findings (Annual Report, 1964) that the Fe₃-(OH)₃-H₂O-CO₂ system determines the pH values of reduced soils high in Fe,

TABLE 8. Influence of the decrease in PCO₂ (caused by bubbling N₂) on pH and Eh of the soil solutions of three soils, ten weeks after flooding.

Duration of N ₂ bubbling (min)	Calcareous loam		Maahas clay		Luisiana clay	
	pH 7.6, O.M. 1.5%	Eh (mv)	pH 6.6, O.M. 2.0%	Eh (mv)	pH 4.6, O.M. 4.1%	Eh (mv)
0	6.70	+145	6.80	+ 4	6.99	- 45
5	7.36	+ 13	7.65	- 75	7.61	-103
10	7.80	- 73	8.00	-146	8.00	-167
15	8.09	-127	8.30	-210	8.20	-217
20	8.20	-145	8.41	-245	8.28	-275
25	8.38	-147	8.48	-274	8.32	-319
30	8.41	-161	8.50	-298	8.40	-348

especially at low PCO_2 's.

The influence of the partial pressure of CO_2 on the pH and Eh of the soil solution of reduced soils was dramatically demonstrated by bubbling pure nitrogen through them. Within 30 min-

utes, the pH of all three solutions rose to 8.4 (Table 8).

The pH values of flooded soils, determined in stirred aqueous suspensions, are subject to a positive error because of dilution and loss of CO_2 .

CHEMICAL KINETICS OF FLOODED SOILS

In the course of chemical, electrochemical and plant nutritional studies, the chemical kinetics were examined of the soil solutions of more than 200 samples of soils, ranging from an acid-sulfate soil with a pH of 2.8 to a slightly alkaline soil. The earlier findings (Annual Report, 1963, 1964) on the influence of soil properties in the course

of chemical and electrochemical changes in flooded soils were confirmed and these properties were used to explain the behavior of the rice plant on different soils. (See water regime in rice soils and physiological disorders of rice). In this section, only those features which throw new light on processes, mechanisms or interpretations are reported.

Fig. 5. Influence of $Fe(OH)_3$ and MnO_2 and late sucrose addition on the kinetics of solution of pH of anaerobic sand. A = sand + organic matter, B = (A) + $Fe(OH)_3$, C = (A) + MnO_2 .

Chemical changes in anaerobic sand culture

The interpretation of the chemical and electrochemical changes in flooded soils can be greatly simplified if the effects of soil colloids and other soil components can be separated from the reduction process. To this end, studies were made of the chemical and electrochemical changes in the aqueous phase of a mixture of sand and organic matter, with and without $\text{Fe}(\text{OH})_3$ and MnO_2 , kept submerged in pots in the greenhouse. After 16 weeks the solutions were replaced with a solution of sucrose to reactivate the apparently dormant bacteria. The results are shown in Figs. 5-11.

The pH of all three treatments first decreased, apparently because of the production of CO_2 and organic acids, and then increased gradually to fairly stable values reflecting the treatments (Fig. 5). It was highest with the $\text{Fe}(\text{OH})_3$, slightly lower with the MnO_2 , and lowest without either. Addition of sucrose, 21 weeks after submergence, markedly depressed pH. The $\text{Fe}(\text{OH})_3$ and MnO_2 treatments resumed their former pH values but the control did not. The presence of iron and manganese stabilized the pH of the anaerobic medium in the region 6.6 to 6.8.

The redox potentials were highest in the control because of low pH, and least in the $\text{Fe}(\text{OH})_3$ treatment. Sucrose de-

Fig. 6. Influence of $\text{Fe}(\text{OH})_3$, MnO_2 and late sucrose addition on the kinetics of solution Eh of anaerobic sand. (A = sand + organic matter; B = (A) + $\text{Fe}(\text{OH})_3$; C = (A) + MnO_2).

pressed sharply, though temporarily, the potentials of all three treatments (Fig. 6).

The changes in alkalinity (Fig. 7) reflected the differences in the concentration of, chiefly, bicarbonates. Peak alkalinity was highest with MnO_2 because of the ease of reduction of MnO_2 to Mn^{++} ; the subsequent decline was due probably to precipitation as MnCO_3 . Iron showed a lower peak and a slower decline. Alkalinity was least in the control because of insufficient bases. Sucrose sharply increased the concentration of HCO_3^- in the $\text{Fe}(\text{OH})_3$ and $\text{Mn}(\text{OH})_2$ because of the solvent action of CO_2 on MnCO_3 and $\text{Fe}_3(\text{OH})_8$.

The manganese and iron curves were almost replicas of the HCO_3^- curves, showing that water-soluble Fe^{++} and Mn^{++} were present almost entirely as bicarbonates. The dramatic increases of

Fig. 7. Influence of $\text{Fe}(\text{OH})_3$, MnO_2 and late sucrose addition on the kinetics of alkalinity in anaerobic sand (A = sand + organic matter; B = (A) + $\text{Fe}(\text{OH})_3$, C = (A) + MnO_2).

Fe^{++} and Mn^{++} caused by sucrose shows how readily the concentrations of water-soluble Fe and Mn respond to changes in pH and $P\text{CO}_2$ (cf Figs. 8 and 9 with Fig. 5).

Figure 10 shows the changes in concentration of water-soluble NH_3 . Because of the very low exchange capacity of the medium, water-soluble NH_3 may be equated to total inorganic NH_3 . The increase in water-soluble NH_3 following submergence is due to the release of NH_3 from the green manure and straw. MnO_2 markedly accelerated the increase

Fig. 8. Influence of $\text{Fe}(\text{OH})_3$, MnO_2 and late sucrose addition on the kinetics of water-soluble Mn^{++} in anaerobic sand.

apparently by hastening oxidation and by producing a higher and favorable pH for ammonification than in the acid control. The marked decrease in NH_3 following the peak may be attributed to (a) sampling losses and (b) nitrifica-

Fig. 9. Influence of $\text{Fe}(\text{OH})_3$, MnO_2 and late sucrose addition on the kinetics of water-soluble Fe^{++} in anaerobic sand.

tion following diffusion to the surface. The increase in NH_3 after the addition of sucrose may be due to the resurgence of bacterial activity.

Figure 11 shows the high (though temporary) contribution that organic matter can make to water-soluble phosphorus in anaerobic media. The rapid decline in P, following the peak, may

Fig. 10. Influence of $\text{Fe}(\text{OH})_3$, MnO_2 and late sucrose addition on the kinetics of water-soluble NH_3 in anaerobic sand.

be due to precipitation caused by the increase in pH. Both $\text{Fe}(\text{OH})_3$ and MnO_2 depressed the concentration of water-soluble P. Sucrose caused a slight temporary increase in water-soluble P in the $\text{Fe}(\text{OH})_3$ treatment.

Effects of addition of organic matter to reduced soils

The chemical kinetics of flooded soils shows that within a few weeks of submergence, most soils go through a period of intense biological activity characterized by soil reduction and the production of CO_2 , Fe^{++} , Mn^{++} , and organic reduction products in high concentrations. The peak of chemical activity is followed by a relatively steady state which lasts for months (Annual Report, 1963, 1964). This condition is

Fig. 11. Influence of $\text{Fe}(\text{OH})_3$, MnO_2 and late sucrose addition on the kinetics of water-soluble P in anaerobic sand + organic matter.

good for the rice plant. But little is known of the consequences of incorporating organic matter to a soil in the reduced state. Because organic matter may be added to reduced soils (a) during intercultivation of flooded soils and (b) in continuous rice culture, the chemical and electrochemical effects of adding organic matter (1% sucrose) to 17 reduced soils were investigated in the greenhouse.

The response to the addition of sucrose was a sharp burst of bacterial activity resulting in a decrease in Eh, sharp increases in PCO_2 , HCO_3^- , the concentration of Fe^{++} , and organic reduction products, followed by resumption of the quiescent state. Some of these changes in an acid (Soil 14) and a neutral soil (Soil 17) are shown in Figs. 12 and 13. For these reasons, the incorporation of readily decomposable

TABLE 9. The influence of soil properties on the kinetics of NO_3^- (ppm N) in the soil solution of eight soils treated with 0.15% of a mixture of dry straw and green manure and kept flooded in pots in the greenhouse.

Soil no.	pH	O.M. (%)	Weeks submerged				
			0	1	2	3	4
1	7.6	2.3	680	5	0	0	0
26	7.6	1.5	160	1	0	0	0
17	7.0	1.8	107	0	0	0	0
27	6.6	2.0	496	1	1	0	0
9	6.0	4.0	600	9	3	0	0
23	5.7	8.0	1220	813	310	122	12
14	4.6	2.8	310	192	84	19	2

Fig. 12. Influence of flooding and late sucrose addition on some chemical changes in an acid soil.

organic matter into reduced soils is harmful to rice.

Kinetics of denitrification

The soils used in the study of chemical kinetics had unusually high amounts of nitrate because they had been stored indoors in a moist state for several months. These soils enabled us to study (a) the influence of soil properties on denitrification, (b) the influence of nitrate on other chemical changes, and (c) the reaction kinetics of denitrification.

Table 9 shows that nitrate disappeared rapidly in the nearly neutral soils, whereas it persisted in the two most acid soils for 4 weeks. The roughly exponential decrease in concentration of NO_3^- with time suggested the kinetics of a first order reaction. The linear regression of $\log(\text{NO}_3^-)$ on time (Fig. 14) as required by the equation,

$$\log(\text{NO}_3^-) = \log(\text{NO}_3^-)_0 - kt,$$

confirmed that the disappearance of nitrate is a first order reaction, at least in the early stages. The kinetics of the reaction for five soils high in nitrate can be described by the following equations:

$$\text{Soil No. 25: } \log(\text{NO}_3^-) = -1.37 - 1.96 t$$

$$\text{Soil No. 9: } \log(\text{NO}_3^-) = -1.44 - 1.17 t$$

$$\text{Soil No. 24: } \log(\text{NO}_3^-) = -1.99 - 0.94 t$$

$$\text{Soil No. 23: } \log(\text{NO}_2^-) = -1.16 - 0.39 t$$

$$\text{Soil No. 14: } \log(\text{NO}_3^-) = -1.14 - 0.35 t$$

Conformity of the kinetics of denitrification (the first and limiting step of which apparently is reduction of nitrate to nitrite) to that of a first order reaction suggests that the reductant was available in unlimited amounts. The velocity constant, however, varied with the soil, indicating a varying catalytic role for the soil, apparently associated with pH.

Fig. 13. Influence of flooding and late sucrose application on some chemical changes in a neutral soil.

TABLE 10. Influence of NO_3^- on the partial pressure of CO_2 (atm) in flooded soils.

Soil no.	pH	O.M. (%)	NO_3^- -N ^a (ppm)	Weeks submerged					
				1	2	3	4	6	8
3	5.7	1.3	324	0.92	0.66	0.45	0.31	0.23	0.13
4	6.9	2.0	6	0.16	0.19	0.14	0.10	0.10	0.08
14	4.6	2.8	310	0.28	0.50	0.51	0.59	0.71	0.81
21	4.6	4.1	3	0.61	0.44	0.13	0.09	0.10	0.10

^a 1 week after flooding.

Influence of nitrate on chemical kinetics

Nitrate profoundly influenced the chemical and electrochemical changes in flooded soils. It retarded the decrease in Eh, increase in pH, and the reduction of iron (Fig. 15), but caused a build-up of high partial pressures of CO_2 (Table 10). The high partial pressure of CO_2 apparently was due to (a) increased CO_2 production caused by nitrate respiration and (b) insufficient Fe^{++} and Mn^{++} to remove it as bicarbonates or carbonates.

Kinetics of water-soluble sulfate

The changes in concentration of water-soluble SO_4^{--} varied markedly with soil properties. The neutral and alkali soils (Fig. 16, Soils 1, 26, 39), regardless of the initial SO_4^{--} content, lost SO_4^{--} rapidly and contained less than 20 ppm 4 weeks after flooding. By contrast, the acid soils (Fig. 16, Soil 14, 21, 23) showed first an appreciable increase in water-soluble SO_4^{--} followed by a slower decrease to a final concentration of about 1 ppm 16 weeks after flooding. In the acid-sulfate soil,

Fig. 14. Kinetics of denitrification in four flooded soils.

SO₄²⁻ declined steadily from 12,000 ppm at flooding to 5,000 ppm 16 weeks later.

The rapid disappearance of sulfate in the slightly alkaline soils confirms earlier findings that a high pH favors sulfate reduction. The slight increase in water-soluble SO₄²⁻ in the acid soils in the early stages of flooding may be ascribed to release of SO₄²⁻ from anion exchange sites as pH increased, and the subsequent decrease to sulfate reduction. The presence of NO₃⁻ in soil No. 14 apparently delayed both the release of SO₄²⁻ by anion exchange and its subsequent loss by reduction.

Sulfate reduction appears to be a first order reaction described by the following equations:

Soil no.	pH	Equation
1	7.6	log (SO ₄ ²⁻) = -2.48 - 0.48 t
39	8.1	log (SO ₄ ²⁻) = -2.14 - 0.44 t
26	7.6	log (SO ₄ ²⁻) = -3.34 - 0.36 t
23	5.7	log (SO ₄ ²⁻) = -2.57 - 0.17 t
35	2.8	log (SO ₄ ²⁻) = -0.91 - 0.018 t

The velocity constants for the slightly alkaline soils are more than double that for the acid soil and several hundred times that of the extremely acid soil.

Fig. 15. Influence of NO₃⁻ on the kinetics of Eh and pH in two soils.

The kinetics of water-soluble Fe⁺⁺ and Mn⁺⁺

The concentrations of Fe⁺⁺ and Mn⁺⁺ in the soil solution of flooded soils show an apparently logarithmic increase followed by a roughly exponential decrease. The logarithmic increase is due to the activities of proliferating bacteria, while the exponential decrease appeared to be caused by precipitation reaction (Annual Report, 1964). The kinetics of the decrease in the concentration of Fe⁺⁺ and Mn⁺⁺ in the soil solution was studied to ascertain the nature of the precipitation reactions.

Figure 17 shows (a) the kinetics of water-soluble iron in sand, Fe(OH)₃, organic matter, and water incubated anaerobically and (b) the regression of log (Fe⁺⁺) on t. Clearly, the decrease in concentration of Fe⁺⁺ is a first order reaction. But the kinetics of Fe⁺⁺ in soil solutions appeared to be that of

Fig. 16. Influence of soil properties on sulfate reduction in flooded soils.

Fig. 17. Kinetics of water-soluble Fe⁺⁺ in anaerobic sand + 0.1% Fe₂O₃ + organic matter.

Fig. 18. Kinetics of water-soluble Fe⁺⁺ in two flooded soils.

Fig. 19. Kinetics of water-soluble Mn⁺⁺ in anaerobic sand + MnO₂ + organic matter.

a first order reaction with different velocity constants for the steep and the level phases of the precipitation curve (Fig. 18).

The kinetics of the decrease in con-

centration of water-soluble Mn in sand, organic matter, MnO_2 and water incubated anaerobically was that of a two-phase first order reaction (Fig. 19).

ORGANIC COMPONENTS OF ANAEROBIC SOIL SOLUTIONS

Water-soluble organic substances that readily reduce $KMnO_4$ are present in flooded soils (Annual Report, 1964). Some of them compete with rice roots for oxygen; others may poison the rice plant directly. A knowledge of the nature and kinetics of these substances may help the study of physiological disorders of rice caused by reduction products.

The following substances or classes of substances in the soil solutions of six flooded soils were identified by gas, column, and paper chromatography or chemical tests.

- (a) volatile substances: mercaptans; primary and secondary amines; formic, acetic, propionic and butyric acids; and acetaldehyde and acetone;
- (b) non-volatile substances: the amino acids, glycine, sarcosine, alanine, leucine, valine, serine, phosphoserine, threonine, aspartic acid, glutamic acid, asparagine, cystine, methionine, cystathionine, phenylalanine, tyrosine, proline, and β -amino isobutyric acid; and the sugars, arabinose, xylose, ribose, glucose, fructose, galactose, mannose, sucrose, cellobiose and raffinose.

Also, the soil solution of Tungshan silt loam — a soil on which a physiological disease of rice occurs — was rela-

tively high in mercaptans, amines, fatty acids, and sugars.

The volatile organic components of anaerobic soils

The bad odor of strongly reduced soils, commonly attributed to H_2S , may be the combined effect of a variety of volatile organic substances and H_2S . Because soils with a putrefactive odor are often toxic to rice, an attempt was made to separate, identify, and follow the kinetics of the volatile components of the soil solutions of six soils treated with 0.5 percent straw and green manure and kept submerged in pots in the greenhouse.

The volatile components were swept out with nitrogen, assisted by heat when necessary, and trapped in suitable solutions. The entrapped substances were freed, identified, and quantitatively determined by a combination of gas liquid chromatography and microchemical tests. Because H_2S is a toxic product of the anaerobic decomposition of organic matter, it was also determined along with mercaptans, amines, fatty acids, aldehydes, and ketones.

Hydrogen sulfide. In all soils, except the calcareous loam, the concentration of H_2S increased on flooding, reached a maximum 2 weeks later, and decreased to practically zero after 8 weeks (Table 11). Castañas clay, an acid-sul-

TABLE 11. The kinetics of H_2S (ppm) in the soil solution of six flooded soils.

Soil	pH	O.M. %	Weeks submerged					
			1	2	3	4	6	8
Luisiana clay	4.7	2.9	0.00	0.06	0.02	0.03	0.01	0.00
Casiguran sandy loam	4.8	4.4	0.04	0.05	0.04	0.02	0.02	0.01
Maahas clay	6.6	2.0	0.01	0.02	0.01	0.02	0.00	0.00
Calcareous loam	7.6	1.1	0.00	0.00	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.00
Castañas clay	2.8	5.3	0.09	0.39	0.05	0.24	0.03	0.02
Tungshan silt loam	5.8	3.4	0.00	0.05	0.01	0.03	0.00	0.00

TABLE 12. The kinetics of mercaptans (expressed as ppm C_2H_5SH) in the soil solutions of five flooded soils.

Soil	Weeks submerged					
	0	1	2	3	4	5
Luisiana clay	0.03	1.23	0.21	0.17	0.03	0.00
Casiguran sandy loam ^a	0.09	0.44	0.05	0.21	0.14	0.07
Maahas clay	—	—	0.02	0.19	0.03	0.00
Calcareous loam	0.05	0.42	1.15	0.08	0.07	0.12
Castañas clay	0.05	0.40	0.43	0.20	0.15	0.10
Tungshan silt loam	0.13	2.10	0.35	0.29	0.05	0.05

^a Contained 4.75 ppm, 3 days after flooding.

fate soil, had the highest concentration; the calcareous loam, the lowest. None of the soils had an H_2S concentration lethal to rice.

Mercaptans. Methyl and ethyl mercaptans were detected in the soil solutions of all six soils within an hour of flooding. Because Casiguran sandy loam had a strong odor soon after flooding, it was sampled on the third day and found to contain nearly 5 ppm mercaptans in the soil solution, compared with only 0.01 ppm H_2S . Apparently mercaptans gave this soil its bad odor.

Like H_2S , mercaptans gave concentration peaks within 2 weeks of flooding and then declined (Table 12) but showed no marked kinetic differences among the soils. Tungshan silt loam had the highest content of mercaptans both one hour and a week after flooding,

Amines. Unlike H_2S and the mercaptans, the amines tend to increase in concentration with duration of submergence (Table 13). Tungshan silt loam—the problem soil from Taiwan—had the highest concentration of amines throughout submergence; the calcareous loam had the lowest.

Fig. 20. Kinetics of acetate in the soil solutions of four submerged soils.

Volatile fatty acids. Of all the volatile organic components of the soil solution examined, fatty acids were found in the highest concentration in all soils

TABLE 13. Kinetics of amines (as ppm CH_3NH_2) in the soil solutions of six flooded soils.

Soil	Weeks submerged							
	0	1	2	4	6	8	10	12
Luisiana clay	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.15	0.18	0.05	0.41	0.40
Casiguran sandy loam	0.00	0.00	0.03	0.06	0.00	0.15	0.36	0.21
Maahas clay	0.00	0.01	0.03	0.03	0.00	0.04	0.02	0.15
Calcareous loam	0.02	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.01	0.09
Castañas clay	0.07	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.16	0.00	0.28
Tungshan silt loam	0.25	0.68	0.13	0.14	0.37	0.20	0.89	0.50

at all sampling times. Acetic acid constituted the bulk of the acids, with concentrations ranging from 1 to 10 millimoles/liter; propionic acid was next with a range of 0 to 0.4 mm/liter. At no time did the concentration of formic acid exceed 0.1 mm/liter, and butyric acid was hardly detectable at any time in any of the six soils.

The concentration of acetic acid increased on flooding, reached a peak 1 to 2 weeks after flooding, and then declined (Fig. 20). Propionic acid declined rapidly in all soils from about 0.4 mm/liter at flooding to practically none a week later. Formic acid kinetics generally followed the acetate pattern, though at concentrations of about 1 percent of the acetate.

From the ecological standpoint, acetate was present in Luisiana clay and Casiguran loam in concentrations that might be toxic to seedlings during the first 2 weeks of flooding.

Aldehydes and ketones. Acetone and acetaldehyde were identified among the carbonyls. Acetone was detected in all soils except the acid-sulfate soil from submergence to 5 weeks later.

Sugars and amino acids in the soil solutions of flooded soils

Sugars, amino acids, and humic acids are important non-volatile organic components in the solution of flooded soils. Because sugars and amino acids are readily metabolized by bacteria and

may produce an oxygen stress on rice roots, an attempt was made to identify and semi-quantitatively assay the sugars and amino acids in the solutions of six soils treated with a 0.5 percent mixture of straw and *Glyricidia maculata* (1:1) and kept flooded in pots in the greenhouse.

Table 14 shows that arabinose, glucose, fructose and the trisaccharide, raffinose, were present in all soils, especially at the start of flooding. They tended to disappear later. A week after flooding, the highest concentration of sugars was observed in Tungshan silt loam.

The amino acids in the soil solution were separated and quantitatively determined by elution chromatography of samples where this procedure was possible; with others, paper chromatography was used.

Of the 18 amino acids detected (Table 15), the following were relatively abundant in all soils at flooding: alanine, leucine, valine, serine, phosphoserine, threonine, asparagine, methionine, tyrosine and proline.

The total amino acid concentration was highest in Tungshan silt loam followed by the calcareous loam, and least in Casiguran sandy loam.

Submergence caused a decrease in the concentration of amino acids in all soils. Alanine, serine, methionine and phenylalanine seemed the more stable amino acids in flooded soils.

TABLE 14. The distribution of sugars in the soil solutions of four flooded soils at three sampling times.

Sugar	Luisiana clay			Casiguran loam			Maahas clay			Tungshan loam		
	Weeks submerged											
	0	1	2	0	0.5	1	0	1	2	0	1	2
Arabinose	4 ^a	1	1	2	2	3	0	1	0	0	2	0
Xylose	0 ^b	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	2	0
Ribose	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	0
Glucose	4	1	1	0	1	3	4	1	1	4	2	0
Fructose	4	1	1	2	0	3	4	0	0	2	2	0
Galactose	0	1	0	2	1	0	0	0	0	0	2	0
Mannose	4	1	1	2	0	3	4	0	0	2	2	0
Sucrose	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	2	0	0
Maltose	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Cellobiose	0	2	0	2	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0
Raffinose	3	0	0	3	0	0	3	0	0	3	0	0

^a 4 = highest relative concentration.

^b 0 = not detected.

TABLE 15. Distribution of amino acids in the soil solutions of five flooded soils.

Amino acid	Luisiana clay pH 4.6, O.M. 2.8%			Casiguran loam pH 4.8, O.M. 4.3%			Tungshan silt loam pH 5.8, O.M. 3.4% Weeks submerged			Maahas clay pH 6.6, O.M. 2.0%			Calcareous loam pH 7.5, O.M. 1.1%					
	0	7	14	0	7	14	0	7	14	0	7	14	0	7	14			
Glycine	T ^a	+	+	+	0.14	0	+	1.98	0.00	0	+	0.04	0	0	T ^a	+	0	0
Sarcosine	0.00	0.00	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.32	0.00	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00	0.00	0	0
α & β Alanine	1.26	+	0	+	0.34	+	0	6.18	+	+	+	0.37	+	+	2.43	+	0	0
Leucine	1.03	+	+	+	0.14	+	0	2.22	0.00	+	0	0.29	+	0	1.60	+	0	+
Valine	1.34	0.00	0	0	T	0	0	3.55	0.65	+	+	1.05	0	0	3.08	0.00	0	0
Serine	0.75	0.04	+	+	0.24	+	+	1.81	+	+	+	0.27	+	+	1.62	+	0	+
Phosphoserine	0.17	0.00	0	0	0.27	0	0	0.44	0.00	0	0	0.33	0	0	0.38	0.00	0	0
Threonine	0.06	+	0	0	0.24	0	0	5.64	0.00	0	0	0.62	0	0	3.97	0.00	0	0
Aspartic acid	0.06	0.08	+	+	0.13	0	0	1.39	0.00	0	0	0.27	0	+	T	0.00	0	0
Glutamic acid	T	+	+	+	T	0	+	5.84	0.00	0	0	0.68	0	0	T	+	0	0
Asparagine	0.65	+	+	+	0.04	0	+	1.24	0.00	0	0	0.22	0	+	T	+	0	0
Cystine	0.00	0.00	+	+	0.00	0	+	0.00	+	0	+	0.00	0	+	0.00	2.21	0	0
Methionine	1.18	+	+	+	0.11	+	0	1.59	+	+	+	0.37	+	+	1.56	0.05	0	+
Cystathionine	0.00	0.00	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.21	0.00	0	+	0.00	0	0	0.00	0.00	0	0
Phenylalanine	0.00	+	0	0	0.42	+	+	+	+	0	0	0.00	0	0	T	0.47	0	+
Tyrosine	1.42	0.93	0	0	1.93	0.13	0	3.53	+	+	+	0.00	+	+	2.27	2.34	0	0
Proline	1.28	0.00	0	0	T	0.00	0	3.89	0	0	0	0.48	0	0	3.95	0.00	0	0
β -amino isobutyric acid	0.00	0.00	0	0	0.00	0.00	0	0.00	0	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00	0.48	0	0

^a Figures (ppm) and T (trace) refer to elution chromatography.

+ means present.

0 means not detected by paper chromatography.

WATER REGIME IN FLOODED SOILS

In efforts to unravel the chemical benefits of flooding rice soils, further investigations were made in the greenhouse on chemical simulation of some of the presumed benefits of flooding and attempts were made in an outdoor drum study, to achieve some of them by a partially saturated profile.

Confirmation was obtained of earlier findings (Annual Report, 1964) that rice grows luxuriantly in a soil at field capacity if extra available iron, phosphorus and silicon are present, but suffers a setback in the reproductive phase because of the absence of factors associated with saturation of the soil with water. It was found that one of these factors was sufficient available iron;

another, apparently, was prevention of manganese toxicity (only in acid soils).

Chemical simulation of some of the benefits of flooding rice soils

The experiments described in last year's annual report were repeated but an additional treatment was included. Of those soils at field capacity and receiving FeEDTA, CaHPO₄, and silica gel, half were flooded 4 weeks before panicle primordia initiation.

Late flooding markedly increased the grain yield on all soils and, in addition, straw yield on Luisiana clay, compared with the same chemical treatments

TABLE 16. Effects of chemicals and three water treatments on the growth and yield of Peta and the chemical composition of its straw, on three soils in the greenhouse.

Treatment	Tillers (number)	Panicles	Straw (g/pot)	Grain (g/pot)	Spikelets (number)	Fe (ppm)	Mn (ppm)	SiO ₂ (%)	P (%)
Luisiana clay, pH 4.6, O.M. 3.8%									
1. Field capacity (FC)	53.2	41.0	272	66.8	4365	130	1070	5.5	0.035
2. FC+Fe+P+Si	81.0	60.2	349	77.8	5480	110	1040	5.2	0.083
3. (2)+late flood ^a	75.8	60.5	470	105.4	7445	250	445	5.1	0.111
4. Continuous flood	27.5	26.0	275	63.1	6263	325	310	6.3	0.053
Maahas clay, pH 6.6, O.M. 2.0%									
1. Field capacity	52.5	38.8	336	72.8	5516	37	82	6.4	0.107
2. FC+Fe+P+Si	56.5	38.2	389	72.0	5903	48	66	7.2	0.144
3. (2)+late flood	52.8	35.8	320	112.0	6788	80	520	8.7	0.118
4. Continuous flood	57.4	47.2	392	130.6	7466	125	430	8.0	0.143
Calcareous loam, pH 7.6, O.M. 1.5%									
1. Field capacity	All plants died of acute Fe deficiency								
2. FC+Fe+P+Si	38.0	24.8	204	69.4	3904	35	120	8.6	0.120
3. (2)+late flood	46.5	28.5	195	89.4	4867	56	235	6.5	0.120
4. Continuous flood	43.2	34.8	241	99.0	5936	87	280	6.8	0.122

^a 4 weeks before panicle primordia initiation.

TABLE 17. Association between visual Fe deficiency symptoms and the content of Fe (on dry basis) in the topmost fully emerged leaf of Chianung 242, at panicle primordia initiation.

Treatment	Luisiana clay		Casiguran loam		Maahas clay	
	pH 4.7, Fe (ppm)	O.M. 3.8% Fe deficiency symptoms	pH 4.8, Fe (ppm)	O.M. 4.4% Fe deficiency symptoms	pH 6.6, Fe (ppm)	O.M. 2.0% Fe deficiency symptoms
1. Field capacity (FC)	79	faint	100	none	63	clear
2. FC+Fe+ P+Si	109	none	95	none	58	clear
3. Submerged	135	none	115	none	112	none

maintained at field capacity (Table 16, cf treatments 3 & 2). The benefits were associated with a higher concentration of Fe in the straw on all soils, and on Luisiana clay, a higher content of P and a lower content of Mn in the straw.

The benefits of late flooding appeared to be the chemical effects of anaerobiosis rather than the effect of excess water *per se*, for the difference

in soil moisture tension between a soil at field capacity and a saturated soil is of the order 10 to 20 millibars.

Although analyses revealed lower Fe concentrations in the straw from soils at field capacity, no foliar symptoms of Fe deficiency were visible with Peta, an *indica*, except on the calcareous soil at field capacity (Fig. 21) where the plants without added Fe died of acute

Fig. 21. Either flooding or the addition of iron corrected iron deficiency on this calcareous soil. Left to right: soil at field capacity, field capacity + FeEDTA daily, flooded.

Fe deficiency. But when the experiment was repeated with Maahas and Luisiana clays in the wet season of 1965, Chianung 242, a ponlai, exhibited, at the time of panicle primordia initiation, clear Fe deficiency symptoms on Maahas clay at field capacity even with added FeEDTA; faint symptoms of deficiency were also shown on Luisiana clay at field capacity. Chemical anal-

ysis of the topmost fully emerged leaf at this time confirmed the visual observations (Table 17).

The attempt, with a partially saturated profile, to achieve some of the chemical benefits of flooding was unsuccessful because of iron deficiency in the calcareous soil and water stress in the slightly acid and acid clays.

PHYSIOLOGICAL DISORDERS OF RICE

Investigations on physiological disorders of rice on two soils from Taiwan and an acid-sulfate soil from Vietnam were conducted in the greenhouse and laboratory.

It was found that suffocation disease on Tungshan silt loam was due to reduction products, and cured by retarding soil reduction with added MnO_2 or calcium nitrate. The disorder on Silo silt loam was caused by boron toxicity. Excess water-soluble aluminum soon after flooding, and excess water-soluble Fe^{++} later, were the toxic factors in the acid-sulfate soil. Manganese dioxide and lime, combined with prolonged submergence, eliminated both.

Suffocation disease

This physiological disorder of rice occurring in northeastern Taiwan is characterized by a reddish brown discoloration of the leaves, stunted growth, root rot, and low yield. As the recommended remedy of draining the field is not possible because of climate or terrain, chemical retardation of soil reduction with manganese dioxide, calcium nitrate, and calcium chlorate were investigated in the greenhouse using soil shipped from Taiwan.

MnO_2 and $Ca(NO_3)_2$ retarded the fall in Eh and depressed the concentration of water-soluble Fe^{++} and organic

TABLE 18. Influence of retardants of soil reduction on the kinetics of Fe^{++} , oxidizable matter, and Mn^{++} in the soil solution of flooded Tungshan silt loam.

Retardant	Weeks submerged							
	0	1	2	3	5	7	9	11
	Eh (millivolts)							
None	220	165	119	21	24	1	-10	-27
MnO_2	240	196	174	59	48	-2	-1	-20
NO_3^-	243	188	185	72	70	1	26	22
ClO_3^-	243	187	102	15	16	-6	-27	-33
	Fe^{++} (ppm)							
None	0	5	34	87	135	114	105	122
MnO_2	0	2	10	26	54	72	88	107
NO_3^-	0	0	2	14	74	88	43	44
ClO_3^-	0	1	38	12	169	122	154	134
	oxidizable matter (m.e./l.)							
None	53	34	34	36	35	31	22	31
MnO	54	29	27	27	31	28	24	29
NO_3^-	55	29	24	28	31	29	21	28
ClO_3^-	33	20	21	34	37	35	25	29
	Mn^{++} (ppm)							
None	0	11	22	27	21	17	7	6
MnO_2	0	13	38	41	28	28	18	9
NO_3^-	0	5	10	18	26	32	16	8
ClO_3^-	0	9	21	30	26	18	10	6

reduction products (Table 18). They cured the physiological disease, markedly increased yield, enhanced the uptake of Mn and K but depressed that of Fe^{++} (Table 19). $\text{Ca}(\text{ClO}_3)_2$ was much less effective.

The benefits of MnO_2 and $\text{Ca}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ were not responses to the micronutrient, Mn, nor to nitrate, because the soil solution had sufficient Mn^{++} and NH_3 , and MnCl_2 at 25 ppm produced no response. The benefits apparently resulted from a decrease in concentration of reduction products (Table 18). In this connection, the higher content of mercaptans, amines, fatty acids, sugars, and amino acids in Tungshan silt loam

compared with the other five soils is noteworthy.

Boron toxicity

In a study of chemical retardation of soil reduction as a remedy for physiological disorders of rice believed to be caused by reduction products, foliar symptoms of disturbed metabolism persisted in one problem soil although soil reduction had been retarded.

The symptoms were intervenal chlorosis of the upper portion of the older leaves, especially along the margins, followed by the appearance of large, dark-brown elliptical spots in the affected parts which ultimately turned

TABLE 19. Influence of retardants of soil reduction on the yield of rice and the chemical composition of the straw on flooded Tungshan silt loam.

Retardant	Tillers /pot	Panicles /pot	Straw (g/pot)	Grain	N (%)	K	Fe (ppm)	Mn
None	14.5	11.2	26.4	18.1	2.07	3.05	206	452
MnO_2	18.7	19.0	55.8	43.0	1.84	3.52	191	873
NO_3^-	19.5	22.8	64.2	59.5	1.92	3.42	168	991
ClO_3^-	12.2	12.0	29.2	20.4	2.47	2.84	194	364

Fig. 22. Symptoms of boron toxicity.

light brown, rolled, and dried up (Fig. 22). They were almost identical with the symptoms of boron toxicity on rice in solution culture. The boron content of the straw at harvest was 80 ppm compared with 26 to 30 ppm for normal plants.

The soil was a slightly saline, alkaline silt loam from Taiwan. Its only other unusual feature was a boron content in the flooded soil solution of 9.1 ppm compared with less than 1 ppm for two normal soils.

Because some coastal soils contain 10 to 50 times as much boron as inland soils, boron toxicity may be a hitherto unsuspected limiting factor on such soils.

Toxicity of an acid-sulfate soil

Acid-sulfate soils are extremely acid, unproductive soils, covering vast areas in the tropics otherwise suitable for rice cultivation. Reclamation measures, which include leaching with fresh water or sea water, continuous flooding, and liming, appear to be based on divergent experiences rather than on an understanding of the chemical changes in flooded acid-sulfate soils.

The chief obstacle to the growth of rice on acid-sulfate soils appeared to be their acidity because even after months of submergence their pH may not rise above 6.0. At pH values below 6.0, a reduced soil can have more than 5,000 ppm Fe^{++} in the soil solution. Because

(a) water-soluble aluminum at 25 to 40 ppm and water-soluble Fe^{++} at about 500 ppm are toxic to rice, and (b) the activities of $AlOH^{++}$ and Fe^{++} decrease a hundred-fold per unit pH increase, raising the pH of the soil appeared to be the best method of overcoming the toxicity of these soils. An attempt was made to increase the pH by (a) liming and (b) insuring the presence of sufficient reduced Fe^{++} and Mn in the solid phase to buffer the pH of the soil in the range 6.7 to 7.2.

A greenhouse study of the effects of (a) lime at 0.4 and 0.8 percent in factorial combination with 0.5 percent $Fe(OH)_3$ and 1.0 percent MnO_2 and (b) prolonged submergence of the soil on the chemical and electrochemical changes and the growth of rice in an acid-sulfate soil from Vietnam, confirmed the surmise that excess water-soluble Al in the early stages of flooding and excess water-soluble Fe^{++} were the two chief toxic factors.

Calcium carbonate increased the pH of the soil and soil solution (Fig. 23), markedly depressed the concentration of Fe^{++} (Fig. 26), Al and SO_4^{--} (Tables 20, 21, 22) in the soil solution, and markedly improved the growth of rice. $CaCO_3$ at 0.4 percent saved the plants from death and enabled them to produce a moderate amount of straw and grain; $CaCO_3$ at 0.8 percent doubled this straw and grain yield (Table 23).

The death of plants in the untreated

TABLE 20. Influence of $CaCO_3$, MnO_2 and $Fe(OH)_3$ on the kinetics of Al (ppm) in the soil solution of a flooded acid-sulfate soil.

Treatment			Weeks submerged						
$CaCO_3$	MnO_2	$Fe(OH)_3$	0	1	2	4	6	8	16
(%)									
0.0	0.0	0.0	40.0	70.0	68.0	60.0	35.0	25.0	1.0
0.0	1.0	0.0	40.0	40.0	33.0	18.0	15.0	5.0	0.7
0.0	0.0	0.5	37.0	52.0	36.0	20.0	18.0	8.0	1.5
0.0	1.0	0.5	39.0	35.0	30.0	28.0	20.0	7.0	1.3
0.4	0.0	0.0	0.3	1.1	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	0.7
0.4	1.0	0.0	0.3	0.8	0.6	0.6	0.4	0.3	0.5
0.4	0.0	0.5	0.5	0.9	0.6	0.7	0.8	0.9	0.8
0.4	1.0	0.5	0.6	0.5	0.6	0.4	0.8	1.0	0.6
0.8	0.0	0.0	0.6	0.3	0.6	0.5	0.5	0.1	0.2
0.8	1.0	0.0	0.8	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.2
0.8	0.0	0.5	0.7	0.3	0.2	0.1	0.2	0.4	0.3
0.8	1.0	0.5	0.8	0.3	0.3	0.5	0.2	0.1	0.4

TABLE 21. Influence of CaCO_3 , MnO_2 and $\text{Fe}(\text{OH})_3$ on the kinetics of Fe^{++} (ppm) in the soil solution of a flooded acid-sulfate soil.

Treatment			Weeks submerged					
CaCO_3	MnO_2	$\text{Fe}(\text{OH})_3$	0	2	4	8	12	16
(%)								
0.0	0.0	0.0	0.5	490	645	799	785	768
0.0	1.0	0.0	0.8	136	166	174	229	279
0.0	0.0	0.5	0.8	761	968	1204	1165	1114
0.0	1.0	0.5	0.4	153	210	320	363	438
0.4	0.0	0.0	0.3	190	351	520	500	412
0.4	1.0	0.0	0.3	163	217	260	245	158
0.4	0.0	0.5	0.7	263	453	690	773	660
0.4	1.0	0.5	0.4	168	285	370	373	343
0.8	0.0	0.0	0.1	133	152	147	121	58
0.8	1.0	0.0	0.1	72	81	96	96	45
0.8	0.0	0.5	0.1	170	263	298	254	207
0.8	1.0	0.5	0.1	106	173	228	173	175

soil was due to the high concentration of aluminum (68 ppm) and Fe^{++} (490 ppm) in the soil solution at planting (2 weeks after submergence). CaCO_3 at 0.4 percent depressed the concentration of Al and Fe^{++} to 1.0 and 190 ppm, respectively, and enabled the plants to grow. But the high concentration of water-soluble Fe^{++} (>400 ppm) during the greater part of the growing season (Table 21) caused iron toxicity, indicated by reddish-brown discoloration and drying up of older leaves and a high content (460 ppm) of Fe in the straw.

CaCO_3 at 0.8 percent (a) depressed the concentration of Al and Fe^{++} in the soil solution to 0.6 and 133 ppm, (b) did not permit the Fe^{++} concentration to rise above 152 ppm at any

stage of submergence, thus preventing iron toxicity and, despite osmotic stress caused by a high electrolyte concentration ($\kappa > 8.0$ mho/cm), enabling the plants to produce double the yield of the 0.4 percent CaCO_3 treatment. The absence of visual symptoms, and the low content of Fe^{++} in the straw (128 ppm), confirmed the absence of Fe^{++} toxicity.

These observations indicate that (a) the death of plants in the untreated acid-sulfate soil was caused by excess Al and Fe^{++} , (b) Al toxicity was overcome by liming the soil to give a pH of 4.7 at planting, (c) both Al and Fe^{++} toxicities were averted by liming to a pH of 5 to 5.5 to give a pH of about 6 a few weeks after flooding, and (d) the amount of CaCO_3 required to cor-

TABLE 22. Influence of CaCO_3 , MnO_2 and $\text{Fe}(\text{OH})_3$ on the kinetics of water-soluble SO_4^{--} (g/l) in a flooded acid-sulfate soil.

Treatment			Weeks submerged					
CaCO_3	MnO_2	$\text{Fe}(\text{OH})_3$	2	8	12	24	28	37
(%)								
0.0	0.0	0.0	2.11	2.50	3.12	1.67	1.39	1.18
0.0	1.0	0.0	2.90	2.90	3.12	1.94	1.90	1.63
0.0	0.0	0.5	2.40	2.50	3.20	1.67	1.54	1.20
0.0	1.0	0.5	2.80	2.15	2.60	2.14	2.08	2.05
0.4	0.0	0.0	2.00	2.30	2.78	1.26	1.19	0.025
0.4	1.0	0.0	2.00	2.03	2.49	2.50	2.03	1.30
0.4	0.0	0.5	1.45	2.30	2.60	1.29	0.079	0.019
0.4	1.0	0.5	1.65	1.98	2.75	2.14	1.90	1.48
0.8	0.0	0.0	1.75	1.78	2.05	0.049	0.047	0.012
0.8	1.0	0.0	1.89	1.13	2.43	1.66	1.45	0.005
0.8	0.0	0.5	1.63	1.63	2.00	0.073	0.059	0.005
0.8	1.0	0.5	1.63	1.70	1.93	0.079	1.08	0.005

Fig. 23. Influence of CaCO_3 on the kinetics of soil solution pH of a flooded acid-sulfate soil.

rect the toxicity to rice of the soil under study is 8 to 16 ton/ha.

Manganese dioxide at 1 percent by weight of the soil (a) markedly retarded the fall in redox potential, (b) increased by about 0.2 units the pH of the soil solution, (c) depressed the concentration of Al (Table 20) and Fe^{++} (Table 21), (d) increased the concentration of Mn^{++} in the soil solution to $>1,000$ ppm in the unlimed soil and (e) apparently retarded sulfate reduction (Table 22).

Manganese dioxide prevented the death of plants in the unlimed soils, alleviated iron toxicity (Table 24), and markedly improved the growth and yield of rice in the soils treated with 0.4 percent CaCO_3 but produced no

marked benefit (cf with the no- MnO_2 -treatment) in the presence of 0.8 percent CaCO_3 (Table 23).

MnO_2 enabled the plants to grow in the unlimed soil because it (a) depressed the concentration of water-soluble Al and Fe^{++} to 33 and 130 ppm, respectively, at planting, (b) did not permit Fe^{++} in the soil solution to rise above 279 ppm (Fig. 24), and (c) progressively lowered the concentration of Al during growth, apparently by increasing the pH. Grain yield, however, was low (Table 23) because of (a) osmotic stress, (b) more than 1,100 ppm Mn^{++} in the soil solution, and, perhaps, (c) Ca deficiency caused by Mn^{++} : Ca^{++} antagonism.

In the presence of 0.4 percent CaCO_3 , MnO_2 markedly improved the yield of rice because it depressed the concentration of Fe^{++} in the soil solution to less than 200 ppm. MnO_2 produced no significant response in the presence of 0.8 percent CaCO_3 because CaCO_3 at this level eliminated Al and Fe^{++} toxicities.

The beneficial response of the rice plants to MnO_2 , and its association with low Al and Fe^{++} in the soil solution, confirmed the earlier finding that excess Al and Fe^{++} at planting, and later excess Fe^{++} alone, were the two main factors lethal to rice on the acid-sulfate soil.

Ferric hydroxide at 0.5 percent by weight of the soil (a) increased the pH

TABLE 23. Influence of CaCO_3 , MnO_2 and $\text{Fe}(\text{OH})_3$ on the growth and yield of rice on a flooded acid-sulfate soil.

Treatment			Tillers /pot	Panicles /pot	Straw (g/pot)	Grain (g/pot)	Sterility (%)
CaCO_3	MnO_2	$\text{Fe}(\text{OH})_3$					
(%)							
0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	—
0.0	1.0	0.0	4.7	4.7	16.6	7.5	32.6
0.0	0.0	0.5	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	—
0.0	1.0	0.5	3.0	2.7	7.6	2.9	50.1
0.4	0.0	0.0	9.0	8.5	35.5	29.2	22.3
0.4	1.0	0.0	18.7	14.7	55.2	49.9	28.3
0.4	0.0	0.5	6.3	5.3	20.5	8.7	49.8
0.4	1.0	0.5	11.7	5.0	37.4	19.6	37.0
0.8	0.0	0.0	19.3	17.0	69.4	58.2	30.8
0.8	1.0	0.0	23.3	18.7	77.2	57.7	31.6
0.8	0.0	0.5	16.3	16.3	75.3	49.2	33.8
0.8	1.0	0.5	24.5	18.3	100.0	40.3	38.0

S.E. (Grain) = 1.90

of the soil solution by about 0.1 unit, (b) markedly increased the concentration of water-soluble Fe^{++} (Fig. 22), and (c) depressed the concentration of Al from 68 to 36 ppm at planting.

$\text{Fe}(\text{OH})_3$ did not prevent the death of plants in the unlimed soil although it depressed Al to sub-lethal levels. The plants turned purplish-brown, wilted, and died within a day. Apparently 760 ppm Fe in the soil solution at planting was lethal (Table 21).

In the 0.4 percent CaCO_3 treated soil, $\text{Fe}(\text{OH})_3$ depressed growth and produced typical iron toxicity symptoms. The concentration of Fe^{++} in the soil solution exceeded 450 ppm in the vegetative phase and 700 ppm in the reproductive phase; the straw contained 868 ppm. The grain yield was small and the percentage sterility high. In the soils that received 0.8 percent CaCO_3 , $\text{Fe}(\text{OH})_3$ produced only the mildest symptoms of Fe toxicity. MnO_2 counteracted the adverse effects of $\text{Fe}(\text{OH})_3$ by depressing the concentration of Fe and also the Fe:Mn ratio in the soil solution.

The aggravation of the foliar symptoms of Fe toxicity by the addition of $\text{Fe}(\text{OH})_3$ to the acid-sulfate soil in which lime had prevented Al toxicity suggests that Fe^{++} toxicity may retard or prevent the growth of rice on similar soils.

Fig. 24. Effects of CaCO_3 , MnO_2 and $\text{Fe}(\text{OH})_3$ on the kinetics of Fe^{++} in the soil solution of a flooded acid-sulfate soil.

Because the chemical kinetics of the flooded acid-sulfate soil indicated a decrease in concentration of Al, Fe, and electrolytes with prolonged submergence, the effects of continuous flooding

TABLE 24. Association between the concentration of Fe^{+2} (ppm) in the soil solution of a flooded acid-sulfate soil treated with CaCO_3 and $\text{Fe}(\text{OH})_3$ and the degree of injury to rice plants.

Treatment	Weeks submerged			Injury
	2 ^a	6	12	
0.5% $\text{Fe}(\text{OH})_3$	760	1050	1165	Plants wilted, browned and died within a day.
None	565	725	785	Leaves rolled, browned and plants died in a week.
0.5% $\text{Fe}(\text{OH})_3$ 0.4% CaCO_3	263	625	773	Stunting, severe bronzing ^b and drying up of older leaves at 6 weeks.
0.4% CaCO_3	190	471	500	Bronzing at 6 weeks.
0.8% CaCO_3	170	283	254	Slight bronzing at 6 weeks.
0.5% $\text{Fe}(\text{OH})_3$ 0.8% CaCO_3	133	149	121	No bronzing.

^a Seedlings transplanted.

^b Purple-brown color of foliage, associated with iron toxicity.

TABLE 25. Effects of continuous flooding (F) and air-drying the previously flooded soil before reflooding (D) on (a) the concentration of water-soluble Fe++ and Mn++ (ppm) at 2 stages of the development of the rice plant and (b) the yield of rice and the severity of iron toxicity.

No.	Treatment		Water	Weeks submerged		Straw (g/pot)	Grain (%)	Sterility (%)	Straw		Iron toxicity		
	CaCO ₃	MnO ₂		Fe(OH) ₃	2				13	Fe		Mn	
(%)													
				Fe++	Mn++	Fe++	Mn++						
(ppm)													
1.	0.0	0.0	0.0	F	730	6	527	4	0	—	—	—	lethal
2.	0.0	0.0	0.0	D	255	12	1180	10	132	78	615	58	severe
3.	0.0	1.0	0.0	F	410	572	325	700	170	72	200	1390	absent
4.	0.0	1.0	0.0	D	70	1530	425	1950	213	34	92	2070	absent
5.	0.0	0.0	0.5	F	950	11	623	8	0	0	—	—	lethal
6.	0.0	0.0	0.5	D	240	18	1630	16	133	67	774	95	severe
7.	0.0	1.0	0.5	F	490	706	655	1020	213	35	343	3640	mild
8.	0.0	1.0	0.5	D	120	806	768	1420	264	90	229	3910	mild
9.	0.4	0.0	0.0	F	253	5	96	3	181	128	233	188	mild
10.	0.4	0.0	0.0	D	120	13	890	11	156	92	340	95	mild
11.	0.4	1.0	0.0	F	178	685	29	270	210	137	43	1310	absent
12.	0.4	1.0	0.0	D	53	1380	99	1550	190	70	67	3220	absent
13.	0.4	0.0	0.5	F	365	5	177	3	231	109	363	93	mild
14.	0.4	0.0	0.5	D	154	15	1080	11	206	112	400	97	mild
15.	0.4	1.0	0.5	F	296	582	66	n.d.	231	153	114	1370	absent
16.	0.4	1.0	0.5	D	61	1060	172	n.d.	204	130	109	3100	absent
17.	0.8	0.0	0.0	F	53	2	52	n.d.	221	97	82	109	absent
18.	0.8	0.0	0.0	D	80	6	310	10	146	93	167	138	absent
19.	0.8	1.0	0.0	F	84	202	13	90	177	113	64	1580	absent
20.	0.8	1.0	0.0	D	28	441	163	460	165	103	62	1440	absent
21.	0.8	0.0	0.5	F	167	5	86	3	221	114	155	303	absent
22.	0.8	0.0	0.5	D	104	8	381	7	181	83	118	308	absent
23.	0.8	1.0	0.5	F	139	70	64	49	221	133	81	826	absent
24.	0.8	1.0	0.5	D	52	344	104	304	210	132	90	1840	absent

S. E. (Grain) = 2.37

were compared with those of air-drying the soil before reflooding and planting.

Compared with prolonged flooding, air-drying followed by flooding (a) raised Eh, depressed pH and increased specific conductance, (b) increased water-soluble Al and water-soluble SO_4^{--} and (c) markedly increased water-soluble Mn^{++} in the soils previously treated with MnO_2 . Also, air-drying reversed some chemical changes; in the continuously submerged soils, Fe^{++} and Mn^{++} decreased progressively, whereas in the air-dried soils they increased to levels as high as the earlier peaks of the continuously submerged treatments.

Water management influenced growth, yield, and foliar symptoms through its effect on the concentration of Fe^{++} in the soil solution at two critical phases of the growth of the plant (Table 25).

The seedlings planted in the continuously flooded unlimed soil died within a day of planting, although the Al concentration was less than 1 ppm. Apparently 760 ppm Fe^{++} in the soil solution was lethal. Air-drying before reflooding enabled the plants to grow in

a medium low in Fe^{++} at the start, but the high concentration of Fe^{++} (>1,000 ppm) 11 weeks later caused severe iron toxicity.

In sharp contrast to the unlimed soils, the once previously limed yielded much better when kept continuously flooded than when air-dried prior to flooding.

The highest yields in this greenhouse experiment were obtained with a continuously flooded soil that had previously been treated with 0.4 percent CaCO_3 , 1 percent MnO_2 and 0.5 percent $\text{Fe}(\text{OH})_3$. Apparently, CaCO_3 eliminated Al toxicity, MnO_2 alleviated iron toxicity, and $\text{Fe}(\text{OH})_3$ prevented H_2S injury (Table 25).

The following provisional measures are recommended for the reclamation of acid-sulfate soils: (a) leaching the soil with fresh water to remove salts, chiefly sulfates; (b) liming to an aerobic pH of 4.7 to prevent Al toxicity; (c) applying MnO_2 to counteract Fe toxicity; (d) adding Fe_2O_3 (red earth) to counteract H_2S toxicity in soils low in Fe; and (e) maintaining a continuous flood after these combined treatments.

Soil Microbiology

Research during 1965 was continued along the same major lines developed the previous year. Research projects were aimed at obtaining a better understanding of microbial activities in flooded soils, and the implications these may have for rice production. Chief emphasis was placed on the following topics: nitrogen transformations in flooded soils, nitrogen fixation in flooded soils, microbial transformations of inorganic forms of sulfur, pesticide residues, and plant-microorganism interactions.

NITROGEN TRANSFORMATIONS IN FLOODED SOILS

Studies on soil nitrogen were continued with major attention being given to the following aspects: (a) the chemical distribution of nitrogen in tropical rice soils, (b) the fate of applied nitrogen in submerged soils, and (c) nitrogen fixation in rice soils.

Chemical distribution of nitrogen in tropical rice soils

Results of earlier studies on the chemical distribution of nitrogen in two tropical rice soils, Maahas clay (pH 6.6., O.M. 2.0%, Total N 0.14%) and Louisiana clay (pH 4.7, O.M. 3.2%, Total N 0.21%) (Annual Report, 1964) revealed that major differences existed between the soils in the distribution of nitrogen among the organic fractions. In an extension of these studies, two more soils were chosen for analysis. These soils were Calabanga clay (pH 6.2, O.M. 4.8%, Total N 0.26%) and a silt loam from the Ilan region of Taiwan (pH 5.8, O.M. 3.4%, Total N 0.20%).

Considerable differences were found in the distribution of nitrogen in the organic fractions of these two soils. Whereas in the earlier studies, amino sugar nitrogen represented from 6.5 to 11.6 percent of the total soil nitrogen, the present study revealed that only 1.5 and 3.8 percent of the total soil nitrogen of Calabanga clay and Ilan soil respectively was present in the amino sugar fraction. As the amino sugar content is probably derived from chitin and fungal tissue, these lower figures may reflect lower fungal populations within the two soils.

Soluble alkali-stable nitrogen was found to be low in the Ilan soil (18.4% of total soil N). However, the same fraction in Calabanga clay contained 48% of the total soil N which is comparable to the results obtained with the two soils used in the earlier studies.

More than one-third (36.3%) of the total soil nitrogen of Ilan soil was found in the hydrolyzable $\text{NH}_4^+ - \text{N}$ fraction, whereas only 15% of the total nitrogen was found in this fraction of Calabanga clay. Hydrolyzable ammonium nitrogen represents the nitrogen that was

released by aeration of the acid hydrolyzate of the soil under alkaline conditions. Soil constituents that may release their nitrogen during acid hydrolysis, and therefore be included in this fraction, would be certain amino acids, amino sugars, amides, and non-exchangeable ammonium in "fixed" positions on the clay mineral. The large value obtained for this fraction, and the low value obtained for the soluble alkali-stable nitrogen fraction of Ilan soil, suggests that major differences exist in the amino acid, amide, and amino sugar contents of the two soils.

Non-exchangeable ammonium nitrogen released by hydrofluoric acid treatment of the soil residue after acid hydrolysis accounted for 3.1% of the total nitrogen of the Ilan soil. The non-exchangeable ammonium nitrogen content of Calabanga clay was 0.8% of the total soil nitrogen and was comparable to the figures obtained for Maahas clay and Louisiana clay. Ammonium fixation in Ilan soil, reflected by the greater amount of fixed ammonium released by hydrofluoric acid treatment, and in part by the large amount of hydrolyzable NH_4^+ (which would contain some of the fixed ammonium), is in keeping with the high potassium fixation recorded for this soil.

The distribution of nitrogen into the humin fractions was approximately the same for both soils and represented about 30 percent of the total soil nitrogen.

In summary, analysis of the chemical distribution of nitrogen in four different tropical rice soils (two clay soils of different nitrogen content, a latosolic soil, and a silt loam) has provided results which indicate that major differences among the soils exist in the distribution of nitrogen into the soluble alkali stable N, hydrolyzable $\text{NH}_4^+ - \text{N}$ and amino sugar N.

Fate of applied nitrogen in submerged soils

Following submergence of a soil, there is an increase in its ammonium content. The increase follows an asymp-

otic course when the soil nitrogen content is low, and a logarithmic course for soils rich in nitrogen (Annual Report, 1964). Whichever course is followed, it represents the balance between the two opposing processes of mineralization and immobilization. Very little is known of the extent of nitrogen immobilization in submerged tropical soils.

The fate of applied nitrogen in flood-

Fig. 1. Immobilization of fertilizer nitrogen ($(^{15}\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4$) into soil organic nitrogen following flooding of Calabanga clay.

ed soils was investigated to: (a) obtain a measure of nitrogen immobilization, and (b) trace the movement of inorganic nitrogen into the soil organic pool of nitrogen and its subsequent release.

The two soils used in these greenhouse studies were Maahas clay, and Calabanga clay. Ammonium sulfate ($(^{15}\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4$) was added to the soils at a depth of 5 cm from the surface, and at the rate of 122 kg/ha N, just prior to flooding. The soils were kept submerged for 18 weeks during which time soil samples were removed, fractionated, and the amount of ^{15}N and ^{14}N in each fraction was determined.

The patterns of ^{15}N distribution into the various nitrogen fractions of the two soils during the 18 weeks of submergence were generally similar. However, peaks of ^{15}N in the organic fractions, indicating immobilization, usually occurred earlier and were larger in Calabanga clay than in Maahas clay.

Figure 1 illustrates the results obtained for the distribution of ^{15}N into the exchangeable ammonium fraction and three major organic fractions of Calabanga clay. The finding that a large proportion of the fertilizer nitrogen was immediately immobilized into the hydrolyzable NH_4^+ -N fraction was surprising. The true nature of this immobilization is not known but apparently the nitrogen of this fraction is rapidly mineralized during the first week of submergence. For the remaining 17 weeks of submergence the ^{15}N content of the hydrolyzable NH_4^+ -N fraction remained reasonably constant, representing approximately 14 percent of the applied nitrogen. Immobilization of nitrogen into this fraction was also found for Maahas clay; peak values for ^{15}N in the hydrolyzable NH_4^+ -N fraction were found at 1 and 4 weeks after submergence. At the end of the 18-week period, the hydrolyzable NH_4^+ -N fraction of Maahas clay contained approximately 6 percent of the applied nitrogen.

Immobilization of applied nitrogen into the soluble alkali-stable fraction was detected for both soils; peak values for ^{15}N incorporation for Calabanga clay were at 1 week and 4 to 7 weeks after submergence (Fig. 1). The incorporation of ^{15}N into this fraction of Maahas clay followed a similar pattern but peak values were obtained at 2 weeks and 5 to 7 weeks. The two distinct phases observed for the immobilization of nitrogen into this fraction of the two soils suggest changes in the microflora. The following interpretation is suggested: The first period of immobilization possibly represented the activities of the aerobic and facultatively anaerobic population during the early stages of reduction of the soil. With further reduction and depletion of growth substrates, the aerobic population declined with

subsequent mineralization of the nitrogen contained in the cellular material of these organisms. The second period of immobilization represented the establishment of an anaerobic population favored by the further reduction of the soil. Depletion of growth substrates again was followed by mineralization of the nitrogen of the microbial cells.

The amino sugar nitrogen fractions of both soils also received some of the applied nitrogen, but this was never more than about 6 percent of the applied nitrogen.

Although the total nitrogen in the exchangeable NH_4^+ -N fraction remained fairly constant after about 4 weeks of submergence, the amount of ^{15}N declined in both soils. As this decline in ^{15}N content could not be accounted for in the organic fractions, loss through nitrification and subsequent denitrification is suggested. The percent recoveries of the applied ^{15}N from the exchangeable NH_4^+ -N fraction at the end of the 18-week period were 35% for Calabanga clay, and 43% for Maahas clay. No more than 70% of the applied nitrogen was present in the exchangeable NH_4^+ -N fraction (presum-

ably available to a rice plant) at any sampling time during the 18-week period.

Immobilization of fertilizer nitrogen into the humin fractions did not amount to more than 8 percent of the applied nitrogen. Loss of fertilizer nitrogen into the fixed NH_4^+ -N fractions (released only by hydrofluoric acid treatment) of the two soils was less than 2 percent.

While further studies are required, the following conclusions are suggested from the foregoing results: (a) immobilization and mineralization of nitrogen occur simultaneously in a submerged soil; (b) the most important organic nitrogen fractions in terms of immobilization are the hydrolyzable NH_4^+ -N fraction and the soluble alkali-stable nitrogen fraction; (c) nitrogen entering the exchangeable NH_4^+ -N fraction following submergence is largely derived from the hydrolyzable NH_4^+ -N fraction, soluble alkali-stable N fraction, and amino sugar N fraction; and (d) considerable losses of nitrogen occur from a flooded soil even after 4 weeks of submergence.

NITROGEN FIXATION BY RICE SOILS

Studies on nitrogen fixation by rice soils were continued to determine: (a) the magnitude of nitrogen fixation, (b) the effect of soil amendments upon nitrogen fixation, and (c) the effect of soil inoculation with nitrogen-fixing microorganisms upon the magnitude of nitrogen fixation.

Three Luzon soils (Maahas clay, pH 6.6, O.M. 2.0%, Total N 0.14%; Louisiana clay, pH 4.7, O.M. 3.2%, Total N 0.21%; and Calabanga clay, pH 6.2, O.M. 4.8%, Total N 0.26%) were used in these studies. The soils were flooded and incubated for 28 days in sealed containers with an atmosphere (N_2 , O_2 and He) enriched with $^{15}\text{N}_2$ (65 atom % excess). One series was incubated in the light and the other in the dark so that any effect of light could be determined. Several types of organic matter were added to the soils in order to test the effect of such additions upon nitrogen fixation. At the end of the incubation pe-

riod soil nitrogen was converted to the ammonium form which was analyzed for enrichment with the heavy isotope of nitrogen.

All three soils fixed detectable amounts of nitrogen (Table 1). Higher native organic matter content of the soil was associated with more active nitrogen fixation when the soils were incubated in the light. Although these experiments were conducted in the laboratory, the results indicate that gains in soil nitrogen in the unamended soils of 9 kg/ha (Maahas clay), 21 kg/ha (Louisiana clay), and 58 kg/ha (Calabanga clay) per year are feasible as a result of nitrogen fixation.

Organic matter additions to Maahas clay and Louisiana clay generally resulted in an increase in nitrogen fixation when the soils were incubated in the light. Similar additions to Calabanga clay on the other hand resulted in a depression of nitrogen fixation. In-

TABLE 1. The effect of organic matter amendments upon the fixation of atmospheric nitrogen by submerged rice soils.

Soil amendment ^a	Calabanga clay	Luisiana clay	Maahas clay
	atom % excess ¹⁵ N in soil nitrogen ^b		
None	0.066 (0.025)	0.028 (0.013)	0.022 (0.063)
Rice straw	0.033 (0.035)	0.078 (0.028)	0.048 (0.016)
Green manure	0.067 (0.042)	0.028 (0.022)	0.035 (0.032)
Rice roots	0.052 (0.090)	0.035 (0.022)	0.038 (0.022)
Cellulose	0.018 (0.016)	0.025 (0.022)	0.365 (0.063)

^a The following rates were used: rice straw (5,000 kg/ha), green manure (*Sesbania* at 5,000 kg/ha), rice roots (20,000 kg/ha wet weight), and pure cellulose (5,000 kg/ha).

^b Figures in parentheses represent the atom % excess ¹⁵N of dark-incubated samples.

creased fixation associated with increased organic matter may be attributed to either an increased supply of organic substrate for heterotrophic nitrogen-fixing species, or an increased supply of carbon dioxide for the photosynthetic nitrogen-fixing species.

Because ammonium is known to inhibit nitrogen fixation, it was interesting to find that the ammonium liberated through the mineralization of soil nitrogen following submergence, plus that released from the nitrogen-rich *Sesbania*, had no inhibitory effect upon nitrogen fixation by the three soils.

Soils incubated in the dark generally gave lower values for the amounts of nitrogen fixed than soils incubated in the light (Table 1). On three occasions, the amount of fixed nitrogen was greater in the dark-incubated soil. The reasons for this are not clear but may have been due to sampling errors. In only five instances out of the 15 pairs of results in Table 1 (light versus dark incubation) are the increases in fixation due to illumination greater than the amounts fixed in the dark. The results therefore suggest that heterotrophic nitrogen-fixing microorganisms fixed more nitrogen in these soils than photosynthetic species. This is based on the assumption that the nitrogen-fixing systems operating in the dark-incubated soils are also functioning at equivalent rates in the soils incubated in the light. Earlier studies revealed the presence of significantly high populations of anaerobic nitrogen-fixing bacteria in two of these soils (Maahas clay and Luisiana clay).

Effect of inoculation on nitrogen fixation by rice soils

Both organisms used in this study were isolated from Maahas clay. One of them, a blue-green alga (*Nostoc* sp.) was isolated in monoalgal culture which produced luxuriant growth in nitrogen-free liquid medium. However, because it has not been possible so far to isolate this alga in a bacteria-free state it is not known definitely whether it is capable of nitrogen fixation. A suspension of the alga, which had developed in nitrogen-free liquid medium, was used as the soil inoculant.

Fig. 2. Cells of the nitrogen-fixing *Clostridium* sp. from a 44-hour-old colony of nitrogen-free agar slide culture. Phase contrast at magnification 1,920 x.

The second soil inoculant was a washed suspension of a pure culture of *Clostridium* sp., a nitrogen-fixing anaerobic bacterium (Fig. 2). As studies on the nitrogen-fixing ability of this organism revealed that it fixed most nitrogen during the logarithmic growth phase (Fig. 3), cultures at this stage of growth were chosen for the prepara-

tion of inocula. Each soil sample received an inoculum equivalent to approximately 2.5×10^7 bacterial cells.

Three soils (Calabanga clay, Louisiana clay and Maahas clay) were flooded, inoculated and incubated in the light in sealed containers with an atmosphere (O_2 , N_2 and He) enriched with $^{15}N_2$ (65 atom % excess). After 28 days incubation, the soil nitrogen was converted to ammonium which was analyzed

TABLE 2. Effect of soil inoculation upon nitrogen fixation by submerged rice soils.

Inoculum	$^{15}N_2$ fixed per 7 g soil		
	Calabanga clay	Louisiana clay	Maahas clay
None	10.6	6.2	5.9
Blue-green alga	9.7	9.7	7.6
<i>Clostridium</i> sp.	10.7	2.9	4.2

Fig. 3. Nitrogen fixation and growth in nitrogen-free medium of *Clostridium*, isolated from the rhizosphere of rice plants.

for enrichment with ^{15}N . Total soil nitrogen was determined and the amount of nitrogen fixed per soil sample calculated (Table 2). Increases in nitrogen fixation through algal inoculation of 56 and 28 percent were obtained for Louisiana soil and Maahas soil, respectively. A slight decrease in nitrogen fixation was found when Calabanga clay was inoculated with the alga. In-

oculation with the nitrogen-fixing bacterium apparently depressed nitrogen fixation.

The results of the studies on nitrogen fixation by rice soils indicate that: (a) significant amounts of atmospheric nitrogen can be fixed by the free-living microflora of flooded soils, (b) organic matter additions in the form of rice straw, rice roots and green manure

to certain soils can result in greater fixation of atmospheric nitrogen, (c) the heterotrophic nitrogen-fixing bacteria play a significant role in the nitrogen-fixing process of submerged soils in spite of the apparent lack of abundant

growth substrates, and (d) algal inoculation can cause an increase in the amount of nitrogen fixed by a flooded soil. Studies on the process of nitrogen fixation in submerged soils will be continued.

MICROBIAL TRANSFORMATIONS OF SULFUR

Studies on the microbial transformations of inorganic sulfur in acid-sulfate soil were continued. Cultures of organisms active in these transformations were isolated, and studies on the oxidation and reduction of inorganic sulfur compounds were initiated.

Soil studies

The objectives of these studies were to determine the effect of additions of lime (8,000 kg/ha) and rice straw (10,000 kg/ha), alone and in combination, to flooded and non-flooded acid-sulfate soil upon: pH, sulfate reduction, sulfide oxidation, and the microbial populations responsible for sulfur transformations.

One series of acid-sulfate soil samples were kept flooded and another series kept at field capacity for 3 months. After this initial period, treatments were reversed: the flooded samples were drained and kept at field capacity, and the previously non-flooded samples were submerged. The soil samples were kept under these conditions for a further 18-week period. Lime and straw were added prior to the initial 3-month period. At regular intervals throughout the total 7-1/2-month period, the following determinations were made: Eh, pH, sulfate, total sulfide, hydrogen sulfide, and populations of both sulfate-reducing and sulfur-oxidizing bacteria.

The results of these studies may be summarized as follows:

(a) additions of lime and rice straw had little effect on the pH of the non-flooded acid-sulfate soil;

(b) additions of lime to the flooded soil resulted in a pH of 6.2 after 12 weeks of flooding; but upon draining and oxidation, the pH of the soil fell rapidly to 4.1, indicating no lasting effect of liming;

(c) additions of lime and straw to the flooded soil increased sulfate reduction, as indicated by the production of sulfides (Table 3), and decreased sulfate content;

TABLE 3. The effect of additions of lime and rice straw upon sulfide formation in acid-sulfate soil following submergence.^a

Soil amendment	Total sulfide ppm (dry soil)	Hydrogen sulfide
None	192	105
Lime	286	105
Rice straw	310	172
Lime + rice straw	361	203

^a Sulfide levels in soil after 12 weeks of submergence.

(d) straw additions increased the rate of reduction of the flooded soil and resulted in increased populations of sulfate-reducing bacteria, and an increase in the amount of sulfide formed (Table 3);

(e) liming the non-flooded soil had no apparent effect on the population of sulfide-oxidizing bacteria, but increased the amount of sulfate formed during the first 3-month period;

(f) populations of sulfide-oxidizing bacteria declined rapidly after flooding in all treatments and none could be detected in the soil 6 weeks after submergence;

(g) the sulfate content of the soil increased, and populations of sulfide-oxidizing organisms developed rapidly, when the flooded soils were drained;

(h) populations of sulfate-reducing bacteria declined rapidly when flooded soils were drained and allowed to oxidize;

(i) decrease in sulfate content and formation of sulfides were coincident

with the rapid development of populations of sulfate-reducing bacteria when the non-flooded soils were flooded.

The results of these studies agree with the earlier finding (Annual Report, 1964) that the soil microflora play a significant role in the acidification of this soil through the oxidation of reduced inorganic sulfur-containing compounds to sulfate.

Pure culture studies

A pure culture of a sulfate-reducing bacterium (probably *Desulfovibrio* sp.) was isolated from the flooded acid-sulfate soil. Studies on the mechanisms involved in sulfate reduction by this organism are in progress.

A pure culture of a bacterium capable of oxidizing elemental sulfur to sulfate was isolated by enrichment culture technique from the non-flooded acid-sulfate soil.

Fig. 4. Cells of *Thiobacillus* sp. from thiosulfate liquid medium showing phase-dense polar bodies. Phase contrast, magnification 3,600 x.

The isolate (Fig. 4) has the following morphological and cultural characteristics: (a) short rods, 0.5 by 1 to 2.5 microns, non-motile, gram-negative; (b) will not grow on nutrient agar; (c) produces small, convex, yellowish colonies on thiosulfate agar, utilizing carbon dioxide as a source of carbon; (d) in liquid medium, elemental sulfur and thiosulfate are oxidized to sulfate and the pH of the medium reaches a final value of about 3.0; and (e) elemental sulfur and tetrathionate are

produced during the oxidation of thiosulfate to sulfate. These characteristics are similar to those described for *Thiobacillus neapolitanus*. The organism is an autotroph, deriving its energy for growth from the oxidation of reduced inorganic sulfur compounds to sulfate and utilizing carbon dioxide as a source of carbon.

As this organism appears to be the most abundant species of *Thiobacillus* occurring in the acid-sulfate soil and undoubtedly plays an important role in the acidification of this soil, it was selected for the following studies on the oxidation of inorganic sulfur-containing compounds.

Growth

A mineral medium containing thiosulfate, aerated with a mixture of air and carbon dioxide (99%:1%) at a rate of 84 liters per hour was used for cultivating the bacterium. During the course of the growth of the organism, samples of the culture solution were removed and analyzed for the following inorganic sulfur compounds: thiosulfate, sulfite, sulfate, and polythionates.

Fig. 5. The oxidation of thiosulfate by a growing culture of *Thiobacillus* sp. in thiosulfate liquid medium.

Sulfate was the major product of the oxidation of thiosulfate by this organism (Fig. 5). Smaller amounts of tetrathionate, trithionate, pentathionate and sulfite were detected. Considerable amounts of elemental sulfur were formed in the medium during growth but were not assayed. As thiosulfate hydrolyzes below pH 5.0 to yield sulfite, sulfur dioxide and, possibly, elemental sulfur, hydrogen sulfide, and pentathionate, the detection of some of these compounds during the growth of the organism in the thiosulfate medium (pH 5.0) does not necessarily indicate that they are intermediates in the biological oxidation of thiosulfate.

Respiration studies

Respiration studies using washed suspensions of *Thiobacillus* sp. (harvested from the thiosulfate medium after 6 days incubation) were performed to obtain information on the metabolism of inorganic sulfur compounds by the organism. In these experiments, the cell suspensions were provided with four forms of inorganic sulfur ($S^=$, $S_2O_3^=$, $S_4O_6^=$ and $SO_3^=$); their oxidation was determined by measuring oxygen uptake and the amount of sulfate formed.

Figure 6 shows an example of the results obtained for oxygen utilization. No oxygen uptake could be detected when the cells were supplied with 8 micromoles of sulfite. This may have been due to the toxicity of sulfite. The amounts of sulfate formed from 8 micromoles of $S_2O_3^=$, $S^=$, $S_4O_6^=$ and $SO_3^=$ were 12.0, 7.3, 12.8, and 0 micromoles, respectively.

The conversion of sulfide-sulfur to sulfate was almost complete, utilizing approximately 5 micromoles of oxygen during the oxidation. These results suggest that the conversion of sulfide to sulfate may be represented by the following equation:

The recoveries of the sulfur of thiosulfate and tetrathionate as sulfate were only 75 and 40%, respectively. Elemental sulfur is formed from thiosulfate during the growth of the organ-

Fig. 6. Oxidation of inorganic sulfur compounds by washed suspensions of *Thiobacillus* sp.

ism and its formation during respiration studies may account for the incomplete recovery of sulfur as sulfate. Assuming the formation of elemental sulfur during the oxidation of thiosulfate, the following equation is suggested by the results obtained:

These preliminary studies are being expanded so that a more complete knowledge of the metabolism of inorganic sulfur compounds may be obtained.

Autotrophic growth

The role of the autotroph is an important one in the complex soil environment. However, the reasons why strict autotrophs are unable to use organic compounds as sources of energy still defies explanation.

Studies on the autotrophic nature of the *Thiobacillus* sp. isolated from the acid-sulfate soil were initiated during the year.

The organism was provided with a variety of organic acids with and without thiosulfate; the growth of the or-

ganism, the production of sulfate, and pH of the culture solution were determined over a period of 12 days. Table 4 summarizes the results obtained for cultures supplied with both thiosulfate and organic acid. No growth and no sulfate production was found when the organism was provided with organic acid alone, indicating that it could not utilize these sources of carbon for energy. Stimulation of growth and sulfate production were detected when fumarate, α -ketoglutarate, citrate, and malate were added to the growth medium. Whereas an addition of succinate stimulated growth, it did not stimulate sulfate formation. The mechanism involved in stimulated thiosulfate oxidation are not understood. Further studies are in progress.

TABLE 4. Effect of organic acids on the growth of *Thiobacillus* sp. and thiosulfate oxidation by this organism.^a

Added acid (500/ μ g/ml)	pH	Optical density of culture (μ mole/ml)	SO ₄ ⁼
None	3.6	0.050	10.6
Fumarate	3.8	0.149	18.4
α -ketoglutarate	3.3	0.108	20.6
Pyruvate	4.8	0.027	4.5
Succinate	3.9	0.161	9.4
Acetate	4.8	0.004	0.0
Citrate	3.3	0.081	21.3
Formate	4.7	0.004	0.0
Malate	3.2	0.125	21.7

^a Results from determinations made after incubation for 12 days at 30 C.

PESTICIDE RESIDUES

Applications of insecticides at recommended field rates to soil can rarely be demonstrated to have a pronounced effect (detrimental or otherwise) upon the soil microflora. In fact, application rates often exceeding one hundred times the recommended dosage are usually required before any effect can be detected in the laboratory. It was unusual, therefore, to find that gamma-BHC applied at recommended rates into the flood water of rice paddies had a pronounced stimulatory effect upon the algal population. Results of studies initiated in late 1964 indicated that the stimulatory effect resulted from the inhibition by gamma-BHC of small animals which feed upon the algae. In the absence of these predators, the mass of algal tissue developing in the treated fields was visibly much greater than that developing in untreated fields.

In view of the dynamic state of the soil microflora, such a major shift in the biological equilibrium of the flooded-soil environment would be expected to cause changes in other segments of the soil population. Because the chemical changes which take place in a soil following submergence are largely governed by the activities of the soil microflora, it is important to know what effect additions of gamma-BHC have

upon the microflora and its activities, for some of these effects may lead to undesirable soil properties. Also, as the nitrogen-fixing algae have so often been considered important in maintaining fertility in submerged rice soils, it is important to know how they are affected by gamma-BHC. For these reasons, studies were continued in 1965 on the effects of gamma-BHC applications upon the following:

- (a) algal populations in submerged soils
- (b) the mineralization of soil nitrogen in flooded soils
- (c) nitrogen fixation by rice soils and
- (d) anaerobic nitrogen-fixing bacteria and phosphate-dissolving microorganisms in submerged soils.

Studies on the persistence of this insecticide in submerged soils were also initiated.

Effect of gamma-BHC upon algal populations in flooded soils

As the results of earlier experiments (Annual Report, 1964) indicated that applications of gamma-BHC in excess of 15 kg/ha may have an inhibitory effect upon algal populations in flooded soils, the effect of additions of gamma-

Fig. 7. Effect of γ -BHC on algal populations in submerged paddy soils. (A) First application of γ -BHC (active compound) at rates 2 and 20 kg/ha; (B) Second application of γ -BHC (active compound) at rates 3 and 30 kg/ha Louisiana clay: pH 4.7, O.M. 3.2%, Total N 0.21%, Maahas clay: pH 6.6, O.M. 2%, Total N 0.14%.

BHC at the recommended rate (5 kg/ha) and 10 times this rate (50 kg/ha) upon the algae in Maahas clay and Louisiana clay was studied. In these experiments gamma-BHC was applied, in accordance with the procedure recommended by the Entomology Department, as a split application viz., at 4 weeks (2 and 20 kg/ha) and at 8 weeks (3 and 30 kg/ha) after the soil was flooded. Applications of the insecticide at usual field rates to both soils resulted in a marked increase in algal populations (Fig. 7). No inhibition of algal development was detected at the higher level of gamma-BHC, although the algal numbers were generally less than in

soils treated at the recommended rate.

When the developing algal populations were subjected to detailed microscopic examination, it was found that the blue-green algae gave the greatest response to applications of gamma-BHC. Numbers of blue-green algae in the flood water of the treated soils 4 weeks after the first application of the insecticide were approximately 200 times greater than the numbers in the unamended soils. Figure 8 shows the results obtained with Louisiana clay. Populations of the other major algal groups e.g., unicellular and filamentous green algae, also increased in the treated soils.

Fig. 8. Effect of γ -BHC on populations of algae in Louisiana clay.

The results of these studies indicate that applications of gamma-BHC up to 10 times the recommended level have no detrimental effect upon algal populations in flooded soils. In fact, if suitable species are present, the increased numbers of indigenous filamentous blue-green algae may lead to increases in soil nitrogen through fixation of atmospheric nitrogen.

Experiments were performed to get some idea of the mass of algal tissue developing in flooded soils both in the presence and absence of gamma-BHC. Two soils (Maahas clay and Louisiana clay) were flooded, and glass sampling tubes, open at both ends but with a very fine nylon net fixed to one end, were placed with the net resting on the soil surface and the other end approximate-

ly 2 mm below the water surface. The soils were treated with gamma-BHC at the same rates as before (5 and 50 kg/ha). The irrigation water was sampled periodically, and the mass of algal growth determined. Sampling was effected by bringing another tube of the same diameter down onto the open end of the sampling tube and cutting a disc from the algal bloom on the water surface. The sample tube was then removed, the algae retained by the net plus the disc were washed, dried, and weighed.

TABLE 5. Effect of gamma-BHC upon the weight of algal tissue developing in submerged soils.^a

Soil	Amendment	Dry weight of algal tissue (g/sq m) ^b
Maahas Clay	None	568
	5 kg/ha gamma-BHC	699
	50 kg/ha gamma-BHC	758
Louisiana Clay	None	683
	5 kg/ha gamma-BHC	926
	50 kg/ha gamma-BHC	750

^a Samples taken 14 weeks after soil submergence.

^b Computed on a surface area basis of flood water, 8 cm deep.

The results of this study indicate that large amounts of organic matter in the form of algal tissue are synthesized in the flood water of a submerged soil and that additions of gamma-BHC enhance this production (Table 5). Excretory products of viable algal cells, and also the products of decomposition of algal tissues, may supply added energy-rich material to the heterotrophic nitrogen-fixing bacteria, thereby increasing the amount of nitrogen-fixed by heterotrophic species.

Effect of gamma-BHC upon the mineralization of soil nitrogen in flooded soils

Mineralization of organic nitrogen is one of the most important microbial processes in submerged rice soils since

it releases nitrogen in a form which is available to the rice plant. Any cultural practice which might inhibit this process, such as pesticide applications, would be undesirable.

In a study of the effect of gamma-BHC upon nitrogen mineralization, it was found that application rates up to 10 times the recommended rate had no effect upon this process in Maahas clay. In Louisiana clay, however, significantly more exchangeable ammonium nitrogen was found in the treated soils (Fig. 9). The increase in exchangeable ammonium, following additions of gamma-BHC, may have been caused by the

tion of native soil nitrogen in either Maahas clay or Louisiana clay.

Effect of gamma-BHC upon nitrogen fixation by submerged soils

In view of the tremendous increases in algal populations which were found following additions of gamma-BHC to submerged soils, and the possible influence this might have upon the nitrogen-fixing capacity of flooded soil, laboratory studies were conducted to test the effect of gamma-BHC upon nitrogen fixation by rice soils. Three soils (Maahas clay, Louisiana clay and Calabanga clay) were flooded and in-

Fig. 9. Effect of γ -BHC on the mineralization of soil nitrogen in submerged soil.

(A)—First application of γ -BHC (active compound) at rates 2 and 20 kg/ha.

(B)—Second application of γ -BHC (active compound) at rates 3 and 30 kg/ha Louisiana Clay: pH 4.7, O.M. 3.2%, Total N 0.21%.

activities of the increased numbers of nitrogen-fixing blue-green algae, or by a stimulation of decomposition of native organic matter by the large additions of organic algal tissues. Algal populations in Louisiana clay were generally four to eight times larger than in Maahas clay. It is considered unlikely that gamma-BHC *per se* stimulates nitrogen mineralization.

The results of this study show that applications of gamma-BHC up to 10 times the recommended rate had no detrimental effect upon the mineraliza-

cubated for a month in the light in sealed containers with an atmosphere (N₂, O₂ and He) enriched with ¹⁵N₂ (65 atom % excess). One series of soils received 6 kg/ha of gamma-BHC. At the end of the incubation period, soil nitrogen was converted to the ammonium form which was analyzed for enrichment with ¹⁵N.

The results in Table 6 show that increases in nitrogen fixation in Maahas clay and Louisiana clay of 91 and 62 percent, respectively, were associated with an application of gamma-BHC. The

nitrogen-fixing system of Calabanga clay, however, was partially inhibited by an addition of gamma-BHC. The results indicate that applications of

TABLE 6. Effect of gamma-BHC upon nitrogen fixation by rice soils.

Soil amendment	Atom % excess ^{15}N in soil nitrogen ^a		
	Maahas clay	Luisiana clay	Calabanga clay
None	0.022	0.028	0.066
Gamma-BHC (6 kg/ha)	0.042	0.045	0.035

^a Determined after incubation for one month in the light.

gamma-BHC at recommended rates to Maahas clay and Luisiana clay may increase soil nitrogen by stimulating the nitrogen-fixing processes. The inhibitory effect of gamma-BHC upon nitrogen fixation in Calabanga clay is not understood. Further studies are indicated.

Effect of gamma-BHC upon certain sections of the microflora of submerged soils

The effect of gamma-BHC upon nitrogen-fixing anaerobic bacteria, aerobic phosphate-dissolving fungi and bacteria, and anaerobic phosphate-dissolving bacteria was studied. The insecticide was added at the rate of 6 kg/ha to the flood water of Maahas and Luisiana clay, 6 weeks after flooding. Populations of the selected organisms occurring in the soil were followed for 11 weeks after applying gamma-BHC.

No detrimental effect upon the populations of any of the selected organisms was detected. One other point of interest arising from these studies was that populations of phosphate-dissolving bacteria were approximately 10 times greater in the Maahas clay soil than in the latosolic Luisiana soil. Also, the presence of phosphate-dissolving fungi was detected only in the latosolic soil.

Persistence of gamma-BHC in submerged soils

Two soils (Maahas clay and Luisiana clay) treated with gamma-BHC (6 kg/ha) 6 weeks after flooding and untreated were sampled periodically and the algal populations determined quantitatively. Algal populations were much higher in the treated soils. At about 7 weeks after treatment, however, the numbers of algae began to decrease, and by the eleventh week were equal to or less than the numbers in the untreated soil.

Throughout the experimental period, the flood water of the untreated soils contained large numbers of small crustaceans. However, none were visible in the treated soils until around 6 to 7 weeks after the applications of gamma-BHC were made. The beginning of the decline in algal populations in the treated soils coincided with the recolonization of the flood waters by crustaceans. A second application at the rate of 6 kg/ha of the insecticide was made during the eleventh week after the first application. No quantitative measure of algal numbers was made, but frequent observations of the flooded soil revealed an apparent increase again in algal numbers as a result of the killing of the crustacean population by gamma-BHC. The time elapsing between the second application of gamma-BHC and the recolonization by the crustaceans was shorter than that which was noted following the first application. Recolonization after a third application was even more rapid. If the crustaceans can be considered to be biological indicators for the presence of gamma-BHC, then the persistence of the insecticide in the two soils following the first application is around 7 weeks. Also, the shortening persistence of gamma-BHC, indicated by the shorter recolonization times following a second and third application of the chemical suggest the progressive establishment of populations of microorganisms active in the degradation of gamma-BHC, and a role for the soil microflora in the factors governing the persistence of the chemical. Current studies, forming part of a project sponsored

Fig. 10. The persistence of γ -BHC in sterilized and unsterilized Louisiana clay following submergence.

jointly by the National Science Development Board of the Philippines and IRRI, using specific chemical procedures, have confirmed some of these findings.

Samples of Louisiana clay (sterilized and non-sterilized) were flooded, treated with gamma-BHC (80 ppm) and incubated at 30 C. Samples were removed every 10 days for 50 days, extracted, and analyzed by gas chromatography for residual gamma-BHC. The results in Fig. 10 show that the insecticide disappeared more rapidly from the non-sterilized soil than from the sterilized soil, indicating a biological effect on the persistence of gamma-BHC. Loss from the sterilized soil was probably due to co-distillation of the insecticide with water vapor. Further studies are in progress.

PLANT-MICROORGANISM INTERACTIONS

Additional attempts were made during the year to further define the rhizosphere of the rice plant in terms of microbial populations and root exudates. The effects of inoculating soil with a blue-green alga, and inoculating seed with a nitrogen-fixing bacterium, upon the yield of rice grain were also studied.

Root exudate studies

The figures recorded (Annual Report, 1964, pp. 252 and 253) for the total carbohydrate content of root exudates of rice varieties were incorrectly computed. These figures should have been as follows: Chianung 242, 18.1, Norin 22, 8.0, Norin 36, 8.2, Norin 29, 12.4, Norin 37, 18.4, and Norin 32, 25.1 (mg/g dry wt of root).

Root exudate studies with Chianung 242 were continued through the year. Root exudates of aseptically raised seedlings were found to contain 17.7 mg of carbohydrate material per g (dry weight) of root tissue after 10 days incubation. This represented approximately 160 μ g carbohydrate per seedling.

Chromatographic analysis of the root exudates revealed the presence of four

monosaccharides, one trisaccharide, and two oligosaccharides. Quantitative analysis of these carbohydrates following elution gave approximately 86 percent recovery of the total carbohydrate assay (Table 7). Acid hydrolysis of the eluted oligosaccharides followed by paper chromatography of the hydrolyzates showed that the major components were glucose and xylose.

TABLE 7. Carbohydrate content of root exudates of seedlings of Chianung 242.

Carbohydrate	Amount recovered (mg/g dry wt root)
Glucose	2.03
Raffinose	0.93
Fructose + arabinose	4.66
Xylose	1.09
Oligosaccharide I	4.20
Oligosaccharide II	2.34

The results of these studies show that considerable amounts of carbohydrate are released into the rhizosphere of rice seedlings in the form of root exudates. These exudates undoubtedly play an important role in determining the rhizosphere microflora during the early stages of development of the rice plant.

Rhizosphere studies

The significance of phosphate-dissolving bacteria in the increase in water-soluble phosphorus, which occurs after a soil is flooded, is uncertain. However, phosphorus that has been mobilized following flooding may be precipitated with iron in the rhizosphere after oxidation of this zone by rice roots. Phosphate-dissolving bacteria occurring in the rhizosphere may help to render this phosphorus available to the plant.

To obtain information on the occurrence of phosphate-dissolving bacteria in the rhizosphere, rice plants (Chianung 242) grown in Maahas clay were sampled at five stages from transplanting to maturity, and the numbers of aerobic and anaerobic phosphate-dissolving bacteria occurring in the rhizosphere were assessed.

TABLE 8. Rhizosphere effect on aerobic and anaerobic phosphate-dissolving bacteria in soil planted to rice.

Age of plant (days)	R:S ^a	
	Aerobic	Anaerobic
21	47	183
34	17	24
55	5	22
90	4	3
114	3	14

$$^a R : S = \frac{\text{Numbers of bacteria/g rhizosphere soil}}{\text{Numbers of bacteria/g non-rhizosphere soil}}$$

Large populations of both anaerobic and aerobic phosphate-dissolving bacteria (12.2×10^6 and 7.8×10^6 cells/g dry root weight, respectively) were detected at the transplanting stage (21 days). Populations of anaerobic phosphate-dissolving bacteria in the rhizosphere declined from transplanting to maturity when there were 2.4×10^6 cells/g dry weight of root. On the other hand, the numbers of aerobic phosphate-dissolving bacteria increased after transplanting, reaching a maximum population at tillering (37×10^6 cells/g dry root wt). After this stage the num-

bers declined, and at maturity a population of 7.1×10^6 cells/g dry weight of root was found.

The rice roots were found to exert a strong rhizosphere effect upon both types of phosphate-dissolving bacteria, particularly during the early stages of rice plant development (Table 8).

The large populations of phosphate-dissolving bacteria in the rhizosphere of the rice plant, and the large R:S ratios suggest that these organisms may be important in mobilizing precipitated phosphorus in the rhizosphere.

Soil and seedling inoculation

Inoculation of rice paddies with suitable nitrogen-fixing blue-green algae has been reported to increase rice yields when no fertilizer nitrogen was applied. For this reason, experiments were conducted during the year on the effect of two different methods of inoculation upon the yield of grain and straw.

The methods of inoculation attempted were: (a) inoculation of the flood water with a blue-green alga isolated from Maahas clay (refer to Section on nitrogen fixation in rice soils) and (b) inoculation of seedlings (germinated 3 days) with a suspension of a nitrogen-fixing bacterium (2.3×10^5 cells/seed) isolated from Maahas clay (*Clostridium* sp., refer to Section on nitrogen fixation in rice soils). The flood water was modified to provide a more suitable environment for the algae by applying lime (1,000 kg/ha) and molybdenum (0.28 kg/ha). The plants were sprayed weekly with sevin, and gamma-BHC was applied to the flood water (total application, 5 kg/ha). The soil used in both studies was Maahas clay.

Statistical treatment of the results in both experiments showed that no significant increase in either yield of grain or straw could be attributed to inoculation. The failure to produce any effect due to inoculation may have resulted from the choice of unsuitable species for the inoculation. Also, any nitrogen added in the form of algal tissue may not be available to the present crop. Further studies are required to assess the value and practicability of algal inoculation of rice paddies.

Agronomy

The major topics of agronomic research in 1965 were: (1) maximization of annual rice yields with intensive cultural practices, (2) grain yield in relation to date of planting, (3) soil fertility and fertilizer management, (4) weed control in lowland and upland rice, and (5) other cultural practices, including water management, spacing, planting methods, and the effects of insecticidal applications on the nitrogen status of the plant and soil.

Favorable weather conditions prevailed in the 1965 wet season and the average yields were the highest in the 4-year history of the Institute. Although dry season weather was normal, yields in some cases were nearly 9 metric tons per hectare and yields of more than 8 tons were achieved with five different varieties in at least 10 experiments. The wet season experimental results were extremely good with yields in most experiments exceeding 6 tons in the more favorable treatments. Much credit for the high yields must be attributed to improved pest control and the use of improved varieties, but weather also played a major role.

The pattern of rainfall and solar radiation for the 1964 and 1965 crop years is shown in Figs. 2 and 3 on pages 12 and 13. The rainfall recorded during the rainy season was only half the normal value. By November, 43.2 inches had fallen compared with 73.6 inches for the long-term average. Although solar radiation curves were slightly lower (7.7%) than normal in the 1965 wet season, the lower rainfall in September and October (< 50% of normal) is thought to have been a major contributing factor to the high yield. In addition, directly related to these two factors, the 1965 season was virtually free of typhoons; only two tropical storms or typhoons with center within 75 miles were

reported.

The varieties which have been especially high-yielding in soil fertility experiments during the 1965 dry and wet seasons are Taichung (Native) 1, B5580, PI 215936, and Milfor-6(2). These produced an average total yield of from 13,444 kg/ha/2 crops to 14,781 kg/ha/2 crops, whereas the tall, weak-strawed variety, Intan, produced only 6,242 kg/ha/2 crops.

Varieties such as Taichung (Native) 1, 6993 (B5580), Milfor-6(2), and PI 215936 yielded 8,239 and 8,632 kg/ha rough rice during the dry season. During the wet season, Taichung (Native) 1 and IR9-60 yielded more than 7,000 kg/ha, and 6,993 and PI 215936 produced 6,200-6,300 kg/ha. The best fertilizer treatment combination resulted in 15,383 kg/ha/2 crops in the nitrogen-response experiments.

Most of the high yields obtained during the dry season are attributed to the use of high-yielding varieties with effective, precise cultural practices and, during the wet season, a combination of favorable weather (less rainfall, slightly higher sunlight intensity) and careful management.

These management practices require a well-established stand, adequate nitrogen, precise and timely pest and weed control, and a plentiful and assured water supply.

MAXIMUM YIELD AND CONTINUOUS CROPPING EXPERIMENTS

During the year, the maximum yield experiment was harvested three times, making the ninth consecutive harvest from the experiment since its beginning. The treatments consisted of four levels of applied nitrogen, four varieties, and three planting methods — a re-design of the experiment reported last year. The inclusion of direct-seeding as a variable in the experiment made the requirement for short duration varieties more stringent, for the time during which the field is occupied is longer for direct-seeded rice than for that which is transplanted.

Figure 1 and Table 1 illustrate the best treatment combinations from the

48 treatments used in each of the seven crops in the 1963 to 1965 crop years. Despite instances of heavy rainfall, low light intensity, and serious disease problems during the course of the study, the annual crop totals represent substantial increases in yield over traditional methods. The off-season crop in 1964 was particularly disappointing because of low light intensity and severe virus infection, particularly in transplanted treatments.

Table 1 shows the total yield and daily production possible if the best combination of variety and treatment had been used exclusively for three successive crops. The best treatment and

Fig. 1. Maximum yields and treatment combinations in a continuously cropped rice experiment. The best 3-crop combination yielded 17.8 ton/ha in 384 days, IRRI.

variety combinations from the three successive crops harvested up to November, 1965, produced gross yields of 17,814 kg/ha in 384 days, which is an increase of about 1,500 kg/ha or 3.1 kg/ha/day over the best three-crop combination reported last year. The second best choice would have been continuous production of the variety Chia-

nung 242 which, from three successive crops, would have yielded a total of between 15,000 and 16,000 kg/ha. The third choice would be three crops of Milfor-6(2) at its optimum planting method and fertility level.

A gross yield of 14,800 kg/ha and a daily output of 38.6 kg/ha/day from Milfor illustrate the potential of pre-

TABLE 1. Yield and production efficiency from a continuous-rice-production experiment in three-crop cycles.

Duration of 3-crop cycle (including land preparation)	June, 1964 to July, 1965 398 days		Oct., 1964 to Nov., 1965 384 days	
	(kg/ha)	(kg/ha/day)	(kg/ha)	(kg/ha/day)
1. Best treatment and variety combination	15,909	40.0	17,814	46.4
2. Best treatment, Chianung 242	15,449	38.8	16,492	42.9
3. Best treatment, Milfor-6(2)	13,606	34.2	14,838	38.6
4. Transplanted, Milfor-6(2)	11,397	28.6	13,426	35.0
5. Transplanted, Chianung 242	12,693	31.9	14,659	38.2
6. Mean treatment, transplanted	10,374	26.1	13,249	34.5
7. Mean treatment, broadcast	11,709	29.4	13,727	35.7
8. Mean treatment, drilled	12,200	30.6	14,134	36.8
9. Minimum treatment & variety combination	6,883	17.3	9,262	24.1

sently available varieties when grown under improved cultural practices. The treatment means for the transplanting treatment of all varieties gave yields of 13.2 metric ton/ha in the second three-crop cycle; broadcast and drilled treatments gave slightly higher yields but the differences were not statistically significant. The minimum treatment and variety combination was still capable of yielding between 6.8 and 9.2 metric ton/ha per year, or between two and three times the present average output from traditionally managed rice crops.

The minimum experimental yields are, at worst, substantially higher than the annual output from irrigated rice, managed for a single crop during the year. The increased production from the second three-crop combination can be attributed principally to two factors: the use of Taichung (Native) 1 as the test variety; and intensified plant protection measures, including applications of at least 9 kg/ha of γ -BHC, and 12 sprays of sevin at 3 kg/ha each.

Under the high levels of management practiced in this experiment, Taichung

(Native) 1 yielded 10% more than Chianung 242 in the dry season and 17% more in the wet season as the average of all treatments. On a best treatment basis, it produced 31 and 23% more grain in the dry season than Milfor-6(2) and 9795 respectively, and 19 and 37% more during the wet season.

The extensive plant protection measures, particularly insecticide application, were to detect even the small treatment differences and to obtain the maximum possible grain yield under experimental conditions. However, on a farm basis, these insecticide applications, particularly the sevin treatments, can be reduced considerably without greatly increasing the hazard of loss.

Figure 2 illustrates the yield and successive crop combinations when the Milfor variety was either transplanted or broadcast with the optimum levels of nitrogen determined from the experiment. This variety yielded between 4 and 5 ton/ha. Even without fertilizer nitrogen, and under conditions of low light and high rainfall, its yields were high on the fertile Maahas clay.

Fig. 2. Grain yield of the indica variety Milfor-6(2) in the best treatments in a continuous cropping experiment, IRRI, 1963-65.

GRAIN YIELD IN RELATION TO PLANTING DATE

An experiment was begun in 1963 with monthly plantings of three non-seasonal, early-maturing *indica* varieties, Peta, Milfor-6(2), and Taichung (Native) 1. Each variety on each date was planted at three spacings and at two levels of nitrogen.

vere rat damage, heavy infestation of bacterial leaf blight, virus disease, or direct damage from leafhoppers and stem borers. The problems of disease and pest protection have been greatest for plantings made in March and April or September and October. The yield

Fig. 3. Yields of indica varieties planted at four spacings each month during two years. Only crops without damage from predators were recorded, IRRI, 1964 and 1965.

The current crop season completes the second full year in which data have been collected and some preliminary analysis of the relationship between rice yield and some environmental factors measured during the experiment is now possible. Of principal interest has been the correlation of the growth and yield of the three varieties with solar radiation. Figure 3 shows the relationship of the mean yields of all three varieties, plotted against date of planting, with separate curves drawn for each spacing. In plotting the curves, those values believed to represent normal growth under well protected, good management conditions were used.

In several plantings no harvest was made or yields were poor because of se-

vere rat damage, heavy infestation of bacterial leaf blight, virus disease, or direct damage from leafhoppers and stem borers. The problems of disease and pest protection have been greatest for plantings made in March and April or September and October. The yield curves follow a distinct trend, and on the average, higher yields were obtained from closer spacings, either 15 x 15 or 25 x 25 cm. These differences are not significant between themselves but the two closest spacings apparently give slightly better yields than the two wider ones.

In Fig. 4, grain yield for all varieties, spacings, and nitrogen levels is plotted against total solar radiation for the 30 days preceding harvest. This figure is used because physiological evidence indicates that most of the photosynthetic activity contributing to grain filling, and starch formation occurs late in the plant's life. The yield curve follows solar radiation values closely. The correlation coefficient, based on values from

Fig. 4. Mean yields for three varieties (Taichung (Native) 1, Milfor-6(2), and Peta) at four spacings and two levels of nitrogen plotted against solar radiation totals during the last 30 days of the crop, IRRI.

May, 1964, to November, 1965, is 0.86 and highly significant. This represents a mean of all values obtained after improved plant protection measures had been initiated.

Figure 5 shows the relationship of the correlation coefficient between solar radiation and yield for the varying periods of time from the 6th to the 45th day before harvest. The three varieties differ substantially in their response to solar radiation. The correlation coefficient for the yield of Peta, which is tall and leafy and normally lodged by the time heading has occurred, shows little change from the 45th to the 50th day. Both Milfor and Taichung (Native) 1, however, show improvements in the correlation coefficient with the longer periods. Both 40 and 45 days were more closely correlated with yield for these varieties than the 30-day units selected on the basis of the earliest information which was based on Peta. The fundamentally different curve for the Taichung (Native) 1 correlation is believed to reflect a different growth pattern, possibly involving greater relative carbohydrate storage with later translocation to the panicle than for other varieties.

Fig. 5. Correlation coefficients for yield of three indica varieties with solar radiation during periods of varying length before the sixth day before harvest. IRRI, 1964 and 1965 seasons.

The early senescence of leaves in Taichung (Native) 1, probably a normal part of its maturation, also contributes to the lack of correlation with solar radiation values late in the crop cycle. The

greater disease susceptibility of Taichung (Native) 1 may also contribute to its failure to photosynthesize in the late stages of maturity. Both Milfor and Peta generally retain more green leaf tissue at maturity, and their yields are therefore generally more closely correlated with solar radiation values near harvest.

other two varieties and was consistently the lowest. Taichung (Native) 1 showed the highest average values and was highest for all plantings in both seasons.

The greatest efficiency of just over 20 grams of grain/g-cal was obtained from the planting made in July, 1965, which matured during a relatively

Fig. 6. Grain production efficiency (g/g-cal/cm²/day) for three indica varieties in a date-of-planting experiment, IRRI, 1964 and 1965 seasons.

A value of considerable agronomic significance and physiological interest is the grain production efficiency figure for solar radiation (Fig. 6). The average number of grams of grain produced/g-cal/cm²/day during the last 30 days of growth was 11.8. The values varied significantly among varieties: Peta, 8.4 grams; Milfor, 11.5 grams; and Taichung (Native) 1, 15.5 g-cal/cm²/day. The values also varied considerably with different planting dates. Peta, in general, varied less than the

cloudy period. The curve for Taichung (Native) 1 indicates that this variety has a fundamentally efficient grain production capacity during periods of low radiation as well as during periods of higher radiation and that it is actually greater during periods of low radiation. The values for g grain/g-cal/cm²/day are being studied as units for evaluating the basic agronomic efficiency of the combination of varietal productive capacity and management practices.

SOIL FERTILITY AND FERTILIZER MANAGEMENT

With rice varieties with a better plant type, either selected or developed by the Institute, different fertilizer practices

are needed. The desired varieties are to be adapted to a high level of nitrogen nutrition and should provide grain yield

Fig. 7. Effects of nitrogen levels on the grain yield of seven varieties, IRRI, 1965 dry season.

response to fertilizer even on fertile soils. The emphasis in soil fertility research has been (1) to determine the optimum fertility requirement for maximum grain yield from both traditional and improved varieties grown in the dry and wet seasons, and (2) management of fertilizer nitrogen to obtain more efficient usage at lower application rates without reducing the yield.

Soil variability is such that experiments on applying nitrogen give results which differ according to the conditions under which they were obtained. Conflicting results have been reported

on matters such as rate of application, source of nitrogen, and method and time of applying fertilizer. Experiments at the Institute and on outside farms have been designed to increase our understanding of fertilizer management practices under various environmental conditions, including adequate irrigation, pest control, and supply of other plant nutrients.

Other topics studied included (1) phosphorus availability and fertilizer response in a latosol reported to have a phosphorus status which is either deficient or marginal, (2) silica fertilization in lowland rice, (3) effects of soil-

Fig. 8. Effects of nitrogen levels on the grain yield of eight varieties, IRRI, 1965 wet season.

applied insecticides on nitrogen transformation, insect and disease control, and grain yield of rice, (4) cooperative fertility experiments at one of the Phil-

ippine Bureau of Plant Industry experiment stations, and (5) cooperative nitrogen-response experiments in farmers' fields.

Fig. 9. While the tall leafy, late-maturing indica variety Intan lodged severely at heading without N fertilizer, the dwarf, nitrogen-responsive, early-maturing indica varieties like 6993 (B5580), Taichung (Native) 1, and IR9-60 stood erect even at 105 kg/ha N until nearly time of harvest, IRRI, 1965 wet season.

Nitrogen responsiveness and yield potential of different varietal types

The response of a variety to nitrogen must be measured over several seasons and a wide range of soil and climatic conditions before drawing conclusions or making predictions. While some varieties yield better at low levels of fertility, others attain their potential yield only after heavy fertilization. Furthermore, precise response curves can be obtained only by testing a large number of nitrogen application rates.

Experiments in the dry and wet seasons involved seven or eight varieties differing in height, tillering ability, and hence in response to nitrogen.

Dry season. The varieties used were Taichung (Native) 1, and 6993 (B5580) which are dwarf early-maturing *indica* varieties; PI 215936 and CI

Fig. 10. Effect of nitrogen levels on dry matter production of two varietal types at harvest, IRRI, 1965 wet season.

9545 which are intermediate in height and early-maturing ponlai varieties; Arkrose x Bluebonnet, a weak-strawed, fairly tall, but early-maturing *indica* rice; 81B-25, a tall late-maturing *indica* rice from Surinam; and Intan, a tall and extremely weak-strawed *indica* rice from the Philippines. Nitrogen was harrowed-in at a rate which varied from 0 to 210 kg/ha in 30 kg increments.

Early-maturing, dwarf varieties yielded considerably better at higher levels of fertility than did medium- to late-maturing varieties (Fig. 7). The deep soil of the experimental area was left in a weed fallow during the previous cropping season. The two crops of weeds plowed under before the experiment commenced resulted in a build-up of soil fertility, and most varieties yielded 6,000 kg/ha rough rice without added nitrogen. Variety 6993 (B5580) was the only one which did not lodge at harvest even at 210 kg/ha N. Prior to harvest, 2.5 inches of rain fell in half an hour and most varieties, including the early dwarfs, lodged. The variety 6993 did not lodge, thus demonstrating that it is adapted to high fertility and adverse climatic conditions; its grain yield (8,238 kg/ha) was the highest of the seven varieties tested. The varieties lodged in the following sequence:

Intan > Bluebonnet X Arkrose > PI 215936 = CI 9545 > Taichung (Native) 1 > 81B-25 > 6993 (no lodging).

Results of this study permit the following generalizations:

(1) 6993 (B5580), PI 215936, CI 9545, and Taichung (Native) 1 are high-yielding, early-maturing (115-125 days from seeding to maturity) varieties adapted to high levels of fertility (at least 90 kg/ha N).

(2) Arkrose X Bluebonnet is a weak-strawed line, not adapted to high fertility.

(3) Intan and 81B-25 are adapted only to low levels of fertility.

Wet season. The wet season experiment was conducted on a different site from that conducted in the dry season. Laboratory analysis before planting revealed that the soil contained 53-164 kg

/ha $\text{NH}_4^+\text{-N}$ (wet analysis).

During the wet season also, dwarf varieties outyielded medium to tall varieties (Fig. 8). Without nitrogen fertilizer, Intan lodged severely at an early stage of growth, but at higher levels of nitrogen it lodged even earlier. The dwarf, early-maturing varieties, such as 6993, Taichung (Native) 1, and IR9-60, were extremely resistant to lodging even at high levels of nitrogen (Fig. 9). Taichung (Native) 1 was badly affected by bacterial leaf blight 3 weeks before harvest and lodged severely but nevertheless yielded 7,145 kg/ha of rough rice.

Compared with the no-nitrogen controls, the yields of both IR9-60 and Taichung (Native) 1 were significantly higher where 60 kg/ha N were applied. IR9-60 apparently has the same yield potential as Taichung (Native) 1 and under the experimental conditions was more resistant to bacterial leaf blight. They are both top yielders in comparison with the other six varieties. This is the first variety developed at the Institute to be included in the fertility experiment and its performance was equal to that of the Taiwan dwarf. Further tests under a wide range of soil and environmental conditions, including some in farmers' fields, will determine its potential as a commercial variety.

Varieties with better plant type, such as Taichung (Native) 1 and IR9-60, not only responded to added nitrogen with increased grain yield, but also increased straw yield and hence dry matter production. On the other hand, a tall leafy variety, Intan, produced more straw than grain at any given nitrogen level; the grain and straw yields actually decreased at higher nitrogen levels, resulting in low total dry matter production (Fig. 10).

At all fertility levels, IR9-60 produced substantially more straw than Intan, and even more than Taichung (Native) 1. The difference in plant height at harvest between IR9-60 and Taichung (Native) 1 was only 2 cm (average of all fertility levels). At earlier stages of growth, Intan was much more vegetative than IR9-60 or Taichung (Native) 1. Thirty days after trans-

planting (51 days from seeding) the height response to added nitrogen was 25 cm for Intan, 14 cm for Taichung (Native) 1, and 10 cm for IR9-60. These increases correspond to 36, 23, and 18 percent respectively over the check. At harvest they had narrowed to 7 to 11 percent.

An earlier study (Annual Report, 1964) indicated that nitrogen content at an early growth stage was correlated positively with yield. With applications of 90 and 105 kg/ha N, both IR9-60 and Taichung (Native) 1 had higher nitrogen contents 30 days after transplanting than Intan. IR9-60 had a higher nitrogen content 30 days after transplanting than Intan at any level of fertility and was also more efficient, as indicated by the high plant nitrogen content, in utilizing native soil fertility (no N added) than either Taichung (Native) 1 or Intan. This may explain why IR9-60 produced more grain and straw in the no-fertilizer treatment.

During the 1965 dry and wet seasons, Taichung (Native) 1 produced, with the best treatment combination, 14,781 kg/ha/2 crops rough rice, followed by variety 6993 with 14,547 kg/ha/2 crops and Intan with 6,242 kg/ha/2 crops. These yield data indicate the potential of the two extreme varietal types under the experimental conditions.

Time of nitrogen incorporation

Sometimes freshly incorporated organic material produces conditions toxic to rice seedlings. When organic sources of nitrogen (such as green matter of ipil-ipil leaf) are used, a practice in some Asian countries, it may be desirable to incorporate them a few weeks before transplanting. Flooding the soil a few weeks before transplanting has proved to be advantageous (Annual Report, 1963). The 1964 wet season data (Annual Report, 1964) showed that Maahas clay was able to retain nitrogen if organic matter was well-incorporated and the soil kept under continuous submergence. It may also be advantageous to incorporate inorganic fertilizer and maintain continuous submergence before transplanting.

During the dry season, an experiment

Fig. 11. Relationship between nitrogen content (%) in plant at 30, 60, and 90 days after transplanting, as affected by various methods of N application, and grain yield of Chianan 8, IRRI, 1965 dry season.

was conducted in which two sources of nitrogen (ipil-ipil leaf — *Leucaena glauca* — and ammonium sulfate) were incorporated at 3, 2, 1, 0 weeks before transplanting. The plots were then kept continuously submerged. The two varieties used were B572-A3-47, an early-maturing, medium height *indica* grain type from Texas, and Taichung (Native) 1.

Results show that ammonium sulfate can be applied 3 weeks before transplanting in Maahas clay under continuous submergence without any reduction in grain yield (Table 2). If land must be prepared 3 weeks before transplanting, a heavy soil with high exchange capacity (45-60 m.e./100 g soil) can retain $\text{NH}_4^+\text{-N}$ without any appreciable loss or reduction in grain yield. With an organic source of nitrogen (ipil-ipil leaf) the incorporation one week before transplanting provided enough time for the organic matter to decompose and provide adequate available nitrogen without significant reduction in grain yield (Table 2). The va-

TABLE 2. Effects of time of N incorporation and period of submergence on the grain yield of B572-A3-47 and Taichung (Native) 1, IRRI, 1965 dry season.

Grain yield at 14% moisture (average, 3 replicates)								
Period of submergence (weeks)	Time of N incorporation (weeks before transplanting)	B572-A3-47			Taichung (Native) 1			Mean (time of incorporation)
		No nitrogen	80 kg/ha N as		No nitrogen	80 kg/ha N as		
			(NH ₄) ₂ SO ₄	Ipil-ipil leaf		(NH ₄) ₂ SO ₄	Ipil-ipil leaf	
		(kg/ha)			(kg/ha)			
3	3	5218	6572	5725	6528	7140	6516	6283
2	2	4997	5468	5861	6622	6109	6810	5978
1	1	5081	6290	5835	5966	6715	7200	6181
0	0	4364	6332	4645	5825	7203	6535	5817
Mean (sources)		4915	6165	5516	6235	6792	6765	

Duration (days):	125-135 days		139 days
<i>Analysis of Variance:</i>		L.S.D.	cv ($\bar{x}$) %
Sources**		474	3.8
Time of N incorporation ^{n,s} .		—	3.9
Variety**		343	1.3
			CV (X) %
			19
			17
			8

riety B572-A3-47 produced significantly lower yield when planted in plots treated with ipil-ipil leaf than when planted in the ammonium sulfate treatments. The difference was striking in non-submerged treatments (0 week). These differences due to organic and inorganic sources of nitrogen did not occur with Taichung (Native) 1. Under both low (no fertilizer) and high levels (80 kg/ha N) of fertility, Taichung (Native) 1 considerably outyielded B572-A3-47.

At transplanting, Maahas clay contained maximum NH₄⁺-N when submerged for 2 weeks with either organic or inorganic sources. Nitrogen, from either source, increased to between 140 to 150 kg/ha within 2 weeks of submergence, compared with a 20-kg increase after 3 weeks of submergence without added nitrogen, and a net increase of 120-130 kg/ha N with added nitrogen. However, during the first 2 weeks of submergence (NH₄)₂SO₄ treated plots contained 96 kg more nitrogen (274 kg/ha N) than the ipil-ipil treated ones (178/kg N). In general (NH₄)₂SO₄ treated plots contained more NH₄⁺-N at planting than did ipil-ipil treatments, resulting in increased height and tiller number during the first 30 days

after transplanting. At harvest, the plots of all treatments contained the same amount of NH₄⁺-N (about 50 kg/ha N) as at the time of nitrogen incorporation.

Fig. 12. Relationship between nitrogen content (%) in grain and straw as affected by various methods of N application and grain yield of Chianan 8, IRRI, 1965 dry season.

Forms and methods of application of nitrogen fertilizer

In many southeast Asian countries, the high cost and limited availability of nitrogen fertilizer restricts its use. But larger yields are possible only from better varieties adapted to higher levels of fertility. To utilize available nitrogen supplies most effectively, better management is needed to increase the efficiency of nitrogen usage at lower levels of application. One of the methods known to increase nitrogen efficiency is to place the fertilizer in the reduced layer of the soil. Another procedure might be to adjust fertilizer release rate to better meet the nitrogen-demand curve of the crop. This procedure might be particularly useful with long duration varieties. A field-placement test was conducted during the 1965 dry season using both ammonium sulfate and urea as standard and as slow-release products.

A medium-release EAP (emulsified asphalt-paraffin) coated ammonium sulfate material (3032)¹ gave the best

¹ Experimental materials were received from the Esso Research and Engineering Company, Linden, N.J., U.S.A.

TABLE 3. Effects of some standard and slow release nitrogen fertilizer materials on the grain yield of Chianan 8, Peta, and Intan, IRRI, 1965 dry season.

		Grain yield at 14% moisture						
		Chianan 8		Intan		Peta		
Fertilizer material	Percent nitrogen	Rate of release in hours (75% of total)	Method of application					
			Broadcast and incorporated	Placement 15 cm deep	Broadcast and incorporated	Placement 15 cm deep	Broadcast and incorporated	Placement 15 cm deep
			(kg/ha)		(kg/ha)		(kg/ha)	
Ammonium sulfate (AS)	20.6	—	6254	6202	4125	3780	1846	1800
Urea	45.0	—	5637	7002	5433	2170	2150	2121
EAP 3011 (AS)	18.5	150	6040	7099	1297	3605	2360	2122
EAP 3032 (AS)	17.0	650	6034	7701	5022	4893	3848	2800
EAP 3035 (AS)	17.5	4000	5384	6363	4618	5061	3264	2659
EAP 3031 (Urea)	35.0	600	6541	6993	2967	4311	3284	3358
EAP 3055 (Urea form)	38.00	—	5416	5673	4739	5300	3037	3671
No nitrogen	—	—	4154		3702		2552	
Mean (methods)			6044	6719	4029	4160	2827	2647
Rate of N applied:	80 kg/ha							
Maturity (days)			118		149		140	
Analysis of Variance:			LSD		cv ($\bar{x}$) %		CV (X) %	
Fertilizer sources** (Chianan 8)			902		5		14	
(Intan & Peta)			1027		5		30	
Methods of application** (Chianan 8)			408		2		11	
(Intan & Peta)			1027		14		40	

Fig. 13. NH₄⁺-N remaining in Maahas clay soil at various dates after transplanting as affected by methods of N application, IRRI, 1965 dry season.

yield with Chianan 8, a ponlai variety, when 80 kg/ha N were placed at a 15-cm depth. An increase of 1,700 kg/ha rough rice resulted from the placement treatment (Table 3). In increasing

grain yield per unit of nitrogen applied, placement of 80 kg/ha N at 15 cm was 88 percent more efficient than broadcast application and incorporation with a harrow.

The nitrogen content of the plant in percent was consistently higher throughout the growth cycle where placement at 15 cm was practiced, than where the fertilizer was broadcast and harrowed in. This increase of nitrogen content with deeper placement caused a significant increase in the number of productive tillers and ultimately increased grain yield significantly. There was a significant relationship between nitrogen content in the plant at various stages of growth and grain yield (Figs. 11 and 12). Throughout the growing season, the Maahas clay soil contained more $\text{NH}_4^+\text{-N}$ in the 15-cm placement treatments than in the broadcast-and-incorporated treatment. The difference was quite striking at the early growth stage (Fig. 13).

Standard ammonium sulfate placed 15 cm deep did not improve grain yield significantly because one of the four replicates lodged severely at an early growth stage. Extremely slow release materials, such as EAP 3035 and ureaform, released nitrogen too slowly to be useful during the early growth period of rice. Even so, one of the slowest release materials, EAP 3035, gave an increase of 1,000 kg of rough rice in the placement treatment over broadcast and incorporated (Table 3).

With tall *indica* rice varieties, such as Intan and Peta, there was no conclusive trend because these varieties lodged severely before heading (Table 3). These results demonstrate again that to obtain the full benefit of placement, or to be highly responsive to nitrogen and adapted to high levels of fertility, the varieties must be resistant to lodging.

During the wet season, fertilizer at 40 kg/ha N produced significantly more grain than the check. Except for some minor differences in grain yield due to fertilizer material, none of the treatment differences, either due to method of application or to variety, was statistically significant (Table 4). In this experiment, the highest total yield, 13,341

kg/ha rough rice/2 crops, was obtained with Chianan 8 in the dry season and Chianung 242 in the wet season, to which EAP 3032 (ammonium sulfate, 650 hours release time) was applied at a depth of 15 cm.

Efficiency of different nitrogen sources in flooded Maahas clay

The efficiency of applied nitrogen is sometimes considerably improved if the fertilizer is placed in the reduced layer of flooded soil. To measure these effects quantitatively, an experiment was conducted during the 1965 dry season on Maahas clay soil using three methods of nitrogen application and two sources of N, $(\text{N}^{15}\text{H}_4)_2\text{SO}_4$ and $\text{CO}(\text{N}^{15}\text{H}_2)_2$. The effects of the treatments on per-

Fig. 14. Relationship (correlation coefficient and regression factor) between utilization of added nitrogen [$\text{CO}(\text{N}^{15}\text{H}_2)_2$ and $(\text{N}^{15}\text{H}_4)_2\text{SO}_4$] and grain yield of Milfor-6(2). **BI**: broadcast and incorporated. **S**: split application. **P**: placed at 10 cm. IRRI, 1965 dry season.

centage utilization of added nitrogen and on grain yield were measured.

The methods of application were: (1) complete incorporation prior to transplanting, (2) placement as a ball at 10 cm depth, and (3) half incorporated before transplanting and half surface

broadcast at panicle initiation. The variety used was the tall, but stiff-strawed *indica*, Milfor-6(2) from the Philippines.

All nitrogen-fertilized treatments yielded significantly more grain than the check (Table 5). The highest yield was obtained from nitrogen placed at 10 cm, irrespective of source. This method of application produced significantly higher grain yield than either of the other two methods, between which there was no significant difference.

The amounts of nitrogen taken up from soil and fertilizer by the plants confirmed the trends shown by the yield data. The amounts absorbed, in kg/ha, were:

10 cm placement	154
split	119
broadcast	113
no nitrogen	93

Fig. 15. Anhydrous NH_3 was applied in a 40-cm swath at desired depth from a portable applicator fabricated from an oxygen cylinder, pressure regulator and a light knife.

The percentages of nitrogen in the grain derived from the fertilizer were:

10 cm placement	29%
split	20%
broadcast	16%

And, in the straw:

10 cm placement	23%
split	16%
broadcast	14%

When the efficiency of applied nitrogen was calculated on the basis of the percentage of added nitrogen recovered from the grain and straw, it was shown that the 10-cm placement method was far superior to either of the other two. For placement, split application, and broadcast, the values were 68% > 34% > 27%, respectively.

Placement of nitrogen in the reduced zone also resulted in a higher grain yield than either split application or the broadcast and the incorporated treatments. The efficiency of applied nitrogen (kg rough rice/kg N) by the three methods of application was 43, 23, and 14 for subsoil placement, split application and broadcast-and-incorporated, respectively. The relationship between utilization of added nitrogen (N^{15} -la-

belled urea and ammonium sulfate), and grain yield of Milfor-6(2) was highly significant (Fig. 14).

There was no significant difference between the fertilizer sources in terms of grain yield, but in terms of percentage utilization of added N, urea was slightly inferior. The results demonstrate the greater efficiency of nitrogen utilization possible if fertilizer is applied properly even at 60 kg/ha — quite a modest amount for a dry-season crop with a grain yield of 8,448 kg/ha rough rice.

Anhydrous ammonia and medium-pressure nitrogen solutions

The efficiency of anhydrous ammonia as a nitrogen fertilizer merits critical evaluation because the manufacturing and transportation costs are low, and the nitrogen content high, compared to solid fertilizer. The application devices available for using anhydrous ammonia are mostly designed for highly mechanized systems of farming and cannot be used with lowland rice in Asian countries. Therefore, a knapsack unit for applying anhydrous ammonia was fabricated with the cooperation of Agricul-

TABLE 4. Effects of some standard and slow release fertilizer materials on the grain yield of B572-A3-47 (819) and Chianung 242, IRRI, 1965 wet season.

Grain yield at 14% moisture (average, 4 replicates)

Fertilizer material	Rate of release in hours (75% of total)	Method of application				Fertilizer mean
		819 (B572-A3-47)		Chianung 242		
		Broadcast and incorporated	Place-ment 15 cm deep	Broadcast and incorporated	Place-ment 15 cm deep	
Ammonium sulfate (AS)	—	5029 ^(kg/ha)	5189	5684 ^(kg/ha)	5545	5362
Urea	—	4775	4898	5345	5614	5158
EAP 3011 (AS)	150	5190	5237	5400	5725	5388
EAP 3032 (AS)	650	5248	5293	5322	5640	5376
EAP 3035 (AS)	4000	5186	4905	5813	5663	5392
EAP 3031 (Urea)	600	4771	4809	5123	5183	4972
EAP 3055 (Urea form)	—	5135	4693	5692	5125	5161
No nitrogen	—		3880		4463	4172
Mean (methods)		5048	5003	5483	5499	
Mean (varieties)			5026		5491	
Rate of N applied:	40 kg/ha					
Duration (days)			112		123	
Analysis of Variance:		LSD	cv($\bar{x}$) %		CV(X) %	
Varieties ^{n.s.}			3		9	
Fertilizer material**		309	2		9	
Method of application			2		9	

TABLE 5. Management of nitrogen fertilizer (N¹⁵) in lowland rice and its effects on grain yield of Milfor-6(2), IIRRI, 1965 dry season.

Variety: Milfor-6(2)		Grain yield at 14% moisture (average, 4 replicates)		
Method of application of 60 kg/ha N				
Nitrogen sources	Complete incorporation at planting	Placement 10 cm deep at planting	Split application 30 kg at planting + 30 kg at ear initiation	Mean (sources)
Urea CO(N ¹⁵ H ₂) ₂	6839	8567	7080	7287
(N ¹⁵ H ₄) ₂ SO ₄	6754	8330	7581	7555
No nitrogen		5924		
Mean (methods)	6796	8448	7330	
Duration: 133 days				
Efficiency of applied N (kg rough rice/kg N)				
		42	23	
Analysis of Variance:				
	LSD	cv($\bar{x}$) %	CV(X) %	
Treatment**	670	3.1	9	

tural Engineering, and used in an experiment with transplanted rice (Fig. 15).

Two experiments were conducted during the dry and wet seasons: (1) to compare anhydrous ammonia and a medium-pressure nitrogen solution with standard solid fertilizers such as ammonium sulfate, (2) to determine the depths of application necessary for efficient nitrogen use.

Dry season. The dry season experiment was conducted with PI 215936 planted at 20 x 20 cm spacing. The (NH₄)₂SO₄ applications were made 37 days after transplanting at 0, 10, and 15 cm depths. Anhydrous NH₃ (82% N) and an ammonia-urea-ammonium nitrate solution (45% N) were both applied at 0, 5, and 10 cm depths using the portable anhydrous NH₃ applicator and knapsack sprayer.

There was a general response to nitrogen; all treatments receiving nitrogen produced significantly more than the no-nitrogen check (Table 6). The nitrogen solution treatment produced significantly less than the (NH₄)₂SO₄ treatment, but other differences between sources were not significant. The yield differences between treatments receiving 60 and 120 kg/ha N as anhydrous ammonia were not significant. At both 60 and 120 kg/ha, placement at 5 cm was significantly more effective than surface application in the irrigation water. At this high

rate of application, there may have been a loss of nitrogen as NO₃ where the anhydrous ammonia was applied to the irrigation water. At the lower rate of 60 kg/ha N, conversion of ammonium nitrogen to nitrate nitrogen probably took place slowly enough to permit utilization by the plants.

Wet season. Anhydrous ammonia and a non-pressure urea solution (20% N) were both applied at 25 and 50 kg/ha N at depths of 0, 2.5, 5, 10, and 15 cm. Ammonium sulfate was applied by the standard method of broadcasting and incorporating, also at rates of 25 and 50 kg/ha N.

Significant responses were obtained to nitrogen when it was applied as either anhydrous ammonia or urea solution, but not when it was broadcast as solid ammonium sulfate (Table 7). Nevertheless, differences in grain yield obtained with the three sources of nitrogen were not significant. Differences in yield obtained with different rates and depths of application were not significant.

The data indicate that anhydrous ammonia is as good a source of nitrogen as any other standard fertilizer material. There is, however, a need to determine the swath interval necessary to insure adequate fertilizer distribution.

Nitrogen transformation in flooded Maahas clay

In general, alternate flooding and drying of rice soils leads to losses of

Fig. 18. Effects of nitrogen rates on the efficiency of fertilizer nitrogen (kg rough rice/kg N) and grain yield of PI 215936, Milfor-6(2), IRRI, 1965 dry and wet seasons.

to 6,000 kg/ha of rough rice during the wet season.

The differences between the actual amount of $NH_4^+ + NO_3^- - N$ present

in uncropped Maahas clay at the 110th day of flooding, and the amount removed by rice (average of PI 215936 and Milfor-6(2)) plus what remained in the soil in the same plot with rice, varied from +2 to -17 kg/ha N^+ (Table 8). When Maahas clay was continuously flooded, the amount of nitrogen, either mineralized from the soil or from the fertilizer, that could not be accounted for was a maximum of only 17 kg/ha N. At harvest about 94 kg/ha N remained in the soil.

If 94 kg/ha N is considered the amount of mineral nitrogen ($NH_4^+ - N$ but mostly $NH_4^+ - N$) present in the soil at transplanting, and the amount removed by a crop of rice plus that remaining in the soil at harvest is 152 kg/ha N without added N (Table 8), then the amount mineralized during 110 days of flooding is $152 - 94 = 58$ kg/ha N. The crop removed 60 kg/ha N which is essentially the same amount (Fig. 17).

Similarly, at 60 kg/ha of applied N, the amount mineralized during 110 days

TABLE 7. Grain yield of PI 215936 fertilized with anhydrous ammonia, ammonium sulfate (standard practice), and a urea solution at five depths, IRRI, 1965 wet season.

Variety: PI 215936		Grain yield at 14% moisture (kg/ha) (average, 4 replicates)					
		Source and rate (kg/ha) of applied N					
Depth of placement (cm)	Anhydrous ammonia (82% N)		Urea solution (20% N)		Ammonium sulfate (20% N) Broadcast and incorporated ^a		Mean (depth)
	25	50	25	50	25	50	
0 (Irrigation water)	4783	5254	4786	5166			4997
2.5	5194	5563	5161	5670			5397
5	5551	5531	5228	5797			5527
10	5545	5788	5265	5695			5573
15	5517	5667	5793	5882			5715
Mean (rates)	5318	5561	5247	5642	4542	5170	
Mean (sources)	5440		5445		4856		

Duration (days): 122

Yield with no nitrogen

Analysis of Variance:

Treatment^{n.s.}

Fertilizer^{n.s.}

Rate^{n.s.}

Depth of placements^{n.s.}

Control vs. fertilizer** 908

^a Standard practice.

4325

LSD

cv($\bar{x}$) %

CV(X) %

6

12

TABLE 6. Grain yield of PI 215936 fertilized with anhydrous ammonia and two other sources of nitrogen at four depths, IRRI, 1965 dry season.

Depth of placement (cm)	Source and rate (kg/ha) of N applied						Mean (depth of incorporation) (kg/ha)
	Ammonium sulfate		Anhydrous ammonia		Ammonia-urea Ammonium nitrate		
	21% N (as ball)		82% N (high pressure)		45% N (medium pressure)		
	60	120	60	120	60	120	
0 (Irrigation water)	6001	6429	5472	5561	5554	5266	5714
5			6346	6555	5637	5984	6130
10	6770	6998	6403	6380	5039	6010	6267
15	6085	6569					6327
No nitrogen				4136			
Mean (rates)	6285	6665	6074	6165	5410	5753	
Mean (sources)	6475		6120		5582		
Duration (days):	123						
Analysis of Variance:			LSD	cv($\bar{x}$) %	CV(X) %		
All treatments**			817	4.8	10		
Sources (S)**							
Depth (D)**							
Control vs. Treated**							
Rate (R) ^{n.s.}							
S X R, S X D, R X D, S X R X D ^{n.s.}							

analyzed, either immediately or after storing at 4 C, for NH_4^+ and NO_3^- -N. Plant samples were collected at the same time and analyzed for total nitrogen. These determinations were to study the effect of nitrogen rates on the nitrogen status of soil with and without a crop of rice, and to relate these changes in soil nitrogen to those in plant nitrogen and grain yield at harvest.

Dry season. The amount of mineral N (NH_4^+ + NO_3^- -N) released from unfertilized Maahas clay after 110 days of submergence was 150 kg/ha N, of which 135 kg/ha N was in NH_4^+ -N form (Fig. 16). Since the rates of nitrogen applied varied from 0 to 150 kg/ha N, the total amount of NH_4^+ -N contained in the soil was 0 + 135, 30 + 135...150 + 135 and the total amount of mineral N (NH_4^+ + NO_3^- -N) released from soil + fertilizer was 0 + 150, 30 + 150...150 + 150 kg/ha N. The actual amount of NH_4^+ -N recovered from the soil without rice, however, was 1 to 59 kg/ha N less than the predicted release; the actual

amount of NH_4^+ + NO_3^- -N recovered from the soil without rice was 1 to 63 kg/ha N less than the predicted release (Fig. 17). These discrepancies are thought to have been caused by (1) losses from the applied fertilizer, with a maximum loss of 50%, or (2) reduced mineralization of soil N in the presence of added fertilizer.

Maahas clay, without a crop of rice, released 79 to 135 kg/ha N as NH_4^+ -N during 110 days of submergence (Fig. 16), a period sufficient to mature a short duration variety if transplanted as 21-day-old seedlings. There were 128 kg/ha NH_4^+ -N released during the first 45 days of submergence. Since this period coincides with panicle primordium initiation of many short duration varieties, they may not need additional nitrogen at that time if adequate fertilizer is incorporated before transplanting. In the current experiment, for example, where no nitrogen was applied after transplanting, the highest yield was nevertheless between 7,000 to 8,000 kg/ha during the dry season, and 5,000

Fig. 18. Effects of nitrogen rates on the efficiency of fertilizer nitrogen (kg rough rice/kg N) and grain yield of PI 215936, Milfor-6(2), IRRI, 1965 dry and wet seasons.

to 6,000 kg/ha of rough rice during the wet season.

The differences between the actual amount of $\text{NH}_4^+ + \text{NO}_3^- - \text{N}$ present

in uncropped Maahas clay at the 110th day of flooding, and the amount removed by rice (average of PI 215936 and Milfor-6(2)) plus what remained in the soil in the same plot with rice, varied from +2 to -17 kg/ha N^+ (Table 8). When Maahas clay was continuously flooded, the amount of nitrogen, either mineralized from the soil or from the fertilizer, that could not be accounted for was a maximum of only 17 kg/ha N. At harvest about 94 kg/ha N remained in the soil.

If 94 kg/ha N is considered the amount of mineral nitrogen ($\text{NH}_4\text{NO}_3 - \text{N}$ but mostly $\text{NH}_4^+ - \text{N}$) present in the soil at transplanting, and the amount removed by a crop of rice plus that remaining in the soil at harvest is 152 kg/ha N without added N (Table 8), then the amount mineralized during 110 days of flooding is $152 - 94 = 58$ kg/ha N. The crop removed 60 kg/ha N which is essentially the same amount (Fig. 17).

Similarly, at 60 kg/ha of applied N, the amount mineralized during 110 days

TABLE 7. Grain yield of PI 215936 fertilized with anhydrous ammonia, ammonium sulfate (standard practice), and a urea solution at five depths, IRRI, 1965 wet season.

Variety: PI 215936		Grain yield at 14% moisture (kg/ha) (average, 4 replicates)					
		Source and rate (kg/ha) of applied N					
Depth of placement (cm)	Anhydrous ammonia (82% N)		Urea solution (20% N)		Ammonium sulfate (20% N) Broadcast and incorporated ^a		Mean (depth)
	25	50	25	50	25	50	
0	4783	5254	4786	5166			4997
(Irrigation water)							
2.5	5194	5563	5161	5670			5397
5	5551	5531	5228	5797			5527
10	5545	5788	5265	5695			5573
15	5517	5667	5793	5882			5715
Mean (rates)	5318	5561	5247	5642	4542	5170	
Mean (sources)	5440		5445		4856		
Duration (days):		122					
Yield with no nitrogen				4325			
Analysis of Variance:		LSD		cv($\bar{x}$) %		CV(X) %	
Treatment ^{n.s.}				6		12	
Fertilizer ^{n.s.}							
Rate ^{n.s.}							
Depth of placements ^{n.s.}							
Control vs. fertilizer**		908					

^a Standard practice.

of submergence was 183- (94 from soil at start + 60 kg applied N) i.e. 29 kg/ha N. Likewise, at 120 kg/ha applied N, the amount mineralized was 3 kg/ha N and the crop removed 123 kg/ha N. At 150 kg/ha applied N, there was essentially no net removal of soil nitrogen by the plant and the plant nitrogen was accounted for entirely by nitrogen fer-

actual sources and their relative amounts is being determined in other experiments involving N¹⁵.

In the dry season, with each 30 kg/ha N increment there was a significant increase in grain yield up to 90 kg/ha N with both PI 215936 and Milfor-6(2) with an efficiency of nitrogen fertilizer of 25 and 52 kg rough rich/kg N, re-

TABLE 8. Nitrogen balance sheet in Maahas clay under continuous submergence with and without rice (average of PI 215936 and Milfor-6(2), IRRI, 1965 dry season).

Nitrogen applied (kg/ha)	Crop removal (a)	Amount remaining after harvest		Crop removal + amount remaining after harvest	Amount present at harvest without rice	Balance unaccounted for (a + b) - c
		NH ₄ ⁺ (b)	-NO ₃ ⁻ = N (b)	(NH ₄ ⁺ + NO ₃ ⁻ -N) (a + b) kg/ha	(NH ₄ ⁺ + NO ₃ ⁻ -N) (c)	
0	60.2	92.0		152.2	150.4	+1.85
30	75.9	97.8		171.6	179.2	-7.6
60	92.4	91.0		183.4	179.2	+4.2
90	115.9	91.8		207.8	199.4	+8.3
120	122.8	94.8		217.7	208.7	+8.9
150	127.4	96.3		223.5	240.9	-17.3

tilizer (Fig. 17). These results indicate that when the amount of nitrogen fertilizer reaches 120 kg/ha, the plant utilization is supplied by fertilizer but the

spectively (Fig. 18). However, the highest grain yields (8,064 and 7,436 kg/ha) were obtained at 150 and 120 kg/ha N, respectively. During the wet season

TABLE 9. Effects of NPK fertilization on the grain yield of PI 215936, 6993 (B5580), and Taichung (Native) 1. Long-term fertility experiment, IRRI, 1965 dry season.

Treatment no.	Fertilizer treatment			Variety			Mean treatment (kg/ha)
	N	P ₂ O ₅	K ₂ O	PI 215936	6993 (B5580)	Taichung (Native) 1	
	(kg/ha)			(kg/ha)	(kg/ha)	(kg/ha)	
1	0	0	0	3690	3352	4579	3907
2	100+40	0	0	7298	7703	7591	7531
3	0	30	0	3644	3404	4522	3857
4	0	0	30	3772	3545	4821	4046
5	100+40	30	0	7066	7716	7449	7410
6	100+40	0	30	7596	7590	7192	7459
7	100+40	30	30	7444	7658	7606	7569
8	100+40 ^a	30	30	7379	7443	7603	7475
Mean (varieties)				5986	6051	6433	
Kg rough rice/kg N				26.1	29.9	25.4	
Analysis of Variance:				LSD	cv($\bar{x}$) %	CV(X) %	
Variety**				267	1	6	
Fertilizer treatments**				436	2	7	
Variety x fertilizer treatments*				754	4	8	
^a (Compost + inorganic) (24.6 kg N + 115.4 kg N)							

TABLE 10. Effects of NPK fertilization on the grain yield of PI 215936, 6993 (B5580), and Taichung (Native) 1. Long-term fertility experiment, IRRI, 1965 wet season.

Treatment no.	Fertilizer treatment			V a r i e t y			Mean treatment (kg/ha)
	N	P ₂ O ₅	K ₂ O	PI 215936	6993 (B5580)	Taichung (Native) 1	
	(kg/ha)			(kg/ha)	(kg/ha)	(kg/ha)	
1	0	0	0	4524	4507	5478	4836
2	60	0	0	6266	5966	6913	6382
3	0	30	0	4939	4396	5573	4969
4	0	0	30	4667	4305	5392	4788
5	60	30	0	6055	6013	7054	6374
6	60	0	30	6162	5875	6983	6340
7	60	30	30	6134	6111	7025	6424
8	60 ^a	30	30	5988	5637	6837	6155
Mean (varieties)				5592	5351	6407	
Kg rough rice/kg N				18.1	25.3	20.7	
<i>Analysis of Variance:</i>				s.e.	LSD	cv($\bar{x}$) %	CV(X) %
Treatment combinations**				164	462	2.8	6
Variety**				58	164	1.0	—
Treatment means**				95	268	1.6	—
^a (Compost + inorganic) (24.6 kg N + 35.4 kg N)							

there was a significant increase in grain yield over the check with PI 215936 at 45 kg/ha N (Fig. 18). With Milfor-6(2) none of the rates showed any significant differences in grain yield. In the wet season, PI 215936 and Milfor-6(2) produced highest grain yields of 6,258 and 6,004 kg/ha, respectively. Both varieties matured 9 to 12 days earlier during the wet season.

Milfor-6(2) produced 13,444 kg/ha rough rice/2 crops, indicating the yield potential of this variety type when properly managed.

Long-term fertility experiment

To determine fertility trends, a simple factorial trial started during the 1964 wet season was continued. The eight fertility treatments imposed during 1964 were retained but the nitrogen rate was raised to 140 kg/ha N during the dry season and the three varieties were changed to PI 215936, 6993 (B5580), and Taichung (Native) 1. All three varieties are considered highly responsive to nitrogen and are short to medium in height.

During the dry season, the average yield increases with 140 kg/ha N was

3,798 kg/ha of rough rice or about 27 kg rough rice/kg N (Table 9). Top yields for all three varieties without added fertilizer were from 3,400 to 3,900 kg/ha. All three varieties matured within 115 days in both seasons except Taichung (Native) 1 which matured in 121 days during the dry season.

During the wet season, the response to added nitrogen was less than that in the dry season. The average yield increase with 60 kg/ha N was 1,469 kg/ha or about 21 kg of rough rice/kg N (Table 10). Taichung (Native) 1 yielded 1,000 kg more rough rice than either PI 215936 or 6993 (B5580), and its highest yield was 7,054 kg/ha rough rice. Both under low and high fertility conditions, Taichung (Native) 1 showed higher grain yields over the other two improved varieties. This indicates that Taichung (Native) 1 will outyield most varieties if the incidence of disease is low. During the wet season (June 1 to October 15), the amount of rain received at the Institute was 26.7 inches, compared with 57.4 inches in the 1964 wet season. Also, in August, September and October, 1965, there was slightly higher solar energy (intensity of sun-

light) which partially explains the high grain yield during the current wet season.

As expected, dry and wet season results show that the addition of phosphorus and potassium, alone or in combination with nitrogen, did not produce any significant difference in grain yield (Tables 9 and 10). However, with increased removal of nitrogen by the rice plant there was a corresponding increase in the removal of phosphorus and the relationship between nitrogen yield and phosphorus yield was highly significant; the *r*-values were 0.94** and 0.90**, with regression equations of $y=3.48 + 0.184X$, and $y=1.70 + 0.2813X$, for the 1965 dry and wet seasons, respectively. The results show that, on the average, for each additional kilogram of nitrogen removed, 0.23 kg of phosphorus was removed. Under continuous culture with two crops of rice a year, the time may come when yield responses to phosphorus will occur.

During the dry and wet seasons the total amount of dry matter produced (oven-dry) was 22,727 kg/ha/2 crops. The grain-straw ratio of the three varieties did not change between seasons

(Table 11) and the average yield of rough rice was 13,824 kg/ha/2 rice crops. On an annual basis, Taichung (Native) 1, PI 215936, and 6993 (B5580) produced 14,660, 13,862, and 13,827 kg rough rice/2 crops, respectively.

The amount of straw produced (average of three varieties) was 12,602 kg/ha/2 crops (Table 11), indicating that these better varieties will produce not only high yields of grain but also of straw.

Dry season grain yields are higher than wet season yields, and as a consequence more nitrogen is required. In this experiment, 140 kg/ha N was required to reach the maximum dry season yield, but the wet season crop reached its maximum on 60 kg. Although the levels were quite different, the efficiency of applied nitrogen was about the same for both seasons: approximately 25 kg rough rice or 48 to 50 kg dry matter/kg N. The results suggest that if plants with desirable features are used, the return on fertilizer investment is similar for both seasons provided the amount of nitrogen applied is optimum for variety and environment.

TABLE 11. Effect of N fertilization on the average grain (PI 215936, 6993 (B5580), Taichung (Native) 1), straw and dry matter production and grain-straw ratio during dry and wet seasons.^a Long-term fertility trial, IRRI, 1965 dry and wet seasons.

	Average ^a of 3 varieties (PI 215936, Taichung (Native) 1, B5580)							
	Without added N				With added N ^b			
	Grain	Straw	Total	Grain straw	Grain	Straw	Total	Grain straw
	(kg/ha)				(kg/ha)			
1965 dry season	3937	2888	5870	1.36	7489	7093	12541	1.06
1965 wet season	4864	3524	7214	1.38	6335	5509	10186	1.15
Total (dry & wet seasons)	8801	6412	13084		13824	12602	22727	
Efficiency of applied N in dry matter production (kg dry matter yield/kg N)					<i>Dry season</i>		<i>Wet season</i>	
					47.6		49.5	
Efficiency of applied N in grain production (kg grain yield/kg N)					25.4		24.5	

^a Grain and straw yield at 14% moisture, total dry matter production at 0% moisture.

^b 140 kg/ha N dry season
60 kg/ha wet season

Fig. 19. PI 215936 responds remarkably well to high levels of applied nitrogen (top). Without added nitrogen, it grows poorly even when given the best insect and weed control treatments and a continuous water supply (bottom). IRRI-BPI cooperative fertility experiment, 1965 dry season.

TABLE 12. Effects of NPK fertilization on the grain yield of PI 215936 and 6993 (B5580). IIRI-BPI (Maligaya Experiment Station) cooperative fertility experiment, 1965 dry season.

Grain yield at 14% moisture (average, 4 replicates)				
N	Fertilizer treatment		Variety	
	P ₂ O ₅	K ₂ O	PI 215936	6993 (B5580)
	(kg/ha)		(kg/ha)	(kg/ha)
0	0	0	1755	2331
100+60	0	0	6599	5846
0	30	0	1976	2398
0	0	30	2146	2088
100+60	30	0	7164	6173
100+60	0	30	6889	5769
100+60	30	30	7128	6316
Mean			4802	4417
Maturation (days):	122			
Kg rough rice/kg N:			31.2	23.3
Analysis of Variance:		LSD	cv($\bar{x}$) %	CV(X) %
Treatments**		663	5	10

For the dry season crop, 140 kg/ha N increased the nitrogen content of the dry matter by 0.19, 0.08, and 0.27% for Taichung (Native) 1, 6993 (B5580), and PI 215936, respectively, and the average yield from 3,937 to 7,489 kg rough rice/ha. In the wet season, for 60 kg/ha applied N, the corresponding increases were 0.04, 0.07, 0.19%, and from 4,864 to 6,335 kg/ha.

IIRI-BPI cooperative fertility experiments

Experiments were conducted in collaboration with the Philippine Bureau of Plant Industry at the Maligaya Experiment Station in Central Luzon where conditions are representative of a large rice-growing section of the country. Analyses of the experiment station soils indicated only a slightly lower nitrogen content (0.08%) than in Maahas clay (0.14%); a similar high level of fertility and high yield potential was therefore anticipated.

During 1965, experiments with NPK factorial treatments were conducted in both dry and wet seasons to determine the fertility requirement at Maligaya. The varieties used were 6993 (B5580) and PI 215936 during the dry season, and B572-A3-47 (821) and Chianung 242 during the wet season.

Dry season. Eleven-day-old seedlings were transplanted January 15 at a spacing of 20 x 20 cm. Fertilizers were applied at rates of 0-160 kg/ha N, 30 kg/ha P₂O₅, and 30 kg/ha K₂O, either alone or in combination. The nitrogen application was split: 100 kg/ha was harrowed in before planting, and 60 kg/ha topdressed at panicle initiation. The combination of varieties and management practices used in this dry, sunny season experiment resulted in efficient use of fertilizers and in high return on the fertilizer investment (Table 12).

PI 215936 yielded 4,986 kg more rough rice per hectare with 160 kg/ha N than without added nitrogen, giving an efficiency of 31.2 kg rough rice/kg N. Variety 6993 produced 3,730 kg more rice than the check, or 23.3 kg/ha N. The return on the fertilizer investment, where nitrogen costs about four times as much as rough rice, was about 600 percent. PI 215936 yielded the most grain (7,164 kg/ha) with the 160 kg/ha N + 30 kg/ha P₂O₅ treatment (Table 12); variety 6993 yielded 6,316 kg/ha with the same fertilizer treatment. Phosphorus or potassium, whether applied alone or in combination with nitrogen, did not affect significantly the grain production of either variety.

Wet season. Twenty-one-day-old seed-

lings were transplanted on July 14 at a spacing of 20 x 20 cm. Fertilizer supplying 80 kg/ha N, 30 kg/ha P₂O₅, and 30 kg/ha K₂O were applied, either alone or in combination, and harrowed in before planting. The two varieties averaged 3,972 kg/ha rough rice without added nitrogen and 5,484 kg/ha with 80 kg/ha N, giving an efficiency of 18.9 kg rough rice/kg N (Table 13), which was lower than the dry season figure. During the monsoon season with limited sunlight, the efficiency of added nitrogen is normally reduced. However, by using varieties with better plant type such as Chianung 242, or 9792, added nitrogen can be used more efficiently for wet season grain production. Both Chianung 242 (5,959 kg/ha) and 9792 (5,198 kg/ha) produced highest yields with 80-30-30 fertilizer application. Phosphorus or potassium, whether applied alone or in combination with nitrogen, did not significantly affect the grain production of either variety. However, with continuous cropping in Maligaya soil, a response to added phosphorus may appear eventually.

During the dry and wet seasons, the highest total grain yield was 13,022 kg rough rice/ha/2 crops with best treatment combination, indicating the yield potential in Central Luzon for two crops with good fertilization and precise management. Without fertilizer, even with good insect and weed control and water management, the yield was only 5,731 kg/ha rough rice/2 crops. Figure 19 shows the response of PI 215936 to nitrogen during the dry season.

Yield potential and nitrogen responses of three improved varieties

From the dry season fertility experiment, it seems that the nitrogen-supplying capacity of the soil at Maligaya Experiment Station is lower than that of Maahas clay in the Institute's experimental field. To obtain the same yields, a higher level of applied nitrogen is therefore necessary at Maligaya. During the wet season, an experiment was conducted to determine the nitrogen responsiveness of three varieties (6996 (B5711), PI 215936, and Milfor-6(2)) which have performed well at the In-

TABLE 13. Effects of NPK fertilization on the grain yield of Chianung 242 and B572-A3-47 (9792). IRRI-BPI (Maligaya Experiment Station), cooperative fertility experiment, 1965 wet season.

Grain yield at 14% moisture (average, 4 replicates)					
Fertilizer treatment			Variety		
N	P ₂ O ₅	K ₂ O	Chianung 242	B572-A3-47 (9792)	Mean treatment
	(kg/ha)		(kg/ha)	(kg/ha)	(kg/ha)
0	0	0	3885	3490	3688
80	0	0	5469	4945	5207
0	30	0	4246	4067	4156
0	0	30	4081	3471	3776
80	30	0	5675	5072	5373
80	0	30	5546	4895	5220
80	30	30	5858	5198	5528
Mean (varieties)			4966	4448	
Maturation (days):			114		
Kg rough rice/kg N applied:			19.6	18.2	18.90
Analysis of Variance:			s.e.	LSD	cv($\bar{x}$) %
Treatment combination**			187	616	4.0
Variety**			71	234	1.5
Treatment means**			132	435	2.8

stitute. Nitrogen was applied from 0 to 130 kg/ha N, in 40 kg increments. All treatments received 40 kg P₂O₅; all fertilizers were incorporated at harrowing, and the plots were kept under continuous submergence. On the average, the three varieties produced 15 kg rough rice/kg applied N even at 100 kg/ha N, and produced the highest average yield of 5,797 kg/ha at 130 kg/ha N (Fig. 20).

Fig. 20. Effects of nitrogen rates on the efficiency of fertilizer nitrogen (kg rough rice/kg N) and grain yield of PI 215936, Milfor-6(2) and B5711 (6966). IRRI-BPI Cooperative N-response experiment, 1965 wet season, Maligaya Station.

The results show that varieties that are potentially high-yielding at the Institute will perform equally well at the Maligaya Experiment Station provided higher levels of nitrogen fertilizer are applied along with effective insect, water, and weed control measures. These varieties and management factors will not insure high yields, however, unless fertilizer is applied. In these experiments the wet season yield was only 3,483 kg/ha without added N, compared with 5,797 kg/ha of rough rice when 130 kg/ha N was applied — an increase of 2,300 kg/ha.

Nitrogen response experiments in farmers' fields

IR9-60 (Peta x I-geo-tze), developed at the Institute, shows promise as a commercial variety, particularly in areas where tungro virus is not serious. It is a dwarf, early maturing, nitrogen-responsive *indica* variety with fair seed dormancy. To evaluate its yield potential, three experiments were conducted in farmers' fields at Sta. Rosa, Biñan, and Cavite during the 1965 wet season in collaboration with the Experimental Farm. Nitrogen was applied in 30 kg increments from 0 to 90 kg/ha N at Sta. Rosa, and 0 to 120 kg/ha N at Biñan and Cavite. A few phosphorus treatments were also included in the Cavite

TABLE 14. Effects of nitrogen levels on the grain yield of IR9-60 and PI 215936 grown in a farmer's field, Sta. Rosa, 1965 wet season.

Grain yield at 14% moisture			
Rate of nitrogen applied ^a	Variety		Mean
	IR9-60	PI 215936	
(kg/ha)	(kg/ha)	(kg/ha)	(kg/ha)
0	5,650	4,420	5,035
30	6,209	3,934	5,071
60	6,127	4,000	5,063
90	6,121	3,186	5,653
Mean (varieties)	6,026	3,885	4,955

Maturity (days)

114

107

Analysis of Variance:

s.e.

LSD

cv($\bar{x}$) %

CV(X) %

Varieties (V)*

32

573

0.6

25

N- rates (N)

633

13

18

25

V X N

895

18

25

^a 40 kg P₂O₅ and 40 kg K₂O applied uniformly.

experiment as analysis indicated that the soil was low in extractable P. At Sta. Rosa and Biñan, PI 215936, a ponlai variety, was also included in the experiments.

In Biñan, although IR9-60 and PI 215936 produced average yields of 5,629 and 4,236 kg/ha rough rice respectively, rats severely damaged some of the plots because both varieties matured earlier than the surrounding fields. The results were therefore inconclusive.

At Sta. Rosa, IR9-60 produced, on the average, 6,026 kg/ha rough rice compared with 3,885 kg/ha for PI 215936 (Table 14). The highest yield of 6,209 kg/ha was obtained with IR9-60 with 30 kg/ha N. PI 215936 lodged severely at all nitrogen levels and produced the most rice (4,420 kg/ha) without added nitrogen. IR9-60 did not lodge at any level of added nitrogen (Fig. 21) and the grain yield differences between nitrogen treatments were not statistically significant. Without added nitrogen,

IR9-60 produced 5,650 kg/ha rough rice. Failure to respond to nitrogen can be explained by soil analytical data. The Sta. Rosa soil has higher total nitrogen (0.16%), organic matter (2.4%), and 0.02 N H_2SO_4 -ext. P (74 ppm), compared to the Institute soil (total N:0.14%; O.M: 2%; ext. P:20 ppm). Both soils have similar pH values (6-6.5). The total amount of insecticides applied was 11 kg γ -BHC (four applications), 3 kg active ingredient, sevin (one application), and 3 liters of commercial endrin. The cost of insect protection is not high when yields as high as those of IR9-60 are obtained.

In Dasmariñas, Cavite, IR9-60 grown in a farmer's field matured in 110 days. With only three applications of γ -BHC (8 kg/ha active ingredients) and one application of sevin (3 kg/ha active ingredients) adequate protection against pests was obtained. There was a significant increase in grain yield up to 60 kg/ha N (Table 15). Beyond that rate,

Fig. 21. As the new IRRI varieties are developed, agronomists study their yield potential and N-responsiveness both on the IRRI farm and in farmers' fields. N-responsiveness of IR9-60 in Sta. Rosa, Laguna, 1965 wet season.

the grain yield differences were not statistically significant. However, even at 120 kg/ha N, IR9-60 did not lodge, indicating its adaptation to heavy fertilization and resistance to lodging. The soil in the experimental area was very

shallow and analytical data were as follows: pH 6.3, 2% O.M., 50 kg/ha NH_4^+ -N and 17 ppm 0.02 N H_2SO_4 -ext. P. Despite the indifferent soil conditions, IR9-60 produced an average yield of 4,390 kg/ha without added nitrogen,

TABLE 15. Effects of nitrogen levels, with and without phosphorus, on grain yield of IR9-60. Fertility trial in a farmer's field, Dasmariñas, Cavite, 1965 wet season.

Applied N (kg/ha)	Without P (kg/ha)	+ 26 kg P/ha (kg/ha)	+ 52 kg P/ha (kg/ha)	Mean N rates (kg/ha)
0	4334	4397	4438	4390
30	5105	5203	5360	5223
60	5778	5717	5979	5825
90	5889	5977	5901	5922
120	5879	5883	5510	4757
Mean	5397	5435	5438	
Duration (days): 119				
Analysis of Variance:		s.e.	LSD	cv($\bar{x}$) %
Treatments**		180	541	3
				CV(X) %
				5

again demonstrating that some of the dwarf *indicas* will outyield many tall traditional varieties even where native soil fertility is low. Although wet soil analysis indicated that the experimental area contained less 0.02 N H_2SO_4 -ext. P than many other Philippine lowland soils, there was no significant increase in grain yield when phosphorus was applied with various levels of nitrogen.

Phosphorus availability and fertilizer response in a laterized red soil

Results of a greenhouse study in 1964 indicated that on continuous submergence the phosphorus-supplying capacity of Luisiana clay (Humic latosol²; pH, 5.1; organic matter, 3.14%; total N, 0.19%; predominant clay mineral; kaolinite) was almost as high as that of Maahas clay, a soil containing montmorillonite as the dominant clay mineral. The chemical analyses of air-dry soil showed Luisiana clay to be extremely deficient (2 ppm P) in 0.02 N H_2SO_4 -extractable phosphorus compared to Maahas clay (20 ppm P). A field experiment was conducted during the 1965 dry season (November through April) on

Luisiana clay — in a farmer's field in Laguna Province to obtain information on its nitrogen- and phosphorus-supplying capacities with and without nitrogen and phosphorus fertilizers.

The fertilizers were incorporated during land preparation; PI 215936 and Milfor-6(2) varieties were planted at 20 x 20 cm spacing.

Growth differences were apparent during the first 2 months in the phosphorus treatments. There was also a significant response to phosphorus amounting to 1,000 kg rough rice/ha with PI 215936 when no nitrogen was applied (Table 16), but the same amount of phosphorus in combination with 30 kg/ha N did not significantly increase grain yield over the control. With Milfor-6(2), no treatment differences were statistically significant (Table 16). It is apparent that the phosphorus-supplying capacity of Luisiana clay is not seriously limiting yield since both varieties, in treatments without added nitrogen or phosphorus (check plots), produced 5,387 kg/ha rough rice. The cooperating farmer grew Binohangin in the paddy adjacent to the experiment. The variety lodged severely

² Tentative classification by the Department of Soils, UPCA.

even without fertilizer application and averaged 2,159 kg/ha rough rice, demonstrating the several-fold increased grain yield possible from carefully managed, lodging resistant varieties.

months but dropped to 6.6 at harvest. Phosphorus uptake also reached a peak 2 months after transplanting (Fig. 22). These results indicate that on continuous submergence the availability of

Fig. 22. Relationship of pH and E_6 (Eh at pH 6) of Louisiana clay on the P uptake at various stages of rice growth under continuous submergence. Fertility trial, Louisiana, Laguna, 1965 dry season.

Unlike many latosols, the phosphorus-supplying capacity of Louisiana clay is fairly high after a period of submergence. The soil was reduced by the second month after transplanting, but returned to an oxidized condition after heading of the rice (Fig. 22). The pH values rose to near neutrality within 2

months and uptake of phosphorus by the rice plant, is associated with the degree of reduction; the E_6 value (Eh at pH 6) dropped from 140 mv to 92 mv after 1 to 2 months of submergence. On flooding, phosphorus availability in Louisiana soil is increased, as indicated by the higher phosphorus uptake by the

Fig. 23. Effects of N and P fertilizer treatments on the changes of 0.02 N H₂SO₄ extractable-P in Louisiana clay and P uptake at various stages of rice growth. Fertility trial, Louisiana, Laguna, 1965 dry season.

Fig. 24. Effects of N and P fertilizer treatments on the changes of NH_4^+ -N in Louisiana clay on the N uptake at various stages of rice growth. Fertility trial, Louisiana, Laguna, 1965 dry season.

rice plant and the lower phosphorus content of the soil during the first 2 months of plant growth (Fig. 23).

Data on ammonium N in the soil and the nitrogen content of the rice plants at all growth stages indicated a high

nitrogen status in both plant and soil (Fig. 24). The correlation between extractable phosphorus in the soil and grain and straw phosphorus were highly significant ($r=0.55^{**}$ and 0.38^{**} , respectively).

TABLE 16. Effects of N and P fertilization in Luisiana clay on the grain yields of PI 215936 and Milfor-6(2), 1965 dry season.

Grain yield at 14% moisture (average, 4 replicates)					
Fertilizer treatments			Variety		Mean treatment
N	P	K	PI 215936	Milfor-6(2)	
(kg/ha)			(kg/ha)	(kg/ha)	(kg/ha)
0	0	25	5542	5232	5387
30	0	25	6092	5752	5922
0	20	25	6589	5112	5851
30	20	25	5660	5895	5778
Mean (varieties)			5971	5498	
Duration (days):			139	148	
<i>Analysis of Variance:</i>			LSD	cv($\bar{x}$) %	CV(X) %
Treatments*			811	6.8	10
Farmer's field (Binohangin) yield:			2,159 kg/ha		

Silica fertilization in lowland rice

The role of silica in the rice plant has been stated to be mostly physical, i.e., it stiffens the straw to prevent lodging, and promotes resistance to plant diseases. It is also thought to have a nutritional and physiological role.

Wet season data for 1964 demonstrated that rice yields can be increased by silica fertilization of Maahas clay. During the 1965 dry season, an experiment was conducted (1) to compare ground rice hull (26% SiO₂) and ashed rice hull (96% SiO₂) with calcium silicate (40% SiO₂) as sources of silica, and (2) to determine the silica response of PI 215936 and Milfor-6(2). Five rates of SiO₂ as rice hull (0 to 2,000 kg/ha) along with 90 kg/ha N were incorporated by harrowing. Calcium silicate was broadcast and partly incorporated with a hand weeder a week after transplanting.

There were distinct growth differences with silica treatments; rough rice yields increased significantly by 390 kg (from 7,907 to 8,297 kg/ha) when ground rice hull was applied at 250 kg/ha SiO₂ to PI 215936, and by 365 kg (6,959 to 7,324 kg/ha) with Milfor-6(2) (Table 17). With further increase in silica rate, there was no further increase in grain yield. However, there

was a significant decrease of grain yield in all calcium silicate-treated plots.

There was a mean increase of 718 kg/ha dry matter (oven-dry) production and most of this was accounted for by the first 250 kg/ha SiO₂ applied. The total dry matter production increased from 12,500 kg/ha without silica to 13,210 kg/ha with silica. With the application of silica fertilizers, there was an increase in straw yield of 389 kg/ha (8,080 to 8,469 kg/ha) for Milfor-6(2), whereas with similar applications of silica to PI 215936 there was an increase of 1,429 kg/ha (6,127 to 7,556 kg/ha).

The apparent growth response to added silica, particularly in PI 215936, is mostly a response in straw rather than grain yield.

Straw strength of Milfor-6(2) (P₂/E, including leaf sheath) increased with applications of 250 kg SiO₂/ha but beyond this rate there was no further increase (Fig. 25). In PI 215936, there were no differences in straw strength. A similar trend was also measured with P₁/E (without leaf sheath). The variety Milfor-6(2) has basically stronger straw than PI 215936 (Fig. 25) at all levels of applied silica; PI 215936 lodged earlier than Milfor-6(2) irrespective of silica treatment. With an application of 250 kg/ha SiO₂, the silica content (%)

Fig. 25. Effects of various levels of silica on straw strength of PI 215936 and Milfor-6(2) with or without leaf sheaths, IRRI, 1965 dry season.

of root, straw, and grain was increased; there was a decrease in phosphorus content (%) in the roots and an increased phosphorus content in the straw and grain (Table 18), suggesting that the

higher silica status of the plant improved the transport of phosphorus from roots to tops. This was consistent for both Milfor-6(2) and PI 215936.

Rate and time of silica application

Experiments were conducted with calcium silicate (40% SiO₂) during the dry and wet seasons on the Institute farm to obtain information on the rate and time of silica fertilization on grain yield. Silica fertilizer was applied (1) all at planting, (2) split between planting and panicle initiation, (3) split between planting and 50% tillering, and (4) split between 50% tillering and panicle initiation. Nitrogen was applied uniformly to all plots. The varieties used were PI 215936 and Peta during the dry season, and PI 215936 and Milfor-6(2) during the wet season.

All varieties, particularly Peta, lodged early and severely except Milfor-6(2) which lodged only at a late stage of growth during the wet season. There was an increase in grain yield with PI 215936 in the dry season from 6,976 kg/ha to 7,451 kg/ha rough rice with 1,000

TABLE 17. Grain yield of PI 215936 and Milfor-6(2) fertilized with sources and rates of silica, IRRI, 1965 dry season.

Grain yield at 14% moisture							
Rate of silica application	PI 215936			Milfor-6(2)			Mean (rates)
	Ground rice hull	Ashed rice hull	Calcium silicate	Ground rice hull	Ashed rice hull	Calcium silicate	
(kg/ha SiO ₂)	(kg/ha)			(kg/ha)			
0	7907	7907	7907	6959	6959	6959	7433
250	8296	8155	7289	7324	7052	6507	7437
500	8058	7827	7462	6817	6922	7028	7352
750	7880	8007	7176	6850	7306	6743	7327
1000	7940	7789	7328	6654	6758	7162	7272
2000	8077	7974	7200	6785	7066	6760	7310
Mean (sources)	8042	7950	7291	6886	7021	6840	
Mean (varieties)		7798			6926		
Rate of applied N:	90 + 40 kg/ha						
Duration (days)	122-125			133			
Analysis of Variance:	LSD			cv($\bar{x}$) %		CV(X) %	
Variety (V)**	548			1.4		16	
Treatment (T)**	361			1.8		7	
V x T _{n.s.}	—			—		—	

TABLE 18. Effects of silica fertilization on silica and phosphorus content in grain, straw and root of PI 215936, and Milfor 6(2), IRRI, 1965 dry season.

	PI 215936						Milfor-6(2)					
	Grain		Straw		Root		Grain		Straw		Root	
	Si	P	Si	P	Si	P	Si	P	Si	P	Si	P
	(%)		(%)		(%)		(%)		(%)		(%)	
Control	1.9	0.08	7.0	0.13	5.4	0.66	2.6	0.09	5.9	0.18	5.4	0.08
Added silica (250 kg/ha SiO ₂)	2.6	0.10	8.1	0.14	6.4	0.52	3.0	0.10	6.6	0.19	6.4	0.10

kg/ha SiO₂ all applied at planting. Peta lodged irrespective of the treatment, but the yield increased from 1,374 to 1,770 kg/ha rough rice with the application of silica. These data confirm that the yield of varieties like Intan, Peta, and Tjeremas, which are easily lodged, can be improved with SiO₂ applications even on soils that are relatively high in soil silicon content, but that they are consistently inferior to stiff-strawed varieties in fertile soils in the wet season. In this experiment, the highest yield with Peta did not exceed, 1,770 kg/ha.

During the wet season, Milfor-6(2) produced 5,332 kg/ha with 1,000 kg/ha SiO₂ split between planting and panicle initiation, but none of the treatment differences was significant.

From these studies it seems that to evaluate the response to silica fertilization, the varieties should be fairly resistant to lodging and not excessively vegetative.

Effect of insecticides on nitrogen status of plant and soil

Following the application of insecticides such as γ -BHC to irrigation water, the plants appear dark-green in color, healthy, and vigorous in comparison with non-treated plants. Sevin, a carbaryl insecticide, is used successfully against the rice leafhoppers that transmit virus diseases. In addition to controlling insects, both insecticides may also alter the nitrogen status of the soil and plant. Incorporation of γ -BHC and seven in the top 10 to 15 cm of soil is a less costly method of application and may give a longer residual effect.

Dry season. An experiment was conducted during the 1965 dry season to determine the effects of γ -BHC and sevin, applied in irrigation water (standard practice at the Institute) or incorporated in the soil, on the nitrogen status of the soil and plant, insect control, and grain yield.

The varieties used were PI 215936, Tainan 3, and Taichung (Native) 1 all of which are potentially high-yielding but susceptible to virus diseases. Treatment combinations of γ -BHC and sevin, together with 100 kg/ha N, were incorporated during land preparation.

The highest grain yield was obtained with the standard practice (three applications of γ -BHC into the irrigation water and a weekly spray with sevin). Taichung (Native) 1 produced the highest yield of 8,632 kg/ha (Table 19) with the standard practice. (This was the highest yield with Taichung (Native) 1 in any experiment reported.) There was a significant increase of 1,000 kg/ha rough rice with 20 kg/ha sevin incorporated in the soil (average of three varieties). These increases in grain yield with insecticide application either to the irrigation water or to the soil are mostly derived from better stem borer control as evidenced by the significant decrease in white head counts (Table 20). There was a significant negative relationship between the number of white heads and grain yield of PI 215936, Tainan 3, and Taichung (Native) 1 with r -values of $-0.85^{**} > -0.79^{**} > -0.64^{***}$, respectively. The nitrogen status of neither the soil nor the plant was altered directly by the added insecticide. However, plants pro-

TABLE 19. Effects of soil application of insecticides on the grain yield of PI 215936, Tainan 3, and Taichung (Native) 1, IRRI, 1965 dry season.

Grain yield at 14% moisture						
Treatment number	Active ingredient		Variety			Mean treatment
	γ -BHC	Sevin	PI 215936	Tainan 3	Taichung (N) 1	
	(kg/ha)		(kg/ha)	(kg/ha)	(kg/ha)	
0	No insecticides		6103	5831	5269	5734
1	Standard practice ^a		7885	6721	8632	7746
2	9	—	5155	4376	5813	5115
3	18	—	4835	4385	4283	4501
4	—	20	6614	6924	6941	6826
5	—	40	6676	6399	7267	6781
6	9	20	5987	5538	6583	6036
7	18	20	5833	4663	4813	5110
8	9	40	6556	6758	5267	5893
9	18	40	6434	5478	6301	6071
Mean (varieties)			6900	5617	6797	
Rate of applied N:			100 kg/ha			
Duration (days)			123	123	121	
Analysis of Variance:			LSD	cv($\bar{x}$) %	CV(X) %	
Insecticide treatments**			791	4.7	14	
Variety*			468	2.0	11	

^a 3 applications of γ -BHC and weekly spray with sevin.

tected from rice stem borers were able to take up more nitrogen than the control plots with no insecticide treatment.

Wet season. During the wet season, the experiment was repeated with lower rates of γ -BHC (1-9 kg/ha active ingredient) and from 5 to 50 kg/ha sevin (a.i.) in combinations and incorporated in the soil before transplanting. These treatments were compared with three applications of γ -BHC (8 kg total) applied in the irrigation water together with sevin (30 kg total) sprays at 10-day intervals (standard practice).

Tainan 3, potentially a high-yielding ponlai but extremely susceptible to virus disease, was used. As in the dry season, the highest grain yield was obtained with the standard practice (3,898 kg/ha rough rice) and the lowest in the control plots (2,333 kg/ha), followed by three applications of γ -BHC in irrigation water and 5 kg of sevin incorporated into the top soil (3,836 kg/ha). There was an increase of grain yield from 2,411 kg/ha in no-sevin, no-BHC treatments to 3,249 kg/ha with 20 kg sevin (a.i.) incorporated in the soil

Fig. 26. Effects of increased levels of sevin (active ingredient) incorporated in soil on number of virus hills in Tainan 3 sampled from three center rows, IRRI, 1965 wet season.

TABLE 20. Effects of soil application of insecticides on white head counts of PI 215936, Tainan 3, and Taichung (Native) 1, IRRI, 1965 dry season.

White head counts (average, 4 replicates)						
Treatment number	Insecticide applied		Variety			Mean treatment
	γ -BHC (active ingredient) (kg/ha)	Sevin (kg/ha)	PI 215936	Tainan 3	Taichung (N) 1	
0	0	0	58	118	86	87
1	Standard practice ^a		12	35	2	24
2	9	—	112	275	47	145
3	18	—	145	453	42	213
4	—	20	56	83	17	52
5	—	40	41	36	10	29
6	9	20	145	307	38	163
7	18	20	92	239	45	125
8	9	40	67	193	17	92
9	18	40	84	248	16	116
Mean (varieties)			81	199	32	

Analysis of Variance:	LSD	cv($\bar{x}$) %	CV(X) %
Insecticide treatments**	46	22	67
Variety*	44	16	86
V X T*	79	39	67

^a 3 applications of γ -BHC and weekly spray with sevin.

without any γ -BHC treatment or sevin spray — an increase of 838 kg/ha rough rice by using only 20 kg/ha sevin incorporated in the soil. There was a significant reduction of white heads from 139/20.9 to 10/20.9 sq m, in the standard practice, and to 29 from three applications of γ -BHC in irrigation water + 20 kg/ha sevin incorporated in the soil.

With increased rates of sevin application, the number of virus hills decreased with up to 30 kg/ha active ingredient and the differences in the number of virus hills between no-sevin and 30 kg/

ha sevin was significant; beyond the rate of 30 kg sevin the difference in the number of virus hills was not significant (Fig. 26).

As in the dry season, there was no evidence of any relationship between γ -BHC or sevin applied in irrigation water and mineralization of nitrogen from Maahas clay soil. The dark-green healthy appearance of rice plants following γ -BHC application is probably a simple reflection of the higher proportion of undamaged leaf tissue and improved vigor compared to plants not protected from insect pests.

STUDIES OF OTHER CULTURAL PRACTICES

Spacing trials with transplanted rice

During the 1965 dry season, nine early, stiff-strawed rice varieties and six tall, medium duration varieties were grown at spacings of 100, 40, 30, 20 and 10 cm square, and at a broadcast seeding rate which resulted in a mean plant

spacing of approximately 1 x 1 cm. The tall, medium-maturing varieties (140 days) were planted in the seedbed in December and fertilized with 100 kg/ha of nitrogen as ammonium sulfate. The short duration (125 days) varieties were sown in January with a dressing

of 140 kg/ha N given as 100 kg/ha at transplanting and 40 kg topdressing at panicle initiation. Both classes of varieties were transplanted to mature in early May.

Table 21 shows the mean and maximum yields for both classes of variety and the spacing at which the maximum was attained. The mean yields for the early, stiff-strawed varieties were approximately twice those of the tall, later varieties. The tall varieties lodged without exception; all the shorter varieties lodged in the broadcast treatment and at the 10-cm spacing but remained erect without exception in the 1-meter spacing, with the intermediate spacings resulting in lodging for some varieties. Maximum yields of more than 8 tons were obtained with three varieties: a ponlai type (CI 9545) and two American *indicas* (No. 6993 and 6974). Milfor-6(2), a Philippine variety, was among the higher-yielding varieties. The majority of stiff-strawed varieties gave the best yield at 20 x 20 cm spacing.

On the average, the differences between spacings with either class of varieties were not statistically significant from 10 x 10 cm to 40 x 40 cm. Figure 27 shows the relationship between the yield and leaf area index for both groups of varieties. The spacing means for all varieties in the class are plotted as crosses, the arms of which are proportional to twice the standard error of the mean for yield (vertically) and leaf area (horizontally). It is apparent that the yield differences were not significant for either class of variety except for the 1 x 1 meter spacing which was, of course, intended only to determine maximum leaf area production/hill.

An interesting outcome of the measurement of the leaf area index for all of the varieties was absence of a relationship between leaf area index and grain yield. Statistically significant differences were obtained between most of the spacing treatments with respect to leaf area. The leaf area index, however, was clearly determined by the spacing

TABLE 21. Mean and maximum yields in a variety x spacing experiment involving two classes of plant type, 1965 dry season.

Variety and duration	Mean yield	Maximum yield and spacing ^a	
	(kg/ha)	(cm)	(kg/ha)
<i>Late, tall varieties</i>			
1. H-4	4969	10 x 10	5899
2. Sigadis	3943	40 x 40	4612
3. Intan	2728	30 x 30	4058
4. Acheh	2474	Broadcast	4139
5. FB-121	2503	10 x 10	3708
6. Peta	2120	40 x 40	3137
<i>Early, stiff-strawed varieties</i>			
1. C.I. 9545	6563	20 x 20	8449
2. 6993 (CP 231 x SLO-17)	6551	20 x 20	8186
3. 6974 (B572)	6458	30 x 30	8610
4. PI 215936	5948	40 x 40	7507
5. 6966 (B5711)	5935	20 x 20	7459
6. Milfor-6(2)	5763	40 x 40	7150
7. 6989 (B573-20-6)	5690	20 x 20	7296
8. B581-A4-15	4788	20 x 20	5850
9. Zenith	4554	20 x 20	5506

^a Except for 1 m x 1 m spacing, yield differences between spacings were not significant.

Fig. 27. Relation of grain yield to leaf area index and spacing in medium duration, lodging varieties and short duration stiff-strawed varieties, 1965 dry season.

treatment and was not related to grain yield. For any particular spacing mean, the shorter, stiff-strawed varieties characteristically had a lower leaf area index, but with these varieties, as with the taller ones, the differences between spacings were significant for leaf area index but not for yield.

While the stiff-strawed varieties, on the average, produced the highest yield at 20 x 20 cm spacing, the differences

were not significant, and in practice the economics of transplanting would probably dictate a somewhat wider spacing under conditions of high soil fertility.

The practical application is that widely spaced plants (30 or 40 cm distances) will yield as high as closer transplanting under conditions of high soil fertility and high sunlight intensity but it is not possible to generalize concerning an "optimum" LAI for maximum yields.

Water management in relation to rice yield

During the dry season, water use for rice was measured in 16 bottomless metal tanks irrigated from concrete reservoirs. Evapo-transpiration and evaporation were determined in separate measurement tanks, and environmental data were collected to quantify completely the water relationships in the experiment. Eight different systems of irrigation were used with the varieties Chianung 242 and Milfor-6(2) grown with 120 kg/ha N. The water treatments were: (1) deep continuous flooding (10 cm), (2) shallow continuous

TABLE 22. Effects of irrigation treatments on grain yield, straw weight, grain straw ratio and efficiency of water use for Chianung 242 (Methods of irrigation, 1965 dry season).

Treatment	Grain yield		Straw yield		Grain/ straw ratio	Water use 91 days		Water efficiency	
	(kg/ha)	Index	(kg/ha)	Index		Total (mm)	Index	Grain (g/l)	Grain/ straw (g/l)
1. DCF (10 cm)	7563	100	5878	100	1.29	683	100	1.11	1.97
2. SCF (2.5 cm)	7953	105	6789	115	1.18	559	82	1.42	2.64
3. II	8088	107	6708	114	1.24	612	90	1.32	2.42
4. DS	5250	69	4994	85	1.05	409	60	1.28	2.50
5. DS + F	6966	92	5535	94	1.27	794	116	0.88	1.57
6. AI	7562	100	6699	114	1.13	606	89	1.25	2.35
7. AI + F	8391	111	7471	127	1.12	728	107	1.15	2.18
8. IMS	5561	74	5795	99	0.96	498	73	1.12	2.28
LSD _{.05}	1340								
Duncan's multiple range test									
Treatment no.	7	3	2	1	6	5	8	4	
Mean	8391	8088	7953	7563	7562	6966	5561	5250	

Treatment means underscored by the same line are not significantly different at 5% level.

Fig. 28. Comparison of cumulative water use with various irrigation methods, 1965 dry season.

flooding (2.5 cm water), (3) ideal irrigation with mid-season drainage, (4) drained surface, (5) drained surface followed by continuous flooding, (6) alternate irrigation (5 cm of water, 7-day cycle), (7) alternate irrigation followed by continuous flooding at panicle initiation, (8) irrigation (5 cm of water) at moisture stress.

Figure 28 illustrates the cumulative water use with the several systems of water management. Table 22 lists the grain yield, straw yield, total water use, and the efficiency of grain production in grams/liter water. The figures show the relationships between irrigation methods and cumulative water use taken over the entire growth cycle. Values are expressed as percentages of the deep continuous flooding treatment. Reduced amounts of water were used by the drained surface treatment, the irrigation at moisture stress treatment, and the shallow continuous flood treatment.

There was no significant reduction in

water use by the ideal irrigation system, alternate irrigation, or the alternate irrigation followed by flooding. The drained surface treatment followed by flooding required a total amount of water greater than that used in the deep continuous flooding system. The high rate of water use was caused by large increases during the 2 weeks following the 40th day after transplanting when the panicle initials were formed. This marked increase in water use following drainage and soil-drying was investigated in later greenhouse experiments and found to result principally from restoration of water removed from soil storage, primarily in the first few days after re-irrigation.

The analysis of variance produced a significant F value, and the Duncan multiple range test indicated that yields in treatments 4 and 8 were significantly lower than the other treatments in the experiment. No statistical significance could be assigned to the differences between the other treatments.

Both the drained surface and the irrigation at moisture stress treatments reduced the yield of Chianung 242 when these treatments were used throughout. Grain production efficiency, in terms of amount of grain per unit of water, was at a maximum with the shallow continuous flood treatment. This treatment yielded 1.42 grams of grain per liter of water (7.1 ha-cm/ton or 1.42 kg/m³) while the drained surface system, when followed by continuous flooding, yielded only 0.88 grams per liter.

It would appear that shallow continuous flooding is the most truly efficient

system where water is limited or needs to be conserved and managed most efficiently. This system also used the least total quantity of water, 559 mm in 91 days, and produced a yield that was not significantly different from the best. In practice, the shallow flooding treatments would probably increase the cost of weed control, and the system should be altered slightly to include a somewhat deeper flooding early in the crop cycle to help control weeds, with a reduction to shallow flooding until drainage for harvest.

WEED CONTROL

Regional weed control trial

During 1964, a regional weed control trial was conducted as an outgrowth of a weed control short course. The weed control experiment for lowland rice, designed by the delegates, consisted of 12 chemical treatments and two controls: weeded by hand and non-weeded. The chemical treatments consisted of nine chemical combinations as outlined in Table 23.

The best over-all yields were recorded in an experiment in Chiayi, Taiwan, where Chianung 242 was grown as the second crop of 1964. There was superior weed control and yield in plots treated with dichlorobenzonitrile (dichlobenil or casoron 133).

In this experiment the dichlobenil treatment yielded an increase over hand weeding of about 560 kg/ha of rice. The PCP treatment at Suwon, Korea, and the propanil treatment in upland rice at La Granja, Negros, Philippines, were the only other treatments that yielded more than those that were hand-weeded. The value of weed control in terms of kg of rice is given as the difference between the hand-weeded and non-weeded control. The value of the chemical treatments can be estimated from the number of man-days required for the hand-weeding, plus or minus the yield value from the best chemical treatment in relation to hand-weeding.

In three out of seven cases, hand-weeding was superior to any chemical

treatment, but in three locations in the Philippines and one in Thailand the yields were so low that the experiment was inconclusive. Although the combination of propanil and 2,4-D was superior, the increase was so low that it cannot be considered economic.

In many experiments conducted with lowland rice, the low return from weed control can be attributed either to low yields resulting from either inferior varieties, competitiveness of the varieties, bad weather, other inadequate management practices, or the control of weeds by deep water. Substantial returns from weeding did accrue from the experiment with upland rice at La Granja, Negros. The yield increase of 1,939 kg/ha obtained from hand-weeding illustrates the greater importance of the weed problem in upland rice where flooding is not a weed control method. The practical conclusions are that propanil is a suitable herbicide and can be commercially successful in upland rice, and the best method for flooded rice weed control is either hand-weeding alone, or a spray of either MCPA or 2,4-D followed by a moderate amount of hand-weeding.

Weed control in flooded rice

In a wet season weed control test of combinations of chemicals, mechanical, and hand methods selected from experience and screening tests, the yields of rice and costs of control in terms of la-

TABLE 23. Yield of rice in a uniform regional weed control experiment in four Asian countries, 1964 wet season.

Treatment	Rate (active) kg/ha	Bankhen, Thailand	Midsayap, Philippines	La Granja, Philippines	Los Baños, Philippines	Maligaya, Philippines	Chiayi, Taiwan	Suwon, Korea	
									Rough rice (kg/ha)
1. PCP-Na	15.0	2187	2310	3452	2239	1125	4828	3915	
2. Propanil (Stam F-34)	3.5	2392	2060	4363	2472	1277	4435	3913	
3. Propanil + MCPA	3.5+0.8	2220	1950	4361	2280	1068	4322	3900	
4. MCPA (Agroxone-4)	0.8	2335	1740	2797	2262	1059	4665	3837	
5. Propanil + 2,4-D	3.5+0.8	2452	1780	3371	2177	1132	4658	3795	
6. 2,4-D (Hedonal)	0.8	2270	2130	2964	2021	1022	4215	3782	
7. Carbamate (swep)	5.0	2078	1890	3938	1930	1026	4775	3667	
8. Swep + MCPA	4+0.5	2432	1780	4319	1638	1021	4694	3649	
Ametryne									
9. Simetryne	0.5	1939	2050	3514	2122	967	4739	3570	
10. Molinate (Ordram)	5.0	2144	1770	3488	2466	994	4701	3560	
11. MCPA	3.0	2356	1840	3010	2256	1004	4920	3511	
12. Dichlobenil (Casoron 133)	2.0	2099	1920	2819	2223	1250	5253	3409	
13. Non-weeded control		1814	2020	1846	1919	836	3933	2715	
14. Hand-weeded control		2282	2860	3785	2641	1373	4690	3407	
Variety									
		—	Peta	Dina- laga	BPI-76	BPI-76	Chianung Jae 242	Keun	
a. Yield increase from weeding (14-13), kg		468	840	1939	722	537	757	692	
b. Yield increase from best chemical treatment over hand-weeding		170	-550	578	-169	-96	563	508	
c. Best chemical treatment		Propanil +2,4-D	PCP-Na	Pro- panil	Pro- panil	Pro- panil	DBN	PCP- Na	
d. Man-day/ha for hand-weeding		n.a.	8	61	30	n.a.	50	51	

^a Upland rice.

bor and investment were evaluated. A rice paddy planted to Chianung 242 was seeded with 3 kg/ha of weed seeds, principally water grass (*Echinochloa crusgalli*). Standard water management and insect control practices were applied and the field was fertilized with 30 kg/ha N as ammonium sulfate at planting time and topdressed with 20 kg N at panicle initiation.

Table 24 shows the rice yield, toxicity, weeding costs, and other values of interest in the analysis. The cost of hand-weeding was established at 50 centavos per hour, which is the current cost of industrial wages but is high for the normal agricultural labor. One kg of rice was valued at \$0.073, and the costs

of the herbicides are listed at the approximate world price cost to the farmer some distance from ports and warehouses. The cost of "prefix" and "casoron" are somewhat uncertain since they are not widely marketed at present.

The weeds grew extremely well and the field was infested with *Echinochloa crusgalli* to a much greater degree than would be normal for a local paddy field. The test, therefore, was a severe one and, since all costs are high, the returns are conservatively estimated.

The best yields were obtained from the plots hand-weeded twice. The 5,204 kg/ha was not significantly higher than the next five treatments. Without weeding, the potentially high-yielding Chia-

age to squeeze under the wire without receiving a shock; others enter through holes dug in the levees. Furthermore, the fence is electrified only at night, and rats may enter the plots during the day. To deal with rats inside the plots, use is made of traps, cyanogas dusted around burrows, and poisons such as 1080 and warfarin offered as baits in corn, rice, and grated coconut.

The fence system is operated and patrolled every night. Men in the control squad work 8-hour shifts to insure that the fence is operating correctly, to

remove dead rats from the fence, and to kill those merely stunned.

The monthly tallies of rats killed show that the numbers increase in May, reach a peak in July, and then gradually diminish. The reason for this fluctuation may be that in May, June, and July the nearby farms are not planted and the Institute plots thus offer the most enticing food in the district. With the commencement of planting on surrounding farms in late July and August, the rat population at the Institute declines.

nung 242 variety produced only 1,611 kg/ha. In the best treatment, 3,593 kg/ha rice were gained through adequate weed control. As was anticipated from other experiments, the two best-yielding chemical treatments were those with MCPA or 2,4-D followed by rotary weeding, but the use of the rotary weeder before applying the chemicals was significantly inferior to the reverse procedure both in terms of the weed control obtained and the yields of rice. This effect is interpreted as due to increased early weed competition, since the rotary weeder does not thoroughly remove weeds, and possibly to some slight toxicity from late application of the phenoxy herbicide.

A single hand-weeding and a single rotary weeding also gave profitable returns to the cost of weed control although yields were lower. Both the rotary weeding and hand-weeding costs in this test were substantially higher than normal, 616 man-hours being required per hectare for hand-weeding.

The dichlobenil treatment, followed by MCPA produced a relatively high yield with a rather low chemical cost although it appeared quite weedy at the time of harvest. The greatest return per man-hour of labor was derived from a single application of dichlobenil at 0.75 kg/ha from which 135 kg of rice were obtained per man-hour of labor. The poorest return to labor alone was obtained with the two hand-weedings in which only 6 kg of rice were earned. The best returns to investment in weed control were obtained from hand- or rotary weedings and their combinations with the phenoxy acids. In farm practice, these latter two would probably be the best choices for efficiency since the phenoxy acids are readily available. This material would require a low capital investment or cash outlay for chemical and require less labor.

Weed control in upland rice

An important reason for low yields of most upland rice is the absence of effective, low-cost weed control. A few varieties will produce yields nearly equal to those of flooded rice, but many of the short-statured or low-tillering types will

be outgrown and over-topped by weeds, especially under high fertility conditions. Hand-weeding is effective and widely practiced but the cost of human labor is high, and the rice production returns are low. Mechanical methods are used effectively only in coarse-textured soils and are seldom good enough to permit maximum yields. Effective chemical measures could greatly increase the returns to labor and management and entirely change the outlook for upland rice.

During the wet season, a series of weed control experiments was conducted with the *indica* upland variety Palawan. Three principal tests were utilized: one using selective weed control sprays, another with non-selective directed sprays, and the third test consisting of hand-weeding alone with emphasis on proper timing.

Selective sprays. From previous screening tests in upland rice, three herbicides were selected for more precise evaluation: DCPA (tetrachloroterephthalic acid), trifluralin (trifluoro-2,6-dinitro-N,N-dipropyl - p - toluidine), and propanil (2,4-dichloropropionanilide) applied at rates shown in previous tests to give adequate control. Hand-weeded and non-weeded treatments were included. DCPA and trifluralin sprays were applied before the rice emerged, and propanil was applied at 15 days after seeding when the grassy weeds were in the 2- to 3-leaf stage. Table 25 indicates weed control and grain yield from both drilled and broadcast plantings during the wet season.

Generally, yields were satisfactory and superior to the hand-weeded treatments. Weed weight was reduced to nearly zero with the expenditure of 838 man-hour/ha for three hand-weedings. Propanil at 4 kg/ha, trifluralin at 3 kg/ha, and DCPA at 8 kg/ha each followed by sprays of 2,4-D, all gave satisfactory yields but no significant differences were detected in the performance of the three chemicals. Weed control provided nearly 3 tons of additional yield compared with the non-weeded control.

In the second test, non-selective sprays were used to control weeds between the rows by making application

TABLE 25. Yields and weed control data from use of selective, broadcast and non-selective directed herbicidal sprays in upland rice (Palawan), 1965 wet season.

Treatment	SELECTIVE SPRAYS						Mean yield (kg/ha)
	Weed control rating ^a		Weed weight at harvest		Grain yield		
	Drilled visual score	Broad- cast	Drilled (g/sq m)	Broad- cast	Drilled (kg/ha)	Broad- cast	
1. DCPA (8 kg/ha) pre-emergence + 2,4-D (1 kg/ha) 30 days after seeding	1.9	2.0	590	610	2913	2732	2823
2. Trifluralin (3 kg/ha) pre-emergence + 2,4-D (1 kg/ha) 30 days after seeding	1.4	1.8	360	510	3210	3015	3113
3. Propanil (4 kg/ha) + 2,4-D (1 kg/ha) 15 days after seeding	1.5	2.3	420	790	3530	2543	3036
4. Hand-weeding (3 weedings required an average of 280 man-hr/ha)	1.0	1.0	—	—	3943	3626	3785
5. No treatment	5.0	5.0	1230	1410	575	330	453
Mean	2.2	2.4	650	820	2834	2449	
	NON-SELECTIVE DIRECTED SPRAYS (18 days after seeding)						
6. PCP (oil) — 6 kg/ha + 2,4-D (1 kg/ha) 30 days after seeding	2.7		570		2622		
7. PCP (Na) — 6 kg/ha D. oil (60 l/ha) + 2,4-D 30 days after seeding	3.5		670		2020		
8. Paraquat — 2 l/ha + 2,4-D 30 days after seeding	3.7		910		1978		

^a Visual score: 10 = no control; 1 = complete control.

with a shielded nozzle. Three materials were used: pentachlorophenol in diesel oil, sodium pentachlorophenate, and paraquat; they were applied at rates known to give adequate control. Of the three materials used, the PCP (oil) spray gave superior weed control and the highest yield. High variability prevented differences from being significant but none of the three treatments controlled weeds as well as the selective broadcast sprays. Some phytotoxicity was observed with each of the non-selective materials but most of the damage was apparently caused by unsatisfactory operation of the shielding equipment.

Time of hand-weeding in upland rice. Preliminary studies of timing of hand-weeding were reported in the 1964 Annual Report. In the current season, the experiment was repeated, using proce-

dures in which weeding started earlier after seeding, and was repeated at more frequent intervals.

The data in Fig. 29 indicate a maximum yield from a single hand-weeding at about 25 days after seeding. This yield of 2,608 kg was more than a ton below that of rice weeded three times. As in the previous experiment, the delay of hand-weeding beyond 15 to 25 days sharply reduced yields. Based on the differences between weeding at 25 and 45 days, each day's delay in hand-weeding reduced yield by 43 kg/ha and sharply increased labor requirements. When a single hand-weeding was made 15 days after seeding, only 240 man-hr/ha were required, but when the hand-weeding was delayed until 45 days after seeding, labor requirements were 780 man-hr/ha. In addition, the delay

Fig. 29. Yield, percentage of breakage, and labor requirement for weeding in upland rice (Palawan) weeded at four dates after drilling, 1965 wet season.

in hand-weeding greatly increased the amount of direct damage to the rice plant. This was recorded as a visual estimate of leaf and tiller breakage after each weeding. When hand-weeding was delayed for 45 days and the rice plants were well into the tillering stage about 50% of the plants suffered some degree of breakage.

A non-weeded control, as usual, was extremely low-yielding, producing only

670 kg/ha. In plots that were weeded when weeds appeared to be causing competition, the yields were quite satisfactory for upland rice production; 3,740 kg/ha were produced with only 530 man-hr/ha of hand-weeding time. Although yields with the three handweedings were superior by more than a ton of rice, the returns to hand-weeding time, when considering hand-weeding the only input, were about 7 kg/

man-hr for three hand-weedings, and 8.3 kg of rice/man-hr for a single hand-weeding 25 days after seeding. This clearly illustrates the importance of timing when using limited manpower for hand-weeding.

Although there was a reduction in returns to man-hours of labor with additional weedings, it is apparent that production can be greatly increased by thoroughly removing the weeds, and that a single weeding could not be recommended as a practice.

Delayed planting techniques. During the 1965 dry season, use of stale seedbed or delayed planting techniques for weed control in upland rice was examined. The principle of this system is one of delaying seeding after the tillage operations to permit germination and growth of the initial crop of weeds in the field. The planting, either by drill or broadcasting, is then made in the weedy seedbed and weeds are controlled by a broadcast spray of non-selective herbicides before the emergence of the rice. Non-selective sprays are normally much cheaper than the selective materials which are used either pre- or post-emergence.

Ten varieties of rice were drilled with a grain drill in the weedy seedbed in an upland field toward the close of the 1965 dry season. Drilling was completed on the 18th day following rotovation.

The initial light rains of the monsoon season were sufficient to germinate a uniform stand of grassy and broad-leaved weeds at the time of spraying which was 4 days after drilling when the rice was just emerging from the soil. Weed control was effected with (1) 4 kg/ha propanil, (2) 4 kg/ha PCP in diesel oil, and (3) 4 kg/ha PCP in an emulsion of diesel oil and water. Propanil and the PCP emulsion were sprayed at volumes of 330 and 200 liters/ha respectively. The field was sprayed 28 days after planting, with 1.0 kg/ha active 2,4-D as the sodium salt and top-dressed with nitrogen at 40 kg/ha N.

The yields of eight of the varieties are reported in Table 26. Two of the earliest varieties were severely damaged by rats on a rather selective basis and were eliminated from tabulation. Satisfactory yields were obtained from Taichung (Native) 1, CI 9545, No. 6993, PI 215936, and Milfor-6(2), all of which are normally planted as lowland varieties. The best yields and best weed control were obtained with the spray of propanil at the 3- to 5-leaf stage of weed growth. The timing, however, was not optimum for the use of propanil since the rice was younger than it would normally be when planted immediately after land preparation. Weed control with either the PCP oil or the oil emulsion

TABLE 26. Yields and dry weed weight for varieties of rice drilled as an upland crop into a weedy seedbed. Chemicals were sprayed for weed control at the time of emergence of rice seedlings.

Variety	Propanil		PCP-oil-water		PCP-oil	
	Yield	Weed weight	Yield	Weed weight	Yield	Weed weight
	(kg/ha)	(g/sq m)	(kg/ha)	(g/sq m)	(kg/ha)	(g/sq m)
CI 9545	2924	137	2632	147	2053	279
Taichung (Native) 1	2601	91	2042	175	2125	166
6993	2403	350	2524	339	2166	372
PI 215936	2601	289	2069	358	2066	374
Milfor-6(2)	2564	339	1639	510	1261	304
Miltex	1665	122	1873	224	1413	181
Azucena	1949	446	1099	209	1316	428
Palawan	1863	336	1325	560	1120	400
Mean	2321	264	1900	315	1690	313

LSD₀₅ weed wt = 143 g.

Fig. 30. Percentage of seedling survival 30 days after direct seeding in various depths of water. Fifteen high-yielding rice varieties, IRRI, 1965 wet season.

was not significantly lower than the propanil treatment.

This preliminary experiment indicates a promising topic for continued research on non-selective sprays for pre-planting and pre-emergent weed control. It is also probable that the technique will permit not only lower cost herbicides to be used but will minimize the tillage requirements for upland rice.

Direct seeding and water depth

A wet season trial of direct seeding was established in a field sloping uniformly from 5 cm above to 30 cm below water level. Seeds of fifteen varieties of rice were soaked and broadcast in rows 25 cm apart in 4-row plots 6 meters long so that each meter of row represented a 5-cm change in water depth.

Figure 30 shows the relationship of seedling survival, 30 days after seeding, to water depth. Survival was based on seed that germinated 10 days after

seeding at which time no effect of water depth was detected. The best survival at deep depths was made by the tall, high-tillering variety Peta, and the poorest survival by the short-statured Century Patna x SLO-17 cross (6993).

The results did not appear to be directly related to plant height at maturity or seedling growth rate or vigor, and fundamental investigations are required for full understanding. However, in practice, it appears that water seeding for most varieties should not be attempted in depths beyond 20 cm (8 inches); the optimum seems to be in the 5 to 15 cm range for the varieties tested. This is shallower than depths used in temperate zone countries where water temperatures are lower and oxygen concentrations higher, but demonstrates the range of water depths permissible for direct-seeding many *indica* varieties when predators are controlled.

Entomology

The stem borers, leafhoppers, and planthoppers often substantially reduce rice yields throughout Asia. In experiments at the Institute and in several provinces of the Philippines, treated plots produced 1 to 3 ton/ha more rice than did the untreated controls. This increase often represented 50 to 100% more rice than the controls. During 1965, the research program emphasized control of the stem borers and leafhoppers.

Use of insecticides and varietal resistance have been the major approaches in rice stem borer control with attention also being given to biological control, and chemosterilants. All of the germ plasm of rice at the Institute has been screened for stem borer resistance, and selected resistant and susceptible varieties were used to study the pos-

sibilities of varietal resistance, the causes of resistance, and its mode of inheritance. Gamma-BHC in the paddy water has been adopted as the standard stem borer control practice at the Institute. The chemical is being studied in several cooperative projects in the Philippines and other countries and is gaining general acceptance for the control

Fig. 1. Fluctuations in adult and larval populations of different stem borer species throughout the year, IRRI, 1965.

of this pest.

During the year considerable basic information on the γ -BHC was obtained, and a few other insecticides, both contact and systemic, have been identified as alternatives should stem borers develop resistance to the compound.

Studies on residues of γ -BHC were initiated. Some basic studies have been conducted on the mating habits of the moths and the effect of chemosterilants. Intensive surveys of the seasonal fluctuations of stem borers and their parasites have been made and the possibilities explored of using such parasites for stem borer control.

The common stem borer species at the Institute — *Chilo suppressalis* Walker, *Tryporyza incertulas* Walker and *Sesamia inferens* Walker — occur in overlapping generations the year around.

Chilo suppressalis is the most abundant species (Fig. 1). *Chilo traea polychrysa* Meyrick has also been recorded, but the population is low.

The common leafhoppers and plant-hoppers at the Institute are *Nephotettix apicalis* Motchulsky, *Tettigella spectra* Distant, *Cicadulina bipuncta* Matsumura, *Sogatella furcifera* Horvath and *Nilaparvata lugens* Stal. They may occur in sufficient populations to seriously damage rice by direct feeding; several are also vectors of rice viruses. These insects were sampled intensively throughout the year to determine population fluctuations, and several insecticides were tested for their systemic and contact effects. The details of bionomics and population development of *Nephotettix* spp. and *Nilaparvata lugens* are being investigated.

VARIETAL RESISTANCE TO RICE STEM BORER

Screening for varietal resistance

The general screening of the rice genetic stocks at the Institute for stem borer resistance, started in June, 1962, was completed in the 1965 dry season. Over all about 9,000 varieties were tested with the primary objective of discarding the bulk of the susceptible varieties and to identify those with some resistance.

In the January-May period, 2,190 varieties were tested. These varieties were graded for infestation with rice whorl maggot, *Hydrellia* spp. (most probably a new species, the maggots of which

feed on the margin of the unopened leaves, and which are abundant during the earlier stages of plant growth). The damage from stem borers was noted by the number of dead hearts and white heads at 60 days after transplanting and 10 days before harvest, respectively. Percentages of infested tillers and number of living larvae per hill were also recorded on a few selected varieties.

Varieties varied significantly in stem borer infestations. The more susceptible varieties had as much as 5 times more dead hearts, 16 times more white heads, 8 times more infested tillers and 20

TABLE 1. Rice stem borer infestations on some of the 2,190 varieties tested in the field, IRRI, January-May, 1965.

Variety	Dead hearts (%)	White heads (%)	Infested tillers (%)	No. larvae/hill
Fuku-Bozu	3.2	0.8	8.1	0.6
Insen x Trimisimo	4.0	3.0	14.8	0.6
Tung-An-Chung	4.9	1.6	26.7	2.8
Chung-shan	5.3	3.2	8.2	0.6
Kumbi	8.5	0.8	30.1	3.2
Chang-chow	7.4	1.2	32.0	3.0
Pen Gopher	11.3	11.4	63.3	15.8
CI 5794	16.2	14.8	53.6	6.4
Tainan iku 484	10.4	5.2	43.1	11.6

times higher larval populations than did the more resistant varieties (Table 1). Many varieties remained resistant or susceptible throughout the period of plant growth while others were more resistant either to dead heart or white head formations. The differences in varietal susceptibility did not depend on

the early or late maturity of the varieties studied.

Retesting of selected varieties

The resistant and a few susceptible varieties (a total of 1,351 varieties) selected from all of the general screening tests of the 10,000 varieties were plant-

TABLE 2. Intensity of stem borer infestation in some of 1,350 varieties selected from a general screening of 10,000 varieties, IRRI, July-December, 1965.

Variety	Dead hearts (%)	White heads (%)	Infested tillers (%)	No. larvae/hill
Ta-poo-cho	0.39	0.96	24.88	5.0
Lam-kan-mi-thow-gou	1.37	1.69	10.97	0.0
Szu-miao	1.68	1.74	12.19	3.4
DNJ-97	2.36	0.35	11.02	2.0
CO 13	3.95	0.37	30.30	5.4
Chua-dau	2.25	4.39	7.58	0.0
Su-yai 20	2.26	0.87	12.19	3.4
Wan-pai-tsin-3	2.98	3.64	17.85	8.6
Su-miao	2.23	1.25	7.38	1.0
Chen-chia-tao	3.42	1.16	44.36	9.8
Wan keng 10,959	3.33	1.46	16.98	1.8
Hill sel RN BMT 54-U-103	5.25	3.43	31.68	4.4
Tieh-chui-ku	6.45	1.98	28.82	3.4
Rexoro	12.74	6.50	45.40	5.0

Fig. 2. Differences in rice stem borer damage to resistant and susceptible varieties planted in adjacent rows, IRRI, 1965.

ed in July, 1965. Stem borer and rice whorl maggot infestations were recorded. Most of the varieties that reacted as resistant in the general screening also had low stem borer infestation in this experiment (Table 2). Although planted in adjacent rows, some varieties were heavily damaged while others had low infestation (Fig. 2). Since the number of varieties reacting as resistant was fairly large, those showing suscep-

tibility to viruses, lodging, unusually early or late maturity, and other undesirable agronomic characters such as extreme leafiness and tallness were rejected. From these about 60 varieties were selected for further study.

Resistant and susceptible varieties and the striped borer larvae

Repeated greenhouse experiments using large numbers of rice varieties

Fig. 3. Survival of freshly hatched striped borer larvae on resistant and susceptible plants of different ages, IRRI, 1965.

confirmed that stem borer larvae had significantly lower survival on varieties reacting as resistant than on those reacting as susceptible. Detailed investigations were made of the survival and development of uniform numbers of freshly hatched striped borer larvae on Taitung 16 and Chianan 2 (resistant) and Sapan Kwai and Rexoro (susceptible) varieties.

More larvae survived on susceptible than on resistant varieties regardless of plant age (Fig. 3). The larval weights also were consistently higher on susceptible than on resistant varieties, although on both resistant and susceptible varieties larvae were heavier on older plants (Fig. 4). The rate of larval growth was faster on susceptible varieties, on which larvae started and completed their pupation earlier than on resistant varieties (Fig. 5). On older plants, the larval period was reduced by about 5 days on both resistant and susceptible varieties. The total pupation was consistently higher at all stages of growth on susceptible varieties (Fig. 6). On susceptible varieties the larvae

had higher survival, heavier body weights, and faster growth, resulting in heavier pupae than those on resistant varieties.

Field cage studies over a period of four months confirmed that the cumulative rate of development of the stem borer population was faster on a susceptible than on a resistant variety.

Observations made at the termination of the experiment showed that 56.3 percent of the total tillers of variety Sapan Kwai were dead hearts; in contrast, less than 1 percent of the tillers of Chianan 2 were dead hearts.

Low survival and slow rate of growth of larvae on the resistant variety were major factors in determining cumulative population trait. Another important factor responsible for low population in subsequent generations may have been that the moths did not all emerge at the same time and therefore, the mating frequency was reduced. These observations indicate that if suitable resistant varieties were bred, they would cumulatively reduce stem borer population and the damage they cause.

Fig. 4. Average weight per larva 20 days after infestation on different rice varieties at various ages, IRRI, 1964-65.

Causes of resistance

During the year the causes of varietal resistance in rice stem borers were

Fig. 5. Percentages of striped borer pupation on resistant and susceptible varieties at different intervals from infestation. Freshly hatched larvae were used for infesting plants at 30 days after transplanting, IRRI, 1965.

Fig. 6. Percentage of pupation and emergence of striped borer moths at different ages of plants from susceptible and resistant rice varieties, IRRI, 1965.

investigated further. The correlations between stem borer resistance and various plant characters are listed in Table 3. The details of these interactions were discussed in the 1964 Annual Report. Based on these studies and the retesting of varieties from general screening for stem borer resistance, 20 varieties were selected for an investigation of other factors involved in resistance.

Ovipositional preference

The number of eggs laid on different

varieties varied from 5 to 27 per 300 plants. The ovipositional preference played a strong role in the infestation of a variety, as varieties receiving fewer egg masses generally had lower percentages of dead hearts. However, many varieties having a large number of egg masses still produced lower percentages of dead hearts, e.g. Fujisaka 5 and Taitung 16. This discrepancy occurs because the number of eggs laid is primarily an outcome of insect preference for oviposition, whereas the percentage of dead hearts also depends on the suit-

ability of a variety for larval feeding and survival.

Observations on the pattern of occurrence of dead hearts around the plant receiving the egg mass confirmed that such differences exist. In susceptible varieties, generally, three to four dead hearts were formed on the oviposited plant and on others within a radius of two to three hills from it. In resistant varieties the number of dead hearts on the oviposited plant was 1 or 2, and the incidence of dead hearts in the adjacent hills was also considerably lower.

Differences in the ovipositional preference of moths were also studied in a supplementary experiment where varieties Taitung 16, TAM-6 and Rexoro were planted in 5 x 21 hill plots in a circle in 3 replications. The susceptible variety Rexoro had 4 to 20 times more egg masses than the resistant varieties TKM-6 and Taitung 16, a reaction consistent throughout the test (Fig. 7). These data, therefore, show that the

Fig. 7. Number of stem borer egg masses laid on resistant and susceptible varieties planted in a circle in three replications, IRRI, 1965.

moths exhibited a strong preference for oviposition among these varieties. Apparently the highest number of egg masses was laid from 40 to 70 days after transplanting.

Infestation on resistant and susceptible varieties

Observations 35 days after transplanting the 20 varieties studied did not show any significant difference in the percentages of dead hearts formed during different test seasons, but the differences became greater in subsequent observations made 55 and 75 days after transplanting. In these later observations in general, the percentages of dead hearts increased on all of the varieties, but there was a significant difference in the rate of increase among different varieties (Fig. 8). However, it must be emphasized that the increase in infestations will be limited to shorter periods in areas where insects occur in distinct broods. When based on the stem borer infestation, these varieties were grouped as resistant, moderately resistant, and susceptible; the following regression values for increase of dead hearts with plant age were obtained:

Resistant

$$Y = -5.98 + 0.196 X - .001 X^2 \quad r = 0.84^{**}$$

Moderately resistant

$$Y = 5.73 + 0.16 X \quad r = 0.93^{**}$$

Susceptible

$$Y = 18.70 + 0.45 X \quad r = 0.86^{**}$$

Thus, there were definite differences in the rate of development of infestation on these varieties and since the differences were not directly associated with the number of eggs laid, they depended more on plant factors. Also, as such differences were consistent throughout the three different seasons, it was concluded that they were not due to environmental conditions or differences in insect population but to inherent differences in the stem borer susceptibility of the variety.

Fig. 8. Development of dead hearts in 20 varieties at different intervals from transplanting, IRRI, 1965.

Silica and borer resistance

Besides some of the correlations between stem borer susceptibility and

TABLE 3. Correlations between tillers infested by striped rice borer and various plant characters.

Plant characters	Correlation coefficient
Height of culm	.796**
Number of elongated internodes	.632**
Length of the 3rd elongated internode	.715**
Length of the flag leaf	.798**
Width of the flag leaf	.836**
External diameter of culm at half of its length	.672**
at 1/4 to the base	.785**
Internal diameter of culm at half of its culm	.671**
at 1/4 to the base	.790**
Number of tillers per plant	-.756**
Percentages of stem area occupied by vascular bundle sheaths	-.756**

plant morphological characters, as listed in Table 3, resistant varieties had a thicker and more lignified epidermis and more sclerenchymatous tissues than susceptible varieties. It was suspected that stem borer larvae could not easily bore into the culms of varieties containing thick layers of sclerenchymatous tissues which consist of thick-walled cells containing higher percentages of silica. Several workers have noted that the addition of silicate to the paddy soil resulted in increased percentages of silica in the rice plant and led to reduced stem borer infestation. If the variation in silica content between varieties could be shown to be related to resistance to borers, a practical and economical control measure could possibly be developed. Investigations on this aspect were therefore made.

Analyses of hills sampled from field plots showed that varieties differed significantly in silica content, the range

Fig. 9. Correlations between silica content of rice stem and stem borer susceptibility, IRRI, 1965.

being from 9.72 to 13.88%; the percentage of dead hearts was negatively correlated with the silica content of varieties (Fig. 9). In the rice stem silica is localized mostly in the epidermis, the sclerenchymatous tissues, and along the cell walls of the parenchyma. In the epidermis, it is deposited as silica bodies contained in silica cells. The silica cells of different varieties vary in their distribution and shape. Varieties with high silica content had more silica cells in the epidermis, and the number of silica cells was negatively correlated with the percentages of dead hearts formed on a variety (Fig. 10).

As the presence of silica cells in the

Fig. 10. Correlations between number of silica cells in the epidermis of the rice stem and stem borer susceptibility, IRRI, 1965.

epidermis interferes with larval boring, varieties with an uneven and sparse distribution of silica cells should be more susceptible. Such a trend was found in Sapan Kwai (susceptible) which had a low number of silica cells, these being distributed so as to leave vacant spaces on the epidermis; in variety Yabami Montakhab, the silica cells were uniformly distributed and close to each other. The silica bodies in the former were of the oblong type but of the *oryza* type in the latter. In *Oryza ridleyi*, which was recorded as being highly resistant to stem borers, the silica cells were large and dense with dumbbell-shaped silica bodies (Fig. 11). Based on a large number of larvae collected from variety Yabami Montakhab, high in silica, and variety Sapan Kwai, low in silica, the mandibles of the larvae from the former variety were generally worn out in the incisor areas whereas the mandibles of the larvae from the latter variety were not affected (Fig. 12). These results show that presence of silica cells in the plants acted as a mechanical barrier to larval boring.

Fig. 11. Distribution and size of silica cells in stems of *Oryza ridleyi* (A), Yabami Montakhab (B), and Sapan Kwai (C), IRRI, 1965.

Chemical factors

Studies have been initiated to determine the possible chemical differences between plants of resistant and susceptible varieties. The first phase consists of studying the attraction to larvae and suitability as larval food, of different extracts of resistant and susceptible plants. The various solvents used in this study were distilled water, ethyl alcohol, methyl alcohol, propanol, petroleum ether, acetone and chloroform. Basal pieces of 60-day-old Peta plants were soaked in the respective solvents for 48

Fig. 12. Effect on the mandibles of larvae reared on plants high (A) and low (B) in silica contents, IRRI, 1965.

hours and shaken for 1 hour. Filter papers soaked in small amounts of the concentrated extracts obtained were rolled into tubes and placed in glass vials and the solvent completely evaporated.

Of the larvae exposed to randomized and replicated collections of the vials, only 35.8% were attracted to any. But there were significant differences in the number of larvae attracted to different extracts. Also, apart from petroleum ether, significantly more larvae were

Fig. 13. Attraction and feeding of striped borer larvae on filter paper treated with rice plant extracts, IRRI, 1965.

attracted to extracts than to the control vial containing filter paper moistened with distilled water (Table 4). This indicates that all extracts, except petroleum ether, had some larval attract-

ant factor and that none possessed any strong repellent for the larvae. The highest percentages of larvae were attracted to extracts in methyl alcohol, distilled water, propanol and ethyl alcohol; the same extracts also stimulated more larval feeding. The larvae fed little on filter paper treated with water alone (Fig. 13). These results indicate that methyl alcohol extracts will be most suitable for comparisons of resistant and susceptible plants. It also is possible that different solvents may dissolve different stem borer attraction factors.

Inheritance of stem borer resistance

As no rice variety has been found immune to the stem borers, resistance is a comparative quality. It is essential to develop standard measures for resistance and to study the mode of its inheritance. The information presented earlier established that the resistant varieties had lower percentages of larval survival, lower larval and pupal weights, slower rate of larval growth,

and lower intensity of damage per unit of stem borer population. In a project being conducted in collaboration with the Institute plant breeders, these formed the criteria of resistance in the progenies of resistant and susceptible varieties.

The survival and development of 10 freshly hatched larvae was studied on

Fig. 14. Average weight of individual stem borer pupa reared on resistant (Chianan 2), susceptible (Rexoro) and their F₁ hybrid rice plants, IRRI, 1965.

individual plants of the susceptible variety Rexoro, resistant variety Chianan 2 and their F₁ plants. The over-all survival of larvae at 30 days after infestation was 54, 39 and 84%, respectively. The average pupal weights on individual plants are given in Fig. 14. In another experiment the F₂ population of 46 different crosses was planted between their respective parents in the field. Of these seven crosses and their parents, a total of about 5,000 plants were artificially infested with 10 freshly hatched larvae per plant at 40 days after transplanting. The remaining crosses were exposed to natural infestations. The results of one such cross are given in Fig. 15.

It was observed in all of these tests that hybrids from different parents had different reactions to stem borer infestation, thus indicating differences in factors associated with resistance. A range of resistance within a variety was also noted, making it difficult to draw a separation line between resistant and susceptible parents. However, these da-

Fig. 15. Distribution of number of dead hearts on stem borer resistant and susceptible parents and their F₂ progeny, IRRI, 1965.

ta definitely show that even within a variety plants of distinct stem borer reactions can be selected. Further crosses are being studied, using such pure-type lines as parents.

Varietal resistance in stem borer control

As discussed earlier, varieties differed significantly in susceptibility. In a series of these and other experiments some varieties remained resistant or susceptible at all stages of plant growth whereas others were resistant at one stage but susceptible at another. To determine these variations and to evaluate the role of varietal resistance in borer control, an experiment was conducted with 11 varieties in which the plants were protected from stem borer damage at different stages of growth. Gamma-BHC was applied in the paddy water to control stem borer, the application being separate treatments at 1-month intervals to protect the plants at all stages — once at 50 days after trans-

TABLE 4. Attraction and feeding response of striped stem borer larvae to different extracts of the rice plant, IRRI, 1965.

Solvents used for extraction	Larvae attracted		Holes made by larvae on filter paper		Scratched area (sq mm) ^a
	Total no. ^a	(%)	No. holes ^a	Hole area (sq mm) ^a	
Water	13	4.64	81	202	4529
Ethyl alcohol	14	5.00	53	303	3496
Methyl alcohol	23	8.21	72	174	7017
Propanol	12	4.28	73	139	4611
Petroleum ether	5	1.78	71	152	3328
Acetone	11	3.93	78	178	4289
Chloroform	12	4.28	76	212	4771
Control	1	0.35	19	30	782
Total	91	32.5			
LSD (0.01)	11.02		32.6	148.8	233.9

^a The numbers in the table are the sums of five replications based on a total of 280 larvae. The experiment was repeated twice.

planting to protect the plants from maximum tillering to booting, and once at 80 days after transplanting to protect the plants from booting till harvest.

Varieties Chianan 2, Taitung 16, and B581-A6-545 had lower numbers of dead hearts than varieties CP 231, B505-A1-287, and Milfor-6(2), both in

Fig. 16. Percentage of dead hearts formed on different varieties in relation to different times of insecticidal application, IRRI, January-May, 1965.

treated and untreated plots (Fig. 16). Similar results were noted in the white head data which showed that the varieties with the least damage in untreated controls also had the fewest white heads in the treated plots. In a highly susceptible variety, such as Rexoro, or the highly resistant Taitung 16, there was little difference in the white heads among the treated and untreated plots. But in other varieties, the percentages of white heads were significantly lower

Fig. 17. Percentage of white heads formed on different varieties in relation to different times of insecticidal application, IRRI, January-May, 1965.

in plots receiving continuous treatment and those treated at 80 days after transplanting (Fig. 17). No significant differences were recorded in the percentages of white heads in a variety when treated at 50 days after transplanting and receiving no insecticidal treatment. The yields of all these varieties were in accordance with the incidence of dead heart and white head and the efficacy of insecticidal treatment. Thus the variety Rexoro, which had the highest percentage of dead hearts and white heads, produced the lowest yield and also showed little yield increase from untreated to treated plots, as the efficacy of the insecticidal treatment was lower.

Several varieties, such as CP x SLO-17, CP 231 and B505-A1-287, showed significant increases in yield with additional insecticidal treatments indicating their susceptibility throughout the growth stage of the plant. CP x SLO-17 which yielded 4,001 kg/ha in the untreated control produced 7,055 kg/ha, an increase of 3,054 kg/ha in the plot completely protected from borer damage (Fig. 18). Variety Chianan 2, resistant to dead heart formation but susceptible to white heads, when protected during the time of white head formation produced yields almost identical to the plots protected at all stages of growth.

In this experiment, varieties Milfor-6(2), PI 215936, and Taitung 16 had heavy virus incidence ranging from 20 to 50% and their yields were omitted from the final data. These results also show that the yields of several varieties

Fig. 18. Yield of different rice varieties treated with γ -BHC at different times for stem borer control, IRRI, January-May, 1965.

receiving only one treatment at 80 days after transplanting were close to the yields of the plots receiving continuous protection. But this was not so when a single treatment was made at 50 days after transplanting.

Thus, the same insecticidal treatment provided better stem borer control on varieties which had some borer resistance than it did on those highly susceptible. If treated beyond the booting stage, those varieties with resistance during tillering produced yields identical to plots which had been protected with insecticides at all stages of growth.

CONTROL OF RICE STEM BORERS WITH GAMMA-BHC

Systemic effects on *Tryporyza incertulas*

Earlier experiments at the Institute on the systemic effects of γ -BHC were conducted with freshly hatched larvae of the striped borer, *Chilo suppressalis* Walker. Although the results of field experiments conducted in areas where the yellow borer, *Tryporyza incertulas*, the other most common stem borer species, showed that this species was also controlled, no specific data on the ef-

fectivity of γ -BHC and its rate of application for this pest was available.

Insecticide was applied to irrigation water in porcelain pots containing Milfor-6(2) rice plants. Three days after treatment, 10 freshly hatched *Tryporyza* larvae were caged on 3-inch pieces of basal plant parts in glass vials. Larval mortality recorded at 48 hours after caging showed that even as little as 0.75 kg/ha of γ -BHC applied as a sys-

Fig. 19. The standard mortality curves of freshly hatched *Tryporyza incertulas* and *Chilo suppressalis* larvae feeding on plants treated with different rates of γ -BHC, IIRI, 1965.

temic caused more than 50% mortality of the larvae of the species.

Results of field experiments showed that a highly significant mortality of the *Tryporyza* larvae was recorded at all the rates of γ -BHC used and that these larvae were more susceptible than *Chilo* larvae at all the rates of γ -BHC used. This was evident in LC₅₀ values on

Tryporyza and *Chilo* larvae, being 0.64 and 0.96 kg/ha, and LC₉₀ values being 1.375 and 2.225 kg/ha, respectively (Fig. 19). Therefore, for controlling the yellow borer, lower rates of γ -BHC will be required. This may be of particular economic significance as the yellow borer is more widely distributed in tropical regions than the striped borer.

Paddy water depth and effectivity of γ -BHC

In various experiments conducted at the Institute, application of γ -BHC was made in paddies containing approximately 5 cm of standing water. As no information was available on the effectiveness of γ -BHC in fields containing different depths of water an experiment was conducted by applying γ -BHC to rice paddies containing no standing water and 5, 10, and 15 cm of water.

All the treated plots had significantly lower percentages of dead hearts and fewer living larvae per hill than the untreated control with 5 cm of water. The treated plots had significantly higher yields ranging from 1 to 1.6 ton/ha more than the control plots (Table 5). It can be concluded that γ -BHC will be equally effective in paddies containing water up to 15 cm deep.

Vaporizing effects

It had previously been observed that after each application of γ -BHC large numbers of dead stem borer moths floated on the paddy water. Data on the number of dead moths collected before and after γ -BHC applications showed that the number of dead moths on the water rapidly increased after each application of γ -BHC and then declined

TABLE 5. Effectivity of γ -BHC applied at 2 and 3 kg/ha at 50 and 80 days, respectively, after transplanting, to rice fields containing different depths of paddy water, IIRI, February-June 1965.

Treatment	Dead hearts (50-day-old) (%)	No. larvae/10 hills (90-day-old)	White heads (%)	Yield (kg/ha)
No standing water + γ -BHC	5.09	4.33	1.18	5,135
5 cm + γ -BHC	4.57	12.33	2.06	4,815
10 cm + γ -BHC	3.21	10.33	2.97	4,547
15 cm + γ -BHC	2.64	23.66	3.25	4,887
5 cm without γ -BHC (control)	8.49	26.66	2.18	3,558

10 days after the treatment. Beyond this period the number of dead moths on water surface per sample was less than 5, compared to 25 to 75 moths in observations made within 24 hours from treatment (Fig. 20). As discussed earlier, the stem borers do not occur in well-defined broods in the area of the Institute and, therefore, the variations in the number of dead moths on the water can not be attributed to the differences in the natural population of the moths. Thus, the dead moths were apparently directly associated with the application of γ -BHC to the paddy water.

Further studies were undertaken to determine the possible causes of moth mortality after each γ -BHC application. Theoretically, the toxicant could have been effective by: its presence in the dewdrops on plant leaves rendering them toxic to the moths, γ -BHC fumes absorbed on the plant surface killing moths by contact, γ -BHC vapors absorbed by the insect-cuticle killing the

moths, and the moths coming in direct contact with the water surface.

Several experiments were conducted to test these possibilities.

Presence of γ -BHC in dewdrops. The presence of insecticide in the dewdrops obtained from treated fields was confirmed by analyzing the dewdrops in a Perkin Elmer gas chromatograph. At 5, 10 and 15 days after application, respectively, 0.055, 0.022 and 0.009 ppm of γ -BHC was detected in the dewdrops of the treated fields. The dewdrops from untreated fields contained no γ -BHC. A study is underway to determine whether the γ -BHC in the dewdrops was exuded with the guttation fluids or the vapors were absorbed in the dew.

Fumigation effects. In the initial experiments on the mortality of the direct vapors of γ -BHC, γ -BHC was placed in water in the bottom chamber of a desiccator and adult stem borer moths were liberated in the upper chamber. The two chambers were separated by a perforat-

Fig. 20. Number of dead moths in two different plots before and after γ -BHC application, IRRI, 1965.

ed porcelain disc, enabling vapors to pass through, with the moths having no direct contact with BHC in the water. The moths had 80-100% mortality within 24 hours in the desiccators containing the γ -BHC solution, while those in desiccators containing water alone, had less than 5% mortality.

In other experiments, also using technical γ -BHC, air from flasks containing γ -BHC solution was circulated into another flask containing stem borer moths and *Drosophila* flies. The test insects all died within 2 hours in flasks containing the γ -BHC vapors but none died where the air was circulated from flasks containing water alone. These results confirmed the fumigation effect of γ -BHC.

Fumigation effects of different rates of γ -BHC. To simulate natural conditions, the fumigation effect was studied by broadcasting a 6% granular formulation of γ -BHC on the surface of 18-cm diameter porcelain pots containing 3.5 kg of Maahas clay soil covered by 3 to 5 cm of water. The toxicant was used at rates of 0.5, 1, 2 and 3 kg/ha. *Chilo suppressalis* moths and *Drosophila* flies were placed in cages suspended 8 cm above the water level in the pots. The cages were cylinders of cartolina paper with ends covered with nylon cloth, permitting air movement but preventing the escape of insects. Cages and pots were enclosed with Mylar film to prevent loss of fumes through air movement. Fresh cages were used for each caging to avoid possible mortalities caused by vapors condensed on the cage itself.

The *Chilo suppressalis* moths suffered significant mortality on all the treated pots. Fresh batches of test insects were caged at 2-day intervals on the treated pots. On pots treated with 3 kg/ha the mortality increased to reach 100% in cagings made at 10 days after treatment but declined beyond that period. The various details of fumigation effects were studied primarily by caging fresh *Drosophila* flies at 2-day intervals from γ -BHC application till the mortality of the flies reached zero in all of the treatments.

The flies suffered significantly higher mortality in all of the treatments

Fig. 21. Fumigation effect of different rates of γ -BHC application on *Drosophila* flies caged on treated pots, IRRI, September-November, 1965.

than in the untreated control. In cagings made immediately after the insecticidal treatments, the flies suffered 40, 48, 60 and 75% mortality in 24 hours on pots treated respectively with 0.5, 1, 2 and 3 kg/ha of γ -BHC (Fig. 21). On all the treated pots, the fly mortality tended to increase up to 10 days from the time of treatment except those treated with 3 kg/ha where it reached 100% in cagings made at 6 days after treatment and remained the same up to 10 days. At this period the fly mortality was 100, 65, 50 and 40 percent in different treatments but declined later in all treatments. At 16 days after treatment, flies on pots treated with 0.5 kg/ha rate of γ -BHC had less than 5% mortality in contrast to the 3 kg/ha rates in which they suffered more than 50% mortality up to 20 days after the insecticidal treatment. In none of the treatments did the flies suffer significant mortality 30 days after insecticidal application.

Fig. 22. Fumigation effect of 3 kg/ha γ -BHC at different temperatures on *Drosophila* flies, IRRI, October-November, 1965.

As the flies in none of these treatments were in physical contact with the γ -BHC solution, these data confirm that the fly mortality was due to vaporizing effects of the toxicant. Higher rates had higher vaporizing effects spread over a longer period of time.

Effect of temperature on vaporization. To investigate the effect of different temperatures on initial and residual periods of γ -BHC vapors, experiments were conducted at 70, 80, and 90 F with the toxicant at a rate of 3 kg/ha and *Drosophila* flies as bioassay insects.

In cagings made immediately after insecticidal treatments, the flies suffered 100% mortality at 80 and 90 F but only 60% at 70 F. At 80 and 90 F, however, the fly mortalities declined to less than 10% at 35 days after the treatment. By contrast at 70 F the vaporizing effect showed an increase from initial kill up to 20 days beyond which it also declined to less than 20% 40 days after the treatment (Fig. 22). Thus, at higher temperatures γ -BHC had a fast

vaporizing effect and consequently a shorter residual period than at lower temperature. These data also indicate that the fumigation effects of γ -BHC should provide more effective and long lasting insect control where the temperature ranges about 70 F.

Fumigation under field conditions. The vaporizing effect of γ -BHC on insect mortality was investigated under field conditions, plots of variety 9795 being treated with 2 and 3 kg of γ -BHC at 20 and 50 days after transplanting, respectively.

The *Drosophila* flies used as test insects were caged in cartolina paper cages attached at different heights to a bamboo pole placed in the test plots. The fly mortality was recorded at 24 and 48 hours after caging; records of temperature and wind velocity were also made. The flies caged immediately after the insecticidal treatment suffered the highest mortality, and those caged close to the water surface were more affected than those caged at greater heights (Fig. 23). Nevertheless, those in cages 4 feet from the ground suffered significant mortality.

The fumigation effect in the field test lasted up to 10 days, at which time there was no significant fly mortality even in the cages closest to the ground. Similar results were obtained in experi-

Fig. 23. Fumigation effect in field application of γ -BHC on *Drosophila* flies caged at different heights from water level, IRRI, 1965.

ments using *Chilo suppressalis* moths. These results confirm that the application of γ -BHC to the paddy has a substantial fumigation effect on stem borer moths.

Experiments with different life history stages of the insect showed that the fumes were effective only for controlling the adults.

Effect of vapors deposited on plant surface

The possible role of γ -BHC fumes deposited on the plant surface in controlling various insect pests was investigated in another experiment. *Drosophila* flies caged with different parts of a treated plant showed some mortality, but no moth mortality was recorded up to 3 days of caging. This indicates that γ -BHC fumes were deposited on the plants but probably not in adequate quantities to kill the moths.

Fig. 24. Systemic effect in rice plants of different rates of γ -BHC applied to irrigation water on different types of soil. The soils used were Maahas, Luisiana, Casiguran, Calcareous, Suschia, Tungshan, and Antipolo. Except for those labelled on the graph, there were no significant differences between soils, IRRI, 1965.

Effect of applications in different soils

Most of the previous experiments with γ -BHC were conducted at the Institute on a Maahas clay soil. To determine the effectivity of the insecticide on different types of soils, an experiment was conducted with plants growing on Maahas, Luisiana, Casiguran, Calcareous, Suschia, Tungshan and Antipolo soils in 7.5-inch diameter porcelain pots in the greenhouse.

At different intervals after insecticidal treatment of the irrigation water, tillers from each plant were used for bioassaying the presence of γ -BHC using freshly hatched striped borer larvae. Gamma-BHC effectively controlled the larvae on the plants growing in all the types of soils, and the larvae suffered significant mortality at all the rates of the toxicant used in these tests (Fig. 24). In general, the larval mortality was somewhat lower in observations made 3 days after treatment and increased to the highest level in 10 days from the treatment, beyond which it declined at all rates of γ -BHC and in all soils. This suggests that during the first 5 to 10 days plants absorb γ -BHC from the soil and there is little decomposition within the plants, but beyond this period, little toxicant is absorbed from the soil and that already absorbed slowly undergoes decomposition within the plants.

When used at the rate of 3 kg/ha, 80 to 100% larval mortality was recorded on each of these soils in observations made 5 days after treatment. The highest mortality was obtained on plants growing in Calcareous soil whereas those in Casiguran caused the lowest mortality. At 15 days after treatment, although the larvae suffered only 30 to 60 percent mortality, the highest mortality was still obtained on plants growing in Calcareous soil. Plants in Tungshan soil caused the lowest mortality. The reduction in insecticidal activity was somewhat slower beyond 25 days when average mortality of larvae on all soils was 35%.

At 50 days after treatment there was no larval mortality on Tungshan soil but there was still more than 10% in

Suschia, Maahas, Antipolo and Luisiana. The over-all highest insecticidal activity was recorded on Calcareous soil which had more than 30% mortality up to 30 days from treatment. Except 10 days after treatment when plants in Calcareous soil caused significantly higher larval mortality than others, the insecticidal effect did not differ significantly on the other soils.

Similar trends in larval mortality were also recorded when the toxicant was used at a rate of 2 kg/ha. At this rate the treatment was most effective on Calcareous soil where the mortality was 100% 10 days after treatment and remained higher than all other soils after 15 and 20 days. At 25 and 30 days after the treatment, the insecticide was least effective on Tungshan and Suschia soils.

There were similar mortality trends for treatments of 1 kg and 0.5 kg/ha. For all treatments the highest initial kill was on Calcareous soil; residual effect was rapidly lost on Tungshan soils.

These tests were conducted in porcelain pots and do not provide any information about the leaching of γ -BHC from the soils. That such losses occur has been suggested by another experiment using Maahas clay soil where the effectivity of γ -BHC on soil placed in an unpainted clay pot was compared to the soil contained in a polyethylene bag within the pot. The larvae suffered 34.3 percent mortality in plants growing in the former treatment as compared to 85.8 percent in the latter. Most probably, in pots containing no plastic bags, γ -BHC was lost with water either evaporating from the surface of the soil or by leaching. Therefore, another experiment is being conducted to determine the loss of γ -BHC by leaching from different types of soils.

The fumigation effect of γ -BHC was also studied on each of the soils. This was done by caging *Drosophila* flies on each pot 1 inch above the general water level. The results showed that γ -BHC had a significant fumigation effect from all soils even at as low a rate as 0.5 kg/ha. At rates of 2 and 3 kg/ha, more than 80 percent of the flies died on all the soils, except Casiguran, on which the fumigation effect was in

Fig. 25. Fumigation effect on *Drosophila* flies of different rates of γ -BHC applied to different soils. The flies were caged at 24 hours after treatment, IRRI, 1965.

general much lower than on other soils (Fig. 25). Casiguran differed from other soils used in the test; it was sandy whereas the others were clay, clay loam or silt loam. It is known that γ -BHC is less readily absorbed by sandy soils than those of finer texture.

Effect of soil application on rice plants

Research workers frequently observe that plots treated with recommended rates of γ -BHC show much better plant growth than do the adjacent untreated plots. Often this difference becomes so obvious as to suggest a change in nutrient availability. It is also possible that nearly complete protection against insect pests is effected by application of γ -BHC to the paddy water and this permits more vigorous growth.

To investigate this, Milfor-6(2) plants in pots treated with different

rates of γ -BHC were grown in an insect-free greenhouse. The plants in all treatments were more or less of the same height before the insecticidal application; after the treatment, those growing in pots treated with 20, 30 and 50 kg/ha of γ -BHC showed a definite stunting in growth. The differences became more pronounced when a month later the pots received a second application of γ -BHC. Apart from plants in untreated soil and those treated with 1 kg/ha, there was some reduction in plant height from all other treatments. The heights of the plants treated with from 1 to 10 kg/ha of γ -BHC did not differ significantly, but plants treated with 20, 30 and 50 kg/ha were markedly shorter (Figs. 26 and 27).

Before insecticidal treatment the numbers of tillers were identical in all pots; after the first application, there was an apparent reduction in the number of tillers in the pots treated with the higher rates of γ -BHC. At 60 days after transplanting, when a second application of the insecticide was made,

the difference in the number of tillers became more apparent. The plants receiving no insecticidal treatment had an average of 19.6 tillers per hill compared to 10 per hill in pots treated with 50 kg/ha γ -BHC. There was no significant difference between the number of tillers of the untreated plants and those treated with up to 10 kg/ha.

Plants in pots receiving no insecticidal treatment and those treated with up to 10 kg/ha were quite green and luxuriant in growth. However, those growing in pots treated with higher rates of γ -BHC showed yellowing, the tips and borders of the leaves were yellowish brown, and gradually the whole leaf dried up and became dark brown. Those treated with 30 and 50 kg/ha had only partially emerging panicles. The yield data from this experiment is not yet available.

In another experiment, rice plants were grown in water culture solution to which different rates of γ -BHC were later added. The roots of rice plants growing in water culture containing

Fig. 26. Effect of different rates of γ -BHC on height of Milfor-6(2) plants, IRRI, 1965.

Fig. 27. Effect of different rates of γ -BHC on Milfor-6(2) plants, IRRI, 1965.

high rates of γ -BHC were numerous, short and thick. It appeared that higher concentrations of γ -BHC stunted root growth and stimulated formation of new roots which later also became stunted.

It was evident from these results that γ -BHC does not have any stimulating effect on the height or number of tillers of a rice plant. When used at rates beyond 20 kg/ha, it may be significantly phytotoxic; no such effects were noticed at 10 kg/ha or at lower rates.

Cumulative effect on plants and borer control.

A long-range experiment involving continuous application of γ -BHC to the same plot in successive seasons to study its persistence in the soil and any possible phytotoxic effect or loss in insecticidal activity was initiated in January, 1964. As it consists of starting the insecticidal treatment at different intervals after transplanting and then repeating it at 30-day intervals till harvest, the data can also be used for determining the time when the first insecticidal application should be made. In plots where the treatment starts one week after transplanting, a total of three to four treatments are made in a season in contrast to only one application where the treatments are started

within a month from harvest.

No apparent carry-over effect of the insecticide from previous treatment was recorded on newly transplanted crops.

During the dry season, 11 of the treated plots had lower percentages of dead hearts than the untreated controls (Table 6). Similar results were obtained for number of infested tillers and number of living larvae per hill in the treated and untreated plots. Plots where the insecticidal treatments started 7 weeks or earlier after transplanting had a higher number of productive tillers per hill than did the untreated controls or those in which treatments started later. The plots in which insecticidal application started a week after transplanting had received a total of 30 kg/ha of γ -BHC by the end of the experiment. They produced 5,873 kg/ha of rice compared to 2,087 kg/ha in untreated controls. There was a marked reduction in the yield of plots in which treatments were started beyond 7 weeks after transplanting. The yield of plots treated beyond 10 weeks from transplanting did not differ significantly from untreated controls.

These results in general agree with those of previous experiments. Similar results were obtained in experiments conducted during the dry season where the plots receiving the highest amount

TABLE 6. Cumulative effects of γ -BHC applied to the paddy water for stem borer control, IRRI, dry and wet seasons, 1965.

Time treat- ment ini- tiated after γ -BHC transplanting applied (weeks)	Dry season, 1965					Wet season, 1965					Yield (kg/ha)		
	Total applied (kg/ha)	Dead hearts (%)	Average no. pani- cles/hill	White heads (%)	Virus in- fected hills (%)	Yield (kg/ha)	Total γ -BHC applied (kg/ha)	Dead hearts (%)	Before applica- tion	After applica- tion		White heads (%)	Virus infected hills (%)
1	30	2.71	11.45	0.908	13.48	5873	39	1.50	3.4	0.75	7.91	0.62	4579
3	27	4.56	10.04	0.189	27.53	4256	36	2.07	7.25	2.5	7.43	8.99	2960
5	24	2.47	11.71	0.153	20.83	4839	30	3.42	2.95	0.35	6.87	5.77	3772
7	21	6.23	10.97	0.164	31.85	4341	27	5.82	2.90	1.4	5.12	12.23	2539
9	15	a	8.52	0.129	37.72	3009	18	a	a	a	4.17	18.39	2563
10	12	a	10.46	0.254	33.33	2969	15	a	a	a	8.58	10.57	2891
11	12	a	9.35	0.417	33.82	2439	15	a	a	a	10.25	21.06	1749
12	6	a	9.76	0.471	38.21	2321	9	a	a	a	11.76	13.53	1772
13	6	a	7.98	0.939	30.02	2253	6	a	a	a	13.21	8.24	2478
Control	0	9.15	9.24	0.909	38.15	2087	0	4.47	1.75	2.1	11.20	17.56	2029
LSD		3.42	1.99	0.219									

a Not treated before the dead heart counts were made.

of γ -BHC had the lowest insect infestation and damage and produced the highest yield (Table 6). It is significant that during both dry and wet seasons, plots receiving the maximum number of applications of γ -BHC had the lowest incidence of virus.

The yield of plots receiving a continuous application of γ -BHC and those of the untreated controls were 5,873 and 2,087 kg/ha, respectively during the dry season and 4,579 and 2,029 kg/ha during the wet season. This amounted to a minimum increase of 2,550 kg/ha for both seasons. As these plots have been continuously treated with γ -BHC for the last four seasons and have received a total of 39 kg/ha of the toxicant, it can be concluded that intensive use of γ -BHC over a period of four continuous cropping seasons will not be phytotoxic nor will it reduce the effectiveness of the insecticide for stem borer control.

Residue analysis in plant, grain, and soil

A project was initiated to determine the γ -BHC residues in various parts of the plant, husk, bran and polished rice, and in the soil of treated paddies. Plots in various experiments with γ -BHC, and others in which the chemical was used as a standard insect control practice, were sampled in these investigations.

The residues are determined in a gas chromatograph with electron-capture detector. This procedure, the most convenient and sensitive method available,

TABLE 7. Range of γ -BHC residue in grain, plant, dew, and soil, IRRI, 1965.

Sample	Time of γ -BHC application ^a	γ -BHC (ppm of wet weight)
Rice grain	20 days before harvest	
Polished rice		0.03
Bran		0.16
Hull		0.28
Rice plant	30 days before harvest	
Bottom — third		0.17-1.00
Middle — third		0.42-2.19
Top — third		0.25-0.70
Dew drops	5 days after treatment	0.26-0.055
Soil	30 days after treatment	0.040

^a All plots were treated with 3 kg/ha of γ -BHC.

appears suitable for the analysis of γ -BHC in rice plants, soil, and dew.

The method is highly sensitive and minimum determinable concentrations are as follows: plant tissues — 0.01 ppm, soil — 0.004 ppm, and dew — 0.004 ppm. Recovery of γ -BHC added to plant, soil, and dew samples ranged from 88 to 97 percent. The results of some of these analyses revealed the presence of rather low levels of γ -BHC residues in various plant parts, grain, and soil (Table 7).

SCREENING OF INSECTICIDES FOR STEM BORER AND LEAFHOPPER CONTROL

During 1965, 44 different insecticides including several new compounds were tested to discover more effective insecticides for controlling rice leafhoppers and stem borers. The compounds were first tested for ovicidal and larvicidal effects on striped rice borers by topical application in laboratory experiments.

To study the effectivity of various insecticides on rice leafhoppers, 10 adults of *Nephotettix* spp. were caged on rice plants at 1, 5, 10, and 15 days after the

plants were sprayed with various insecticides.

High ovicidal effectivity was recorded in the compounds lebaycid, SD 8447 and UC 8305 but the compounds phosphamidon, bidrin, SD 9129, metasystox, UC 20047, and gusathion gave low percentages of egg mortality, although they caused almost 100 percent mortality of the freshly hatched larvae. It is likely that these compounds could effectively penetrate the larvae cuticle

but not the eggshells.

All but a few of the compounds showed effective larvicidal property, causing almost 100 percent mortality. However, only a few applied as foliar sprays could effectively control 7-day-old larvae feeding within the plants. This might have been due to the poor ability of these compounds to penetrate the plant tissues. The compounds that killed all the larvae feeding within the plants were phosphamidon, lebaycid, EI 4772, dimethoate, roxion, UC 8305, and telothion.

Of the 44 compounds tested, 30 caused more than 50 percent mortality of rice green leafhoppers caged on the plants one day after the insecticidal treatments, and several caused 100 percent leafhopper mortality. However, 5 days after the treatment, only gusathion, lebaycid, EPN, SD 9129, R-5092, trithion, metasystox, and UC 20047 caused more than 50 percent leafhopper mortality. In tests made 10 days after treatment, few compounds caused more than 50 percent leafhopper mortality and, at 15 days after treatment, only gusathion, EPN, and R-5092 caused any significant leafhopper mortality. Gusathion effected 23 per-

cent leafhopper mortality at 20 days after treatment whereas all other compounds achieved less than 5 percent.

Field tests of selected insecticides

Fifteen insecticides were selected for further study in the field. These were applied as foliar sprays to 4- x 8-m plots 50 days after transplanting with variety 9795. Only one spray was made with each of these insecticides in separate treatments at a rate of 300 gal/ha. Gamma-BHC applied to the paddy water at a rate of 3 kg/ha served as a treated control and plots receiving no insecticides were the untreated controls.

To compensate for variations in the initial number of larvae present in different plots, the performance of insecticides was expressed on a percentage basis. These data showed that the highest percentages of larvae were killed in plots treated with γ -BHC, thiodan, gusathion, SD 9129, and lebaycid. Low percentages of larval mortality were recorded on plots treated with UC 20047, DDVP, SD 8447, trithion, phosphamidon, and telothion. The number of living larvae was higher in plots treated with UC 20047, trithion, EPN 300, telothion and γ -BHC. Although the

TABLE 8. Field tests with 15 insecticides for rice stem borer and leafhopper control, IRRI, April-June, 1965.

Insecticide	Spray concentration (%)	10 days after treatment			15 days after treatment		Increase in larval population (%)	White heads (%)	
		No. larvae/10 hills		Larvae killed (%)	No. larvae/10 hills				
		Living	Dead		Living	Dead			
Dimethoate	0.10	1.75	2.25	56.25	114.25	0.25	+	6428.57	6.26
Trithion	0.06	12.25	0.75	5.76	62.75	2.00	+	412.24	9.79
Telothion	0.01	8.75	0.25	2.77	47.00	0.50	+	437.14	5.54
UC 2004 ^a	0.04	46.75	1.25	2.60	46.25	1.00	-	1.06	13.66
R-5092 ^a	0.04	4.25	1.75	29.16	44.50	2.25	+	947.05	7.71
Bidrin	0.03	3.50	1.25	26.31	39.50	1.00	+	1028.5	9.27
DDVP	0.03	4.75	0.75	13.63	36.50	0.50	+	668.42	11.83
Gusathion	0.10	1.75	2.50	58.82	24.00	0.75	+	1271.42	3.18
SD 8447 ^a	0.04	0.50	0.50	50.00	18.25	0.00	+	3550.00	11.40
Lebaycid	0.10	1.25	3.50	73.68	16.50	1.00	+	1220.00	5.24
EPN-300	0.05	5.00	1.70	25.37	14.25	0.25	+	185.00	6.80
Thiodan	0.15	1.75	7.50	81.08	12.75	0.50	+	628.57	2.47
SD 9129 ^a	0.04	1.25	2.75	68.75	11.25	0.00	+	800.00	6.39
Lindane	^b	9.00	13.50	60.00	9.25	0.50	+	2.27	3.50
Phosphamidon	0.05	1.00	0.00	00.00	8.00	0.00	+	700.00	2.58
Control	—	5.75	1.25	17.85	52.50	2.25	+	813.04	12.69

^a Coded numbers: SD — Shell Chemical Co., UC — Union Carbide
R-5092 — Stauffer Chemical Co.

^b Applied to paddy water at 3 kg/ha.

number of larvae killed in several of the treatments was low, the total larval population remained low in these plots because of the initial lower stem borer population (Table 8).

At 15 days after the treatment, there was an increase in larval population in all treatments except UC 20047 in which the larval population decreased by 1 percent. This was probably due to the heavy early infestation on these plots which had about 10 times more larvae than others. The plots treated with γ -BHC showed only an increase of 2 percent in larval population followed by EPN with an increase of 185 percent. In contrast, several of the treatments had up to 300 percent increase in larval population above the numbers 10 days after treatment. This implies that these insecticides exhibited no residual effect in observations made at 15 days after the treatment. Compounds which allowed considerably lower percentages of increase in the larval population had longer residual effects. The lowest numbers of living larvae at 15 days after treatment were found on plots treated with γ -BHC and phosphamidon.

A significant difference was recorded in the percentages of white heads in different treatments. Thiodan, dime-

cron, and gusathion had the significantly lowest percentages of white heads — about five to six times lower than those in the untreated control. The white heads in plots treated with DDVP, UC 20047, SD 8447, and trithion did not differ significantly from the untreated control.

In observations made at 11 days after the treatment, all the treated plots had lower leafhopper populations than the untreated control. The plots treated with gusathion, telothion, phosphamidon, SD 9129, and R-5092 had the lowest leafhopper population in all plots 10 days later except those treated with lebaycid, trithion, and UC 20047, indicating that these insecticides had longer residual effect for leafhopper control. At 21 days after the treatment, the highest rate of increase in leafhopper population was recorded in plots of γ -BHC and SD 9129, telothion, bidrin, and DDVP, indicating no effective residual property; the rate of increase in other plots was much slower, showing various levels of residual effectivity (Table 9).

The field performance of these insecticides also was investigated in a wet season planting of variety 9795. The in-

TABLE 9. Effect of single applications of various insecticides on leafhopper populations, IRRI, April-June, 1965.

Insecticide	Spray concentration (%)	No. leafhoppers at days after treatment		
		11 days Total/plot sample	21 days	
			Total/plot sample	Change from first count (%)
Thiodan	0.15	1.50	2.00	33.00
Phosphamidon	0.05	0.00	1.00	100.00
Gusathion	0.10	0.50	1.70	240.00
γ -BHC	a	4.00	15.00	275.00
Lebaycid	0.10	3.25	1.50	-61.53
Dimethoate	0.10	1.50	1.75	16.66
Telothion	0.015	0.25	3.00	1100.00
EPN 300	0.05	1.25	1.25	0.00
SD 9129	0.04	0.25	3.75	1400.00
R-5092	0.04	0.50	2.00	300.00
Bidrin	0.03	1.50	5.50	266.66
Trithion	0.06	2.25	1.00	-55.55
DDVP	0.0315	1.00	4.50	350.00
SD 8447	0.04	1.25	2.25	80.00
UC 20047	0.04	1.50	1.00	-33.33
Control	b	5.75	6.25	8.69

a Applied to the paddy water at 3 kg/ha.

b Average of four replications. Each sample consisted of 10 sweeps using a 10-inch diameter insect net.

Fig. 28. Effect of different insecticides on leafhopper control, IRRI, 1965.

secticides were applied as foliar sprays at a rate of 300 gal/ha at 15-day intervals from 2 weeks after transplanting to crop maturity. Five sprays were applied of each insecticide. An additional plot in each replication was treated at 30-day intervals with sevidol, a 1:1 γ -BHC and sevin combination, at a rate of 3 kg/ha of each toxicant, as a standard treatment for comparison with other insecticides.

In observations made 40 days after transplanting, the plots treated with thiodan, gusathion, sevidol, and lebaycid had significantly lower percentages of dead hearts than those receiving no insecticidal treatments which did not differ significantly from those treated with phosphamidon, R-5092, trithion, and SD 8447. In counts made 60 days

after transplanting, plots treated with thiodan, and gusathion had the lowest percentages of dead hearts, although all the treated plots, except those treated with R-5092, had significantly lower percentages of dead hearts than the untreated control (Table 10).

At 40 days after transplanting the fewest living larvae were recorded in the plots treated with phosphamidon, gusathion, lebaycid, EPN, and SD 9129; the largest numbers of dead larvae were recorded from the plots treated with sevidol, lebaycid, and SD 9129, although none of these differences was significant. The effects of various insecticidal treatments became more apparent in observations at 20 and 50 days later when there was a continuous decline in the plots treated with gusa-

thion, sevidol, lebaycid, and SD 9129, but the larval population remained more or less constant in treatments with thiodan, dimethoate, telothion, R-5092, DDVP, and SD 8447. The other treatments followed the trend of

population fluctuation of the untreated controls.

The plots treated with thiodan and gusathion had significantly lower percentages of white heads than all other treatments. The percentages of white heads in the control were about six times higher and did not differ significantly from those treated with trithion, DDVP, and SD 8447.

Although these insecticides significantly reduced the leafhopper population, they differed distinctly in residual effects. In observations made 12 days after treatment, only the plots treated with gusathion and bidrin had significantly lower leafhopper populations than the control. In the third leafhopper sampling, 8 days after the next treatment, all of the treated plots had less than one-third the population of the untreated plots (Fig. 28). There was some increase in population of the treated plots in observations made 7 days later, but the rate of increase was much higher in plots treated with R-5092, SD 9129, than in those treated with gusathion, DDVP, and sevidol.

Fig. 29. Effect of foliar application at 15-day intervals of various insecticides on the incidence of virus infection, IRRI, 1965.

TABLE 10. Field tests with 15 insecticides for rice stem borer and leafhopper control, IRRI, July-November, 1965.^a

Insecticide ^b	Spray conc. (%)	% dead hearts at days after transplanting		Larval population/15 hills at days after transplanting			White head count		Yield (ton/ha)
		40	60	40	60	90	No./hill	(%)	
Gusathion	0.10	0.96	4.26	2.25	1.75	2.00	0.39	3.28	5.585
Thiodan	0.15	0.96	1.72	10.75	10.75	10.50	0.33	2.79	5.080
EPN 300	0.05	1.63	6.17	14.75	10.25	4.25	0.45	3.93	4.541
Sevidol	3 kg/ha	0.51	7.78	11.50	1.75	8.75	0.73	7.42	4.241
Lebaycid	0.10	0.97	5.04	3.50	5.75	1.50	0.74	6.62	4.121
SD 9129	0.04	1.71	5.96	3.50	3.50	1.25	0.73	6.67	3.619
Bidrin	0.03	1.87	6.88	6.00	13.25	5.25	0.77	7.31	2.909
Dimethoate	0.10	2.02	8.29	17.50	14.50	20.50	0.83	8.72	2.591
R-5092	0.04	2.49	9.69	8.50	12.25	8.00	0.96	10.48	2.320
Trithion	0.06	2.07	8.48	28.75	13.75	28.00	1.17	12.23	2.159
SD 8447	0.04	2.70	6.34	7.00	5.75	6.00	1.16	12.63	2.125
Phosphamidon	0.04	2.48	9.77	3.75	38.25	3.00	0.88	8.87	1.928
Telothion	0.01	1.02	6.13	21.50	16.75	20.50	0.93	9.91	1.923
DDVP	0.03	1.60	8.62	15.00	14.75	13.50	1.17	14.48	1.292
Control	—	3.63	12.45	8.25	14.75	6.25	1.08	14.99	0.542
LSD		1.57	3.40					3.09	0.872

^a All insecticides were sprayed at 15-day intervals, except sevidol, which was applied to paddy water at monthly intervals.

^b In a current experiment these insecticides are being tested at same concentration.

The plots treated with gusathion, thiodan, dolnack and EPN had less than 5 percent virus infection compared to 34 percent in untreated controls (Fig. 29). All the treated plots had lower incidence of virus than did the untreated controls, and those showing the best leafhopper control, particularly at early stages of plant growth, had the lowest incidence of virus.

The stem borer infestations, leafhopper damage, and virus infection cumulatively affected the yield of rice in this experiment. The treatment with gusathion provided the most effective stem borer and leafhopper control and produced 5,585 kg/ha of rice compared to 871 kg/ha in the control. The plots treated with thiodan, sevidol, lebaycid, and EPN 300 produced the next highest yields, ranging from 4,121 to 5,079 kg/ha. Yields of all treated plots were significantly higher than those of the controls.

Effectivity of three chemicals for ricebug control

Gusathion and thiodan sprays effectively controlled the rice stem borer and rice leafhoppers in field experiments. Therefore, these can possibly be used as standard compounds to control insect pests of rice. These foliar sprays have an advantage over the application of insecticides to the paddy water in that they may also effectively control the ricebugs which cause serious damage to the crop by sucking the juice of the developing grains.

The effectivity of gusathion, thiodan,

Fig. 30. Standard mortality curve of three insecticides for ricebug (*Leptocorisa acuta* Thunb.) control, IRRI, 1965.

and γ -BHC for ricebug control was investigated in laboratory experiments. All of the insecticides caused significant ricebug mortality even at a .0025 percent concentration. The insecticides could be arranged as γ -BHC, gusathion, thiodan, in order of their effectivity: their LC_{50} values were 0.0053, .0062, and .0078 percent; and the LC_{90} values were .02, .04, and .06 percent, respectively (Fig. 30). Considering 90 percent mortality as the desired aim in the field, these tests suggest that γ -BHC, when used at the rate of .022 percent, gusathion at the rate of .040 percent, and thiodan at .06 percent should effectively control ricebugs.

USE OF CHEMOSTERILANTS FOR RICE STEM BORER CONTROL

The spectacular eradication of screw-worm flies from certain parts of the United States of America by the mass-liberation of radiation-sterile males has opened a new avenue for insect extermination. With rice stem borers, the mass release of artificially reared, sexually sterile individuals does not appear to be feasible because of the problems of mass rearing of the insect and the relatively high populations in overlapping generations. It has been calculated that even

at an infestation with as low as 5 percent infested tillers, 1 million male adults will emerge per week per square kilometer. A more feasible approach may be offered through the use of sex attractant and chemosterilants.

Detailed basic information on the sex behavior of the moth is a prerequisite in any such project. To obtain this information, 6,405 stem borer moths from the field were dissected to record the frequency of their mating, which can

Fig. 31. The bursa copulatrix of female moths showing no spermatophore (A), one spermatophore (B), and three spermatophores (C) indicating the number of matings by the moth, IRRI, 1965.

be determined by the number of spermatophores in the *bursa copulatrix* of the female moths (Fig. 31). Of these samples, 38.1 percent were males and 61.4 percent females, of which 12.7 percent were unmated and 60, 21.7, and 4.5 percent had mated once, twice and

thrice, respectively. In laboratory studies, matings were generally observed during the early morning hours.

The number of matings per female was great if the number of males present was increased.

Both male and female moths lived and reproduced even in the absence of food. However, in its absence, there was

TABLE 11. Effects of continuous feeding of chemosterilants on *Chilo* adults, IRRI, 1965.^a

Treatment	Total adults		Mated ♀		Eggs		
	♂	♀	No.	%	No./mated ♀	Reduction eggs laid (%)	Sterile (%)
1% tepa	20	27	16	59	196	44	21
1% apholate	17	25	15	53	178	49	22
1% tretamine	25	23	16	69	174	50	5.5
20% hempa	19	27	13	48	185	53	12.5
Untreated control (10% sugar solution)	20	24	11	44	349	0	0
				(n.s.)			

^a Average of 3 trials.

a 43-percent reduction in the number of eggs laid per female, and 15 percent of the eggs laid were sterile compared to only 2 percent sterile eggs laid by moths fed on 10 percent sugar solution and yeast. The moths caged without food

had a comparatively shorter life span. When the moths were fed chemicals known to be sex sterilants, there was marked reduction in the number of eggs laid per female and an increase in the percentages of sterile eggs (Table 11).

BIOLOGICAL CONTROL OF RICE STEM BORERS

Studies on the biological control of rice stem borers were initiated in August, 1965. The first phase of the program consists of a study of the distribution and abundance of the different rice stem borer species and their natural enemies in various parts of the Philippines. Six ecologically distinct regions have been selected. In each region there are four localities from which 25 hills of rice plants infested with rice stem borers are sampled at 30-day intervals. The number of larvae obtained from each sample is expressed in terms of the time (in minutes) spent in collecting them. This serves as an index of infestation and larval population. Its value has varied from zero,

indicating complete absence of borers, to 4.9 borers per minute, showing heavy infestations in various areas. The usual figures have ranged from 0.2 to 1.5 per minute.

These figures obtained over time, will reflect fluctuations in borer populations. This method provides a direct measure of the actual population at the time observations are being made and is therefore preferable to the usual procedure of recording percentage of infested hills.

The latter procedure may underestimate heavy population of a new infestation and overestimate the population in a field damaged at an earlier stage.

Fig. 32. Pigeonhole cabinets, shown in the background, contain test tubes for rearing borers. Cotton wrapped in thin muslin is used to plug the tubes, IRRI, 1965.

TABLE 12. Summary of results of a survey of rice stem borers and their parasites in the Philippines, September-November, 1965.

Region	Total borers recovered	Percent abundance				Indices of abundance		Parasitism (%)	Important parasites collected
		<i>Chilo</i>	<i>Tryporyza</i>	<i>Sesamia</i>	<i>Chiloatraea</i>	Borer/minute	Parasites/sample		
1	54	44.4	16.7	38.9	0	0.2	1.0	0.4	<i>Tropobracon schoenobii</i> (Vier)
2	52	42.3	40.4	17.3	0	0.3	0.7	0	Unidentified braconid
3	104	8.7	81.7	8.7	0.9	0.8	1.1	2.0	Unidentified ichneumonid
4	158	17.7	74.1	8.2	0	1.1	0.9	1.2	<i>Apanteles</i> sp.
5	238	31.9	60.1	8.0	0	0.7	1.1	0.4	Two unidentified braconids.
6	204	6.9	86.3	6.9	0	1.4	1.6	1.0	<i>Temelucha philippinensis</i> Ashm.
Palawan	106	0	73.6	15.1	11.2	1.1	5.6	1.8	<i>Bracon chinensis</i> (Szep) and <i>Stenobracon trifaciatus</i> Szep. and unidentified braconid.

The hill samples are brought to the laboratory and dissected to determine the number of stem borers which are then reared on rice stalks in individual test tubes for the emergence of any parasites. Such rearing separates the para-

sites from the hyperparasites and is most useful in determining the relative effectiveness of different parasites in various ecological regions. These test tubes containing borers are placed in pigeonhole cabinets (Fig. 32). They

Fig. 33. The Kyoritsu power suction catcher in operation. Twenty sweeps of the suction arm constitute one sample, IRRI, 1965.

are examined every fourth day when the plant stalks are also changed. Room temperature is kept constant at 25 ± 1 C.

For direct field sampling of parasites, a suction catcher (Kyoritsu power suction, catcher Sc-3) is used. Each sample consists of 20 sweeps of the suction arm of the catcher (Fig. 33). In all, 15 samples are taken from each locality, 10 from the rice fields and five from weeds adjacent to them; various parasite species are sorted and a record of their abundance maintained.

The relative abundance of the various borer species followed an interesting pattern (Table 12). *Chilo suppressalis* was the dominant species in regions 1 and 2. In region 3 it was rare. In regions 4 and 5 (the area around Laguna de Bay) it was abundant. It was scarce in region 6 and not recovered at all in Palawan.

The abundance of *Tryporyza incertulas* in all of the regions sampled followed an inverse relation to the abundance of *Chilo suppressalis*. It was the dominant species in all regions except 1 and 2. In Palawan, *Tryporyza innotata* also occurs. However, since it was difficult to distinguish between these two species in the larval instars, the two species were grouped and treated as one.

Sesamia inferens was recovered in all regions, but was relatively more abundant in the north, in regions 1 and 2, and in Palawan. *Chilo traea polychrysa*

was quite rare and was recovered only in region 3 and in Palawan. In the latter, however, the presence of more than one species of this borer is indicated. Specimens of this species as well as that of *Tryporyza* spp. are being prepared for identification.

The over-all abundance of the borers was considered high. Regions 1 and 2 in the north had the lowest infestations, whereas all other regions were heavily infested.

Parasite catches in the field were fairly uniform from region to region except in Palawan where they were high. This may have been because this island has been relatively untouched by those modern pest control practices that are detrimental to the parasites. In one locality in Palawan, the parasite catch was as high as 12.6 per sample.

The incidence of parasitism in all areas was extremely low. In none of the regions was it more than 3 percent. No parasitism was recorded in region 2.

The second step of this program is envisaged as a manipulatory phase in which natural enemies of borers from other countries with similar climatic and ecological conditions will be imported and released. Their effect on the borer populations will be investigated in the light of basic studies conducted in the first phase. As a prerequisite, mass rearing techniques are being standardized for certain parasites.

Agricultural Engineering

Increased rice production is a pressing need in Asia, and an over-all decrease in human energy used in rice production is also necessary if the rice is to be sold at a price acceptable to the consumer and profitable to the grower. Applied scientific research should fill the gaps in existing knowledge of how to produce rice. Agronomic and engineering design techniques may then be used to apply this knowledge. Until this is done, production will remain low and costs high.

Engineering design and economic and engineering systems analysis should be combined with the applied biology of the agronomist to make the best use of the present climate, land, labor, capital, and material resources of the rice farmer. At the same time, systems that offer higher production and lower costs must be explored.

In 1965, a contract was initiated with the United States Agency for International Development to investigate the farm and equipment power requirements to produce rice and associated food crops in the Far East and South Asia. This project, which is to be implemented in 1966, will permit the present agricultural engineering program to be expanded to obtain and integrate research knowledge into a system capable of increasing the production of rice and other food crops. The expanded program will employ one person for operations research and one for engineering design.

The general engineering program already in progress was continued in the fields of farm machinery, irrigation, and bio-engineering to obtain knowledge on factors influencing land preparation, fertilization, planting, irrigation, and harvesting of rice.

LAND PREPARATION

Animal power

Quality and timeliness of land preparation largely depends on adequate power and in Asia this power is provided by animals. The amount of such usable power is limited by the number of animals one man can handle — usually one or two — and the supply of pasture, straw, or other animal feed which is available. In areas where land is limiting, the animals compete directly with man for food. The forage used to maintain the muscle power of mature animals could be better utilized for meat and milk production. The need for a complete analysis of the alternate use of present man labor, and the possibilities of using forage for livestock production rather than work-animal maintenance, must be recognized by specialists in animal husbandry, economics, and policy planning. From an engineering point of view, the present animal power is inadequate and expensive, yet farmers and policy makers are reluctant to consider machines which require money instead of labor and forage.

Standard tractors

Results reported previously indicated that about 70 to 140 Rhp-hr of work were required per hectare for wet land preparation, equivalent to one pass with a rotary tiller, or two passes with a disc harrow. Land preparation cost per hectare depends upon the efficiency and cost of the tillage power and equipment. Animal and small tiller units are fairly efficient, but their original and operation costs are high per horsepower and difficult to lower. Larger 40- to 50-hp tractors offer the opposite choice; their original and operation costs are low per horsepower but their efficiency is also low at the present time. The major problem with the larger tractor is to obtain mobility while providing power to a soil-working tool. As these tractors and their equipment were designed for dry land preparation, failures have outnumbered successes in their use on wet land. However, design and development to improve the performance of these tractors seem more promising than attempts to lower the cost of the small tillers.

TABLE 1. Field performance of I-H D-439 tractor while rotovating flooded clay soils at the Maligaya Rice Research and Training Center.^a

	Range	Average, $\bar{x} + 2\sigma$
Field size, (sq m)	1125 — 9212	3333
Operator hr/ha ^b	1.95 — 2.58	2.16 ± 0.16
Time for 90° turn (sec)		5.54 ± 0.45
Effective field capacity (sq m/hr)	3877 — 5145	4682 ± 313.69
Area (sq m) tilled/RHp-hr	99 — 132	120 ± 8.03
RHp-hr/ha	75 — 100	84 ± 5.95
Fuel consumption (l/hr)	4.40 — 7.47	6.04 ± 0.75
Fuel consumption (l/ha)	9.9 — 17.1	12.99 ± 4.95
Width of rotor (m)		1.5
Average swath (m)	1.54 — 1.77	1.7
Depth of tillage (cm)	10 — 18	13.34 ± 1.42
Slippage (percent) ^c	18.8 — 27.7	22.73 ± 0.02
Penetrometer cone index at 12" depth (psi)	7 — 160	77.65 ± 13.72
Penetrometer cone index at 18" depth (psi)	45 — 215	102.58 ± 18.52
Time to cross levee (sec) ^d	1.4 — 8.1	3.36 ± 0.30

^a 10 trials.

^b 3rd gear, 10th notch.

^c For every 3 rev. of wheels (3πD), D=1.40

^d Average levee height, cm=18.08 ± 1.47.

Average levee width, cm=44.08 ± 3.50.

Fig. 1. A 300-cm rotary tiller with Japanese rotary tiller blades for use with 40- to 60-Rhp tractors.

During 1965, work was concentrated on developing lug wheels and a rotary tiller for the 40-hp tractor size. Special lug wheels were mounted both inside and outside the tire. These wheels and an offset rotary tiller were tested at the Maligaya Rice Research and Training Center. Table 1 lists the average results of 10 tests covering 3.5 hectares. The area was a clay loam which had been flooded for one crop season. Straw and weeds from the previous crop were still on the plots. The tractor and a 150-cm wide rotary tiller were operated at an average forward speed of about 68 m/min. The results were 84 Rhp-hr and 13 l of diesel fuel/ha.

Results with an 8.5 Rhp Japanese tiller, reported in the 1964 tests, were 75 Rhp-hr and 15.4 l of diesel fuel/ha. The 8.5-Rhp tiller operated at a slower, 36 m/min, speed with a 60-cm wide rotary tiller. For ease of handling and efficient operation, the larger tractor should be equipped with a wider rotary tiller based on a design value of about 8 cm width per rated horsepower, and

should be operated at a slower forward speed of 15 to 50 m/min.

Fabrication has been completed of a 300-cm rotary tiller (Fig. 1) which uses Japanese rotary tiller blades and design features. For wet land, Japanese tiller blades are spiral-mounted individually along a shaft with a distance of about 3.5 cm and an angle of 150 degrees between blades, while for dry land most tillers have three to six blades mounted on hubs spaced 15 to 25 cm apart. The cutting pattern of the Japanese blade results in narrow slices 3.5 cm wide and 10 to 20 cm long, whereas the other pattern results in slices 15 to 20 cm wide and 3.5 to 7 cm long. These differences are significant considering that in wet soil the force resulting from the slice may be used to provide flotation and traction as well as to press under straw and puddle the mud. Manufacturers have been encouraged to develop wider equipment for 40- to 50-hp tractors utilizing the Japanese design criteria.

Tractor mobility increases with the use of rotary tillers, however, when the tiller is raised, the tractor must be mobile enough to cross ditches and levees with the traction developed by the wheels alone. Ten types of wheels have been fabricated and tested in an empirical effort to improve the performance of tractors in flooded fields. Figure 1 shows lug wheels which provide both flotation and traction. The wheel lugs are rubber tipped and extend the full tire diameter for better traction. Cut-out 45-degree triangle-shaped box lugs provide flotation yet permit the mud to escape between the lugs, thus avoiding the wave of mud created by wide solid wheels. When mounted on both sides of a standard tire, the lugs provide aggressive action for crossing or straddling levees. Lugs are rubber tipped and mounted on the tire rim with a rubber pad to reduce shock loads.

Four-wheel drive articulated tractors

Further efforts were made to interest manufacturers in the four-wheel drive articulated tractor, as this unit with a disc harrow should be competitive with or superior to the rotary tiller and two-wheel drive tractor. Studies were completed on the tractive performance of a 72-hp tandem tractor equipped with 11 x 36-inch rubber tires and 16 x 48-inch diameter cage wheels. Cantilevered weights were mounted at the rear to vary the front and rear axleloads. A tractor-mounted, hydraulic cylinder cable device was used for slow application and simple measurement of axle torque. The drawbar load was provided by a D-4 tracklayer.

The torque required to steer the tandem tractor was also measured on the same soil by using pressure gauges connected to the hydraulic circuit of the steering cylinders.

Towing tests also were conducted. The rolling resistance (towing resistance) of the tandem tractor was found equal to 1.58 times the self-propelled axle torque of the four wheels. Thus, the effective wheel radius was 1/1.58 or 0.63 meter.

The results of traction tests were expressed by multiple regression equations based on data for two tires with cage wheels corresponding to either the front or rear wheels of the tandem tractor.

$$T_s = 487 + 0.206 W - 3.16 \text{ (C.I.)}$$

$$T_m = 429 + 0.357 W - 1.62 \text{ (C.I.)}$$

$$P_m = -291 + 0.377 W + 2.50 \text{ (C.I.)}$$

$$P_c = -90 + 0.239 W + 2.44 \text{ (C.I.)}$$

where T_s = self-propelled axle torque,

kg-m

T_m = maximum (full slip) axle torque,

kg-m

P_m = maximum, net tractive effort

(measured), kg

P_c = maximum, net tractive effort

(computed as $T_m T_s$ divided by

0.63 meter), kg

W = axleload for two wheels (1290 to 2740 kg)

C.I. = soil cone index (96 to 169 psi at 12" depth)

A highly significant increase of T_s , T_m , P_m , and P_c with axleload or weight indicates that the test soil has a pronounced frictional property and that weight may be important in obtaining traction on flooded soils. This contradicts earlier beliefs that on flooded soils with deep mud, adding weight to the tractor would not increase net traction.

Self-propelled axle torque (rolling resistance) varied inversely with soil cone index. At low cone index greater sinkage was encountered resulting in increased compaction and bulldozing resistance.

Maximum axle torque also was inversely related to cone index. At low cone index the decrease in soil strength was offset by an increase in soil-wheel contact area due to sinkage.

Net tractive effort increased with cone index. On firm soils (high cone

index) conversion of axle torque into tractive effort was more efficient as soil reactions were mostly horizontal.

The torque needed to steer the tandem tractor increased with sinkage and steer angle. Peak values of 850 kg-m,

950 kg-m, and 1,000 kg-m were obtained at sinkages of 20 to 25 cm, 25 to 30 cm, and 30 to 35 cm, respectively. Corresponding maximum steer angles were 45, 35, and 25 degrees, respectively.

SIZES AND SHAPES OF FIELDS

Generally, field sizes and shapes in the Philippines were decided upon without thought of the possible introduction of modern farm machinery. Farmers made small-sized fields, especially on lands with high slopes, and oriented them to incur the least earth work in leveling.

Some farmers now realize that larger fields with appropriate shapes are more adaptable to modern equipment and more efficient for operations such as plowing, harrowing, and irrigation. Still many hesitate to reconstruct their farms because of the volume and cost of the earth work required, even though it is obvious that present sizes and shapes of fields limit the use of farm machinery. Mechanization can be effectively implemented only if field layout and other conditions will permit easy tractor access within the field, from field to field, and from farm to

farm. Precise information on the existing field conditions of lowland rice farms are needed to define more clearly the problems of using farm machinery and implements.

Eleven rice farms around Calauan, Laguna were surveyed and mapped by the plane table method. Dimensions and areas of the fields were measured from the scaled farm map. Later, 50 levee dimensions and field elevations were measured; the top and bottom width of the levees and their heights at the upper and lower fields were measured, and the soil cone index of the 50 fields on each farm at 6-, 9-, 12-, and 15-inch depths were determined with a cone penetrometer. The percentage of slope of the land was measured approximately by measuring distances between contour intervals.

The average field size was 566 sq m. Field dimensions of the 11 farms

Fig. 2. Map of rice farm showing present field layout and area in square meters and contour lines for future field layout.

ranged from 13 to 22.1 m wide and 20.3 to 39.4 m long. Average dimensions were 19.2 m wide by 29.5 m long.

There was no definite pattern followed in laying out the fields with respect to the slope of the land. In many cases the contour lines were diagonal to the rectangular fields, and the length of the field was thus limited. However, if contour levees were used the length of the field would be limited only by boundaries (Fig. 2).

Average levee dimensions were 19 cm top width, 33 cm bottom width, 18 cm levee height on upper field side, 29 cm levee height on lower field side, and an average difference of 12 cm between fields. In general, the means varied only ± 3 cm from one farm to another. Farmers on the 11 farms followed a similar pattern in making the levees, with little regard to slope or field size. The average levee base width and ele-

vation difference would form a hydraulic gradient of 0.33 slope with zero water depth to almost 1.0 when fully flooded. Average levee volume would be about 6 cu m/100 lin m. Earth work to build levees was at a minimum. The major problem in altering the field size and shape would be the cut and fill required to combine adjacent fields. The average field size of 566 sq m, and the elevation difference of 12 cm, would require about 600 cu m cut and fill per ha to combine adjacent fields and to double field size.

Soil bearing pressures were measured at 50 sites on each farm by taking cone penetrometer readings at 6-, 9-, 12-, 15-, and 18-inch depths. Using a cone index reading of over 35 psi at 15 inches as a criterion, approximately 84 percent of the farm area surveyed would permit mechanical land preparation with power tillers or tractors with lug wheels.

SOIL DEPTH

The use of tractors instead of animals to prepare land usually results in a deeper soil profile over a few years. The merits of this deeper soil are not clearly understood as the mixing of infertile subsoil with a fertile topsoil usually reduces yields for several crops. Yet, plowing and added fertilizer may improve the entire soil profile and bring it to a new state of equilibrium. Deeper soils offer a greater reserve or holding capacity for water and nutrients. The management or timeliness of water or fertilizer applications are obviously not as critical in a soil 50 cm deep as in one 10 cm deep. However, the relative importance of the various intermediate depths is not as clear.

Grain and straw of the variety Tainan 3, grown in the 1964 wet season experiment on soil depth, were analyzed for nitrogen content. During the 1965 dry season, the soil was again thoroughly mixed and placed in tanks with sloping floors to provide depths of 6 to 40 cm. Plants of variety PI 215936 in the deeper center rows were taller, greener, and yielded more (Fig. 3).

Sloping concrete floors were placed

in two additional 5.4 x 8.4 m plots to provide depths ranging from 0 to 72 cm in each plot. Thoroughly mixed Maahas clay soil was added to each plot, and each plot was split: one half fertilized (50 kg/ha N) and the other not fertilized. The fertilized plots dramatically responded in vegetative growth at all soil depths from 0 to 70 cm. However, the grain yield increased in only the 0 to 40 cm depths.

Grain and straw yield increased with increased soil depth in the form of a modified exponential equation of the form, $y = k + ab^x$ (Fig. 4). However, total nitrogen recovered from the grain and straw showed a linear trend with a sharp break at a soil depth of 40 cm (Fig. 5). The slope of the nitrogen regression lines indicates that 32 g of nitrogen were extracted per cu m of soil in the 0 to 40 cm range. From 40 to 70 cm soil depths, the extracted nitrogen averaged only 6 g/cu m of soil. Total soil nitrogen recovered from the straw and grain was apparently the same in both the fertilized and non-fertilized plots. The additional 50 kg/ha N shifted the regression lines equivalent to a re-

Fig. 3. Forty-seven-day-old PI 215936 seedlings planted in plot with soil depth shallow on edges and deep in the center.

covery of 40.7 kg N in the grain and straw. The fertilizer application was thus equivalent to an additional soil depth of $\frac{40.7}{320} = 12.7$ cm.

Grain yields of the two plots showed a similar shift as if soil depth were increased by the nitrogen. Straw yields, however, show an upward shift due to the added nitrogen. Additional experiments on the interaction between ap-

TABLE 2. Effect of soil depth on yield of Tainan 3, 1964 wet season (spacing 30 x 30 cm not fertilized).

Soil depth (cm)	Straw ht. (cm)	Tillers/ sq m	Panicles/ sq m	Weight (g/sq m)				Nitrogen content (g/sq m) ^a		
				Panicle	Straw	Grain	Plant	Straw	Grain	Plant
4	66	58	38	99	64	91	163	.39	1.12	1.51
8	68	68	56	153	129	138	282	.69	1.58	2.27
12	70	83	71	223	152	202	375	.76	2.29	3.05
16	72	110	71	256	206	231	462	1.48	2.70	4.18
20	74	121	77	285	246	258	531	1.62	3.72	5.34
24	77	129	87	340	264	293	604	1.96	3.89	5.85
28	79	141	90	363	310	310	673	2.20	4.42	6.62
32	79	146	82	341	336	299	677	2.53	4.14	6.67
36	80	152	92	383	332	331	715	2.59	5.10	7.69
k	89	175	96	433	539	356	924	4.23	6.46	10.57
a	-24	-129	-53	-339	-468	-272	-763	-4.05	-5.55	-9.48
b	.882	.805	.734	.798	.890	.767	.845	.889	.857	.869

Centimeters soil depth estimated for 90 and 95 percent of maximum value k.

Y = 0.9k	46	40	28	40	78	35	54	81	60	67
Y = 0.95k	61	53	38	52	102	45	70	122	78	88

^a Average soil N = 21.4 g/cu m or 86 kg/ha N to 40 cm depth.

Values of coefficients in formula $Y = k + ab^x$; $x = \frac{\text{Soil depth} - 4}{4}$

plied nitrogen, soil depth, and time and depth of application should be conducted to allow prediction of the depth and time nitrogen should be added, and to what depth land preparation should incorporate straw and fertilizer to form a deeper profile.

Fig. 4. Effect of soil depth and nitrogenous fertilizer (50 kg/ha) on straw and grain yield (1965 dry season).

The results to date indicate that in the treatments with more than 30 cm soil depth applied nitrogen is largely reflected in straw weight. Yield increases of grain are more pronounced in soils less than 30 cm deep. Fertile soil depths up to 40 cm definitely increased yields.

Fig. 5. Effect of soil depth and nitrogenous fertilizer on plant nitrogen content.

Soil depths of less than 40 cm respond more to fertilizer applications. For uniformly mixed soil less than 40 cm deep, the yield response to depth is almost linear, while on deeper soils the modified exponential trend becomes apparent.

Data in Tables 2, 3, and 4 demonstrate the full implications of soil depth. The values of k , a , b , and x of the equation, $y = k + ab^x$ are given as well as the solution of the equation for soil depths representing 90 and 95 percent

TABLE 3. Effect of soil depth on yield of PI 215936. 1965 dry season. (Spacing 15 x 20 cm, not fertilized.)

Soil depth (cm)	Straw ht. (cm)	Tillers/ sq m	Panicles / sq m	Weight (g/sq m)			Nitrogen content (g/sq m) ^a		
				Straw	Grain	Plant	Straw	Grain	Plant
8	48	88	83	122	122	244	.81	1.47	2.28
14	50	116	116	193	192	382	1.09	2.48	3.57
20	56	149	145	294	284	578	1.57	3.54	5.11
26	60	185	178	405	384	788	2.16	4.98	7.14
32	64	208	187	461	446	906	2.59	5.81	8.40
38	68	232	216	546	575	1121	3.33	7.80	11.13

^a Average N removed by plant from soil = 29.3 g/cu m or 117 kg/ha N to 40 cm depth.

TABLE 4. Effect of soil depth on yield of PI 215936, 1965 dry season. (Spacing 15 x 20 cm; not fertilized (NF) and fertilized (F) 50 kg/ha N.)

Soil depth (cm)	Straw ht. (cm)		Number/sq m				Weight (g/sq m)				Nitrogen content (g/sq m) ^a									
	NF	F	Tillers/sq m	Panicles/sq m	Straw	Panicle	Grain	Plant	Straw	Grain	Plant	Straw	Grain	Plant						
	NF	F	NF	F	NF	F	NF	F	NF	F	NF	F	NF	F						
10	56	66	168	305	151	218	283	605	261	455	229	400	544	1060	1.33	3.42	2.09	3.88	3.42	7.30
20	66	75	259	316	196	221	496	751	406	503	356	442	902	1254	2.49	5.81	3.96	4.97	6.45	10.78
30	76	81	268	337	208	231	653	905	485	533	426	468	1128	1438	4.20	8.05	5.14	6.02	9.34	14.07
40	77	82	274	341	207	233	688	918	553	595	486	522	1241	1513	5.53	9.42	6.40	7.32	11.93	16.72
50	81	83	272	344	209	237	679	915	590	604	518	519	1268	1519	5.92	9.94	7.21	7.35	13.13	17.29
60	81	82	274	349	217	234	745	925	610	622	585	508	1355	1547	6.80	10.21	7.42	7.53	14.22	17.74
70	80	83	281	348	212	245	769	1008	598	675	525	570	1367	1683	6.88	10.78	7.35	8.29	14.23	19.07
k	83	83	280	349	214	244	772	956	663	680	552	573	1368	1664	7.66	10.78	7.78	8.12	15.02	18.57
a	-28	-19	-97	-51	-58	-28	-505	-397	-396	-228	-322	-177	-833	-646	-6.75	-7.82	-5.78	-4.54	-12.54	-12.09
b	.539	.333	.373	.513	.4	.693	.515	.401	.661	.759	.608	.717	.532	.649	.697	.576	.65	.626	.605	.577

Centimeters soil depth estimated for 90 and 95 percent of maximum value k.

Y = 0.9k	30	18	22	16	21	14	38	26	53	54	45	44	40	41	70	46	57	47	52	44
Y = 0.95k	41	24	30	26	28	33	49	33	70	79	60	65	50	57	(90)	58	73	62	62	57

^a Average soil N = 32 g/cu m or 128 kg/ha N to 40 cm depth.

Values of coefficients in formula,

$$Y = k + abx$$

$$x = \frac{\text{Soil Depth} - 10}{10}$$

of maximum yield k . The value, k , may be due to either solar radiation or a limited supply of nitrogen. Native soil nitrogen taken into the plant varied from 21.4 to 32 g/cu m. Thus, Maahas clay supplied the equivalent of 86 to 128 kg/ha N from the top 40 cm of soil. A plow layer of 40 cm and over may be

impractical because depth limits the movement of men and machines. However, depths up to 30 cm are not a problem. The present animal land preparation has created a plow sole at depths of 10 to 15 cm which will undoubtedly be too shallow for the most efficient production.

FERTILIZER APPLICATION

Anhydrous ammonia (82% N) is a promising fertilizer material for flooded rice fields as it is low in cost and readily held in the wet soil. The positive pressure of the gaseous form allows precise metering and placement of the nitrogen at a desirable depth in the mud.

The Agricultural Engineering Department fabricated a knapsack anhy-

drous applicator for use by the Agronomy Department on puddled soils (Fig. 6). This unit will contain 10 kg of N and permit its placement at 0 to 20 cm depths at rates of from 0 to 240 kg/ha. The depth is controlled by a plate, and the rate is controlled by a pressure regulator, orifice size, and by ground speed. Details of fabrication and calibration are available to interested persons.

Fig. 6. Anhydrous ammonia applicator.

TABLE 5. Variety PI 215936 grain, straw, and total plant weight for anhydrous ammonia application rates of 5 to 235 kg/ha N^a.

Applied nitrogen (kg/ha N)	Grain (g/sq m)	Panicles +straw (g/sq m)
5	433	844
15	480	907
25	513	1025
35	518	1029
45	515	1071
55	548	1157
65	546	1140
75	549	1106
85	518	1061
95	523	1153
105	536	1106
115	521	1147
125	519	1255
135	459	1059
145	480	1101
155	472	1087
165	434	1026
Average 175 to 235	486	1070

^a Harvested Nov. 29, 1965. This was a wet season crop in which the gross solar radiation during the 8 weeks prior to November 28 was as follows (in order from last week before harvest)—

1930: 2010; 2119; 1803; 2413; 1899;
1959; 2785 —

Total, 16918 g-cal/sq cm.

An experiment was carried out in which the speed was maintained constant and the pressure was changed to obtain varying rates of nitrogen from 10 to 240 kg/ha, applied between rows of an established planting. Variety PI 215936 was transplanted at 5 x 45 cm spacing on August 16-17. Three replicates were fertilized on September 22-23 at rates varied in 10 kg/ha increments. The plants reacted visually to these application rates. Lodging started earliest and was most severe at rates over 80 kg but occurred at rates as low as 35 kg. Yields of grain and straw approached a maximum at 65 kg/ha N and gradually declined at higher levels of nitrogen (Table 5). The solar radiation, rather than nitrogen, limited yields. The plants were a healthy green and showed promise of maximum yield if adequate sunshine had been available.

The backpack applicator should be useful in applying anhydrous ammonia to extensive field demonstration plots. Farmers can observe the variable rate and decide reasonably well at which point nitrogen application ceases to be advantageous. A commercial model could also be made for backpack use and be rented to farmers by the fertilizer dealer.

SPACING

Mathematical equations to predict the effect of plant spacing and sunlight on yield are necessary to decide on method of planting. Adjustments in the method of planting should improve either yields or labor productivity if the results are approximately predictable. Plant populations of over 50 plants/sq m are best achieved by direct seeding, either broadcast or in drilled rows. Transplanting may be square or in rows, but transplanting at more than 25 plants/sq m is prohibitive in labor requirements.

Provided other conditions are adequate, rice yields should be proportional to the solar radiation intercepted by the plant. Plant population or spacing significantly influences panicle number and the interception of solar radiation.

Sparse plantings may not tiller sufficiently to utilize the sunlight fully, whereas overpopulation results in lightweight panicles, death of the lower leaves, and excessive and early lodging of plants. Prior knowledge of the rice plant's reaction to spacing would permit adjustments to prevent excessive lodging yet allow absorption of 80 to 95 percent of the sunlight.

Square transplanted

The results of the 1964 spacing experiment (Annual Report, 1964) were used to design the 1965 dry season, experiments No. 2a and 2b. Replications were increased in No. 2a to improve precision at close spacing. Plant density was increased to cover the range of 200 to 400 plants/sq m using the de-

Fig. 7. Experiment No. 2a — Square transplanted PI 215936 at flowering, April 6, 1965.

sign described previously. Forty-one spacings were used; these ranged from 1 to 400 plants/sq m (Fig. 7).

Experiment No. 2b consisted of comparisons of row planting with a square arrangement. In certain treatments seedlings were transplanted 5 cm apart in simulated drilled rows spaced at distances ranging from 5 to 144 cm. In other treatments both row spacing and distance between plants within a row were varied to give approximately square spacing. Actual distance in the square plantings ranged from 5 x 5 cm to 144 x 144 cm (Fig. 8).

Several additional experiments were made at intervals throughout the wet season to gain information on yield in relation to solar radiation, and to compare transplanting with direct seeding by broadcast and drilled row methods. The percentage of light penetrating to ground level, or the light transmission ratio (LTR), was taken at flowering time to estimate the effect of sunlight absorption on yield. The theoretical maximum yield for any one planting would depend on the solar radiation during the last few weeks prior to har-

vest and the efficiency of conversion.

Maximum yields for all spacings within an experiment may be estimated by a regression equation of $y = a + b$ (LTR), in which a is maximum yield if all sunlight were intercepted and used as efficiently as it is used by widely spaced plants. Maximum yields seldom occur as the yield curve breaks at LTR values of 5 to 20 percent, when mutual shading and lodging become excessive. The a -intercept and the $(-100b)$ of the equation should be equal if the LTR is taken precisely, as no light is intercepted when $\text{LTR} = 100$. In practice, however, the adjustments of the light meters and shadows cause the LTR values to be variable at wide spacings. Thus the a value is a better estimate of maximum yields and the $-b$ value is the rate of change from maximum yields as LTR decreases.

Adequate data are not yet available for a thorough analysis of the various relationships, but the statements below seem to be justifiable simplifications based on the present experimental data. (Detailed tables have been prepared and are available on request so that persons

Fig. 8. Experiment No. 2b₁ and 2b₂ — Variety PI 215936 square transplanted and transplanted drill rows at flowering April 6, 1965.

interested in bio-mathematics can plot and compute for many combinations of spacing, panicle number, panicle weight, lodging index, and leaf area index, and attempt to find the best prediction equations.)

1. Lodging occurs when the LTR is less than 5 to 10 percent in bright, clear weather and 10 to 20 percent in cloudy weather.

2. Panicle number and leaf area index (LAI) determine LTR; yields thus vary directly with panicle number until excessive competition occurs.

3. Average individual panicle weight is almost constant at wide spacings and is probably genetically determined, while at close spacings the individual average panicle weight is reduced in direct proportion to the area available per panicle and the solar radiation. Individual PI 215936 panicles require 40 to 60 cm² for full development; while PI 215936 x CI 9214 panicles require about 45 cm², and Fujisaka 5 panicles about 24 cm².

4. Panicle weight per square meter is determined by panicle number and average panicle weight. Panicle number per square meter increases rapidly with

plant populations from 1 to 10 plants per square meter in the form of a modified exponential equation:

Y_1 Panicles/sq m = $k + ab^x = k(1 - b^x)$ in which $k = -a$ and is the maximum fully developed panicle number per square meter, and x is the number of plants per square meter. The two equations, $Y = a + b(LTR)$ and $k + ab^x$, give about the same results.

The approximate genetic maximum panicle size, and leaf area per panicle, should be reflected in the square centimeters required for full development of a panicle, while tillering ability of the plant is reflected in b^x ; theoretically, when $x = 1$, then $b^x = b$. Tables 6 and 7 list prediction equations for panicle number and yield in panicle weight per sq m. Yield may be converted to clean grain weight by multiplying by a factor of 0.85 to 0.90. Note that in Table 7, the k value approximately equals the a value, especially for panicle number.

Drill rows

The results of several experiments in which drill row planting and transplanted were compared (Figs. 8 and 9) indicate that row spacings may be

TABLE 6. Prediction equations of panicle number (Y_1) and panicle weight (Y_2) per square meter when plants per square meter (x) are varied.

Expt. no.	$Y_1 = k + ab^x$	$Y_2 = k + ab^x$
1	252 - 250(0.756) ^x	433 - 426(0.664) ^x
2a	168 - 166(0.721) ^x	754 - 921(0.658) ^x
2b ₁ square transplant		850 - 850(0.71) ^x
2b ₂ drill row transplant		850√1 - (0.71) ^{2x}
3	221 - 242(0.896) ^x	578 - 594(0.818) ^x
4	215 - 217(0.907) ^x	638 - 618(0.94) ^x

wider than hill spacings. Tentative prediction equations of yield (Y) are proposed with the following forms:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{square transplant } Y &= k(1 - b^x) \\ \text{drill row } Y &= k\sqrt{1 - b^{2x}} \end{aligned}$$

These are based on the yield results of two spacing experiments and the observed lodging pattern. Drilled rows spaced 45 to 60 cm apart are probably similar in mutual shading to square spaced transplants 25 to 33 cm apart. Yields of drill rows from 20 to 95 cm apart were almost equal. Yield was apparently best near the last lodged row which was found to be at spacings which ranged from 45 to 75 cm, although there was little decline up to 95-cm row spacings. Additional information from rows spaced 100 to 200 cm will be necessary to predict the decline of yields at wider spacings.

Land preparation, fertilizer application, and direct seeding in rows could be completed in one operation if drill rows were 50 to 100 cm apart, while harvesting standing plants with a mechanical stripper would eliminate the problem of separating wet grain and straw. Additional investigation of yields of drilled rice would enable the machine designer to take advantage of the plant's inherent ability to compensate for spacing.

Individual plants

An experiment was initiated to further evaluate the plant's ability to compensate for spacing. Seven widely different varieties were selected and interspaced hexagonally with a density of one plant per square meter. Approximately 150 plants of each variety were

Fig. 9. Experiment No. 4 — Variety PI 215936 x CI 9214 direct seeded in drill rows (left) and square transplanted (right).

TABLE 7. Prediction equation of panicle number (Y_1) and panicle weight (Y_2) per m when the light transmission ratio (LTR) is measured at flowering.

Expt. No.	$Y_1 = a + b(\text{LTR})$	$Y_2 = a + b(\text{LTR})$
1	190 - 224(LTR)	519 - 576(LTR)
2a	258 - 228(LTR)	818 - 723(LTR)
3	226 - 319(LTR)	599 - 520(LTR)
4 (transplant)	164 - 224(LTR)	377 - 492(LTR)
4 (seeded drill row)	228 - 297(LTR)	377 - 77(LTR)
5 (seeded drill row)	459 - 385(LTR)	430 - 174(LTR)

Fig. 10. Relationship of grain and panicle weight to product of upper leaf area and period from transplanting to harvest.

grown in this manner so that each was a replicate. Twenty-five healthy plants (25 replicates) were measured at harvest and the data, summarized in Table 8 and Fig. 10, indicate that the product of leaf area and growth period is closely related to yield. This relationship

could be explored further to enable estimates of field production to be made from greenhouse experiments.

The leaf spread at the top of the plant is 80 to 128 cm, indicating that row spacing could be in this range before serious yield reduction occurred.

Fig. 11. Evaporation was recorded from a 2.40 x 2.40 x 0.60 meter sunken pan.

uary and early February, but under the influence of the northeast monsoon, dry season conditions prevailed in March and April. The temperature in January and February was about 24 C but rose to a maximum of 29 C in April.

Evaporation and rainfall were measured from three metal tanks, size 2.40 x 2.40 x 0.60 meters, with closed bottoms. All tanks were installed with the bottoms 40 cm below the soil surface. The soil which had been removed for the installation of the tanks was placed in each tank up to the external soil lev-

el. Water level was recorded to 0.1 mm scale division on a water level recorder in one tank and checked by hook gauges in the others.

Gross solar radiation, mean air temperature, relative humidity, and wind velocity were measured in the College of Agriculture Weather Station 1 km distant. The data for 25 days were discarded because of heavy rain, wind, or irrigation disturbances, but accurate evapotranspiration measurements were obtained for 94 days.

Assuming that theoretical evapora-

Fig. 13. The relationship of evapotranspiration in vegetative and reproductive stage to mean air temperature and relative humidity.

Under a contractual system of wage payment of 33 kg of rough rice (P10.00) per ton-km which the laborers set themselves, six laborers each carried a 50-kg load 12 km and returned the 12 km unladen (thus transporting a total of 0.6 ton-km in a day. Only two men out of eight were able to carry the 50-kg load 15 km and return unladen to transport 0.75 ton-km in 6 hours. The men worked to exhaustion to earn about twice the normal wage rate. They then refused further work even though permitted to set their own contract rates.

Table 9 is a guide for persons interested in the rate of manual transport of palay.

TABLE 9. Rate of manual transport based on $T = 340 W^{-0.931}$ (two-way travel on smooth grassed shoulders of earth road).

Weight (kg)	Man-hour/ton-km
10	39.8
15	27.3
20	20.9
25	17.0
30	14.3
35	12.4
40	11.0
45	9.8
50	8.9
^a — — — — —	
60	7.5
70	6.5
80	5.8
90	5.2
100	4.7

^a Values over 50 kg extrapolated, and allowance made for narrow path, and poor walking conditions.

IRRIGATION

Irrigation projects in tropical countries have been designed mostly to provide supplemental water for rice during the wet season. The water required is supplied by effective rainfall and supplemental diversion irrigation. As the water usually is distributed free, farmers tend to get more water than is actually needed. The total water required by rice under flooded conditions must be estimated more precisely in the future by designers of irrigation systems and others concerned with irrigation because water costs for reservoirs and pumping are becoming the limiting factor in dry season rice production.

Because of limited research data, the designers of an irrigation system usually have to assume quantities of water used by evapotranspiration and lost by seepage and percolation. Presently, the evapotranspiration is calculated by empirical formulae based on climatic data. The water losses by gravity and overflow in paddy fields are calculated as a percentage of water requirement. Irrigation designers often assume 1 cm/day as the total requirement of rice.

Evapotranspiration or consumptive use

A high correlation between solar radiation and evapotranspiration was demonstrated for rice at the Institute in 1963. The measurements were made from a small tank, but similar results were obtained in the field during the 1964 wet season (Annual Report, 1964). Additional measurements of solar radiation, pan evaporation, and other climatic indices of evapotranspiration from rice were made on the same experimental plot from January 5, 1965 (Figs. 11 and 12). Water depth was maintained at 60 to 90 mm; multiple metal levees almost eliminated seepage losses. Decrease in water level in the 400-sq m plot with 1 m buffer area was regarded as evapotranspiration plus percolation. Three piezometers were installed to measure the water table and study the effect of percolation.

Twenty-day-old seedlings of PI 215936 were transplanted at 20 x 20 cm spacing on January 5 and harvested 119 days later. Heavy rains fell in Jan-

The ratio 0.0108/0.0172 indicates that 63 percent of gross solar radiation was used in evapotranspiration.

Solar radiation largely determines temperature and relative humidity. Thus these climatic elements are correlated with evapotranspiration. Figure 13 shows the relationship between evapotranspiration to relative humidity and mean air temperature. These climatic factors showed a lower correlation coefficient than solar radiation.

Figure 13 shows daily evapotranspiration from the field and daily solar radiation. The cumulative evapotranspiration of 94 days in three different stages of growth shows the same slope as the regression equation for the daily evapotranspiration values (Fig. 14). Many researchers have reported that during heading the rice plant uses more water than either before or after this stage. In this experiment, the difference between the vegetative and reproductive stages of growth were not significant. However, during the ripening stage when the leaves turned brown the rate was a little lower.

Figure 14 also shows the cumulative evapotranspiration compared with the cumulative evaporation. The ratio between ET and E is almost constant for vegetative, reproductive, and ripening stages. Solar radiation is the major factor in the vaporization of water from the evaporation pan and ET from the crop, and both were highly correlated with solar radiation.

Percolation

Deep percolation is the downward flow through a depth of soil. Seepage is the lateral loss of water from a shallow depth of standing water through levees and boundary soil profile. Under field conditions percolation and seepage are major losses which may exceed the evapotranspiration. Percolation mainly depends on vertical permeability, porosity, texture and structure of soil, depth of soil profile, pan formation, and ground water table.

The seepage and percolation rates of an experimental area of Maahas clay were reported (Annual Report, 1963, 1964) as 0.50 and 0.15 mm/day. During

1965, additional measurements were made on the piezometric head with three piezometers installed to depths of 50, 100, and 150 cm in the buffer area of the experimental plot. Percolation rates increased as the piezometer heads and hydraulic gradient increased. Soil permeability (k) was found to be constant at 2.2 mm/day, while seepage from the experimental plot was found to be negligible due to the metal levees and a buffer area in which water was maintained at the same level as in the plot.

Seepage

Seepage through earth levees under field conditions is a major source of water loss. Seepage is affected by soil permeability, soil cracks, and insect tunnels. Laminar flow formulae may be applied for calculating rate of seepage due to permeability. However, turbulent flow may occur through small channels and exceed laminar flow. Thus, the condition and age of the levee affect the rate of seepage. The turbulent flow varies from place to place along the levee. Several methods for measuring seepage were compared in an attempt to develop a simple method, applicable for use on irrigation projects, to estimate re-usable water that may seep out of higher fields into lower fields.

Seepage through 10-meter long levee

This first experiment was conducted to measure seepage through representative strips of levee 10 m long. Seven sites were selected and metal levees installed.

The regression equations for seepage (l/hr/lin m) and depth of water (cm) were significant for the following sites:

$$\text{Site 1 } y_1 = -5.801 + 1.915x_1 \quad r = 0.741$$

$$\text{Site 2 } y_2 = -7.871 + 1.510x_2 \quad r = 0.748$$

$$\text{Site 5 } y_5 = -0.338 + 5.367x_5 \quad r = 0.949$$

$$\text{Site 6 } y_6 = +2.629 + 1.196x_6 \quad r = 0.650$$

$$\text{Site 7 } y_7 = -2.183 + 2.815x_7 \quad r = 0.661$$

Fig. 12. Evapotranspiration and percolation were obtained from a 20 x 20 meter field plot by use of a water level recorder and piezometer tubes.

tion in the rice field follows the thermodynamic conditions, it takes 582 g-cal to evaporate 1 cc of water at 26.5 C, thus 582 g-cal/cm²/day of solar radiation should evaporate 10 mm of water in the field, or

$$y = \frac{1}{58.2} x = 0.0172x$$

where y = mm of water
and x = g/cal/cm²

For the 1965 dry season, the relationship of pan evaporation to gross solar radiation was

$$y = -0.19 + 0.0098x$$

with r = 0.9035. In comparison with the theoretical evaporation equation, the ratio,

$$\frac{Y_{pan}}{Y_{Th}} = \frac{0.0098x}{0.0172x} = 0.55$$

indicates that 55 percent of the gross solar radiation was used in evaporation of water from the 2.40 x 2.40 x 0.60 m sunken pan.

The best estimate of evapotranspiration was obtained by subtracting the night evaporation pan losses from the 400-sq m field night losses. The difference of night evaporation pan and night field data was assumed to be gravity losses due to percolation and seepage for one-half day. The formula for calculating evapotranspiration was

$$ET = (ET+SP)_d + 2E_n - (ET+SP)_n$$

where ET = evaporation, mm/day
(ET+SP)_d = evapotranspiration + percolation in the daytime, mm

E_n = pan evaporation in the nighttime, mm

(ET+SP)_n = evapotranspiration + percolation in the nighttime, mm

The relationship of evapotranspiration to gross solar radiation during vegetative and reproductive stage was

$$y = 0.0108x.$$

Fig. 14. Cumulative water losses from the field related to cumulative gross solar radiation.

to irrigate four lower plots. The computed water requirement of the lower plots was based on a 6 mm/day rate of $P + ET$. To supply this requirement, total excess water from the highest plot was computed to be 26 l/hr/lin m. The amount of seepage through one meter of levee was to be adequate to irrigate a 104-m strip below the levee. To maintain the necessary rate, the depth of water in the high plot was maintained at about 5.5 to 6 cm.

After the highest plot had been flooded to a depth of 8 cm, water seeped to the lower plots; hydrograph patterns displayed a sharp peak indicating rapid movement into the first plot, but patterns were smoother for lower ones,

and the fourth plot hydrograph was almost static.

In the second experiment, the natural grade was 0.25 percent, and the plots differed in elevation by an average of 6 cm. The seepage rate in the highest plot with a depth of 10 cm of water, was only 5 l/hr/lin m—sufficient to maintain the water requirement of 0.6 cm/day for an area of 20 sq m, or only a 20-cm strip below the levee. A parallel pattern was given by the hydrograph.

The last two experiments thus indicated that the rate of seepage through an earth levee may be used to supply a 20- to 100-m strip of lower land when water levels are 1 to 10 cm deep.

To check the over-all accuracy of the 10-m strips, two water level recorders were installed to record water level of complete plots. One plot gave reliable data on the seepage rate through a 168-m levee. The equation, $y_s = -0.468 + 4.322x$ with $r = 0.942$, was obtained for the relationship of rate of seepage of the entire plot to depth of water.

The regression equation of Site 5 represents seepage from levees bordering ditches, while Sites 6 and 7 represent the seepage from levees between plots. Using average weighted y values the rate of seepage from the entire plot was: $\bar{y}_{5,6,7} = 0.136 + 2.526\bar{x}$. This differs from y_s and indicates that three 1 x 10 m plots when used as seepage meters would only approximate the rate of seepage.

Lateral seepage into drains

A second experiment was conducted to estimate the seepage which reappears in surface ditches or streams and is available to lower areas. If re-used, the seepage losses from higher elevations would not be lost, and the seepage from the perimeter levees could be of economic importance from a water conservation point of view.

Accurate measurement of each individual length of levee is not practicable, but an approximate estimate can be made by measuring the water which reappears in surface ditches. A 3-inch throat Parshall flume was installed and water flow from a 1,540-m ditch drain measured daily.

Flow rates for rainy days were higher than for dry days (Fig. 15). During the first period after rain, the flow through levee openings and from the road bed gave a high discharge rate. The flow then decreased gradually until stable. The steady flow rate on rainy days was usually higher than on dry days; thus, two regression equations were chosen to best fit the data.

Reusable seepage water from this 1,540-m road ditch averaged 5.4 l/hr/lin m on dry days and 13.6 l/hr/lin m on wet days. The flow of water increased 1.6 to 4.7 l/hr/lin m/cm in average water depth. These values may

Fig. 15. Relationship of rate of seepage to depth of water in the field, measurement of seepage into drains of Plot B.

serve to estimate perimeter seepage losses from other projects with similar levees. Field engineers may check these values by setting up a similar experiment on drains which are near boundary levees.

Reusable water from higher fields

A third study was conducted to estimate the flow from upper fields through levees to lower fields. Metal levees along the side levees adjacent to drains minimized seepage from the plots to the road drains, thus the water lost from one plot entered directly into the next lower plot.

In the first of the experiments, the average levee thickness was 30 cm at the top and 40 cm at the base. The natural grade was 0.7 percent, and the average difference in elevation between plots was 18 cm. Seepage from the highest plot was maintained at a rate sufficient

RESEARCH ON SOURCES OF OUTPUT GROWTH

The 1964 annual report presented a conceptual framework for analyzing the historical and potential sources of agricultural output growth, and utilized this framework to analyze in detail historical trends and regional differentials in rice production, area, and yield in the Philippines. Similar work on rice production, area, and yield in Thailand was completed in 1965. The results of the Thailand analysis were compared with those of the Philippine analysis and a similar analysis for Taiwan was initiated.

The common hypothesis that underlies this set of studies is that the yield differences among major rice producing areas within southeast Asia at the present time, primarily reflect variations in the environmental factors under which rice is grown (primarily soil, season, water and weather differ-

entials), rather than differences in variety or cultural practices.

Rice production, area, and yield in Thailand

The long-term trend in rice production, area, and yield in Thailand can be divided into three major periods: (a) one of rapid growth in production, rapid increase in area with relative stability in yield from the early 1900's until approximately 1920, (b) a period of relative stability in total production with increases in area planted being offset by declining yield from the early 1920's until the late 1940's, and (c) a period of rapid growth in production based on increases in area planted but relative stability in yields from the late 1940's to the present. There is some indication that the long-term decline in rice yield per hectare in Thailand finally ended

Fig. 1. Long-term trend of rice production, area, and yield in Thailand (1907/08 to 1963/64).

Agricultural Economics

The research program in Agricultural Economics has concentrated on the relationships between technological change and the growth of rice production. Four aspects of technological change were emphasized: (a) the sources of output growth, (b) productivity and efficiency in rice production, (c) rice supply, demand, and price behavior, and (d) institutional factors affecting technological change. A large share of the department's total effort in 1965 centered on the issues of rice supply, demand, and price behavior.

in the mid- or late 1950's (Fig. 1).

Since the early years of this century, the national average yield in the Philippines has been lower than in Thailand. In 1908-09 when the national average yield in Thailand was 1.67 ton/ha the national average yield in the Philippines was 0.68 ton/ha.

More rapid growth in yields in the Philippines compared to Thailand has narrowed this difference. During the last two years (1962/63-1963/64) the national average yield in Thailand was 1.54 ton/ha while that in the Philippines was 1.25 ton/ha. Most of the yield decline in Thailand occurred between the early 1920's and the mid-1950's. In both countries yields have tended to increase in the last few years.

Rice yields differ substantially among regions in Thailand (Fig. 2). Fourteen provinces achieved yields greater than 1.96 ton/ha. All the provinces in the highest yield category are located in central and northern Thai-

land. The highest average yield for the 3-year period was in Pechaboon province (3.24 ton/ha) in the upper part of the central plain. Of the six provinces with an average yield of less than 1 ton/ha, five were in the northeast and one in the central plain.

There have been important differences in the growth of production, area, and yield among the several regions of Thailand during the period since the early 1950's. The most rapid increases in production took place in north Thailand (Fig. 3). In the north, production increased by more than 60 percent between 1950/51 to 1952/53 and 1961/62 to 1963/64. The average yield per hectare rose by 42 percent, from 1.52 to more than 2.14 ton/ha, and accounted for almost three-fourths of the total growth in rice production in the north. The rate of growth in the production of rough rice was also relatively rapid in the northeast where total production increased by 41 percent.

Fig. 3. Rice production in various regions, Thailand (1947/48 to 1963/64).

Fig. 2. Distribution of rice yields among Thai provinces (three-year average, 1961/62 to 1963/64).

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Fig. 3. Rice production in various regions, Thailand (1947/48 to 1963/64).

Fig. 4. Rice yields in various regions, Thailand (1947/48 to 1963/64).

In contrast to north Thailand, however, area increased more rapidly than yield in the northeast, and accounted for almost two-thirds of the increase in total regional production. In the south, production increased by only 29 percent during this same period. Changes in yield per hectare were about as important as increases in area in accounting for the increase. The central plain which accounted for the largest absolute increase in rice production, experienced the slowest rate of growth in production. Yield increased by 22 percent, from 1.45 to 1.77 ton/ha and accounted for approximately 85 percent of the total increase in production.

Between 1947/48 to 1963/64 there was an apparent increase in yield in all regions (Fig. 4). Among the four regions of Thailand, average yield in the northern region was highest and had the most rapid yield increases over the last 16 years. However, in the northeast, average yield was lowest and yield increased slowly. Average yield in the central plain and the south fluctuated between 1947/48 to 1961/62 but in the last 3 years the rice yield increased sharply in both areas.

Effects of irrigation and weather on rice yields

In Thailand most of the rice grown is irrigated or rainfed. The percentage of upland rice is low — probably not more than 1 percent in recent years. The second crop or dry season production, also low, accounts for less than 1 percent of the total area planted (or harvested). Most of the dry season crop is grown in the north and in the central plain. The relative importance of irrigated and rainfed rice areas varies sharply, however, among provinces. In central Thailand almost half of the area planted, and in the north more than one-fourth of the area planted, is irrigated (Fig. 5).

The yields reported by the Royal Irrigation Department for irrigated areas are substantially higher than yields estimated for non-irrigated areas. Both the irrigated and non-irrigated areas have experienced yield increases since 1958/59. Irrigated land represents such a small portion of the total increase in the northeast that the higher yield on irrigated land had a relatively minor impact on the average yield for the en-

Fig. 5. Regional distribution of rice area, Thailand (3-year average, 1961/62 to 1963/64).

ture region. In the central plain the estimated yield on non-irrigated land has risen more rapidly than on irrigated land.

Differences in the portion of the area planted to rice that is irrigated in each region substantially influence the regional average yield. In those regions in which only a small share of the land is irrigated, the average yield is close

to that from non-irrigated land. The data in Table 1 attempt to measure the effect of different regional irrigation patterns on regional yields. The data in the last column are estimates of the average yields that would have been reported for the region if the distribution of hectareage between irrigated and non-irrigated areas in the region had been the same as the national average. In the central plain, for example, the actual average yield in 1961/62 to 1963/64 was 1.766 metric tons of rough rice per hectare, or almost 17 percent above the national average. If the distribution of area between irrigated and rainfed culture had been the same as the national average, the 1961/63 average yield in the central plain would have been 1.394 ton/ha or 8 percent below the national average.

A relatively high percentage of the variation in yield from year to year can be explained by variations in the percentage of damaged area in the northeast and the central plain. In addition, most of the upward trend in yield in these two regions in recent years appears to be the result of sequence of years in which the damaged area had declined continuously. If the damaged area again rises to the 12 to 17 percent range, as in 1958/59 and 1959/60, the average yield in the central plain could again drop to around 1.5 ton/ha. In the northeast, a damaged area of 9 to 12%, as in 1957/58 and 1959/60, could again result in a yield of around 1 ton/ha.

Regional comparisons between the Philippines and Thailand

Clearly, national average yields per hectare harvested are lower in the Phil-

TABLE 1. Effect of differences in regional production patterns on Thailand regional average yields.

Region	Actual yield		Standardized yield ^a	
	ton/ha	Index	ton/ha	Index
Thailand (1961/62-1963/64)	1.514	100.0	1.514	100.0
Central Plain	1.766	116.6	1.394	92.1
Northeast	1.123	74.2	1.409	93.1
North	2.144	141.6	2.125	140.4
South	1.602	105.8	1.770	116.9

^a The regional yields of rough rice for irrigated and non-irrigated areas are weighted by the national area distribution to obtain the standardized yields.

ippines than in Thailand and are relatively lower today than a decade ago (Table 2). A comparison of yields in central Thailand and in the central Luzon area of the Philippines — the two regions which account for a relatively high percentage of the rice entering the commercial market in the two countries — reveals a somewhat different pattern than does a comparison of the national average yields of the two countries. Average yields in the two regions are almost identical and have risen at approximately the same rate over the last decade.

It is also possible to compare yields in the regions where area harvested has been expanding most rapidly. Most of the expansion in rice area in Thailand has been in the northeast. The Philippines has experienced a rapid expansion in area in southern and western Mindanao, particularly since 1956-57. In the early 1950's, rice yields in southern and western Mindanao were substantially higher than in northeastern Thailand. With the rapid expansion in area in southern and western Mindanao, yields have declined and are now slightly higher than in northeastern Thailand. The process of area expansion apparently occurs primarily through the addition of upland and rainfed rice areas. Rice yields under this type of cultivation are low and are apparently not very different in northeastern Thailand and southern and western Mindanao in spite of rather substantial differences in soil and climate.

Implications of production, area, and yield data

Despite numerous deficiencies, the data examined are consistent with the hypothesis that both the yield increases of the last decade, and the yield differences among major rice-producing areas in the Philippines and Thailand, primarily reflect variations in the environmental factors under which rice is grown rather than differences from variety planted or cultural practices. After the effects of the environmental factors are taken into account, there is little yield increase or yield differential left to be explained by such factors as

TABLE 2. Comparison of yield of rough rice (metric ton/ha harvested) in the Philippines and Thailand, 1953/54-1963/64.

	National average yields		Major commercial regional yields				Regions with rapid expansion			
	Ratio (2)/(1)		Central Thailand	Central Luzon	Ratio (5)/(4)	Northeast Thailand	Western Mindanao	Ratio (8)/(7)	Cagayan Valley	Ratio (10)/(7)
	Thailand	Philippines	(4)	(5)	(6)	(7)	(8)	(9)	(10)	(11)
1953/54	1.39	1.20	1.61	1.33	0.83	1.08	2.04	1.89	1.59	1.47
1954/55	1.26	1.21	1.38	1.50	1.09	0.93	1.47	1.38	1.31	1.41
1955/56	1.36	1.19	1.53	1.61	1.05	1.01	1.35	1.34	1.25	1.24
1956/57	1.44	1.21	1.60	1.61	1.01	1.13	1.36	1.20	1.25	1.11
1957/58	1.30	1.02	1.30	1.41	1.08	1.03	1.04	1.01	1.08	1.05
1958/59	1.36	1.11	1.56	1.51	0.97	1.01	1.04	1.03	1.28	1.27
1959/60	1.29	1.13	1.46	1.39	0.95	0.93	1.03	1.11	1.38	1.48
1960/61	1.39	1.16	1.59	1.57	0.99	1.03	1.13	1.10	1.09	1.06
1961/62	1.44	1.23	1.51	1.80	1.19	0.94	1.14	1.21	1.21	1.29
1962/63	1.49	1.25	1.73	1.82	1.05	1.16	1.26	1.09	1.28	1.10
1963/64	1.59	1.24	1.86	1.86	1.00	1.17	1.26	1.08	1.13	0.97

new varieties, better cultural practices, or more intensive use of technical inputs such as fertilizer and insecticides or by economic and social differences among regions and between Thailand and the Philippines.

In both the Philippines and Thailand, most of the lowland rice is grown during the rainy season without irrigation. Under this rainfed system of cultivation, village or provincial average yields rarely exceed 1.5 ton/ha. In fully irrigated areas in both countries, however, such as in Chiangmai (Thailand) or Laguna (Philippines), it is not uncommon for average yields to exceed 3 ton/ha in the wet season and 3.5 tons in the dry season over fairly substantial areas. On individual farms, such as those participating in contests or under experimental conditions, the yields of the same varieties are frequently in the 4 to 4.5 ton/ha range in the wet season and 5 to 6 metric ton/ha range in the dry season.

A major implication of the foregoing analysis is that the factors which permit a province or a region to increase its yields from 1.5 ton/ha in the wet season to the levels currently being achieved in the higher yielding areas of each country are primarily outside the control of the individual farmer in the major rice-producing areas such as central Luzon or central Thailand. The modifications in the environment necessary to achieve effective water control (irrigation and drainage) during both the wet and dry season and effective pest control will have to come primarily from public or semi-public agen-

cies capable of organizing resources in a manner not available to the individual tenant or farm owner.

A second major implication is that the same limitation on environmental control, which prevents farmers from achieving the yield potentials inherent in existing varieties, will represent an equally severe limitation on achievement of the yield potentials inherent in the new varieties that are now being developed for future introduction. Some of these varieties are being designed to be even more sensitive to effective environmental control, technical inputs, and management than existing varieties. Thus, the same public investment and institutional innovations required to narrow the gap between typical and potential yields under present circumstances will be a necessary condition if the introduction of the new varieties is to be reflected in higher aggregate yields.

These inferences raise a major issue in the strategy of agricultural development. Failure to make adequate public investment in irrigation and to develop adequate public programs of disease and pest control will clearly dampen the returns from investment in research and development, on varietal improvement, and the cultural practices associated with the use of other technical inputs. On the other hand, failure to move ahead along these lines will limit the public and private return that can be realized from more adequate investment in irrigation and more effective programs of disease and pest control.

PRODUCTIVITY AND EFFICIENCY IN RICE PRODUCTION

Technological innovations must at some point prior to widespread adoption meet the test of producing increased income to individual farmers. In a low wage rate economy, such as that characteristic of most areas of southeast Asia, this test imposes quite different burdens on research workers than in economies such as those of the United States and Western Europe where labor has long been in short supply, or in Japan where the farm labor force has been declining.

Labor intensity and cultural practices and yields

Until recently the Philippines has had a rather favorable relationship between area cultivated and population. In spite of relatively high rates of population growth, the area cultivated per person in total population rose until the late 1930's and remained relatively stable until the late 1950's. In recent years, however, the long-term rising trend in total cultivated area has leveled off,

Fig. 6. Long-term trend of area cultivated per person in the total population (Philippines, 1902/03 to 1963/64).

and cultivated area per person in the total population has begun to decline. It may be that the decade between 1960 and 1970 will be viewed by historians as the period of the closing of the land frontier in Philippine agriculture (Fig. 6).

In recent years, there has been also a decline in cultivated land per farm and per farm worker. It seems clear that over the next several decades land area per worker in Philippine agriculture will decline. An attempt is being made, therefore, to explore the implications for rice yields of increasing labor in-

tensity. It is hypothesized that there are substantial interactions between labor use and the productivity of other inputs such as fertilizer. Research on this problem involves both experimental and survey phases.

The experimental results showed that there was a yield response to low levels of labor input. During the 1964 and 1965 wet seasons, on both fertilized and unfertilized plots with variety BPI-76, yields increased when labor input was increased from 1/4 to 1 man/ha. Assuming a price of ₱12/cavan of rough rice, and a labor wage of ₱3.50/day, the

TABLE 3. 1965 dry season yields (kg/ha) at four labor levels and four nitrogen levels, variety Peta, 25 x 25 cm.

Labor rate (men/ha)	kg/ha N				Mean
	0	40	80	100	
1/2	3964.3	5178.0	5088.5	4991.0	4805.5
1	5746.5	5143.5	5290.0	5047.0	5306.8
1 1/2	5008.0	4911.5	5596.0	4784.5	5075.0
2	4926.0	5509.0	6118.5	4735.5	5322.3
Mean	4911.3	5185.5	5523.3	4889.5	5127.4

TABLE 4. 1964 dry season yields (cav/ha)^a of selected farms in Calauan, Laguna, variety Intan.

Labor (men/ha)	kg/ha N			Mean
	15-29	30-44	45 and above	
0.25-0.49		109.51	124.25	116.88
0.50-0.74	104.10	109.78	106.34	106.74
0.75-0.99		86.30		86.30
1.00	109.58 ^b	58.26		92.47
1.50	43.27			43.27
2.00		117.01		117.01
3.00	64.48			64.48
Mean	86.20	96.17	115.29	95.21

^a Based on after-harvest production measured in cavans. 1 cavan at 14% MC = 40.19 kg.

^b Two farms.

Fig. 7. Rice yields at different labor input levels, wet season, BPI-76, 30 x 30 cm.

optimum labor force was estimated from the 1965 wet season data at 0.66 man/ha and 0.69 man/ha for unfertilized and fertilized (40 kg/ha N) rice respectively. The optimum force in the 1964 wet season was only 0.22 man/ha due to low yields caused by adverse weather (Fig. 7).

The 1965 dry season experiment with the variety Peta included four nitrogen and four labor levels. Mean yields showed a positive yield response to nitrogen up to 80 kg/ha and a suggestive labor effect at low levels (Table 3).

The experimental results show that increasing labor beyond 1 man/ha does

not significantly increase yields. The higher yield level at 40 kg/ha N during the wet season, and increasing mean yields up to 80 kg/ha N during the dry season, suggests a positive response to fertilizer and a possible favorable interaction between labor and fertilizer. The interaction is more clearly suggested by increasing yields at 80 kg/ha N from 1/2 to 2 men/ha.

During 1965, survey data were collected from 12 farms. In the dry season the variety Intan responded to nitrogen (Table 4) but the labor intensity was not meaningfully related to yield, possibly because the amount of fertilizer used and the availability of operating capital was related to size of farm. The following relationships were established:

$$Y = 356.6 N^{.01843} L^{-.48329} \quad r = 0.506$$

$$N = 11.81 + 9.40 A \quad r = 0.686$$

$$L = 2.24 - 0.48 A \quad r = 0.677$$

where:

Y = yield per hectare

N = kg/ha N

L = potential labor intensity (men/ha)

A = farm size (hectares)

In the 1965 wet season the yield of the variety Malagkit responded to increased labor (Fig. 8). No fertilizers and little insecticide were applied.

Results on the farms surveyed generally agreed with those from the experiments. The availability of fertilizers and other short-run inputs appear to affect the relationship between labor and yield.

Fig. 8. 1965 wet season yields of selected farms in Calauan, Laguna, variety malagkit, 0 N fertilizer.

RICE SUPPLY, DEMAND, AND PRICE BEHAVIOR

Rice and corn occupy a dominant position among the agricultural commodities produced for domestic consumption in the Philippines. Together they account for approximately 5 of the 8 million hectares of cropland harvested annually. The traditional export crops—primarily coconuts, sugar and tobacco—account for another 2 million hectares, and minor crops such as bananas, root crops and others account for approximately 1 million hectares. In addition to absorbing a major share of the resources devoted to agricultural production, rice and corn price policy represents a major administrative and legislative concern.

During the year an attempt was made to estimate statistical supply and market surplus relations for rice and corn for major geographic regions of the Philippines using time series data. The basic output response function utilized for both rice and corn was $Q^*_t = f(P^*_t, F^*_t, A^*_t, T^*_t)$. Where Q^*_t is the desired output during production period t , P^*_t is the expected harvest price of the crop, F^*_t is an index of expected prices of inputs, A^*_t is an index of the expected prices of competing crops, and T^*_t is a measure of the expected yield of

Economics of varietal choice

In choosing among available varieties, farmers employ a number of criteria. These may include such factors as the yield potential, susceptibility to pests and disease, variability of yield under different weather conditions, and others. Similarly, in formulating breeding objectives, the plant breeder gives either implicit or explicit importance to the various characteristics which he may attempt to incorporate in the rice plant. During the year a project was designed to explore the possibility of using game theory techniques to enable the breeder to select an appropriate strategy, or the farmer to select a suitable variety. The preliminary investigation was conducted by a scholar from Korea as a basis for further investigation in Korea.

rice or corn relative to alternative crops. Two types of linear models were used for estimation purposes: simple regression models and distributed lag adjustment regression models. Estimates were made of the price elasticities of hectareage, that is, the percentage change in hectareage resulting from a 1-percent change in price, derived from the estimated statistical supply functions.

For rice, short-run elasticities typically fall in the .10 to .30 range (Ilocos, Southern Tagalog, Eastern Visayas, and Southern and Western Mindanao). However, in the two regions with the largest relative shares of irrigated land, Central Luzon (which produces more rice than any other region) and Bicol, elasticities in the .40 to .60 range were obtained. The elasticity in Western Visayas, the third largest producing region, is apparently above .60. Supply elasticities in Cagayan and in Northern and Eastern Mindanao could not be shown to be positive under any criteria.

For corn, short-run elasticities from simple models and distributed lag models are in relatively close agreement. In Ilocos the simple elasticities were not

significantly different from zero. In the Cagayan Valley, Bicol, and Southern and Western Mindanao, the corn elasticities fell in the .10 to .30 range. Higher hectareage supply elasticities were obtained in Southern Tagalog, Eastern Visayas, and Western Visayas. The Southern Tagalog region is a major center of commercial livestock production for the Manila market. The two Visayan regions are the major areas where corn is used for direct food consumption. Supply elasticities in Central Luzon and in Northern and Eastern Mindanao could not be shown to be positive under any standards.

It appears, therefore, that (a) the supply elasticity for corn is highest in areas dominated by strong commercial markets, and (b) the supply elasticity for rice is highest in areas with strong commercial markets and/or relatively extensive irrigation development. The short-run hectareage response elasticities for rice are usually larger than those for corn.

The price elasticity estimates for rice and corn in the Philippines are quite comparable with estimates obtained from the same crops and for other subsistence crops in other Asian countries. And in those regions where production of rice and corn is highly market oriented, Philippine rice and corn producers are at least as responsive to price changes as producers of commercial crops in other Asian countries.

It can be shown mathematically that the price elasticity of hectareage is a lower limit to the price elasticity of output, provided that yield does not respond inversely to price changes. A lower estimate of the elasticity of the market surplus (that is, the amount of rice entering commercial channels) with respect to price can be obtained by multiplying the price elasticity of hectareage by the average marketed proportion. The marketed proportions among Philippine regions range from .37 to .65. Therefore, the marketed surplus elasticities are at least 1.5 to 2.5 times as large as the output elasticities.

The supply elasticity data reported in this paper indicates that Philippine rice and corn farmers are reasonably responsive to changes in the price of rice and corn relative to each other and to other commodities, even in the short-run. This implies that changes in relative prices are effective in determining the allocation of land among the several agricultural commodities. It seems quite clear, for example, that the declining price of rice relative to corn during the period prior to 1959/60 was associated with the more rapid increase in the hectareage devoted to corn than to rice. In recent years the decline in area devoted to both rice and corn and the rise in commercial crop area is clearly related to the rapid increase in the price of sugar and copra relative to rice and corn prices. It also indicates that price support, subsidy or import programs, undertaken with other objectives, to reduce prices to consumers for example, are rather rapidly reflected in shifts in production. An analysis of marketing margins indicates that price changes at one level of the marketing system are typically reflected rather rapidly and with little changes in the marketing margin at other levels.

While prices of rice and corn in the Philippines have apparently been fairly efficient in their resource allocation function, there is little evidence to indicate that price changes represent an effective device for influencing aggregate agricultural output. This is consistent with our findings in the section on "Research on Sources of Output Growth" that, at present, most yield variations are primarily a reflection of environmental differences rather than differences in varieties or cultural practices which might be expected to respond to market incentives.

As additional irrigated land becomes available and as new technical inputs are introduced into production, it will be necessary, of course, to reevaluate this conclusion. Clearly, rapid growth in productivity is not likely until farmers exhibit both a hectareage and a yield response to changing relative prices.

INSTITUTIONAL FACTORS IN AGRICULTURAL DEVELOPMENT

In 1964, data was presented which indicated that share tenure acts to inhibit adoption of output-increasing innovations, such as the use of higher levels of fertilizer. Further analysis of experimental data indicates that share tenure may actually increase incentives to adopt cost-reducing innovations particularly when the landlord shares part of the cost, as in many areas in the Philippines.

During 1965 it was possible to test the relationships between tenure and productivity utilizing data from five barrios in the province of Bulacan. The data used in this test was collected by the UPCA Department of Agricultural Information and Communications under the direction of Dr. Gloria Feliciano.

In addition to a positive test of the productivity hypotheses, the Bulacan data permit a test of the implications of the theory of the firm regarding the effect of share and fixed rent lease tenure systems for the use of purchased technical inputs and family labor. More specifically it permits a test of the following three hypotheses:

(a) Farms operated under lease tenure achieve higher levels of land productivity (kilograms of rough rice per hectare) and higher levels of labor productivity (kilograms of rough rice per day of available family labor) than farms operated under share tenure.

(b) A higher percentage of farms operated under lease tenure use purchased technical inputs (fertilizer and insecticides) than of farms operated under share tenure.

(c) A higher percentage of the family labor potentially available for rice production is employed off the farm on farms operated under share than under lease tenure.

The data collected from all five barrios appear consistent with the first two hypotheses. For the entire group of farms both land and labor productivity is higher on lease tenure than on share tenure farms. A higher percentage of lease than share tenure farms use fertilizer and insecticides. However, a higher percentage of the labor force on lease tenure farms work off farm than on share tenure farms.

Examination of the data by size of farm indicates, however, that on the smaller-size farms (2 ha and less) share tenants typically achieve higher productivity levels than lease tenants. Furthermore, on the smallest size farms (1 ha and less) a higher proportion of share than of lease tenants use fertilizer and insecticides. It is apparent, therefore, that the first two hypotheses are confirmed, in the aggregate, primarily because of the differential impact of tenure on resource use and productivity on the larger-size farms. It was also noted that the data for the larger-size farms was consistent with the third hypothesis.

Data were examined separately for the two barrios, Santol and Balatong B, which account for a relatively high percentage of all lease tenants in the five barrios. The area in which the two barrios are located appears relatively homogeneous with respect to soil and irrigation. There are, however, other major differences between the two barrios. Barrio Balatong B appears to be a more traditional community than Barrio Santol. It is characterized by less adequate communication (poorer roads, fewer radios), less contact outside the community (through extension workers, non-farm employment), more traditional attitudes toward authority, lower level of education, an older age distribution, and a consumption rather than production value orientation. These characteristics are based on tabulated data from the Bulacan survey.

The individual barrio comparisons indicated that average land and labor productivity is higher on lease tenure than share tenure farms in Barrio Balatong B but not in Barrio Santol. In both barrios, however, lease tenants typically operate larger farms and obtain higher yields on these larger farms than share tenants. There is a strong negative relationship between size of farm and both land and labor productivity on share tenure farms in both barrios.

No clear-cut relationships are indicated between tenure, farm size, and the use of purchased inputs. Fertilizer and insecticides are used by a relatively high

percentage of both share and lease tenants in Barrio Santol, and by a relatively low percentage in Barrio Balatong B.

A higher percentage of share tenants than of lease tenants are engaged in off-farm work in both barrios. However, the percentage for both tenure classes is relatively high in Barrio Santol and low in Barrio Balatong B.

The most striking conclusion to emerge from the inter-barrio comparisons is that differences in productivity between barrios are substantially greater than the intra-barrio differences in productivity associated with tenure.

The test indicated two major exceptions to the hypothesized relationships: (a) In the smaller-size ranges, share tenure farms appeared to achieve higher levels of productivity and to use higher levels of purchased inputs than owner-operated or lease tenure farms; (b) Productivity differences between tenure classes were smaller in a barrio characterized by high off-farm employment opportunity than in a barrio with few off-farm employment opportunities.

A major implication of the data presented in this section is that the first step in achieving greater precision in predicting the productivity implications of changes in land tenure arrangements is to reject the assumption that there

is any single optimum land tenure system. It seems reasonable to hypothesize that the relationship between land tenure and productivity varies (a) with the extent of commercial (or subsistence) production, (b) with the level, rate and direction of technological development, and (c) with the extent of diffusion (or concentration) of political and economic power.

These conclusions should not be interpreted to imply the desirability of waiting to implement land tenure reform policies, particularly a shift from share to fixed rent lease tenure, until the relatively late "stage" of a nation's economic development. Share tenure clearly encourages inefficient use of the tenant labor relatively early in the development process — probably as soon as the product market becomes generally monetized. It acts as a tax on the adoption of output-increasing technology — dampening tenant's incentives to adopt output-increasing technology embodied in current inputs, and the landowner's incentive to increase output with new capital equipment. Finally, the strong negative relationship between farm size and productivity on farms operated by share tenants acts as an incentive for the landowner to keep the size of unit operated by the tenant small.

COOPERATIVE PROJECT ON CORN

In cooperation with the U.P. College of Agriculture, and the Institute of Economic Development and Research, the agricultural economist assisted in a project concerned with price and

market relationships of corn. A complete account of this work will be presented in the Institute's Technical Bulletin series.

Statistics

As in past years, the Department of Statistics was concerned with the following activities: (1) consulting with research workers on the problem of design and analysis of experiments and surveys, and extending computational services in the analysis of data, (2) providing instruction on statistical techniques with special reference to their applications to agricultural research, and (3) conducting theoretical and experimental studies on statistical problems related to rice research.

CONSULTATION AND COMPUTATION SERVICE

The department participated in 1,392 individual or group consultations with the Institute staff and scholars, and with research workers from the University of the Philippines College of Agriculture, Philippines' Bureau of Plant

Industry, and Thailand's Rice Department. A total of 1,167 analyses was performed, with an average of 12 variables, and an average sample size of 78 observations.

INSTRUCTION

The statistician taught two courses in statistics for graduate students at the UPCA. Part I of a manuscript entitled, "Statistics in Rice Research," which served as basic instructional material for these courses and as a general ref-

erence for agricultural research workers, was revised and will soon be ready for publication. Upon request, more than 300 copies of the manuscript were distributed to agricultural research workers in 14 countries.

STUDIES OF STATISTICAL PROBLEMS

Statistical studies related to rice research are aimed at giving research workers statistical tools to help them interpret the results obtained, not only in the experimental fields, but also in farmers' fields.

This report contains the consolidated results of studies on sample and plot size, number of replications, and sampling methods appropriate for examining the incidence of stem borers, other insect pests, and viruses. Multivariate models, which have now been introduced into rice research, are also described.

Size of sample

In 1964, a linear relationship between the standard deviation (s) and the mean ($\bar{x}$) was established for 22 rice plant characteristics with the use of data from at least two seasons. Pooled estimates within season estimates for the 22 characteristics were utilized to determine the size of sample (n) needed under three different assumptions. These techniques were applied to 33 further characteristics during 1965. The results may be used by research workers for increased precision of experimentation.

Eating quality. Results on the variability of judges in taste panel tests are given in Table 1 for six eating quality characteristics. The initial estimates of

$cv(X)$ in percent are given for the overall mean of a given characteristic. The consistency or the interaction of the judges with the nature of the rice samples is generally measured by the sign of the slope. The five judges appear to be consistent in this regard for aroma in both hot and warm samples. The results clearly indicate how the panel judges reacted to changes in the material.

The binomial distribution was used to test the ability of candidates to discriminate different levels of eating qualities of rice. Each candidate was requested to discriminate between two even and one odd samples ($P=1/3$) repeated 10 times. The hypothesis was set at a minimum of $n_0=6$ correct choices of the odd sample. This framework is given in Table 2 for $P=1/4, 1/3, 2/5$ and $3/5$. Note that one can increase the sensitivity of the experiment by changes in its structure such as the number of replications and the level of P .

Pooled estimates. Method I. The size of sample (n) is derived from the simple relationship,

$$n = [cv(X) \% / cv(\bar{x}) \%]^2$$

where

$$cv(X) \% = (s/x) 100 \%$$

$cv(\bar{x}) \%$ is the desired precision of the estimator, $\bar{x}$,

s and $\bar{x}$ are pooled estimates obtained from 1962 to 1965.

There are two forms of linear relationship between the standard deviation (s) and the mean ($\bar{x}$). One form is characterized by grain yield per plant in grams where the cv(X) ranges from 12 to 66 percent. This result implies that the value of cv(X) will vary with the mean ($\bar{x}$). Other characteristics exhibited a constant cv(X). These relationships are shown in Fig. 1 for grain yield, plant height, tiller number and lodging index. Detailed results of these studies are given in Tables 3, 4, and 5 for between plants, within plants and between composites, respectively.

As indicated in Tables 1, 3, 4, and 5, the range of cv(X) is from 1 to 50 percent, and the precision of sampling is given at levels of cv($\bar{x}$) = 5 or 10 percent. From these results, Table 6 was constructed as guide in decision-making on the size of sample needed for a given level of precision.

Assume that an experiment gave the following information:

mean grain yield ($\bar{x}$) per plant
 = 32.9 g
 standard deviation (s)
 = 7.6 g at 6 degrees of freedom

If the required precision [cv($\bar{x}$)] to be detected in the new experiment is 5 percent, then

$$n = [cv(X) \% / cv(\bar{x}) \%]^2 = (23/5)^2 = 21 \text{ plants}$$

where

cv(X) is computed as $(7.6/32.9)100\%$
 = 23%.

A sample of 21 plants will be needed in order to attain a 5 percent level of precision of the new experiment. The cv(X) from Fig. 1 will also give 23 percent.

Method II. This method specifies the width of the true difference (d) and a

TABLE 1. Variability of judges for six eating quality characteristics of rice. (Lowland)

Type of sample	Eating quality	Judge number	Relationship	cv(X) %
Hot	1) Aroma	1	s = 0.38 + .1623 $\bar{x}$	28
		2	s = 1.57 - .1272 $\bar{x}$	34
		3	s = 1.90 - .2387 $\bar{x}$	15
		4	s = 0.96 + .0665 $\bar{x}$	46
		5	s = 2.66 - .8010 $\bar{x}$	30
	2) Flavor	1	s = -2.40 + .2690 $\bar{x}$	18
		2	s = 1.10 - .0423 $\bar{x}$	20
		3	s = 0.66 - .0046 $\bar{x}$	12
		4	s = 1.33 - .1160 $\bar{x}$	37
		5	s = 1.10	57
	3) Cohesiveness	1	s = 0.61 + .0225 $\bar{x}$	20
		2	s = 0.62 + .0397 $\bar{x}$	27
		3	s = 4.52 - .8482 $\bar{x}$	22
		4	s = 0.48 + .0774 $\bar{x}$	22
		5	s = 1.46 - .1888 $\bar{x}$	24
	4) Tenderness	1	s = -0.02 + .1368 $\bar{x}$	13
		2	s = 1.67 - .1266 $\bar{x}$	19
		3	s = 0.66 + .0323 $\bar{x}$	14
		4	s = 1.17 - .1284 $\bar{x}$	18
		5	s = 0.81 - .0623 $\bar{x}$	13
	5) Gloss	1	s = -0.38 + .6198 $\bar{x}$	40
		2	s = -1.30 + .4717 $\bar{x}$	13
		3	s = 2.46 - .3862 $\bar{x}$	21
		4	s = 0.61 + .1132 $\bar{x}$	24
		5	s = 1.15 - .0826 $\bar{x}$	25
6) Color	1	s = -0.28 + .4845 $\bar{x}$	31	
	2	s = 0.53 + .3383 $\bar{x}$	54	
	3	s = -1.19 + .8097 $\bar{x}$	40	
	4	s = 0.49 + .1549 $\bar{x}$	33	
	5	s = 0.57 + .0472 $\bar{x}$	37	

TABLE 1. Variability of judges... (continued)

Type of sample	Eating quality	Judge number	Relationship	cv(X) %
<i>Cold</i>	1) Aroma	1	s = 0.63 + .2361 $\bar{x}$	60
		2	s = 1.06 - .1615 $\bar{x}$	40
		3	s = 2.35 - .4044 $\bar{x}$	8
		4	s = 0.28 + .3510 $\bar{x}$	48
		5	s = 1.87 - .4231 $\bar{x}$	39
	2) Flavor	1	s = 0.41 + .0964 $\bar{x}$	21
		2	s = 0.49 + .0363 $\bar{x}$	17
		3	s = 1.56 - .2208 $\bar{x}$	11
		4	s = 1.66 - .2870 $\bar{x}$	40
		5	s = 4.39 - 1.3750 $\bar{x}$	31
	3) Cohesiveness	1	s = 1.59 - 0.2232 $\bar{x}$	29
		2	s = 0.59 + .0221 $\bar{x}$	22
		3	s = 2.72 - .5311 $\bar{x}$	12
		4	s = 1.11 - .0384 $\bar{x}$	28
		5	s = 1.12 - .0572 $\bar{x}$	27
	4) Tenderness	1	s = 1.83 - .2233 $\bar{x}$	30
		2	s = 0.60 + .0330 $\bar{x}$	17
		3	s = 0.26 + .0642 $\bar{x}$	11
		4	s = 1.12 - .0128 $\bar{x}$	32
		5	s = 0.24 + .1318 $\bar{x}$	19
	5) Gloss	1	s = -0.25 + .6351 $\bar{x}$	49
		2	s = 0.60 - .0183 $\bar{x}$	14
		3	s = -0.56 + .2983 $\bar{x}$	15
		4	s = -0.07 + .2607 $\bar{x}$	24
		5	s = 1.78 - .2777 $\bar{x}$	32
6) Color	1	s = -0.59 + .8132 $\bar{x}$	44	
	2	s = 0.36 + .0402 $\bar{x}$	18	
	3	s = 0.40 + .0463 $\bar{x}$	17	
	4	s = 0.83 + .0286 $\bar{x}$	36	
	5	s = .2493 $\bar{x}$	25	

probability of 50 percent that the (1- α) confidence interval will be no wider than 2d. The solution for the sample size is

$$n \geq t^2_{(\alpha, \infty)} s^2/d^2$$

where

$t_{(\alpha, \infty)}$ is the tabular 't' value at α with infinite degrees of freedom,

s^2 is the sample variance and s is expressed as a percent of the mean,

and

d is the true difference or width of the interval and is expressed as a percent of the mean.

The solution for (n) will require an iteration procedure. Generally, it requires two or three iterations before the solution converges to a fixed value. The results are given in Table 7 for d=5

and 10 percent of the mean, cv(X) at 1 to 50 percent, and $\alpha = .01$ and $.05$.

With the simple example given in Method I, it is now desired to use a 95 percent (1- α) confidence interval and a width of the true difference (d) is specified to be 10 percent of the mean. The first iteration will use $n = \infty$. Thus,

$$\begin{aligned} n &\geq t^2_{(\alpha, \infty)} [cv(X) \%/d]^2 / d^2 \\ &\geq (1.96)^2 (23)^2 / (10)^2 \\ &\geq 20 \text{ plants.} \end{aligned}$$

The second iteration will use $n = 20$ and $(n - 1) = 19$. Our solution is

$$\begin{aligned} n &\geq t^2_{(.05, 19)} (23)^2 / (10)^2 \\ &\geq (2.09)^2 (23)^2 / (10)^2 \\ &\geq 23 \text{ plants.} \end{aligned}$$

The third iteration will also give $n \geq 23$ plants. This sample size may be interpolated from the last column of Table 7.

With $n \geq 23$, the probability is 50 percent that the 95 percent confidence interval will not exceed 2d.

Fig. 1. Determination of sample size (n) when the mean range ($\bar{x}$) per plant and the coefficient of variation [cv(X)] in percent of grain yield, plant height, tiller number and lodging index are known, IRRI, 1965.

Method III. This is an improvement over Method II. As before, there is available an estimate of variance (s^2) based on (δ) degrees of freedom. The

problem is to estimate the sample size (n) with a probability ($1 - \beta$) that the ($1 - \alpha$) confidence interval for the mean will be no wider than $2d$.

A formula suitable for computational purposes is written as

$$d^2/s^2 = t^2 (\alpha; n-1) F_{(\beta; n-1, \delta)} / n.$$

Again, this method will require an iteration procedure in order to solve for (n). The required iteration is done on the right member of the equation since the left side is fixed. In this form,

d , s^2 and $t_{(\alpha; n-1)}$ are as defined in Method II,

while

$F_{(\beta; n-1, \delta)}$ is the F value at the β probability level with (n-1) and δ degrees of freedom.

In this approach, the probability ($1 - \beta$) is not fixed at 50 percent but may be at any probability level desired. The results using this method are shown in Table 8 with $d=5$ and 10 percent, cv(X) at 1 to 50 percent, $\beta = .10, .25$, and $\alpha = .01$ and $.05$.

The problem in the example is to determine the sample size (n) such that the probability ($1 - \beta$) is 90 percent that 95 percent ($1 - \alpha$) confidence interval will not exceed $2d$. The available information is as follows:

$\bar{x} = 32.9$ g $d = 10$ percent of 32.9 g
 $s = 7.6$ g $\beta = .10$
 $\delta = 6$ d.f. $\alpha = .05$

The formula is

$$d^2/s^2 = [t^2_{(.05; n-1)} F_{(.10; (n-1), 6)}] / n.$$

TABLE 2. The binomial distribution as framework in testing the ability of candidates to discriminate levels of eating qualities of rice.

No. of correct choices	P = 1/4		P = 1/3		P = 2/5		P = 3/5	
	P(w) ^a	AcP(w) ^b	P(w)	AcP(w)	P(w)	AcP(w)	P(w)	AcP(w)
10	.00000	—	.00002	.00002	.00010	.00010	.00605	.00605
9	.00003	.00003	.00034	.00036	.00157	.00167	.04031	.04636
8	.00039	.00042	.00305	.00341	.01062	.01229	.12093	.16729
7	.0031	.0035	.0163	.0197	.0425	.0548	.2145	.3823
6	.0162	.0197	.0569	.0766	.1115	.1662	.2508	.6331
5	.0584	.0781	.1366	.2131	.2007	.3669	.2007	.8338
4	.1460	.2241	.2276	.4407	.2508	.6177	.1115	.9452
3	.2503	.4744	.2601	.7009	.2150	.8327	.0425	.9877
2	.2816	.7560	.1951	.8960	.1209	.9536	.0106	.9983
1	.1877	.9437	.0867	.9827	.0403	.9940	.0016	.9999
0	.0563	1.0000	.0173	1.0000	.0061	1.0000	.0001	1.0000

^a $P(w) = \left[\frac{n}{w} \right] P^w Q^{n-w}$

^b AcP(w) = accumulated P(w)

TABLE 3. Form of equation for (s) and coefficient of variation [cv(X)] in percentage by characteristics, between plants, IRRI, 1965.^a

Characteristics	Relationship between s and $\bar{x}$	Coefficient of variation [cv(X) %]
1. Grain yield per plant (g)	$s = 3.38 + 0.10\bar{x}$	12-66
2. Plant height at harvest (cm)	$s = 0.04\bar{x}$	4
3. Seedling height (cm)	$s = 1.99$	7-20
4. Panicle length (cm)	$s = 0.08\bar{x}$	8
5. Culm diameter of 1st basal internode (mm) [BI ₁]		
d ₁ (outer diameter)	$s = 0.08\bar{x}$	8
d ₂ (inner diameter)	$s = 0.09\bar{x}$	9
6. Culm diameter of 2nd basal internode (mm) [BI ₂]		
d ₁ (outer diameter)	$s = 0.09\bar{x}$	9
d ₂ (inner diameter)	$s = 0.10\bar{x}$	10
7. Length of blade (cm)	$s = 0.10\bar{x}$	10
8. Width of blade (mm)	$s = 0.11\bar{x}$	11
9. Slenderness ratio	$s = 51 + 0.07\bar{x}$	13-33
10. Length of ligule (mm)	$s = 1.31 + 0.10\bar{x}$	13-25
11. Number of tillers	$s = 0.16\bar{x}$	16
12. Number of panicles	$s = 0.17\bar{x}$	17
13. Sterility (percent)	$s = 0.20\bar{x}$	20
14. Weight of straw (g)	$s = 0.23\bar{x}$	23
15. Culm area (sq mm)		
BI ₁	$s = 1.80 + 0.14\bar{x}$	22-40
BI ₂	$s = 1.09 + 0.20\bar{x}$	24-47
16. Internode length (cm)		
BI ₁	$s = 0.35\bar{x}$	35
BI ₂	$s = 0.32\bar{x}$	32
17. Lodging index	$s = 0.39\bar{x}$	39
18. Culm length (cm)	$s = 3.60 + 0.04\bar{x}$	6-14
19. Number of outside vascular bundles	$s = 0.07\bar{x}$	7
20. Number of inside vascular bundles	$s = 0.07\bar{x}$	7
21. Length of outer glumes (mm)	$s = 0.48$	8-22
22. Total number of spikelets	$s = 0.09\bar{x}$	9
23. Number of functional sheets	$s = 0.65 + 0.05\bar{x}$	15-64
24. Sclerified tissues (percent)	$s = 0.48\bar{x}$	48

^a Data used from two or more seasons.

Starting at $n=31$

$$(3.3)^2 / (7.6)^2 = (2.04)^2 (2.80) / 31$$

$$0.19 \neq 0.51.$$

With $n=59$, the right-hand side of the equation

$$= (2.00)^2 (2.76) / 59$$

$$= 0.19.$$

This says that, if we draw a sample of 59 plants, the probability is 90 percent that the 95 percent confidence interval will be less than or equal to 6.6 grams (2d) in width. The solution $n=59$ may be interpolated from the results given in column 6, Table 8.

Comparing $n=23$ plants in II and $n=59$ plants in III, the latter is considerably greater than 23. Method II sets

$F=1$ in III. The solution corresponds to a β of 0.50. With a sample of 23 plants, there is only a 50-50 chance that the 95 percent confidence interval will be less than 6.6 grams in width.

Sub-sampling within the plant. Precision of estimates of characteristics of the rice plant is governed by the number of plants and the number of sub-units in the plant if the characteristic is measured on the plant basis. Suppose we are interested in the length of panicle. The problem will be to sample the appropriate number of plants and also the number of panicles within each plant. Detailed results of the within-plant variability for 13 characteristics

TABLE 4. Form of equation for (s) and coefficient of variation [cv(X)] in percentage by characteristics, within plants, IRRI, 1965.^a

Characteristics	Relationship between s and $\bar{x}$	Coefficient of variation [cv(X) %]
1. Number of spikelets per panicle	$s = 0.08\bar{x}$	8
2. Number of grains per panicle	$s = 0.10\bar{x}$	10
3. Anther length (mm)	$s = 0.09\bar{x}^b$	9
4. Number of cells in sclerenchyma	$s = 0.11\bar{x}$	11
5. Thickness of sclerenchyma (mm)	$s = 0.11\bar{x}$	11
6. Number of filled spikelets	$s = 0.14\bar{x}$	14
7. Culm thickness (mm)	$s = 0.14\bar{x}$	14
8. Number of air spaces	$s = 0.15\bar{x}$	15
9. Tiller weight (g)	$s = 0.17\bar{x}$	17
10. Number of empty spikelets	$s = 0.20\bar{x}$	20
11. Awn length (cm)	$s = 0.03 + 0.26\bar{x}^b$	26-34
12. Number of spikelets per panicle	$s = 0.08\bar{x}$	8
13. Number of grains per panicle	$s = 0.10\bar{x}$	10

^a Data used from two or more seasons unless specified.

^b One season.

TABLE 5. Form of equation for (s) and coefficient of variation [cv(X)] in percentage by characteristics, between composites or determinations within composites, IRRI, 1965.^a

Characteristics	Relationship between s and $\bar{x}$	Coefficient of variation [cv(X) %]
1. Length of grain (mm)	$s = 0.04\bar{x}$	4
2. Width of grain (mm)	$s = 0.05\bar{x}$	5
3. Breaking strength (g/mm ²)		
BI ₁	$s = 0.35\bar{x}$	35
BI ₂	$s = 0.28\bar{x}$	28
4. Alkali test		
Spreading	$s = 0.03\bar{x}$	3
Clearing	$s = 0.05\bar{x}$	5
5. Protein (percent)	$s = 0.01\bar{x}$	1
6. Amylose (percent)	$s = 0.02\bar{x}$	2
7. Ash (percent)	$s = 0.02\bar{x}$	2
8. Pentosans (percent)	$s = 0.15\bar{x}$	15
9. Iodine blue value	$s = 0.02\bar{x}$	2
10. Crude fiber (percent)		
Rough rice	$s = 0.01\bar{x}$	1
Brown rice	$s = 0.03\bar{x}$	3
Polished rice	$s = 0.09\bar{x}$	9
11. Crude fat (percent)		
Rough rice	$s = 0.01\bar{x}$	1
Brown rice	$s = 0.01\bar{x}$	1
Polished rice	$s = 0.10\bar{x}$	10
12. Breaking hardness (kg)	$s = 0.19 + 0.15\bar{x}^b$	17-21
13. Crushing hardness (kg)	$s = 0.22\bar{x}^b$	22
14. Hulls (percent)	$s = 0.01\bar{x}^b$	1
15. Head rice (percent)	$s = 0.01\bar{x}^b$	1
16. Total milled rice (percent)	$s = 0.01\bar{x}^b$	1
17. Bran (percent)	$s = 0.06\bar{x}^b$	6
18. Caryop size (mm)	$s = 0.04\bar{x}$	4
19. Embryo size (mm)	$s = 0.07\bar{x}^b$	7

^a Data from two or more seasons unless specified.

^b One season.

TABLE 6. Size of sample (n) needed for a desired percentage of standard error [$cv(\bar{x}) = 5, 10$ percent] depending on the percentage standard deviation of a unit [$cv(X) \%$], IRRI, 1965.

[Use $cv(X) \%$ in Tables 1, 3, 4 and 5]

$cv(X) \%$	$cv(\bar{x}) \%$		$cv(X) \%$	$cv(\bar{x}) \%$	
	5	10		5	10
2	1	1	26	27	7
4	1	1	27	31	8
6	1	1	30	36	9
8	3	1	32	41	10
10	4	1	34	46	12
12	6	1	36	52	13
14	8	2	38	58	14
16	10	3	40	64	16
18	13	3	42	71	18
20	16	4	44	77	19
22	19	5	46	85	21
24	24	6	48	92	23

The least number of samples taken is always two in order to have an estimate of variance.

TABLE 7. Size of sample (n) required for specified difference (d) and significance level (α) when the coefficient of variation [$cv(X)$] in percent is known, IRRI, 1965.

[Use $cv(X) \%$ in Tables 1,3,4 and 5]

$cv(X) \%$	d = 5 percent		d = 10 percent	
	$\alpha = .01$	$\alpha = .05$	$\alpha = .01$	$\alpha = .05$
2	1	1	1	1
4	4	2	1	1
6	10	6	2	1
8	17	10	4	2
10	26	15	7	4
12	38	22	10	6
14	52	30	13	6
16	67	39	17	10
18	86	50	12	12
20	106	61	26	15
22	128	74	32	19
24	152	89	38	23
26	179	104	45	26
28	207	120	52	30
30	238	138	59	35
32	271	157	68	39
34	305	178	76	44
36	342	199	86	50
38	381	222	95	55
40	444	246	111	61
42	488	271	122	68
44	535	297	134	74
46	584	325	146	81
48	634	354	159	89
50	687	384	174	96

The least number of samples taken is always two in order to have an estimate of variance.

are given in Table 4. Two plants were located at random from each plot and within each plant the results in Tables 4, 6, 7 or 8 were applied. As more information is obtained, the component of variance approach will be utilized.

Number of replications in field experiments

Variations among experimental data are caused not only by the effect of treatments, but also by the extraneous factors which tend to mask the effect of treatments. If these variations, commonly called experimental errors are controlled, precision is increased and conclusions made more definite. Experimental accuracy is improved by: (a) increasing the size of the experiment either by providing more replicates or more treatments or both; (b) refinement of the experimental techniques; and (c) correct handling of the experimental material through skillful selection and grouping. Here we are concerned with first of these possibilities; the last two are more or less the responsibility of the researcher.

From the results of studies in 1964 on uniformity data, the size of plot recommended was between 2 to 5 sq m. This range can be increased by as much as four times, depending on the cultural or management requirements of the exper-

TABLE 8. Size of sample (n) required for specified difference (d), significance level (α) and width coefficient (β) when the coefficient of variation [cv(X)] in percent is known, IRRI, 1965.

[Use cv(X) in Tables 1, 3, 4 and 5]

cv(X) %	d=5 percent of mean ($\bar{x}$)				d=10 percent of mean ($\bar{x}$)			
	$\beta = .10$	$\beta = .10$	$\beta = .25$	$\beta = .25$	$\beta = .10$	$\beta = .10$	$\beta = .25$	$\beta = .25$
	$\alpha = .05$	$\alpha = .01$	$\alpha = .05$	$\alpha = .01$	$\alpha = .05$	$\alpha = .01$	$\alpha = .05$	$\alpha = .01$
2	4	7	3	4	3	4	1	3
4	10	16	6	10	5	7	3	5
6	19	30	11	20	7	11	5	8
8	30	50	19	33	10	16	7	11
10	46	77	29	50	14	22	9	15
12	64	108	40	70	18	31	12	20
14	85	146	55	90	24	40	16	26
16	109	189	70	128	30	50	20	31
18	138	237	89	163	36	63	24	41
20	171	297	109	199	45	77	29	50
22	200	353	130	242	55	92	35	60
24	242	421	160	287	64	108	40	73
26	286	494	187	320	74	126	47	80
28	330	571	209	363	85	146	55	93
30	376	647	238	417	97	167	62	111
32	435	730	278	473	109	189	70	128
34	475	852	302	526	123	211	79	145
36	560	>1000 ^a	361	579	138	237	89	163
38	600	"	386	646	153	267	99	180
40	651	"	418	722	171	297	109	199
42	713	"	456	790	185	323	122	220
44	785	"	503	871	200	353	130	242
46	870	"	557	965	221	390	145	266
48	950	"	605	>1000	244	424	160	287
50	> 1000	"	668	"	258	452	173	315

^a implies greater than.

iment, without deviating greatly from the optimum solution. If series of experiments have been designed in such a manner as to simulate a uniformity field, then information is obtained to answer the problem of size of plot and number of replications for a given level of precision.

Techniques were applied to the maximum yield trials of the Department of Agronomy for the (I) 1964 wet season, (II) 1964-65 off-season and the (III) 1965 dry season. The analyses of variance (ANOV) for grain yield are shown in Table 9. A split-plot with sub-sampling was used for all the experiments. The ultimate size of plot is 1 x 5 m, or 5 sq m. A split-plot design with sub-sampling gives four sizes of plot and their estimates of variance. Using these four pairs of plot sizes and plot

variances, the index of soil variability (b) can be estimated by fitting the variance relation,

$$V(\bar{x}) = V_1/x^b$$

or $\log V(\bar{x}) = \log V_1 - b \log x$

where $V(\bar{x})$ is variance of the mean among plots of size x basic units, V_1 is the variance among ultimate plots of size unity (5 sq m in this case), and b is the index of soil heterogeneity which is a measure of correlation between contiguous units. If $b=1$, then the units making up the plot of size x units are not correlated and $V(\bar{x})$ decreases as x increases. If $b=0$, then $V(\bar{x})=V_1$ so that there is no gain in precision by using bigger plots. In general, b has a value between zero and one.

These relationships for the three seasons are shown in Fig. 2. The estimate of b varies seasonally; $b=0.59, 0.23,$

TABLE 9. Analysis of variance for grain yield in kilograms per hectare.^a

SV	DF ^b		MS ^b (000)		
	I	II & III	I	II	III
Total	287	383	—	—	—
Replication (R)	3	3	2,204	10,793	1,956
Variety (V)	2	3	115,176	3,660	64,128
Error (a)	6	9	1,440	1,287	1,748
Treatment (T)	11	11	2,013	11,884	3,286
(V x T)	22	33	814	710	926
Error (b)	99	132	478	306	635
Sampling error	144	192	217	80	153

^a Source of basic data: Maximum yield trials, Department of Agronomy, IRRI, 1964-65.

^b I — wet season, 1964; II — off-season, 1964-65; III — dry season, 1965.

Fig. 2. Relationships between plot size (x) and variance of the mean $[V(x)]$ for the 1964 wet season, 1964-65 off-season, and 1965 dry season.

and 0.67 for the 1964 wet season, 1964-65 off-season; and 1965 dry season, respectively. The pooled value of b for all seasons is 0.50.

In an experiment involving v treatments laid out in randomized complete

blocks, an experimenter using an ultimate plot size x , may wish to detect a true difference of magnitude d between treatment means in 80 percent ($P = .80$) of similar experiments at the $\alpha = .05$ level of significance. How many replications r should he use if from past experience he expects a given $CV(X)$ and an index of soil heterogeneity equal to b ? Or, if he uses r replications, what would be the least magnitude of d that he could expect to detect? The solutions to these questions are given by the equations,

$$r = 2(t_1 + t_2)^2 C^2 / d^2 x^b$$

or

$$d^2 = 2(t_1 + t_2)^2 C^2 / r x^b$$

where

$$t_1 = t_{\alpha, (v-1), (r-1)}$$

and

$$t_2 = t_{[2(1-P)], (v-1), (r-1)}$$

With the average b value from the three maximum yield trials and a one-tailed test (t -value at $\alpha = 0.05$), the values of the true difference d were tabulated for varying plot sizes ($x = 1, 2, 3$), number of replications ($r = 2, 3, 4, 5, 6$), number of treatments ($v = 6, 12, 18$), coefficient of variation [$CV(X) = 5\%$, 10%], and $P = .80$ and $.90$. The average results for the three seasons are shown in Figs. 3 and 4 for $P = 0.80$ and $P = 0.90$, respectively.

The importance of local control, such as the refinement of the experimental techniques and correct handling and conduct of the experiment, as reflected by the coefficient of variation (CV), is evident from Figs. 3 and 4. An experiment with a $CV(X) = 5\%$ and $r = 2$ can

Fig. 3. Relationship between the true difference (d) expressed as percent of the mean and plot size (x) for varying number of treatments (v) and replications (r), levels of $CV(X)$, $\alpha = .05$ and $P = .80$ (average of three seasons).

detect magnitudes of d as small as an experiment with $r=6$ but with a level of $CV(X)=10\%$. On the average, the range of $CV(X)$ at IRRRI is from 5 to 15 percent. It can be noted, that in terms of d , $r=2$ tends to separate itself from other r values. Smaller levels of d can be detected in experiments where r is increased to 3 or 4.

Unless the CV is high, it is not worthwhile to increase the size of plot (x) for grain yield to more than 5 square meters. The same results are indicated for the number of treatments (v). The cultural and management requirements of the treatments must be considered in relation to larger size plot. One must also consider the aspect of a "practical" difference as contrasted to a "significant" difference.

Fig. 4. Relationship between the true difference (d) expressed as percent of the mean and plot size (x) for varying number of treatments (v) and replications (r), levels of $CV(X)$, $\alpha = .05$ and $P = .90$ (average of three seasons).

Methods of estimating stem borer damage in rice fields

Stem borer incidence in a rice field is usually measured as the number of dead hearts (X_i) per hill at various stages of vegetative growth, or the number of white heads (X_i^*) per hill at maturity. Incidence may also be expressed as the ratio of $\bar{X}_i$ or $\bar{X}_i^*$ to the number of tillers in a hill (Y_i) or to the number of bearing panicles (Y_i^*) at harvest time, respectively. These ratios are expressed as

$$r_i = (X_i/Y_i) \quad \text{for number of dead hearts to total number of tillers in a hill,}$$

and

$$r_i^* = (X_i^*/Y_i^*) \quad \text{for number of white heads to total number of bearing panicles in a hill.}$$

The parameters in the population of dead hearts (X_i) and total tiller (Y_i) are

$$\bar{R} = \sum_{i=1}^N r_i / N \quad \text{as the population mean of ratios,}$$

and $\bar{Q} = (X./Y.)$ as the ratio of population totals X. and Y. or ratio of population means $\bar{X}$ and $\bar{Y}$.

Similar formula may be given for the X_i^* s and the Y_i^* 's. It is important to indicate which of the parameters $\bar{X}$, $\bar{R}$ or $\bar{Q}$ is being estimated. The variance of each of these estimators is also available. The estimator $\bar{r}$ is unbiased for $\bar{R}$.

In dealing with incidence of pests, diseases and viruses, the parameters under study must be defined precisely, so that there will be no misunderstanding on what is being measured. Previous results from experimental fields show that random sampling will result in estimators with very high sampling variability even for large n. Estimated cv(X_i)'s ranged from 100 to 200 percent.

The screening technique was compared in 1964 with the random procedure in sampling for stem borer counts. It is assumed in the application of this technique that the units, U_i with $X_i=0$ can be easily distinguished in the field. If so, these units are screened and ignored in the sampling procedure. The mean of the $X_i=0$ is zero and the variance of the mean is also zero. By definition, the variance for the population σ^2 is larger than σ^2_{nz} , the variance for the non-zero (nz) population. This relationship is described below:

$$\sigma^2_{nz} = (1/P) [\sigma^2 - (PQ)\bar{X}_{nz}^2]$$

where

$\bar{X}_{nz} = \sum_i^{PN} X_i / PN$ is the population mean of the non-zeros,

P is the proportion of N that is non-zero,

Q = (1-P) is the proportion of N that is zero,

and

$$\bar{x} = P\bar{x}_{nz}$$

Our estimator of $\bar{X}$, the population mean of hills attacked in the whole population is

$$\bar{x} = P\bar{x}_{nz} + Q \cdot 0$$

Fig. 5. Relative efficiency of the screening method compared to the non-screening method in sampling for stem borer incidence for varying values of P and CV(X_{inz}).

where

$$\bar{x}_{nz} = (\sum_{i=1}^{n^*} X_i / n^*)$$

n^* is the sample size in the non-zero population,

and

P and Q are as defined before.

The variance of $\bar{x}$ is

$$\sigma^2(\bar{x}) = P^2\sigma^2_{nz} / n^*$$

This form of $\sigma^2(\bar{x})$ indicates that there are three sources which are responsible for the reduction of the variance with screening. These sources are as follows:

- a) σ^2_{nz} will be smaller than σ^2 as indicated by the conditions given above,
- b) P^2 appears in the numerator and $0 < P < 1$.

and

- c) The finite population correction (fpc) of $\sigma^2(\bar{x})$ will be smaller

than in $\sigma^2(\bar{x})$. This relationship is given by

$$[(N_{nz}-n^*)/N_{nz}] < [(N-n^*)/N].$$

Note that the ordinary sample mean which is obtained without screening is $\bar{x}$ and $\sigma^2(\bar{x}) = \sigma^2/n^*$ where we have ignored the fpc. The relative efficiency of the screening technique to the purely random scheme can be expressed as

$$[\sigma^2/P^2\sigma^2_{nz}]100\% = (1/P)[1+Q/cv(X_{inz})^2]100\%$$

which is a function of P and $cv(X_{inz})$. Figure 5 illustrates this relationship. We can substitute the ratios r_i or r_i^* for X_i or X_i^* , respectively.

A field may have sub-areas with different levels of incidence. We can stratify the field in relation to $\bar{X}_i$ where $i=1,2,\dots,L$ refers to the number of strata or sub-fields. Thus, the over-all mean is

$$\bar{x} = \sum_i^L W_i \bar{X}_i$$

where

$W_i = (N_i/N)$ is the weight of the i^{th} sub-area or may represent another weighing pattern which the entomologist may devise,

and

$\bar{X}_i = (\sum_{j=1}^{N_i} X_{ij}/N)$ is the mean of the i^{th} sub-area.

Within each i^{th} sub-area, we can screen out $X_{ij}=0$. Our estimator is

$$\bar{x} = \sum_{i=1}^L W_i [P_i \bar{x}_{i(nz)}]$$

and

$$\sigma^2(\bar{x}) = \sum_{i=1}^L W_i [P_i \sigma_i^2 - Q_i^2 P_i^2 \bar{x}_{i(nz)}^2] / n_i^*$$

The finite population correction may be inserted into this variance formula.

In actual sampling work, precise estimate of P_i and Q_i can be obtained from a relatively larger sample ($n_i^{**} \gg n_i^*$) while an estimate of $\bar{X}_{i(nz)}$ is given by $\bar{x}_{i(nz)}$ from the smaller sample n_i^* . In fact, the estimate of $\sigma_{i(nz)}^2$ can be obtained from the simple variance formula,

$$s_{i(nz)}^2 = k \frac{n_i^*}{j} [X_{ij(nz)} - \bar{x}_{i(nz)}]^2 / (n_i^* - 1)$$

and the estimate of $[P_i^2 \sigma_{i(nz)}^2] / n_i^*$ is obtained from

$$[k P_i^2 s_{i(nz)}^2] / n_i^*$$

where

P_i is derived from a larger sample $n_i^{**} \gg n_i^*$. The size of sample for each stratum may be given as

$$n_i^* = n [N_i S_i / \sum N_i S_i]$$

where

S may be expressed in terms of $\bar{X}_i$.

There is another ratio which is called the population ratio of means or totals and defined as

$$\bar{Q} = (\bar{X}/\bar{Y}) = (X./Y.)$$

where

$\bar{X}$ and $\bar{Y}$ are population means per hill

and

X. and Y. are population totals of hills.

In the literature, it is not clear whether $\bar{R}$ or $\bar{Q}$ is estimated, although in most cases the estimator used is termed the sample ratio of means or totals and is defined as

$$\bar{q} = (\bar{x}/\bar{y}) = x'/y'$$

where

$\bar{x}$ and $\bar{y}$ are sample means,

and

x' and y' are sample totals.

Screening technique in experimental fields. Data from experiments conducted during the years 1962 to 1964, show that for counts (X_i), the technique of screening out the zeros will result in large relative statistical efficiency of about 1,310 percent (Table 10). The coefficient of variability (CV) of the estimator with screening will be reduced by $(1/\sqrt{13})$. If the CV of the estimator for random sampling is 20 percent, then the CV of the estimator using screening will be on the average about 6 percent only. For ratios (r_i), the mean relative efficiency is about 650 percent. From these results, it is concluded that screening can be used as a precise technique for estimating stem borer incidence in experimental fields. This technique can be used in sampling the incidence of other pests and diseases of the rice plant.

TABLE 10. Comparison of $s^2(\bar{x}, \bar{r})$ without screening and $s^2(\bar{x}, \bar{r})$ with screening of zeros. Counts (X_i) and percentages (r_i) of dead hearts, IRRI, 1962-64.^a

Date	Average relative efficiency with screening of zeros (%)	
	Counts (X_i)	Percentage (r_i)
July, 1962	1250 ^b	727
August, 1962	328	318
March, 1963	367	396
August, 1963	4047	1427
March, 1964	543	384
Mean	1310	650

^a Source of experimental data: Department of Entomology, IRRI, 1962-64.

^b IRRI 1964 Annual Report, p. 293.

Sampling studies in applied research plots. During the 1965 dry season, the Philippine Commission on Agricultural Productivity (PCAP) and The International Rice Research Institute (IRRI) in a cooperative project laid out stem borer control applied research plots at nine places in seven provinces. In each of the localities, a randomized complete block experiment consisting of 4 replications and 3 treatments per replication was carried out. The size of the plot was 5 x 10 m and the distance of planting was 20 x 20 cm. The treatments were lindane, folidol and control. The screening technique was recommended for the sampling of stem borer damage. This technique in sampling the non-zeros was applied to each of 25 rows, each row consisting of 50 hills.

The efficiency of the screening technique in the seven areas is shown in Table 11 for dead hearts and Table 12 for white heads. Table 11 indicates the gain in precision of the different stratified schemes. For example, scheme B utilized the pooled-within replication estimates from the ANOV, whereas scheme C used the replicates as strata. The results in Table 11 show that screening for dead hearts in the farmer's field will result in a gain of precision of 7,000 to 10,000 percent. For white heads (Table 12), the relative efficiency for

the lindane treatment is quite remarkable.

TABLE 11. Relative efficiency of the screening technique as compared to the non-screening of zeros for percentage (r_i) of dead hearts in PCAP-IRRI applied research plots, by location and by type of stratification, 1965 dry season.^a

Location	(Control plots)		
	Type of stratification ^b		
	A	B	C
San Fernando, Pampanga	116	128	108
Tagudin, Ilocos Sur	1,461	1,256	1,389
Barcelona, Sorsogon	7,103	6,036	6,643
Magallanes, Sorsogon	10,277	3,580	2,144
Bulan, Sorsogon	33,250	29,283	29,193
Hermosa, Bataan	917	828	725
Morong, Rizal	16,518	7,159	13,798
Mean	9,944	6,896	7,714

^a Based on control plots only.

^b A — average of 4 replications; B — within replication or pooled-within replication from ANOV; C — stratification with replication as stratum.

Sampling studies were also conducted to investigate the variance of the non-zeros within the row for all rows, every second, every third, and every fifth row. Data on percent white heads from four localities were used. They indicated that the variance within the rows were equal for the four sampling schemes. The equality of the row means was also tested and the results showed that the row means in each of the four sampling schemes were equal.

On the basis of these results, a screening procedure is recommended where every 3rd instead of every row is used. A precise estimate $\hat{P}$ is obtained and the labor requirement of sampling is reduced to about one-third. A description of this revised sampling procedure is given below.

Method of screening the zeros. Divide the farmer's paddy field into two strata according to the degree of incidence. From each stratum, locate at random two plots, each plot consisting of 24 rows by 50 hills. Each plot is sampled in accordance with a specific method.

(14)	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	.	.		.
.	.	.	.	.	.	.	.	.	.		.
.	.	.	.	.	.	.	.	.	.		.
22	.	.	.	.	.	.	.	.	.		.
(23)	x	(x)	.	x	(x)	(x)	x	.	.		.
24	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	.	.		.

In each row the number of dead hearts or white heads (X_i), and the number of total tillers or bearing panicles will be recorded from only 3 hills from those attacked [(x)]. If in a row the number of hills attacked is equal to 3 or less, then make observations on all

these hills. If there are more than 3 hills attacked, take a random sample of only 3 hills from each row. Use the table below to locate the random hill in each of the random rows. In this table the attacked hills in a row are numbered 00, 01, 02, . . . , 49.

Table of random numbers for attacked hills.
(Apply this to the random rows only.)

Number of hills attacked	Random numbers	Number of hills attacked	Random numbers
1	Take all	26	01,05,21
2	" "	27	02,07,09
3	" "	28	15,16,18
4	00,02,03	29	06,04,21
5	00,01,04	30	05,09,29
6	02,03,05	31	13,17,20
7	03,05,06	32	08,09,29
8	00,02,06	33	01,10,14
9	00,04,06	34	03,23,29
10	01,07,09	35	04,05,21
11	04,05,08	36	14,16,25
12	00,04,05	37	10,15,19
13	04,07,08	38	02,13,30
14	05,06,09	39	09,16,32
15	11,13,14	40	06,10,32
16	01,04,07	41	07,13,19
17	00,06,07	42	01,06,16
18	03,10,16	43	02,09,18
19	08,11,12	44	14,32,34
20	00,09,17	45	07,27,35
21	00,05,07	46	00,19,34
22	06,14,15	47	05,32,46
23	01,05,17	48	22,29,38
24	09,16,20	49	20,28,42
25	03,05,23	50	21,27,49

Enter the number of dead hearts or white heads ($X_i=1,2,3,\dots$) and the total number of tillers or bearing panicles ($Y_i=1,2,3,\dots$) in the data sheet for each sample row. Apply the stratified estimator described on page 315.

Stem borer incidence and yield losses. Attempts were made to relate incidence of stem borer and grain losses from data obtained from experimental plots at the Institute and from applied research plots in the farmer's paddy fields in 7

locations, PCAP-IRRI cooperative project in the Philippines. A simple linear relationship and a quadratic form were tested with variety Milfor-6(2) as the plant indicator. These two forms were derived for percentage of white heads as the variable X and grain yield as Y.

The forms are:

$$\text{Linear: } P(Y) = 100 - b_1 X \\ dP(Y)/dX = -b_1$$

$$\text{Quadratic: } P(Y) = 100 - b_2 X + b_3 X^2 \\ dP(Y)/dX = -b_2 + 2b_3 X.$$

Fig. 6. Relationship between Z_1 and Z_2 .

The first principal component, Z_1 , may be called an indicator of 'size' or 'volume,' since the positive coefficients are large and approximately the same (0.4) for such characteristics as yield (y), spikelet number per panicle (x_2), number of grains per panicle (x_3), weight of straw (x_5), and plant height (x_7). Z_2 and Z_3 are indicators of 'shape' or 'contrast' owing to the large values of the coefficients of number of mature panicles (x_1) and number of tillers (x_6) in Z_2 (0.6), and sterility (x_4) in Z_3 (0.8).

These findings are supported further by the correlations between the original variables and the principal components given in Table 16. Z_1 is highly correlated with grain yield (y), spikelet number (x_2), number of grains (x_3), straw weight (x_5), and plant height (x_7). Likewise, Z_2 is highly correlated with number of mature panicles (x_1) and tiller number (x_6), and Z_3 with sterility (x_4). Thus, if one is interested in exploring the variations in conditions that lead to variations of the eight original

Fig. 7. Relationship between Z_1 and Z_3 .

TABLE 15. Eigenvalues and probability of eigenvalues for the eight principal components.

Principal component	Eigenvalue	Probability (%)	Accumulated probability (%)
Z_1	4.20	52.6	52.6
Z_2	2.44	30.5	83.1
Z_3	0.87	10.9	94.0
Z_4	0.27	3.4	97.4
Z_5	0.09	1.1	98.5
Z_6	0.08	1.0	99.5
Z_7	0.03	0.3	99.8
Z_8	0.01	0.2	100.0

variables, then one can simplify the analyses by studying the conditions that lead to variations in Z_1 , Z_2 , and Z_3 only.

Interactions between components

Z_1 and Z_2 . The relationships between the principal components — variety, nitrogen level, replication and plant — may give additional information. It was noted that the principal component by plant and by replication for each nitrogen-variety combination is stable. Thus, the mean value of six plants for each component was computed and graphed. The relationship between Z_1 and Z_2 is given in Fig. 6 for the 30 nitrogen-va-

TABLE 16. Correlation between the principal components and the eight characteristics.

Principal component	y	x ₁	x ₂	x ₃	x ₄	x ₅	x ₆	x ₇
Z ₁	0.85	-0.21	0.92	0.93	-0.23	0.88	-0.31	0.89
Z ₂	0.37	0.94	-0.03	-0.25	0.58	0.36	0.91	0.27
Z ₃	-0.28	-0.21	0.27	-0.06	0.78	-0.02	-0.20	0.15
Z ₄	-0.01	-0.10	-0.26	-0.25	-0.03	0.21	-0.11	0.27
Z ₅	-0.21	-0.02	0.04	0.05	-0.06	0.15	0.11	-0.02

riety combinations. In general, the shift of increasing nitrogen is vertical or along the Z₂ axis, while increasing growth duration of the varieties is along the horizontal or Z₁ axis. Higher nitrogen levels will give rise to positive Z₂ while longer growth duration will give positive Z₁. As mentioned earlier, Z₂ is associated with yield, spikelet number, number of grains per panicle, straw weight, and plant height. Thus, for this experiment, increasing levels of nitrogen will be particularly associated with the number of mature panicles and tiller number, whereas increasing growth duration will be related to yield, spikelet number, number of grains per panicle, straw weight, and plant height.

Note that variety Acheh (A) shifted along the Z₂ axis from the 0 to 50N and changed direction along the positive Z₁ from 50 to 150N. These reactions show a shift along two axes at different N levels. The shift along the Z₂ axis will be related to number of mature pan-

icles (x₁) and tiller number (x₆) whereas the shift along Z₁ with higher N level is associated with yield (y), spikelet number (x₂), number of grains (x₃), weight of straw (x₅), and plant height (x₇). The other varieties show only slight shifts along the Z₁ axis with increasing N.

Z₁ and Z₃. The interaction between Z₁ and Z₃ is given in Fig. 7. In general, an increase of nitrogen level is associated with a decrease in Z₃ which is highly correlated with sterility (x₄). The increase in nitrogen level also is associated with shifts along the Z₂ axis in varying degrees. The shift for Acheh (A) is almost horizontal while that for Peta (P) is sloping downwards. Note that Z₂ is related to 'shape' characteristics.

These multivariate approaches will be extended to experiments on spacing x variety, and combinations of nitrogen x spacing x variety. The processing of data for these models was done by the TOSBAC 3400 electronic computer.

Experimental Farm

Apart from providing a labor force upon which other departments may draw, the staff of the Experimental Farm also multiplies the seed of promising new varieties, keeps the station clean, and controls the insects, birds, and rats which could otherwise ruin experiments.

THE INSTITUTE'S EXPERIMENTAL PLOTS ARE PROTECTED against rats by an electric fence. In its first year of operation, this equipment killed over 20,000 rats.

During the year, the farm employed 45 people. These included 28 field workers plus 17 laborers engaged solely in rat control.

Because lowland rice is grown at the Institute in the dry as well as the wet season, the fields are flooded almost continuously. The soils are therefore always too wet and soft to bear the weight of big tractors which, even with

cage wheel attachments, become bogged. Heavy tractors of the four-wheel type are consequently used only on upland areas or lowland fields that have been well drained and fallowed for a season. Hand tractors are used on lowland fields, but carabaos are frequently the most convenient source of power for land preparation in extremely wet areas.

SEED PRODUCTION

During the year, 10.95 ha were planted for seed production. Promising crosses made at the Institute were planted to increase the stock of seed. Since only a small amount of seed was supplied, great care had to be taken to avoid waste. The selections were grown in ordinary wet seedbeds and trans-

planted one plant per hill to cover a wide area. A number of other varieties were also grown to insure a supply of seed for the Institute. These included several crosses made in Texas, a number of *indica* and *ponlai (japonica)* varieties, and some floating rice from Thailand.

Despite constant roguing of the production plots, off-types still appear. To improve purity, the practice has been adopted of harvesting panicles only (rather than the whole hill) representing the variety or cross. Milfor-6(2), PI 215936, and Chianung 242 were harvested in this way, and the method is to be extended to all other varieties and lines.

A total of 50,928 kg (1,157 cavans) of clean dried rice was harvested from the production plots during the year. This included 5,062 kg (115 cavans) from crops planted in late 1964 and not included in the 1964 Annual Report. The production from crops planted and harvested in 1965, including both upland and lowland, was therefore 45,866 kg (1,042 cavans), obtained from 10.97 ha, with an average yield of 4.18 tons per ha. The production from lowland fields was 44,065.60 kg from 9.47 ha,

giving an average yield of 4.65 tons (105.75 cavans) per ha. All the above figures refer to clean, dried rice with 14% moisture.

The Experimental Farm supplies seed on request to other research organizations and for testing by national agencies in selected farmers' fields. This year a ton of Taichung (Native) 1 was sent to India for experiment and multiplication. Rice was also supplied to a US Naval Medical Research Unit in Taiwan where the nutritional value of rice protein is being studied.

Apart from the rice production plots, 71.82 ha were planted for the various departments for experimental and demonstration purposes. The staff also collaborated with the Departments of Entomology and Agronomy on experiments described in the appropriate sections of this Report.

PEST CONTROL

To lessen the incidence of virus attack, a systematic attempt was made to control the leafhopper vectors. Weeds in unplanted fields, along roadsides, and on other waste ground were kept down by cutting. Sprays of sevin were also applied regularly.

Birds continued to be a serious pest in the dry season, and no fully effective method of control has yet been devised.

Rat control became more effective with the development of an electric fence. Since its installation on January 10, this equipment has so far killed 20,476 rats. This indicates its efficacy as well as the enormous numbers of rats attacking rice crops.

The equipment comprises a 6- or 12-V battery, a 6- or 12-V vibrator, an auto-radio transformer, an ammeter, two 100,000-ohm resistors, a fuse, and a socket. The fence is of 1-foot high, 1-inch mesh poultry wire.

The negative pole of the battery is grounded to the vibrator to which the positive pole is also connected through the fuse and ammeter. The 6- or 12-V alternating current from the vibrator is increased to either 110- or 220-V,

depending on the type of transformer used. Of the two leads leaving the transformer, one is grounded, preferably in wet soil, and the other is connected to the fence. Should the fence become overloaded the transformer is protected by the fuse. The ammeter indicates if the fence is grounded.

The fence, supported by insulated bamboo posts 1 meter apart, is erected on top of the levees around the field to be protected. The clearance between fence and ground is between 3/4 and 1 inch, low enough to prevent rats from getting underneath but sufficiently high to avoid grounding. Weeds near the fence are kept cut.

Ditches around the levees remain filled with water so that rats will be wet when they contact the fence and thus receive a more effective shock. The whole object is to stop the rats entering the plots; once inside they are more difficult to control.

The batteries require charging every 2 to 4 days depending on the size of the field protected. To prolong battery life, they are charged each day.

The electric fence does not completely protect the rice because some rats man-

age to squeeze under the wire without receiving a shock; others enter through holes dug in the levees. Furthermore, the fence is electrified only at night, and rats may enter the plots during the day. To deal with rats inside the plots, use is made of traps, cyanogas dusted around burrows, and poisons such as 1080 and warfarin offered as baits in corn, rice, and grated coconut.

The fence system is operated and patrolled every night. Men in the control squad work 8-hour shifts to insure that the fence is operating correctly, to

remove dead rats from the fence, and to kill those merely stunned.

The monthly tallies of rats killed show that the numbers increase in May, reach a peak in July, and then gradually diminish. The reason for this fluctuation may be that in May, June, and July the nearby farms are not planted and the Institute plots thus offer the most enticing food in the district. With the commencement of planting on surrounding farms in late July and August, the rat population at the Institute declines.

Office of Communication

Activities in 1965 helped to delineate sharply the complexity of issues that must be resolved in each country before significant changes in rice-growing practices leading to increased yields can be expected.

The Institute's research on the rice plant has clearly demonstrated that yields can be dramatically increased through the use of different varietal types and improved cultural practices, including effective control of insects and other pests. But such clarifications do not remove the serious human, economic, and social obstacles to establishing these new varieties and practices in the rice paddies of southeast Asia.

TO TEST THE EFFECTIVENESS OF LINDANE for stem borer control, the Institute has established applied research plots in nine locations in seven Philippine provinces. Photo shows the lindane applied research plots in Muñoz, Nueva Ecija.

As an international organization, the Institute works with and through the national agencies in each country, most of which are beset with some problems of financing, staffing, and effective communication between national headquarters and the field. Research findings originating with the Institute can not be absorbed into the rice cultural practice recommendations for a given country or sub-area of a country until the personnel of these national organizations accept them, test them in a variety of local environments, and develop tested modifications.

Recognizing the problems of working with a number of countries simultaneously — with each country having some problems unique to the area — the Office of Communication in 1965

decided to concentrate for a period on work in the Philippines. The decision was based on the ease of working with research findings most readily adaptable to local situations. Until the Office can successfully establish effective patterns of communication from the Institute through the national agencies to the farmer in one country, it would be difficult to try to develop effective patterns in all rice-growing countries.

Work within the Philippines, as outlined below, has confirmed earlier observations in this and other countries that much of the problem of communicating with, influencing, and teaching a given farmer rests in the technical adequacy or appropriateness of the practice for that farmer as well as in the technical competency of the local

extension worker or other so-called change agent.

Continued cooperative work with several national agricultural agencies of the Philippines has made it possible for the Institute and these agencies to begin development of what may be a new approach to agricultural development and extension in this part of the world. Essentially, this approach applies the scientific method to the extension task. It is based on the premise that a research finding is not necessarily useful or valuable for a farmer until it has been tried successfully in the environment where that farmer operates. Thus the Institute encourages a program of applied research for both research and extension organizations. At the same time, the Institute encourages extension organizations to consider technical competency as the primary requisite for the extension worker. Technical competency, in this case, includes the ability to perform the rice-growing tasks that the farmer performs.

Concurrently, work in the Philippines and observations in other rice-growing countries have demonstrated the need for a more adequate flow of technical information from national and regional headquarters to the field. Without such a flow, even technically competent men become out of date within a few years.

No analysis of the many factors involved in bringing about technical change would be complete without recognizing the important role of the industrial sector as well as that portion of the economy responsible for credit and finance. Until adequate channels

are established for the distribution, financing, and sale of chemicals, fertilizers and other supplies necessary in rice production, the extension worker will be rather unsuccessful in bringing about farmer acceptance and use of these materials. Consequently, much effort is being directed to developing and maintaining effective communication with representatives of industrial firms with a stake in agriculture or upon which modern agriculture practices depend.

Efforts of the Office of Communication toward achieving its many objectives are summarized below in five categories although many activities overlap: (a) Dissemination of information; (b) training in rice production and communication; (c) applied research on rice; (d) communication research and evaluation; and (e) consultation and liaison.

Communication and training activities were accelerated in 1965 with the appointment on January 1 of Mr. William G. Golden, Jr., as a rice production specialist, and the appointment on November 1 of Mr. E. A. Jackson to the new post of editor. Other major appointments during the year were Mr. Francisco D. Gorrez, Jr., as administrative assistant to help handle the growing volume of visitors to the Institute and, late in the year, Dr. Arthur A. Muka, extension entomologist at Cornell University, as a visiting scientist. Dr. Muka arrived on November 1 to assist throughout most of 1966 with the applied research program for the control of the rice stem borer.

DISSEMINATION OF INFORMATION

Publications

Processing of Institute publications continued to occupy a significant portion of staff time. This included the work of editors, artists, photographers, and multilith operators, in addition to the typing and proofreading.

The IRRI Reporter, a bi-monthly scientific newsletter, started in January, 1965, was distributed widely to keep scientists, educators, administra-

tors, and others informed of research and training developments at the Institute. Through this means, the Institute made known the availability of journal article reprints.

Established in 1964, the technical bulletin series was continued, with the third bulletin appearing in early 1965. At the end of the year, four new technical bulletins were at various stages of processing.

Because of the great demand for the 1963 Annual Report, 3,000 copies of the 1964 report, consisting of 336 pages, were printed, with the bulk of this supply being exhausted within 6 months of publication.

The Johns Hopkins Press, under a joint publication contract with the Institute, published two books in 1965, each of these being based on an Institute symposium. These books, titled *The Rice Blast Disease* and *The Mineral Nutrition of the Rice Plant*, are being sold throughout the world through commercial book channels.

In December, the editors began reading proof for the third book to be published through the Johns Hopkins Press. This book, based on the symposium on the major insect pests of the rice plant, will be about 700 pages in length.

Other publications during the year included a new general information leaflet on the Institute and a booklet about the training program.

Field days and visitors

Several steps were taken in 1965 so that the ever-increasing number of visitors might be handled efficiently and effectively.

An administrative assistant, appointed to help meet and discuss the Institute's program with visitors, established a series of field plots, in which he supervised the growing of rice for display purposes.

Other activities to help the staff acquaint visitors with the problems and potentials of modern rice culture included the construction of 12 4- x 5-foot display panels in the auditorium, plus another eight identical panels for the halls of the Administration Building.

Several educational exhibits were designed for these panels.

About 150 persons attended the Institute's second invitational field day, April 30. These represented a cross-section of Philippine agricultural research, education, extension, and commercial interests.

In November, an exhibit on the Philippine rice virus diseases and their vectors was constructed, in cooperation with Plant Pathology, for the National Science Fair conducted in Manila by the National Science and Development Board.

Mass media

Activities of the Rice Information Cooperative Effort at the College of Agriculture (See International Activities) materially reduced the demands on the Institute for press releases on recommended rice cultural practices in the Philippines.

In July, work was begun on a motion picture designed to depict, in close-up and over time, the problems and potentials of the rice plant. A committee of scientists helped the Office of Communication develop the outline for the film. Under the present schedule, the film is to be completed in 1966 as part of the Institute's contribution to the International Rice Year.

Because almost any operation in the rice-growing cycle can be found any day of the year at the Institute, still and motion picture photographers interested in rice stories called frequently at the Institute. During the year, mass media representatives from the Philippines, Japan, Hongkong, Vietnam, England, the United States, and the United Nations were assisted.

TRAINING IN RICE PRODUCTION AND COMMUNICATION

In July, 1964, a year-long course was initiated designed to instruct officers from Philippine national agencies in rice production techniques and the principles and methods of communicating information.

In the belief that extension workers (or "change agents") cannot hope to influence farmers to adopt new prac-

tices unless they are themselves skilled in the tasks performed by farmers, the trainees were taught to grow rice with the tools used and under the conditions experienced commercially. The trainees grew their own rice crop at the Institute farm, and attended lectures delivered by the senior scientific staff.

In the first phase, the trainees

learned the skills required to produce rice under field conditions with tools currently being used by farmers, and they grew a crop of rice. Members of the senior scientific staff also provided instructions in the various disciplines, in new rice technology, and in communication principles and methods.

In January, 1965, five additional members of the Commission on Agricultural Productivity staff joined the original group to make a total of 10 trainees to enter the second half of the program, the applied research phase, in which the work emphasized the practical application of the research philosophy and methods taught earlier. The applied research activities were designed (1) to develop a capability to conduct critical experiments in the provinces under field conditions which would provide data upon which sound recommendations and judgments could be based, and (2) to obtain data on the effectiveness of γ -BHC for stem borer control when used under widely differing environmental conditions.

Each trainee designed, installed, and managed an applied research field plot in his own province for evaluating the effectiveness of gamma-benzene hexachloride (lindane) in controlling rice stem borers. Detailed plans were prepared before the plots were established. Each plot area consisted of 800 square

meters in a farmer's field in which three treatments were randomized and replicated four times. Two of the treatments involved the periodic application of either granular γ -BHC to the paddy water or sprays of methyl parathion to the foliage. In the third treatment (the check plot), no chemical was applied.

The plots were all located on the island of Luzon and geographically ranged from 12° 35' to 16° 55' north latitude. All plots were planted to Milfor-6(2) except at Tagudin, Ilocos Sur, where PI 215936 was used. The size, randomization, cultural treatments, and chemical treatments made to the different plots were essentially identical. Yield data are shown in Table 1.

From the field data obtained on dead hearts, white heads, and distribution of stem borer species during the dry season, it became evident that environmental differences among the plots influenced the economic benefit derived from the use of γ -BHC for stem borer control. At Bulan, Sorsogon, the γ -BHC treatment resulted in a highly significant increase in yield over the check, and the economic gain was great. This effect was attributed to the early and intense attack of stem borers in that area.

The difference between the same treatments at Morong, Rizal, however,

TABLE 1. Effect of γ -BHC and methyl parathion for control of rice stem borers, applied research, Philippines, 1965 dry season.

Location in the Philippines	Yields in kg/ha at 14% M.C. (Means of four replications)		
	γ -BHC every 30 days ^a	Methyl parathion every 15 days ^b	Not treated (check)
Calumpit, Bulacan	3109	1759	1420
Muñoz, Nueva Ecija	4102	3272	2333
Gapan, Nueva Ecija	4767	4716	4253
Hermosa, Bataan	5105	3539	2843
Barcelona, Sorsogon	5418	4382	2985
San Fernando, Pampanga	5601	5387	4876
Tagudin, Ilocos Sur	5928	5090	3604
Magallanes, Sorsogon	6115	4661	3220
Morong, Rizal	6606	6018	5765
Bulan, Sorsogon	7066	5057	4278

^aGenerally, three treatments, the first two being at the rate of 2 kg/ha, active ingredient, and the third at 3 kg/ha, active ingredient, applied to paddy water.

^bFolidol M-50 as a spray at manufacturer's recommended rate.

was significant only at the 5% level, and the economic benefit was marginal. At the Morong location, only a slight stem borer attack was recorded late in the growing season. The applied research findings of the trainees has thus helped to identify certain environments in which the threat of serious stem borer damage exists.

Local extension agents at each plot location assisted with the project and learned the principles and procedures for using γ -BHC in stem borer control. Such association with and participation in the applied research activities has helped prepare the local agents to extend this new technology to farmers with confidence in subsequent years.

As a part of their training, the participants in the rice production training program were encouraged to develop a critical approach, to make quantitative measurements, and seek the causes of phenomena observed in the rice paddies. One such phenomenon was the occurrence of large numbers of dead stem borer adults on the water of rice paddies immediately following an application of granular γ -BHC to the paddy water. The entomologist recommended that the trainees make quantitative measurements in an effort to understand the cause of death of the moths. Counts of dead moths on the water were conducted every 7 days and the data related to the date of γ -BHC applications.

In two trials, the number of dead moths on the water surface increased abruptly following γ -BHC applications, decreased to a low level after a period of 3 to 4 weeks, but again rose abruptly following the next application. Subsequent greenhouse, laboratory, and field studies by one of the trainees has

shown conclusively that the phenomenon first observed and measured quantitatively as a part of the training program results from a fumigation effect generated by the γ -BHC. Studies now are underway to evaluate the combined systemic and fumigation effects known to result from an application of γ -BHC into paddy water (see Entomology).

Upon completion of their training in July, nine of the trainees returned to their parent organization (the national agricultural extension agency in the Philippines) for assignment to the provinces, while one of the group (an entomologist) remained at the Institute to study the fumigation effects of γ -BHC. Each of the nine was assigned to a different province and was given the primary responsibility of training five others.

At year's end (after 4 months), there were some indications that second generation training, when conducted under field conditions and away from a training institution, may suffer from lack of facilities and supplies and from general attenuation in subject matter details. While the principle of the "multiplication effect" theoretically may be ideal, it may be difficult in practice to achieve effectively without adequate support and follow-up.

The nine graduates of the rice production training program met at the Institute in November to discuss their field activities and review developments in rice technology since their departure in July. Periodic conferences of this nature are programmed for the future to assist Institute personnel to keep abreast of field activities and for field workers to keep current on new technological developments.

APPLIED RESEARCH ON INSTITUTE RESULTS

The experience of using applied or field research methods as a training mechanism clearly demonstrated how such a program, if systematically followed, could facilitate the eventual acceptance of research findings by rice farmers.

For many reasons the Institute does not try to communicate directly with

the millions of rice growers in the many countries involved. Rather, it seeks to cooperate with national research, educational and resource agencies so that these groups can effectively communicate information designed to bring about changes in rice production and yields.

By working with national agencies

INTER-AGENCY PARTICIPATION in field trips facilitates communication between research and extension. Here, the rice production specialist and his assistant inspect the provincial field trials conducted by a Commission on Agricultural Productivity staff member who completed training at the Institute in applied research methods. Also involved are the two College of Agriculture persons who staff the Rice Information Cooperative Effort.

on applied research or field testing of Institute results and materials, staff members of both the Institute and the agencies become thoroughly familiar with the use of material and how it must be adapted or handled to perform well in different environments. As the result of such cooperative effort, the validity of the message is established, relevant personnel are trained in the techniques involved, and the eventual adoption by the farmer becomes more likely.

BPI-IRRI stem borer plots

In early 1965 the Institute developed a memorandum of agreement with the Philippines Bureau of Plant Industry to engage in a cooperative applied research project to evaluate the use of lindane (the gamma isomer of benzene hexachloride) for the control of rice

stem borers in various parts of the Philippines.

At that time, the Institute had completed 3 years of research on using lindane as a systemic insecticide against stem borers under lowland conditions. Although the rates and timing of applications used at the Institute gave highly effective and economic control under Los Baños conditions, it was necessary to provide means whereby the agency responsible for insect pest control in the Philippines, the BPI, could determine whether and how the chemical might be used to achieve satisfactory control under widely varying conditions.

During the 1965 wet season, 32 plots were established in 16 provinces, all of them uniform in design and treatment and all intended to evaluate the use of γ -BHC. Three rice varieties were used.

A wide array of environments was sampled with plot locations ranging geographically between $7^{\circ} 5'$ and $15^{\circ} 5'$ north latitude in the Philippines. The resulting data have not yet been assembled, but it is apparent that widespread applied research activities are feasible, given a field force of national field agents with a basic agricultural education who can receive 2 to 4 days of intensive specialized training for the task.

This work also requires a small but competent Institute staff to supervise the field activities, monitor progress and problems, and offer technical guidance. These functions were carried out by the rice production specialist and the administrative assistant of the Office of Communication.

As the year ended and the wet season harvest approached, plans were under way to continue the cooperative applied research program with the Bureau of Plant Industry in the 1966 dry season to evaluate further the effectiveness of γ -BHC for control of rice stem borers. The new series of experiments will involve Milfor-6(2) plus any variety which the farmer-cooperator may plant in his production field.

Use of aircraft in tropical rice production

On June 22, 1965, a 1.6-hectare area of puddled soil was direct-seeded with Milfor-6(2) from an airplane, this being the first occasion that this method of seeding has been used in the Philippines. Prior to broadcasting, the pre-germinated seed, and 70 kg/ha of urea was applied by air and harrowed into the soil by conventional means. During the crop-growing season, three applications of γ -BHC, one topdressing of urea, and one spray of MCPA were made

from an airplane. The crop was harvested October 21.

This activity was an applied research extension of experiments on methods of seeding rice which have been conducted on a small scale at the Institute for several seasons by the agronomist. During 1964 and early 1965, the aerial equipment underwent an extensive series of both static and flight calibrations in preparation for the project. The rice production specialist trained a number of others, including participants in the rice production training program, in the techniques of aircraft calibration and in the operation and management of an aerial application of solid materials to a rice field. Standard published references and tested methods were used on all the aerial application work so that the results of the over-all project could be evaluated in terms of the cultural practices rather than in terms of the method of applying the treatments.

While the procedures employed in the experiment are not recommended for the Philippines at this time, the results indicate clearly that fixed wing aircraft equipped with standard venturi-type spreaders and standard spray systems can be employed without great difficulty on lowland rice under tropical conditions in the Philippines.

The average yield of rice (14% moisture content) from the 1.6 hectares was 3,016 kg/ha with a range of from 1,178 to 4,526 kg/ha in the subplots. The low yield in certain subplots and the low average yield was attributable to water grass competition resulting from inadequate water management during the growing season.

Cooperative applied research projects were also begun this year with the Philippine Rural Reconstruction Movement.

COMMUNICATION RESEARCH AND EVALUATION

Pre-demonstration interviews were completed with 60 farmers in each of two barrios in Bulacan Province as part of the study being conducted by the one research scholar in the Office of Communication. This study is concerned with impact of a field demonstration plot on farmers' knowledge, under-

standing, and attitudes relating to the use of fertilizer and selection of rice varieties.

Following the pre-demonstration interviews, the scholar placed demonstration plots in each barrio, using two varieties and three fertilizer levels. After the plots are harvested, he will again

interview the farmers. These interviews were scheduled for completion between January and March, 1966.

The file of research studies relating to social and technological change was increased and the range of contacts with individuals and institutions con-

cerned with similar matters expanded.

Further work on the continuing study of Institute trainees was postponed until a competent research assistant in the social sciences can be recruited.

CONSULTATION AND LIAISON

The professional staff spent a great deal of time consulting with professional visitors to the Institute from other countries, with representatives of the Philippine national agencies, and with farmers and landowners seeking solutions to rice production problems. In many of these activities, the Institute personnel brought together people with problems, and organizations and institutions with resources for solving these problems.

Most frequently, Philippine organiza-

tions sought help and materials for training programs in rice production and communication. By monitoring the bulk of such requests, the Office attempted to minimize the degree to which such requests interfered with the research programs of the professional staff.

At the request of The Rockefeller Foundation, personnel of the Office visited Taiwan twice to help the Joint Commission on Rural Reconstruction and the Taiwan Provincial Department

THE ARTIST-ILLUSTRATOR, THE EDITORIAL ASSISTANT AND THE PRINTER PLAN the layout for one of the issues of *The IRRI Reporter*, the Institute's bi-monthly newsletter.

of Agriculture and Forestry plan a program for the development of training materials in agricultural research and extension. This proposal, submitted by the Taiwan groups to the Foundation in June, was endorsed by the Foundation and transferred to the Institute for administration. The general purpose of the project is to develop approaches and materials that can be used in various countries to facilitate the on-the-job training of research assistants and field workers in extension who may not have more than a high school education. With improved appropriate materials and approaches, it is hoped that senior staff members can increase the efficiency and effectiveness by which they train assistants.

The principal content will be the computational and methodological skills in-

involved in handling specific crops for research or demonstrational purposes. Because the crop is widely grown throughout many of the developing countries, initial developments will focus on rice research, extension, and cultivation. Many of the procedures and operational skills related to rice will be equally appropriate for other crops. The Taiwan working group, established in midsummer, had prepared a preliminary outline by the end of the year, which outline is to be translated from Chinese into English before being submitted to the Institute for technical review.

During the second semester, 1964-65, the communication specialist assisted a member of the College of Agriculture staff in teaching a graduate course in social psychology.

Library and Documentation Center

INTERNATIONAL BIBLIOGRAPHY

Publication of the 1963 and 1964 supplements to the *International Bibliography of Rice Research* was the most significant new achievement of the Library and Documentation Center in 1965. Previous supplements were compiled in the Washington, D.C. area, making use of the National Agricultural Library's vast resources. The 1963 and 1964 compilations, however, used the Institute's collection, both for selection and verification of items for inclusion.

There was more than a 100-percent increase in the number of bibliographic citations from 1962 to 1963. Supplement 1962 has 965 references; 1963 has 1,948, and 1964, 1,739. This increase is attributed to the increasing rice litera-

ture output and to the inclusion of references published in 1961 and 1962 which were not included in the respective supplements.

Included in the 1964 supplement is a list of the rice literature translations available in the Institute's library. This listing will continue to appear in future supplements.

Supplement 1965 was being compiled at year's end. The feasibility of semi-annual supplements and the publications of a quinquennial specific subject index are being considered.

The collection of rice literature citations prior to 1951 is continuing. A thorough search will be needed before publication can be considered.

REFERENCE AND CIRCULATION

In 1965, requests for information were processed from 32 countries. The greatest number of requests came from India, the United States, Japan, Brazil, Vietnam, Sarawak, and Thailand, in that order. Records show a localization of requests within the country of origin. In India, 40 institutions (universities, colleges, experiment stations) within the rice-producing regions received copies of the bibliography. About 70 percent of the requests from India originated from the Central Rice Research Institute at Cuttack and 30 percent were evenly distributed between New Delhi and Uttar Pradesh. The requests from Japan came from three research centers, Nagoya, Kyoto, and Misima. In Thailand, only Kasetsart University has used the Institute's library services.

Rice breeding and genetics outrank

all other subject fields in requests made, followed by entomology and agronomy. Many of the requests were for Japanese literature.

All requests were for the printed forms of information. This indicates that facilities for reading and storage of microfilm are almost non-existent in the regions where the requests originated, and/or that scientists are averse to the use of non-traditional forms, considering that individual scientists originate the majority of the requests.

Within the Institute, from January to November, 1965, 18,640 library materials were circulated. Statistics on direct library use are not kept, inasmuch as the library operates on an open stack basis. The number of reference questions received by telephone increased.

LIBRARY HOLDINGS

During 1965, back issues of the basic periodicals and journals were obtained. The number of serial titles currently total 1,337; 518 by subscription, 363 by exchange arrangements, and the rest as gifts.

A total of 3,155 monographic materials were added to the Institute's collection in 1965, bringing the collection to 15,029 volumes. Other acquisitions included 10 additional maps and 43 theses on microfilm, and 79 translations from Japanese to English.

Other library activities

The monthly circulation of the library list of new acquisitions was continued. The tables of contents of journals were copied upon receipt and routed to the departments concerned.

The Library also purchased and dis-

tributed books to research scholars.

Copies of original, unedited English translations of foreign language rice literature were deposited with the National Agricultural Library in Washington, D.C. These were in turn listed in the NAL's *Bibliography of Agriculture* to make the translations more generally known.

Regularly, master cards of the library's book acquisitions were sent to the National Institute of Science and Technology Library and Documentation Center to form a union catalog of scientific holdings of libraries in the Philippines.

In May, the librarian presented a paper on the IRRI Library and Documentation Center at the National Science Information Symposium, sponsored by the National Science Development Board of the Philippines.

BINDERY

The bindery output during the year was as follows: 1,158 volumes of periodicals, 185 volumes of theses, 500 booklets of the *International Bibliog-*

raphy of Rice Research, 322 pamphlets, 40 volumes of field books, 109 pieces of reprint-file boxes, 51 conference folders, 11 slide boxes, and 10 albums.

International Activities

Under its international program the Institute maintains active contact with rice research centers in other parts of the world, particularly in the tropics. The objectives of these activities are: (a) to identify rice production problems common to many tropical areas, (b) to stimulate research efforts on these problems both at the Institute and at other centers, (c) to introduce findings of other centers into the research program of the Institute, (d) to test results of the Institute's research at other tropical sites and to determine how these may apply and how they must be modified, (e) to encourage interchange of research results among rice scientists throughout the world, and (f) to improve the proficiency of young rice scientists in the use of modern research techniques.

A number of kinds of activities are undertaken to achieve these ends. In previous years these have included training of selected scholars and fellows from many rice-growing countries, advanced training of selected scholars and fellows in the United States, international conferences and symposia, cooperative investigations of problems of mutual interest, and extensive staff travel. The activities have been supported largely by a 3-year grant of \$800,000 from the Ford Foundation.

During the past year certain of these categories were intensified and others were reduced. A new approach was added during the year with the appointment of liaison officers to the staff of The Rockefeller Foundation in Thailand and India and to that of the Ford Foundation in Pakistan and Malaysia.

THE TRAINING PROGRAM

Training young scientists in research techniques is an integral part of the Institute's program. Such training is accomplished by enrolling qualified candidates as active members of the research team. They work closely with the senior scientist in their field of specialization and assume responsibility for conducting research on a special problem. The research fits into the over-all plan of the department's work and the scholar

receives first-hand experience from the planning to the preparation of a final report.

Persons selected for such training come from institutions where teaching and research related to rice production hold an important place and where they are assured continued opportunity to contribute to knowledge of the rice plant following their return. Candidates are nominated by officials of their

home institution and are selected following careful examination of academic records and an interview to determine qualifications, need for further training, and English language proficiency.

Most scholars are in residence for periods of one to two years. If they qualify and wish to do so, they may become candidates for the Master of Science degree at the University of the Philippines, College of Agriculture. In this case they enroll for formal course work at the College and receive research training and thesis advice at the Institute. Normally the special problem results are used to meet the thesis requirement for the degree. This program requires about two years and is a popular one as evidenced by the fact that more than half of the scholars were degree candidates during 1965.

Research fellows are more experienced scientists, usually hold the M.S. or Ph.D. degree and come to the Institute to participate in some special field of study. Normally the fellowship is for a year, although it may be longer or shorter depending upon the requirements of the fellow's program. The fellow may undertake a short but intensive research project using facilities or materials not available in his home country; he may come to familiarize himself with a particular research technique or to review research of potential value to his home station.

In special instances individuals may come to the Institute for periods of less than 6 months if they wish to study some particular technique in use at the Institute or to observe some specific phase of the Institute's program. Nor-

RESEARCH SCHOLARS FROM SEVERAL COUNTRIES DISCUSS their work while relaxing in one of the Institute lounges.

mally, however, participants are present for at least one cropping season since this is considered the minimum time to enable actual participation in the research program.

During 1965 a total of 89 scholars and fellows studied and worked at the Institute for part or all of the year, although no more than 60 were in residence at any one time. The group included people from 11 Asian countries plus Ghana, Holland, Panama, and the United States. Seven persons came for short periods of study as follows:

MR. HONORATO JEREZA, Bureau of Plant Industry, Philippines, spent two weeks at the Institute to study weed control research techniques.

MR. E. J. A. KHAN, research officer-in-charge, Agricultural Irrigation Research Station, University of Ghana, studied the work and organization of the Institute with particular reference to agronomy on a month's program.

MR. D. H. RIS LAMBERS, graduate student, Agricultural University, Wageningen, Netherlands, conducted investigations on seedling vigor in rice varieties and observed rice breeding techniques.

MR. S. SAMPATH, Central Rice Research Institute, Cuttack, India, spent two weeks studying the Institute's collection of African taxa of the genus *Oryzae*.

DR. S. V. S. SHASTRY, botanist, Indian Agricultural Research Institute, India, studied the African collection and reviewed the Institute's varietal improvement program during a 3-week visit.

MR. S. D. VAN HOOGSTATEN, student, Agricultural University, Wageningen, Netherlands, spent 5½ months studying the effects of epiphyllic bacteria on the infection of rice leaves by *Piricularia oryzae*.

MR. AUGUSTINE WYCLIFFE, Ph.D. student at Purdue University, spent a month and a half at the Institute to collect data for a doctoral dissertation to be entitled "Production economics of rice."

Research scholars

A total of 64 research scholars studied at the Institute during 1965. Twenty-two of these completed their training, eight with the Master of Science degree. A total of 33 were enrolled as candidates for this degree and many of these had largely completed the degree requirements at year's end.

Thesis and special research projects of these scholars covered virtually every field of investigation in which the Institute is engaged. The names, home institutions and fields of major interest of these scholars were as follows:

Agronomy

ABDUL MUTTALIB AKHANDA, agronomical assistant, East Pakistan Agricultural Institute, Dacca, East Pakistan. Major research: Cultural practices in upland rice.

R. SESHADRI AYYANGAR, instructor, Osmania University, College of Agriculture, India. Major research: Iron-manganese relationships in rice nutrition.

**SHUEH-KUN CHANG, junior agronomist, Taichung District Agricultural Improvement Station, Taiwan. Major research: The effects of irrigation methods on the yield, water requirement and nitrogen utilization of lowland rice.

EMMANUEL FLORESCA, research aide, Department of Agronomy, IRRI. Major research: Herbicides in rotation crops.

BASILIO MABBAYAD, instructor, College of Agriculture, University of the Philippines. Major research: Planting methods and fertilizer interactions.

ABDULLAH PRAWIROSAMUDRO, assistant agronomist, Cereals Research Institute, Bogor, Indonesia. Major research: Row spacing for direct seeded indica rice in relation to light and management practices.

VICENTE RACHO, soil technologist, Bureau of Soils, Philippines. Major research: Nitrogen transformation of added nitrogen in flooded soils and nitrogen status of the rice plant.

CLEOFAS RODRIGUEZ, agronomist III, Bureau of Plant Industry, Philippines. Major research: Improved rice production practices for Mindanao.

GERONIMO SIMSIMAN, instructor, Department of Soils, College of Agriculture, University of the Philippines. Major research: The use of liquid nitrogen fertilizers in flooded rice soils.

AGAPITO TAURO, agronomist I, Bureau of Plant Industry, Philippines. Major research: An evaluation of weed control practices in flooded rice.

Agricultural Economics

RAYMUNDO FONOLLERA, instructor, Mindanao Agricultural College, Philippines. Major research: Labor intensity in Philippine agriculture.

** Received Master of Science degree.

***SUN SUN AHU, economist, National Agricultural Cooperatives Federation, Korea. Major research: The supply and demand relations for rice in Korea.

ARKOM SOOTHIPHAN, instructor, Department of Agricultural Economics, Kasetsart University, Thailand. Major research: Income ceilings under alternative rice production technologies in southeast Asian countries.

NA MIN SOO, lecturer, Department of Economics, Yonsei University, Korea. Major research: Income ceilings under alternative rice production technologies in northeast Asian countries.

Agricultural Engineering

**LEOPOLDO ALICBUSAN, instructor, College of Agriculture, University of the Philippines. Major research: Design data on traction and steering torque for a tandem tractor on flooded soil.

*RODOLFO DOMINGO, agronomist I, Bureau of Plant Industry, Philippines. Major research: Study on the field sizes and shapes, levee dimensions, elevation and cone index of 13 lowland rice farms in Calauan, Laguna.

*NUKOOL THONGTAWEE, project manager of Pilot Farm Project, Royal Irrigation Department, Thailand. Major research: Irrigation design values of evapotranspiration, percolation and seepage.

Chemistry

***EDILBERTA NOVAL, instructor II and in-charge of the Research Department Chemical Laboratory, Mindanao Agricultural College, Philippines. Major research: Studies on the physicochemical properties of rice hemicelluloses.

Communication

*PEDRO AGCAOILI, agricultural engineer, Commission on Agricultural Productivity, Philippines. Training in rice production, applied research, and communication.

*ERLINDA ALCONCEL, rural youth officer, Commission on Agricultural Productivity, Philippines. Training in rice production, applied research, and communication.

*ANTONIO BALNEG, agricultural extension officer, Commission on Agricultural Productivity, Philippines. Training in rice production, applied research, and communication.

*Completed training.

**Received Master of Science degree.

***Terminated training for personal reasons.

*LETICIA BALUYUT, agricultural extension officer, Commission on Agricultural Productivity, Philippines. Training in rice production, applied research, and communication.

*GREGORIO BAUTISTA, agricultural extension officer, Commission on Agricultural Productivity, Philippines. Training in rice production, applied research, and communication.

*EDDIE CHU, agricultural extension officer, Commission on Agricultural Productivity, Philippines. Training in rice production, applied research, and communication.

*RODOLFO ESCALADA, agricultural extension officer, Commission on Agricultural Productivity, Philippines. Training in rice production, applied research, and communication.

*ARTURO PESAYCO, agricultural extension officer, Commission on Agricultural Productivity, Philippines. Training in rice production, applied research, and communication.

*SATURNINO RONQUILLO, acting assistant provincial agriculturist, Commission on Agricultural Productivity, Philippines. Training in rice production, applied research, and communication.

*LOLITA L. LIM, entomologist, Commission on Agricultural Productivity, Philippines. Training in rice production, applied research, and communication.

LEOPOLDO VILLEGAS, instructor, College of Agriculture, University of the Philippines. Major research: Field demonstration: Its effect on level of knowledge, understanding, attitudes of farmers about choice of a rice variety and use of fertilizers.

Entomology

ARIFIN DJAMIN, Indonesia. Major research: Stem borer resistance in rice varieties.

SANG HEE BAE, research technician, Department of Entomology, Institute of Plant Environment, Korea. Major research: Bionomics of common leafhopper pests of rice.

*AMADOR FRANCES, pest control officer, Bureau of Plant Industry, Philippines. Major research: Efficiency of various insecticides in rice stem borer control.

LOLITA L. LIM, entomologist, Commission on Agricultural Productivity, Philippines. Major research: Fumigation effects of gamma-BHC on various insect pests of rice.

MANOLO PADILLA, junior plant entomologist, Bureau of Plant Industry, Philippines. Major research: Sex attractants in rice stem borer moths.

**SOMPORN PATANAKAMJORN, instructor, Kasetsart University, Bangkok, Thailand. Major research: Varietal resistance to striped borer, *Chilo suppressalis* Walker in rice and

its association with various plant characters.

ALEJANDRO YADAO, senior plant pest control officer, Bureau of Plant Industry, Philippines. Major research: Effectivity of gamma-BHC in rice stem borer control when applied to different types of soil.

Plant Pathology

GUN SIK CHUNG, junior technician, Paddy Crop Section, Office of Rural Development, Korea. Major research: Breeding rice varieties for blast resistance.

FE DIVINAGRACIA, agronomist I, Bureau of Plant Industry, Philippines. Major research: Inheritance of blast resistance on some rice varieties.

SHIH-PAN-YU HSIEH, assistant, Department of Plant Pathology, Taiwan Provincial Chung Hsing University, Taiwan. Major research: Studies on stem rot diseases of rice.

HEI-TI-HSU, research assistant, Department of Plant Pathology, Taiwan Agricultural Research Institute, Taiwan. Major research: Effect of some chemicals on the resistance of rice to blast.

SHIH-TIEN HSU, assistant, Department of Plant Pathology, Taiwan Provincial Chung Hsing University, Taiwan. Major research: Study on bacterial leaf blight of rice.

CESAR VON CHONG, plant pathologist, Estación Experimental Agropecuaria, Ministerio de Agricultura, Comercio e Industrias, Panama. Major research: Physiological races of *Piricularia oryzae*.

Plant Physiology

NGUYEN THI DIEM, assistant chief, Soil Fertility Section, Soil Service, Directorate of Agricultural Research, Vietnam.

**TEOFILO EUGENIO, superintendent, Cagayan Valley Experiment Station, Bureau of Plant Industry, Philippines. Major research: Agronomical methods to improve light utilization in grain production.

JAMALUDIN BIN LAMIN, plant physiologist, Department of Agriculture, Kuala Lumpur, Malaysia. Major research: Environmental factors affecting the yield components.

**SHEN LIAN, junior specialist, Department of Agricultural Chemistry, Taiwan Agricultural Research Institute, Taiwan. Major research: Fate of carbon after assimilation by the rice plant.

RANJIT MULLERIYAWA, Ceylon. Major research: Mineral nutrition disturbances of the rice plant.

YOUNG DAE PARK, research worker, Department of Agricultural Chemistry, Office of Rural Development, Korea. Major research: Effect of silica application on the rice plant.

Soil Chemistry

TAWIN KRUTKUN, instructor, Department of Agronomy, Kasetsart University, Thailand. Major research: A greenhouse study of the influence of internal drainage on the growth and yield of rice on four flooded soils.

**MAI-THI MY NHUNG, assistant chief chemist, Directorate of Research Studies of Agronomy, Forestry and Animal Husbandry, Vietnam. Major research: Chemical and physico-chemical properties of acid-sulfate soils.

PAIBOON PRABUDDHAM, instructor, Department of Agronomy, Kasetsart University, Thailand. Major research: Influence of the duration of submergence of the soil prior to transplanting on the growth and yield of rice.

**WEN LIN YUAN, instructor, Department of Agricultural Chemistry, Taiwan Provincial Chung Hsing University, Taiwan. Major research: Chemical retardation of reduction of slate alluvial soils.

Soil Microbiology

CHING MING CHIOU, technician, Laboratory of Soil Microbiology, National Taiwan University, Taiwan. Major research: Microbial reduction of iron in submerged soils.

SALVADOR SALANDANAN, soil technologist I, Bureau of Soils, Philippines. Major research: Nitrogen transformations in flooded soils.

SOMSAK VANGNAI, instructor, Department of Agronomy, Kasetsart University, Thailand. Major research: Microbiology of acid-sulfate soils.

Statistics

ISIDORO DAVID, instructor, College of Agriculture, University of the Philippines. Major research: Improvement of the survey design in the estimation of palay production in the Philippines.

LILIA A. VARGAS, agronomist I, Bureau of Plant Industry, Philippines. Major research: Statistical background of heritability estimates of quantitative characters and path coefficient analysis in rice.

Varietal Improvement

ZAINUDDIN HARAHAP, chief, Upland Rice Breeding Section, Cereals Research Institute,

**Received Master of Science degree.

Bogor, Indonesia. Major research: Breeding behavior of grain dormancy.

CHENG-CHANG LI, project technician, Taichung District Agricultural Improvement Station, Taichung, Taiwan. Major research: Inheritance of growth duration; quantitative characters in rice.

PENG-TU LIU, project technician, Kaohsiung District Agricultural Improvement Station, Pingtung, Taiwan. Major research: Inheritance of straw strength.

JUSTINO TEPORA, instructor, College of Agriculture, University of the Philippines. Major research: Inheritance of resistance to the blast fungus.

**YU-LONG WU, junior specialist, Kaohsiung District Agricultural Improvement Station, Taiwan. Major research: Effect of nitrogen, spacing and water depth on the heritable plant characters associated with straw strength in rice.

SHENG-TIAN YEN, junior specialist, Taiwan Agricultural Research Institute, Taiwan. Major research: Inheritance of short plant stature and grain dormancy in CP 231 x SLO-17.

Research fellows

Research fellows from Japan, Philippines, Korea, India, Pakistan and the United States participated in the Institute's research program during 1965. There were 19 fellows in all, seven of whom were postdoctoral. They contributed importantly to the research of the departments in which they worked. Their names, home institutions and special topics of study are listed as follows:

MISS SAKURA ANDO, graduate student, Hokkaido University, Japan, spent a year in cytogenetical studies of intervarietal hybrids and induced mutants.

DR. M. N. BANDYOPADHYAY, India, studied the establishment of legumes in paddy soils following rice and aspects of light penetration in the rice crop canopy.

DR. DAISY BOQUIREN, Philippines, spent a year working on sclerotia-forming fungi causing diseases of rice.

MR. MUN HUE HEU, assistant professor, Seoul National University, Korea, is participating in all major phases of rice breeding.

DR. AMINUL ISLAM, reader, Dacca University, East Pakistan, was engaged in a six-month study on the influence of flooding on the availability of native and applied phosphorus to rice.

MR. P. J. JACHUCK, assistant botanist, Central Research Institute, India, spent six

months conducting a biosystematic study of the wild species collected from Africa.

DR. MERVYN KAMRAN, Pakistan, is conducting a two-year study on the biological control of rice stem borers.

MR. KAZUO KAWANO, graduate student, Faculty of Agriculture, Hokkaido University, Japan, studied plant characters related to high nitrogen response.

MR. TECK CHIN KWON, senior agricultural economist, Farm Management Division, Office of Rural Development, Korea, studied the economics of varietal choice.

DR. ROBERT LOE, Columbia University, United States, spent one year at the Institute, studying the mechanism of the development of iron toxicity symptoms.

MR. KUNIO MORIYA, graduate student, Kyushu University, Japan, is studying the quantitative characters in rice and the maintenance of genetic markers.

MR. M. N. PRASAD, graduate student, Institute of Agriculture, India, is spending a year working on general rice breeding.

DR. KANTHADAI RAGHU, University Botany Laboratory, Madras, India, is working on the fate of pesticides in submerged soils.

DR. L. RAMAKRISHNAN, India, conducted a biochemical study of the effects of the blast disease on the rice plant.

MR. MARIANO DE RAMOS, assistant professor, College of Agriculture, University of the Philippines, studied experimental statistics for a year.

MRS. KYOKO SAIO, Food Research Institute, Japan, studied nitrogen metabolism of rice plants with special reference to the chloroplast protein.

DR. NORINDO TAKAHASHI, Tohoku University, Japan, worked for six months on the dormancy of rice seeds with respect to germination inhibitors.

MR. YASUO TAKAMURA, graduate student, Laboratory of Crop Science, Kyoto University, Japan, is conducting studies on temperature effects on the morphology and development of the rice plant.

MR. JUN'ICHI YAMAGUCHI, graduate student, Hokkaido University, Japan, is working on photosynthesis and respiration of the rice population.

Advanced studies in the United States

Financial assistance in support of graduate study was provided to selected individuals as a part of the program to improve technical proficiency in rice research. Grantees were in certain instances research assistants on the In-

**Received Master of Science degree.

titute's staff who had demonstrated good capacity for research. Others were selected from among the group of scholars and fellows who had participated in the training program at the Institute. These grantees are listed below, together with the field of specialty and the name of the university at which each is studying:

Scholarships

ELENA M. BAUTISTA, Philippines, soil microbiology, Cornell University.
 GLORIA B. CAGAMPANG, Philippines, biochemistry, Purdue University.
 ADELINA JAVIER, Philippines, analytical chemistry, University of Illinois.
 RHODA S. LANTIN, Philippines, soil chemistry, Iowa State University.
 LEANDRO N. LUCAS, Philippines, Texas A&M University.
 LETICIA R. MENDIOLA, Philippines, biochemistry, Rutgers University.
 REBECCA C. PASCUAL, Philippines, nutrition, Purdue University.
 IFOR B. SOLIDUM, Philippines, personnel man-

agement, University of Kentucky.
 ABRAHAM B. MEDINA, Philippines, biology, Bowling Green State University.
 ISAAC C. CAGAMPANG, Philippines, agronomy, Purdue University.
 WILFREDO G. ESPADA, Philippines, agronomy, Ohio State University.
 M. S. AHMAD, Pakistan, plant breeding, Texas A&M University.
 CHEN-SENG HUANG, Taiwan, genetics, Louisiana State University.
 TRUONG DINH PHU, Vietnam, soil science, University of Illinois.

Travel grants

ESTER L. ALBANO, Philippines, organic chemistry, Ohio State University.
 ERLINDA PILI, Philippines, seed technology, Mississippi State University.
 ROMEO RAROS, Philippines, entomology, University of Minnesota.
 REMEDIOS SANTIAGO, Philippines, chemistry, University of Florida.
 ELYMAR V. VEA, Philippines, entomology, University of Minnesota.
 CARMEN ZEÑAROSA, Philippines, chemistry, Western Michigan University.

INTERNATIONAL COOPERATIVE RESEARCH

Cooperative activities fall into several categories. Many of the studies originate within a research program at the Institute and require extension to other environmental conditions for full evaluation. Others represent kinds of research in which the Institute is not presently engaged directly, but which are deemed important to the better understanding of the rice plant and its environment. In other instances modest grants-in-aid are made to support investigations at other rice research centers without active participation by Institute personnel. Some of the work is conducted cooperatively with scholars and fellows who have completed their studies at the Institute and have gone back to their jobs in their home countries.

Joint investigation with Taiwan scientists of the suffocation disease of rice was continued in 1965 with emphasis on (a) its diagnosis, (b) laboratory and greenhouse studies to establish its cause, and (c) field tests of ameliorative measures.

Field studies in Taiwan, and labor-

atory and greenhouse experiments at the Institute by a research scholar from Taiwan with soils shipped from that country indicate that the term "suffocation disease" has been used to describe at least three different disorders of the rice plant. These diseases are: (a) a physiological disorder associated with reduction products, (b) boron toxicity, and (c) a virus disease.

True suffocation disease is caused by toxic reduction products and is characterized by black roots and reddish discolorations of the leaves. In these studies it was corrected in the greenhouse by applying calcium nitrate or manganese dioxide to the soil. At Ilan, it was checked by (a) improving drainage and (b) applying commercial manganese dioxide at the rate of one ton per hectare of active MnO_2 .

The Institute does not directly conduct research on the profile characteristics of paddy soils, but has contributed support to such studies by the Center for Southeast Asian Studies, Kyoto University. Soil scientists of the Center have started field studies in Thailand

Bogor, Indonesia. Major research: Breeding behavior of grain dormancy.

CHENG-CHANG LI, project technician, Taichung District Agricultural Improvement Station, Taichung, Taiwan. Major research: Inheritance of growth duration; quantitative characters in rice.

PENG-TU LIU, project technician, Kaohsiung District Agricultural Improvement Station, Pingtung, Taiwan. Major research: Inheritance of straw strength.

JUSTINO TEPORA, instructor, College of Agriculture, University of the Philippines. Major research: Inheritance of resistance to the blast fungus.

**YU-LONG WU, junior specialist, Kaohsiung District Agricultural Improvement Station, Taiwan. Major research: Effect of nitrogen, spacing and water depth on the heritable plant characters associated with straw strength in rice.

SHENG-TIAN YEN, junior specialist, Taiwan Agricultural Research Institute, Taiwan. Major research: Inheritance of short plant stature and grain dormancy in CP 231 x SLO-17.

Research fellows

Research fellows from Japan, Philippines, Korea, India, Pakistan and the United States participated in the Institute's research program during 1965. There were 19 fellows in all, seven of whom were postdoctoral. They contributed importantly to the research of the departments in which they worked. Their names, home institutions and special topics of study are listed as follows:

MISS SAKURA ANDO, graduate student, Hokkaido University, Japan, spent a year in cytogenetical studies of intervarietal hybrids and induced mutants.

DR. M. N. BANDYOPADHYAY, India, studied the establishment of legumes in paddy soils following rice and aspects of light penetration in the rice crop canopy.

DR. DAISY BOQUIREN, Philippines, spent a year working on sclerotia-forming fungi causing diseases of rice.

MR. MUN HUE HEU, assistant professor, Seoul National University, Korea, is participating in all major phases of rice breeding.

DR. AMINUL ISLAM, reader, Dacca University, East Pakistan, was engaged in a six-month study on the influence of flooding on the availability of native and applied phosphorus to rice.

MR. P. J. JACHUCK, assistant botanist, Central Research Institute, India, spent six

months conducting a biosystematic study of the wild species collected from Africa.

DR. MERVYN KAMRAN, Pakistan, is conducting a two-year study on the biological control of rice stem borers.

MR. KAZUO KAWANO, graduate student, Faculty of Agriculture, Hokkaido University, Japan, studied plant characters related to high nitrogen response.

MR. TECK CHIN KWON, senior agricultural economist, Farm Management Division, Office of Rural Development, Korea, studied the economics of varietal choice.

DR. ROBERT LOE, Columbia University, United States, spent one year at the Institute, studying the mechanism of the development of iron toxicity symptoms.

MR. KUNIO MORIYA, graduate student, Kyushu University, Japan, is studying the quantitative characters in rice and the maintenance of genetic markers.

MR. M. N. PRASAD, graduate student, Institute of Agriculture, India, is spending a year working on general rice breeding.

DR. KANTHADAI RAGHU, University Botany Laboratory, Madras, India, is working on the fate of pesticides in submerged soils.

DR. L. RAMAKRISHNAN, India, conducted a biochemical study of the effects of the blast disease on the rice plant.

MR. MARIANO DE RAMOS, assistant professor, College of Agriculture, University of the Philippines, studied experimental statistics for a year.

MRS. KYOKO SAIO, Food Research Institute, Japan, studied nitrogen metabolism of rice plants with special reference to the chloroplast protein.

DR. NORINDO TAKAHASHI, Tohoku University, Japan, worked for six months on the dormancy of rice seeds with respect to germination inhibitors.

MR. YASUO TAKAMURA, graduate student, Laboratory of Crop Science, Kyoto University, Japan, is conducting studies on temperature effects on the morphology and development of the rice plant.

MR. JUN'ICHI YAMAGUCHI, graduate student, Hokkaido University, Japan, is working on photosynthesis and respiration of the rice population.

Advanced studies in the United States

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Rice Information Cooperative Effort (R/I/C/E), is being partially financed by the Institute on a 3-year trial basis.

Work of this staff, consisting of an agronomist and a writer, includes collecting rice research and experience information from the various national agencies, digesting this into materials for use by extension workers and farmers, reconciling conflicting recommendations, and developing pilot informational materials. In addition, the group prepares materials for the mass media and answers a growing volume of letters and personal queries from farmers and landowners.

Activity of the R/I/C/E group reduces the pressure on the Institute for materials that most properly should come from the national agricultural and educational agencies of the Philippines.

The Institute contributed to studies at the Institute of Botany, Academia Sinica (Taiwan) in which Dr. H. W. Li and his associates made thousands of backcrosses of triploid, interspecific hybrids of either AAC, AAE, AAF or AAA genomic constitutions to *O. sativa* (AA genome) in an effort to obtain a series of trisomics which would contain the diploid complement of the *sativa* chromosomes plus an extra chromosome of the wild form. A number of the hybrids were backcrossed to the *sativa* parent for the second time.

Dr. C. H. Hu of the Taiwan Provincial Chung Hsing University made crosses between *O. punctata* and three tetraploid taxa with the BBCC genomes and on the basis of meiotic pairing in the F_1 hybrids determined the genomic constitution of *O. punctata* as BBCC. *O. punctata* appeared to differ from *O. minuta* and *O. malampuzhaensis* by one reciprocal translocation in each case.

Assistance in both field facilities and funds was provided to Dr. H. I. Oka of the National Institute of Genetics (Japan) in conducting phylogenetic studies related to the two cultivated species, *O. sativa* and *O. glaberrima*. The studies cover sterility relationships in *sativa* x *glaberrima* hybrids and amphidiploids, the intervarietal sterility in *sativa*, and natural selection in hybrid populations of *sativa* x wild relatives. Drs. Oka and

H. Morishima also collaborated with the varietal improvement staff in detailed statistical analysis of quantitative traits in the Peta x I-geo-tze cross.

At Hokkaido University, Dr. Manemon Takahashi continued to analyze inheritance patterns of several mutant traits and their linkage relationships among hybrids of indica x japonica crosses. About 70 crosses were grown at the Institute for multiplying F_2 seeds. The test crosses between gene markers show a few interesting forms of gene interaction.

(a) "Red rice" is conditioned either by the complementary genes, *Rc* and *Rd*, or the complementary combination of C^B and Pl^W . The pigments due to *Rc* and *Rd* are largely located in the seed-coat (tegmen), whereas those produced by C^B and Pl^W were concentrated in the pericarp. Pl^W belongs to the purple-leaf allelic series, but differs from *Pl* in expressivity.

(b) One suppressor gene for Pl^W has been found, in addition to another inhibitor which affects *Pl*. One of the inhibitors reduces the pigment production of both *Pl* and Pl^W .

(c) A gene controlling heavy pubescence on the lemma and palea, *Hg*, and another gene controlling pubescence of lemma, palea and leaf blade, *Gl* can be recombined with the *Hl* (hairy leaf) allelic series in Japanese strains to produce different, recombinations of the pubescence genes.

In linkage studies, two genes (bl_3 and d_{41}) are added to the first ("waxy") linkage group. Similarly, *I-Pl* and *er* are added to the sixth (" d_1 ") linkage group.

At the Taiwan Agricultural Research Institute, Dr. S. C. Hsieh has established 23 translocations homozygotes in the Japanese variety Kissin from material collected by the late Dr. W. T. Chang of Chung Hsing University. Crosses between translocation homozygotes and several gene markers were made to test the linkage relationships between semi-sterility and marker genes. In inheritance studies with blast resistance, Dr. Hsieh found a small number of blast-resistant F_2 seedlings in a cross between two susceptible vari-

and have made exploratory trips to Cambodia, Ceylon and the Philippines.

Numerous cooperative studies on the rice stem borers were undertaken. These included tests of the use of gamma-BHC as a systemic at some 16 locations in the Philippines on a cooperative basis with the Bureau of Plant Industry and 10 locations in India under the All-India Coordinated Rice Improvement Program. Additional tests were established by the Department of Agriculture in Malaysia.

Tests on varietal resistance to the stem borers were undertaken at the Rice Experiment Station, Maligaya, through the cooperation of the Bureau of Plant Industry. In Sierra Leone, Africa, studies of Dr. Jean Jordan on predators and parasites which affect the stem borers were supported by a grant from the Institute.

Cooperative studies on the rice blast disease involved research stations in Australia, Cambodia, Ceylon, China (Taiwan), Colombia, Guinea, Hong Kong, India, Indonesia, Japan, Korea, Malaysia, Nigeria, Pakistan, Philippines, Sierra Leone, Thailand, Egypt, United States and Vietnam. Some of the results of these undertakings are summarized in the annual report on plant pathology investigations.

The "penyakit merah" disease, described previously as due to physiological disturbances, was studied in Malaysia. Results demonstrated conclusively that many examples of this disease are of viral origin and resemble the "tungro" disease of the Philippines. Because of similarity in symptomatology, it appears that care must be taken not to confuse certain of the virus diseases with disorders of physiological origin.

The Boyce Thompson Institute for Plant Research and the Hokkaido University are cooperating with the Institute on electron microscopic studies of the rice viruses.

The Chemistry Department is cooperating with the U.S. Naval Medical Research Unit No. 2, Taipei, Taiwan, on studies of the nutritive value of rice proteins for experimental animals. Samples for comparative feeding trials sent to Taiwan have contained 7.0 and

11.7% protein. Initial growth studies with rats using these samples were begun in September, 1965.

Histochemical investigations of the rice grain are being carried out cooperatively with scientists of the UPCA. The object of the studies is to characterize the fine structure of the rice grain by histochemical techniques using light and electron microscopes. Other cooperative studies with the UPCA involve investigations of the relation of starch composition, protein content, and gelatinization temperature to cooking and eating qualities of milled rice. The results of this research are described in the cereal chemistry section of the Annual Report.

Cooperative studies in agronomy included investigations on fertilization-variety interactions conducted at the Maligaya Rice and Corn Experiment Station and in farmers' fields in Louisiana, Biñan, Santa Rosa and Cavite in the Philippines. Tests on planting procedures, weed control and aspects of fertilization of lowland rice were also carried out at the Maligaya Rice Experiment Station, in cooperation with scientists of the Bureau of Plant Industry.

In the area of plant physiology the cooperative project, "Studies on the growth of rice plants in relation to environmental conditions," initiated in 1963, were continued in 1965. This project has involved 30 sites in Korea, Japan, Taiwan, Thailand, Philippines, Malaysia, Australia, and Ghana. Results are summarized in the plant physiology annual report.

Cooperative studies on the "Growth processes of Raminad Strain 3" were undertaken in 1965 at the Maligaya Experiment Station and the Cagayan Valley Rice and Corn Experiment Station of the Philippines. Raminad Strain 3 and similar varieties which are highly photoperiod-sensitive are widely used in the Philippines.

More than a year's negotiation culminated in August 1965 with the establishing at the College of Agriculture, University of the Philippines, of a staff to bring together and disseminate rice cultural practices information for the Philippines. This activity, known as the

working on mechanization programs and on economic aspects of the use of machinery. He attended the Indian Agricultural Engineering Society meetings in New Delhi November 6 to 17 and also visited the Allahabad Agricultural Implements and Power Development Center.

The farm superintendent visited Malaysia in September to study the rice production methods of that country.

The biochemist attended the annual meeting of the Japanese Biochemical Society at Fukuoka, Japan in October, and in November gave an invitational lecture entitled "Mechanism of Fatty Liver Production by Ethionine" at the Enzyme Research Institute, Tokushima University School of Medicine.

In February the entomologist visited the Department of Agriculture at Kuala Lumpur, Malaysia, and its experiment stations at Bukit Merah, Parit Buntar and Alor Star, and University of Malaysia to become acquainted with personnel and start cooperative experiments on the control of rice stem borers with gamma-BHC. He also discussed the possibility of a cooperative experiment on rice gall midge at the Kasetsart University, Thailand. In March-April, he visited West Bengal Experiment Station, Chinsurah, Central Rice Research Institute, Cuttack, and Rice Research Station, Faizabad, U.P. in India to discuss the various insect pests problem of rice and to initiate cooperative experiments. In November he attended the All-India Rice Research Workers Conference at Cuttack. In August he visited agricultural experiment stations in Japan at Nishigahara, Kyoto, Fukuyama and Chikugo to review current entomological research projects.

The soil chemist visited Taiwan in February, June and September to consult with Taiwan scientists and to study the progress of the cooperative project on the control of suffocation disease. In September he visited Japan to consult with soil scientists at the National Institute of Agricultural Sciences, Tokyo.

The plant breeder participated in the All-India Rice Workers' Conference at Cuttack, India, and the Symposium on

the Impact of Mendelism upon Agriculture, Biology and Medicine at New Delhi in February. In May he visited a number of experiment stations in Taiwan where IRRI breeding lines are being grown, and in June and November he assisted in the planting and field selection of IRRI breeding lines at the Bangkhen and San Pah Tong Experiment Stations of the Thai Rice Department. During September he visited a number of agricultural experiment stations and agricultural colleges in Japan.

The geneticist participated in the Symposium on the Impact of Mendelism on Agriculture, Biology and Medicine held in New Delhi, India, during February 15-20. He made two trips to Malaysia and Thailand to inspect cooperative varietal tests and made plant selections in segregating materials. He attended an IAEA-FAO workshop discussion on the standardization and integration of data reporting and processing at the IAEA Headquarters in Vienna during December 13-17. On his return trip, he stopped in Rome and consulted the FAO genetic stocks officer on varietal catalogs.

The head of the Varietal Improvement Department was in the United States on study leave during the first half of 1965. While there he travelled to Panama and Colombia in January to review rice research programs. In March he returned to Panama to attend the Central American Reunion of Workers on Basic Food Crops and in June he visited Costa Rica to review the rice research program in that country. Following his return to the Institute he travelled to Thailand in August to discuss personnel needs of Thailand's Rice Department. In November he attended the "Symposium on the Research Problems of Rice Farming in Japan," Sendai, and visited the National Institute of Genetics at Misima. In December, he attended the IAEA discussion group on standardization of plant breeding terminology and methodology in Vienna.

The communication specialist attended the Conference on Subsistence and Peasant Economics at the East-West Center, University of Hawaii, and while there also reviewed some aspects of the

eties, indicating an interaction of genes in conferring resistance.

With seed of Taichung (Native) 1 initially supplied by the Institute in 1964, the short-statured *indica* variety was grown at several locations in India during the 1965 spring crop. The high yields (5-9 metric ton/ha) obtained from test plots prompted the Indian Ministry of Food and Agriculture to conduct further trials over a wider area and to begin seed increases. The Ministry asked the Institute to supply one metric ton of seed which was airlifted to India in May.

In supplying the seeds to India, the Institute cautioned the Indian officials about some of the inherent defects in

Taichung (Native) 1: its susceptibility to races of blast at Los Baños and its low resistance to the tungro disease and bacterial leaf blight. However, the Indian scientists found that in three years of tests at Cuttack and Coimbatore, Taichung (Native) 1 showed resistance to most of the races of blast in India.

Samples of seed from the world collection and from the Institute's breeding program were supplied to investigators in many parts of the world. Sizeable collections of lines of potential interest went to India, Thailand, Malaysia and Pakistan. A large number of separate requests for seed were met during the year.

INTERNATIONAL TRAVEL

International travel by the senior scientific staff in connection with research, training and related programs is reported in the following paragraphs. Similar travel within the Philippines in support of cooperative activities is not reported because of the number and frequency of such trips.

The agricultural economist visited Australia in February to attend the Farmers and Scientists Joint Conference and the Australian Agricultural Economics Society Annual Conference. He also visited various universities and experiment stations in Australia and en route he visited the University of Singapore. In April he visited Laos to confer with AID officials on the rice production problems of that country. En route he visited Thailand's Rice Department and Kasetsart University. In July, together with the visiting scientist, Agricultural Economics, he again visited Thailand to participate in the annual meeting of the Agricultural Economics Association.

The agronomist visited India in February and in November, participating in rice research workers conferences on both occasions. During the earlier visit, work was reviewed at Chinsurah, Rajendranagar, and Cuttack. In August he attended meetings of the AIBS in Urbana, Illinois, and observed rice research results at Davis and Biggs, California.

The associate agronomist spent 10 days in February observing Indian rice research and cooperative projects at Chinsurah, Tripura, Cuttack, Hyderabad, and New Delhi. In June he visited rice research institutions in Taiwan to review in particular the soil fertility and fertilizer work. In November he visited rice farms, drying and storage facilities in Butte county and research stations at Biggs, California, and attended meetings of the American Society of Agronomy in Columbus, Ohio.

The agricultural engineer visited Thailand and Malaysia March 9 to 21. Accompanied by an engineer of the Thailand Royal Irrigation Department, he examined various irrigation projects and experiment stations in the Central Plains and the northeast and northern regions of the country. In addition he visited the College of Engineering at Chulalongkorn University, The College of Irrigation Engineering of Kasetsart University and the SEATO Graduate School of Engineering. In Malaysia the agricultural engineer visited the Irrigation and Drainage Department, the Selangor Workshop and Motor Pool on tractor operations and observed rice production problems at Penang. In late September and early October he travelled to Japan and Taiwan with the assistant agricultural engineer. Conferences were held with farm machinery manufacturers and research groups

Nigeria as a consultant for the Agency for International Development to review rice production problems and potentials in that country. In November he returned to Japan to present an invitational paper on rice production problems in the tropics.

In February the pathologist attended the FAO-IAEA conference on nutrition breeding which was held in Thailand and en route stopped to observe studies on the "penyakit merah" disease in Malaysia. In July he returned to Malaysia to study further the results of cooperative investigations on the "penyakit merah" problem. In October he attended the American Phytopathology Society's annual meetings in the United States and on his return attended the joint Japan-United States conference on physiological races of the *Piricularia oryzae* fungus.

In January the assistant virologist travelled to Malaysia where he stayed for two months to conduct cooperative studies on the "penyakit merah" disease.

In May the assistant director spent a week in Pakistan to discuss rice research activities with the officials of the government and representatives of the Ford Foundation and to suggest areas in which cooperative undertakings with the Institute might be initiated. In June he travelled extensively in Japan to become acquainted with various rice research operations in that country. In December he spent a 10-day period in India as a member of an AID-

sponsored team to review fertilizer policies and problems related to increasing the production of food grains.

In February the director participated in the international symposium on the Impact of Mendelism on Agriculture, Biology and Medicine, held in New Delhi, India. In conjunction with this trip he visited a number of experiment stations in India to observe their rice research programs. In July, while travelling on home leave, he visited India to discuss the All-India Coordinated Rice Improvement Program and continued to New York to discuss official matters relating to the Institute. While returning to the Philippines he visited a number of experiment stations and agricultural schools in Korea and Japan.

The director was named a member of the Scientific Advisory Committee responsible for planning the development of rice research in India. He travelled to India in September to attend the first meeting of this committee, to visit rice research centers, and to observe experiments on the use of gamma-BHC on rice stem borer control. In November he returned to India to attend a meeting of the Scientific Advisory Committee and to consult on activities of the All-India Coordinated Rice Improvement Program. In connection with this trip he also attended the Southeast Asian conference on the conservation of natural resources, held in Bangkok, and visited rice experiment stations in Malaysia.

Pineapple Research Institute program. In two trips to Taiwan, he helped the Joint Commission on Rural Reconstruction and the Taiwan Provincial Department of Agriculture and Forestry lay the base for a program to design, prepare and test a range of materials for the training of junior assistants for agricultural research and extension organizations. In a two-week trip to Malaysia and Thailand, he discussed rice extension programs with national and provincial officials with special emphasis on those areas where double-cropping has been established. He reviewed extension training efforts underway and planned with a view toward assessing how the Institute might help in this area. While in the United States on home leave, he attended the annual sessions of the Rural Sociological Society and later reviewed progress on the joint publication program with The Johns Hopkins Press, Baltimore, Maryland.

The rice production specialist made two trips out of the Philippines, one to Taiwan and another to the United States, Mexico, the South Pacific Islands, and Australia. While in California, he visited the University of California, Davis, to discuss recent studies on agricultural aircraft, and the California Rice Experiment Station to review the current rice program. The Mexico portion of the trip included a review of the agricultural program of The Rockefeller Foundation and visits to various experiment stations and seed facilities. The trip through the South Pacific Islands included discussions of agricultural research and extension work and first-hand inspection of rice problems and potentials in Tahiti, Fiji, New Caledonia, New Hebrides, Solomon Islands, Papua Territory and New Guinea. In Australia he held discussions at Sydney and Canberra with various officials concerned with rice.

The statistician visited Japan and observed the various systems of electronic data processing. He implemented the programming and processing of IRRI data in the analysis of principal yield components in the TOSBAC 3400 computer. This is a first attempt to use computer systems for IRRI data. He al-

so served as guest lecturer of statistics at Kasetsart University, Bangkok, Thailand, and at the Philippine Executive Academy, University of the Philippines and was nominated as participant to the 1965 World Population Conference in Belgrade, Yugoslavia.

In October the librarian participated in the Third World Congress of Agricultural Librarians and Documentalists in Washington, D.C. where she presented an invitational paper, "Compiling an international bibliography: the Philippine experience and its implications on international needs." The Congress, which was attended by persons from 37 countries, sought to foster worldwide cooperation through the establishment of an international network of agricultural libraries. Also in October, she attended the 1965 Congress of the International Federation for Documentation to learn the latest developments in the organization of information for retrieval.

In April the soil microbiologist attended the annual meeting of the American Society for Microbiologists in Atlantic City where he presented a paper co-authored with Dr. K. Raghu and entitled "The effect of the gamma isomer of benzene hexachloride upon algal populations in submerged soils." In September he visited workers in the fields of soil microbiology and soil chemistry in Japan.

During July and August the associate physiologist travelled to Copenhagen, Denmark, to participate in the Symposium on Ecosystems. En route he made stops in India and Japan to visit rice research centers and at Wageningen, Holland and Rothamsted, England to observe research projects on plant physiology with particular regard to studies on photoperiodism. In October he made a short trip to Taiwan to observe cooperative studies on environmental factors which may limit rice production.

In February the physiologist visited Indonesia, in July Ceylon, and in August Japan, with the objective of observing nutritional problems in commercial rice fields and in experimental programs. In September he travelled to

Publications and Seminars

STAFF PUBLICATIONS

Plant Physiology

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- TANAKA, A., C. V. GARCIA, and DIEM NGUYEN-THI. 1965. Studies on the relationship between tillering and nitrogen uptake of the rice plant. 1. Observation on the leafing and tillering pattern of some rice varieties grown under different nitrogen levels. *Soil Sci. Plant Nutr.* 11: 9-13.
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- JENNINGS, P. R. 1965. Rice breeding in the tropics and its relation to improvement of Japanese varieties. *Inst. Agr. Res. Sendai, Japan.* 23 pp.
- BEACHELL, H. M. and P. R. JENNINGS. 1964. Need for modification of plant type. *In* The Mineral Nutrition of the Rice Plant. Johns Hopkins Press. pp. 29-35.
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SEMINARS

The following topics were the subjects of seminars held at the Institute during 1965. Unless otherwise stated the speakers were staff members.

Bringing rice research findings to the Philippine farm in 1965. Dr. Byrnes and Mr. Golden

Testing of rice varieties and selections for resistance to tungro virus. Dr. Tosi Take Iida, visiting scientist, IRRI

A study of the pathogenic races of *Piricularia oryzae* in the Philippines. Dr. Ou

Growth stage theories and agricultural development policy. Dr. Ruttan

- Mechanization to improve the standard of living in tropical rice-growing areas. Mr. Johnson
- Mineral element disturbances of lowland rice. Dr. Tanaka
- Some problems of rice conditioning and storage in the humid tropics. Dr. Dante B. de Padua, assistant professor, Department of Agricultural Engineering, UPCA
- Food price policy in India. Dr. Raj Krishna, agricultural economist, Institute of Economic Growth, New Delhi, India
- Estimation of the incidence of stem borers and virus diseases in experimental fields. Dr. Oñate
- Role of the Commission on Agricultural Productivity in rice production in the Philippines. Mr. Oscar J. S. Lazo, chief, Communications Media Division, Commission on Agricultural Productivity, Philippines
- Impressions of the 8th International Soil Science Congress. Dr. Ponnampereuma, and Impressions of the Pre-Congress Soils Tour in U.S.S.R. and of the Post-Congress Soils Tour in Roumania, 1964. Dr. Bradfield
- The Filipino barrio system. Father Jaime Bulatao, S.J., chairman, Psychology Department, Ateneo Graduate School of Arts and Sciences, Ateneo de Manila
- Administration, rice research, and technological change. Dr. Chandler
- Some physiological aspects of organization. Dr. F. C. Steward, professor of plant physiology, Cornell University
- The rice industry in relation to the land reform code. Mr. Manuel V. Gallego, president, Rice and Corn Development Corporation, Philippines
- Agricultural research and the Filipino farmer. Dr. Jeremias U. Montemayor, dean, College of Law, Ateneo de Manila, and founder and president of the Federation of Free Farmers
- Toward understanding the Filipino farmer. Dr. Gelia T. Castillo, assistant professor of agricultural education, UPCA
- Competition in crop and pasture communities with particular reference to light. Dr. C. M. Donald, professor of agronomy, Waite Agricultural Research Institute, University of Adelaide, Australia
- Problems and needs in nutrition in Luzon. Dr. Josefina Bulatao-Jayme, supervising medical nutrition scientist, Food and Nutrition Research Center, National Institute of Science and Technology, Philippines
- Evaluation of protein quality. Dr. Carmen Ll. Intengan, assistant research director, Food and Nutrition Research Center, NIST, Philippines
- A $1/8$ fractional experiment of $2^5 \times 4^2$ factorials on the symptom of unusual growth of directly sown paddy-rice in pot experiments. Dr. T. Okuno, mathematical statistician, Laboratory of Experimental Design, National Institute of Agricultural Sciences, Tokyo, Japan
- A $1/3$ fractional replication of 3^5 factorial experiment on direct-sowing of paddy rice in field experiments. Dr. T. Okuno, mathematical statistician, Laboratory of Experimental Design, National Institute of Agricultural Sciences, Tokyo, Japan

- Analysis of the data obtained from various types of experiments by the electronic computer. Mrs. C. S. Okuno, mathematical statistician, Laboratory of Experimental Design, National Institute of Agricultural Sciences, Tokyo, Japan
- The Filipino's mental make-up and science. Miss Josefina D. Constantino, special assistant to the Chairman, Development Bank of the Philippines
- The diffusion of agricultural information: Some emerging patterns in selected Philippine villages. Dr. Gloria D. Feliciano, chairman, Department of Journalism and Communication, College of Arts and Sciences, University of the Philippines
- Bulk storage of grain. Mr. H. J. Griffiths, research scientist, Division of Mechanical Engineering, Commonwealth Scientific and Industrial Research Organization, Australia
- Changes in rice production area and yield in the Philippines and Thailand. Dr. Ruttan
- Isotopes in radiation entomology. Dr. M. E. Jefferson, regional adviser, International Atomic Energy Agency
- Equity and productivity issues in modern agrarian reform legislation. Dr. Ruttan
- Trends of food grain production in India. Dr. M. N. Bandyopadhyay, agronomy research fellow, IRRI
- Present status of The International Rice Research Institute's rice breeding program. Mr. Beachell
- Economic analysis of Philippine rice farmers. Dr. Emilio Quintana, chairman, Department of Agricultural Economics, UPCA
- The role of management factors in rice production. Dr. Moomaw
- Some aspects of the blast disease of rice. Dr. L. Ramakrishnan, research fellow, IRRI
- Phosphorus availability and fertilizer response in rice. Dr. de Datta
- The practice of biological control and its relation to the control of the rice stem borers. Dr. Mervyn A. Kamran, research fellow, IRRI
- Microbiological contributions to the nitrogen status of soil. Dr. MacRae
- Studies on the mode of action of metabolic analogues — Mechanism of ethionine-induced inhibition of protein and RNA synthesis in rat liver. Dr. Natori
- Stereochemical theory of odor. Dr. John Amoore, USDA, Western Regional Research Laboratory, California
- Surface activity of inorganic soil phosphates. Dr. S. C. Chang, soil chemistry expert, UNSF, Soil Fertility Survey and Research Project
- Statistical quality control in agricultural research. Dr. Oñate
- Rice situation in the South Pacific Islands. Mr. Golden
- Taiwan model of agricultural progress-implications to other developing countries in Asia. Dr. S. C. Hsieh, visiting professor, Department of Agricultural Economics, UPCA
- Behavioral Science approaches to the communication of scientific information. Dr. Byrnes

- Inheritance of quantitative characters in Peta x I-geo-tze. Dr. Chang
- A cytogeneticist's look at the evolution of rice. Dr. S. V. S. Shastry, botanist,
Indian Agricultural Research Institute
- Nonpersistence of the tungro virus in its leafhopper vector. Dr. Ling
- Controlling common stem borer and leafhopper pests of rice. Dr. Pathak
- Electron microscopy of viruses in tissues of plant and insect hosts. Dr. Karl Maramorosh, Boyce Thompson Institute for Plant Research, Inc.
- Five-year development program of UPCA. Dr. Dioscoro L. Umali, Dean, UPCA
- Some problems in the production of pineapple in Hawaii. Mr. Hong Yip Young,
visiting scientist, IRRI
- Photosynthesis rates of corn varieties as influenced by light and carbon dioxide.
Dr. Robert B. Musgrave, professor of agronomy, UPCA
- Some observations on rice research in Asia with emphasis on India. Dr. Chandler
- Potato research in Mexico. Dr. John Niederhauser, The Rockefeller Foundation,
Mexico

